

Hosted By:

**NANYANG
TECHNOLOGICAL
UNIVERSITY**
SINGAPORE

Wee Kim Wee School of
Communication and Information
College of Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences

Communicating Environmental Justice

Many Voices, One Planet

IAMCR
2025
Singapore

Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information

NTU Singapore

Young and research-intensive, **Nanyang Technological University, Singapore** (NTU Singapore) is ranked among the world's top universities. Nestled within this vibrant institution, the **Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information (WKWSCl)** is a global leader in communication and information research and education, renowned for its multi-cultural and interdisciplinary faculty, cutting-edge facilities, and international partnerships.

Our outstanding faculty and talented students have been recognised across the world for their impactful, academic and creative works that contribute to knowledge, theory, and society.

IN ASIA
2025 QS World University
Rankings by Subject for
Communication & Media Studies

IN THE WORLD
2025 QS World University
Rankings by Subject for
Communication & Media Studies

IN ASIA
2025 QS World University
Rankings by Subject for Library
& Information Management

IN THE WORLD
2025 QS World University
Rankings by Subject for Library
& Information Management

JOIN THE BEST COMMUNICATION SCHOOL IN ASIA.

Join our world-class faculty in shaping the future of communication at Asia's leading communication school.

Nanyang Assistant Professorship (NAP)

The prestigious NAP scheme offers exceptional opportunities for individuals aspiring to research leadership roles. Successful applicants at the University level will join the Wee Kim Wee School and receive a substantial start-up grant to support their work. We are especially interested in candidates with expertise in AI Communication, Digital Humanities, and Information Studies.

Successful candidates will receive

 Tenure track appointment
with an attractive
remuneration package

 A dedicated White Space
Fund of up to **SGD 250,000** as
part of the startup grant

 Up to **SGD 1 million** start-up
research funding and
scholarships to support PhD
student recruitment

Scan Here
for more information

Applications invited for Lecturer/Senior Lecturer in Digital Journalism with expertise in journalism and new technologies (e.g., automation, analytics, big data, VR), strong multimedia experience, and proven teaching ability. Responsibilities include course and syllabus development, undergraduate teaching, project supervision, industry engagement, and internship oversight.

Lecturer/Senior Lecturer in Digital Journalism

Assistant Professor (Tenure Track) in Information Science

Applications invited for a position in information science requiring expertise in areas such as library technology, analytics, human-computer or AI interaction, informetrics, digital curation, information management, or human information behaviour. Secondary skills in programming or AI are an advantage. Doctorate in a relevant field required.

We also welcome faculty from overseas universities or research institutions to join us under the **Visiting Professor Scheme**.

Scan for details on Faculty Hiring

Find out more about openings at our booth at SHHK Building
or contact us at sci-hr@ntu.edu.sg.

#6

National Universities

#24

Best Global Universities

2024 U.S. NEWS Best Colleges

Northwestern University in Qatar is a global community of award-winning evidence-based storytellers. Through our Institute for Advanced Study in the Global South, Media Majlis Museum, Artificial Intelligence and Media Lab, and our programs in Communication, Journalism and Strategic Communication, and Liberal Arts, we make transformative contributions in research, mediamaking, teaching, and public engagement.

Northwestern | QATAR

Welcome Messages	5
About the Conference	7
Venue Map	8
Pre- and Post-Conference Events	9
Programme at a Glance	11
Opening Ceremony	12
Welcome Session	13
Plenary Sessions	14
Special and Partner Sessions	18
Closing Ceremony	25
Conference Dinner	29
Special Exhibitions and Screenings	30
Day-by-Day Schedule of All Section and Working Group Parallel Sessions	33
Sponsors and Partners	179

TIP:
Click on these buttons to download the app!

Scan this QR Code to download the app

For any issues accessing the event on Whova, please contact hospitality2025@iamcr.org

1
To enhance your IAMCR 2025 experience, download the **Whova app** from the **Google Play Store** or **Apple App Store** on your Android or iOS device.

2
Sign in using the email address you used to register for the conference. First-time users will be prompted to create a password.

3
Once signed in, the app will automatically display events linked to your email. Tap on **IAMCR 2025** to access the event.

4
With Whova, you can view the full programme, build your personal agenda, connect with other participants, receive real-time updates, share photos, and more — **all from your mobile device.**

Dear IAMCR colleagues, friends, and conference participants

I am very pleased to welcome you to the 2025 annual conference of our association, being hosted in vibrant Singapore by the **Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information of the Nanyang Technological University**.

As the world's oldest professional association for media and communication research, it is indeed an honour to lead an organisation home to the most diverse and critically informed scholarship, providing an invaluable intellectual hub for established scholars and emerging researchers, as well as practitioners and policymakers from across the globe.

The conference theme of **"Communicating Environmental Justice: Many Voices, One Planet"** is extremely timely given the continuing ecological threats to our planet. As communication scholars, we have a responsibility to promote awareness of the issues and facilitate the debate to find creative solutions for a safer and more sustainable world. With IAMCR's illustrious history of providing voices to a plurality of opinions and perspectives, I am sure that this theme will receive the attention it deserves in the many panels organised by IAMCR's 16 thematic sections and 21 working groups, as well as keynote and plenary sessions. I encourage you to attend the closing plenary — "Communicating for a Multivocal World" — with representatives from fellow international communication associations and also learn more about next year's conference in Galway, Ireland.

With more than 1700 participants, this IAMCR conference is going to be the largest to date, and I particularly welcome the presence of so many young scholars — the future custodians of our fragile earth — producing new and exciting research in a field that is rapidly changing with the advent of AI.

IAMCR is returning to the 'Lion City' after a quarter of a century, and I have many wonderful memories of that conference. I am convinced that, under the able stewardship of local organising committee, headed by Professors Jack Qiu and Edson Tandoc, and with the support of the excellent IAMCR secretariat, this year's conference will be a resounding success.

I look forward to seeing you all in Singapore.

Warm wishes,
Daya Thussu
President, IAMCR

Dear IAMCR colleagues, students, and friends,

Greetings from Singapore!

On behalf of the Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information at Nanyang Technological University, we are delighted to extend a warm invitation to join us for this year's IAMCR conference, taking place from 13-17 July 2025 in Singapore.

Hosting IAMCR 2025 is a tremendous honour for our school, bringing back cherished memories of the first IAMCR conference we hosted in 2000. As we prepare for this year's event, we are reminded of how much has changed over the past quarter-century — not only in media and communication research, but across our entire planet, which now faces the urgent challenge of climate change.

The theme for IAMCR 2025 is: **"Communicating Environmental Justice: Many Voices, One Planet."**

This theme echoes global efforts to leverage media and communication for sustainable development and to "green" the media industries, including emerging sectors like big data and AI. These initiatives are taking root around the world, and Singapore is no exception. Here, innovative collaborations among academics, practitioners, and public and private sector partners are paving the way toward sustainability and environmental justice.

We are especially proud to highlight that our NTU campus hosts Singapore's largest cluster of net-zero emission buildings. The main conference activities will be held on this vibrant, green campus — and we can't wait for you to experience it firsthand.

Once again, welcome to Singapore, the Lion City.

We look forward to greeting you at IAMCR 2025 and welcoming you to the Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, NTU Singapore.

Jack Qiu and Edson Tandoc
Co-Chairs, IAMCR 2025 Local Organising Committee
Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information
Nanyang Technological University

CITY UNIVERSITY OF HONG KONG DEPARTMENT OF MEDIA AND COMMUNICATION

Since its founding in 2008, the Department of Media and Communication at City University of Hong Kong has become a hub for professionals and academics in areas include:

- Strategic Communication
- Computational Communication
- Health Communication
- Digital Media Technology and Social Impacts
- MERIT: Meta-Evaluation and Research Integration

Northwestern | QATAR Institute for Advanced Study in the Global South

Stop by our booth at #IAMCR25 to meet #IAS_NUQ staff and to learn about our programs and opportunities.

The Institute for Advanced Study in the Global South (#IAS_NUQ) at Northwestern Qatar produces and promotes evidence-based storytelling on the histories, cultures, societies, and media of the Global South.

Through fellowships, multimodal publications, and events, we amplify faculty and student scholarship, mentor future scholars, and advance knowledge that is both locally relevant and globally resonant.

We are committed to advancing rigorous scholarship and creative mediamaking that sheds light on the complex dynamics of the Global South as a geographic, epistemological, experiential, and ethical space.

Research at #IAS_NUQ is organized around four key themes: Genealogies and Epistemologies of the Global South, Arab Media, Culture, and Politics, Southern Digitalities, and Critical Security Studies.

Scan to explore our programs, current opportunities, and #IAS_NUQ_Press publications.

EMERGING MEDIA

About Emerging Media

Emerging Media journal is jointly published by The School of Media and Communication at Shanghai Jiao Tong University and Sage Publishing. The journal was launched in September, 2023 and is currently indexed by DOAJ (Digital Open Access Journal). Emerging Media focuses on the exploration of the emerging issues and future development in the field of media and communication, particularly in the field of media development histories, artificial intelligence (AI), information and communication technologies (ICTs), new media application, mobile technology, user experience design, data science, aesthetics, ethical and cultural studies, as well as social and psychological perspectives.

Submission Details

Since its launch, Emerging Media has received submissions from 40 countries and regions spanning five continents. We accept Colloquium, Research Notes, Original Research Articles, and Book Reviews. All articles are published with open access and free of any article processing charges.

ISSN 2752-3543
EISSN 2752-3551

Journal Website Submission Portal

ias@qatar.northwestern.edu

ias_nuq X IAS_NUQ IASNUQ iasnuq

ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

Outlined by the 37 sections and working groups, the IAMCR 2025 conference explores a broad diversity of topics in media and communication research, brought together under the unifying theme **Communicating Environmental Justice: Many Voices, One Planet**. This year's theme recognises the pressing need to examine how communication practices and infrastructures both contribute to and challenge the global climate crisis. It calls on scholars to interrogate the ways in which environmental justice is framed, contested, and communicated across different social, political, cultural, and technological contexts.

IAMCR 2025 seeks to foster dialogue on how media and communication can amplify marginalised voices, expose environmental inequalities, and promote more inclusive and sustainable futures. From climate activism and indigenous storytelling to greenwashing and platform governance, the conference encourages intersectional and interdisciplinary approaches to understanding the communicative dimensions of environmental justice.

Hosted in Singapore, a multicultural and rapidly urbanising city-state, the conference provides a meaningful location to reflect on both the challenges and innovations involved in balancing economic development with ecological responsibility. IAMCR 2025 invites participants to consider how communication scholarship can contribute to imagining and enacting a healthier, more resilient planet for all.

IAMCR 2024 Conference held in Christchurch, New Zealand.

KEY VENUES

- ① Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information (WKWSCI)
- ② Nanyang Auditorium
- ③ Lee Kong Chian Lecture Theatre (LKC-LT)
- ④ The Hive
- ⑤ Singapore Hokkien Huay Kuan Building (SHHK)
- ⑥ Gaia

FOOD AND BEVERAGES

- ① North Spine
- ② The Quad
- ③ South Spine
- ④ Co-Op Café

BUS STOPS

- ① WKWSCI
- ② Academic Building South

PUBLIC TRANSPORT

• Bus 179
BUS 179 DEPARTS FROM:
 Boon Lay Bus Interchange
 Pioneer MRT Station Exit A
 The bus runs from 0600-2400 hrs from Monday to Saturday and 0630-0020 on Sundays

In the event of an emergency (e.g. fire), please proceed calmly to the designated assembly areas listed below. Do reach out to the IAMCR Hospitality Team should you have any concerns or issues in regard to an emergency (Patricia Ng +65 8100 8390 OR Tan Hui Yu +65 9846 8622).

- ① The Hive, SHHK and Gaia (Bus Drop Off Point in front of Chinese Heritage Centre)
- ② Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information (Carpark S)

PRE- & POST- CONFERENCE EVENTS

TIP:
Click on the event
you're interested in
to learn more!

PRE-CONFERENCE EVENTS

- ✿ AI Inequalities: Critical praxis for digital inclusion
- ✿ Big Tech and Global Influence: Rethinking CSR, Soft Power, and Strategic Communication in a Digital World
- ✿ Digital Economy, Communication and Rural Development: Retrospect, Reflection and Praxis
- ✿ Emotions and Journalism in Today's Dynamic Communication Landscape
- ✿ InterAsian Digitalities: Rethinking Theories and Methods
- ✿ The 50th Anniversary of Communication Policy & Technology

POST-CONFERENCE EVENTS

- ✿ Methods, Approaches, and Challenges of Researching AI and Labour in Creative Media Ecologies from Global Perspectives
- ✿ Rural Development, Media, and African Modernisation: Perspectives for Inclusive Growth
- ✿ Scholarly podcasting: Listening, making, and knowledge sharing

Future-Ready Communication

The School of Communication at Hong Kong Baptist University (HKBU) is renowned as one of Asia's top communication schools.

2/4

ICA Fellows/
Editors-in-Chief or
Senior Editor

4

M.A. and M.S.
Programmes

4

Research Centres

5

Top 2% Scientists
Worldwide 2024

7

Undergraduate Majors

68

Presentations
at the 75th ICA

56/1,415

Faculty/Students

138/4

Journal Articles/Books
Published (2024)

25,000+

Alumni

School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University

Join a World-Class Journey in Journalism and Communication at Tsinghua

Where Global Minds Meet Media Futures

Global Faculty Recruitment

We invite outstanding scholars from around the world to join us in shaping the future of journalism and communication in China. We seek experts in Journalism Studies, International Journalism, Economic Communication, Intelligent Communication, Audiovisual Communication, and related fields. Ideal candidates are passionate educators and researchers who bridge theory and practice, understand both global and Chinese media landscapes, and engage meaningfully with the industry.

Global Student Enrollment

Explore our all-English master's and PhD programs, designed for aspiring international media professionals:

- Global Business Journalism Master's Program
- Tsinghua-NTU Global Science Communication Dual Degree Master's Program
- PhD Program in Communication and Global Development

Global Collaboration

We welcome international partners to collaborate on research, exchange, and innovation. Together, we advance media education and foster cross-border dialogue in a rapidly evolving global landscape.

Research
Postgraduate
Programmes

About
Our School

Career
Opportunities

About TSJC

Contact Us

School of Journalism and Communication
Tsinghua University, Beijing, China

Email: tsjcw@tsinghua.edu.cn

www.tsjc.tsinghua.edu.cn

PROGRAMME AT A GLANCE

	13 JULY SUNDAY	14 JULY MONDAY	15 JULY TUESDAY	16 JULY WEDNESDAY	17 JULY THURSDAY
		Registration Opens 08:00 / Continues all day			
		Parallel Session 08:30–10:00	Parallel Session 08:30–10:00	Parallel Session 08:30–10:00	Parallel Session 08:30–10:00
		Coffee Break 10:00–10:30			
		Plenary Session 2 10:30–12:30	Parallel Sessions 10:30–12:30	Plenary Session 3 10:30–12:30	Parallel Sessions 10:30–12:30
		Lunch Break 12:30–14:00			
			Parallel Sessions 14:00–15:30	Parallel Sessions 14:00–15:30	Parallel Sessions 14:00–15:30
			Coffee Break 15:30–16:00		
			Parallel Sessions 16:00–17:30	Parallel Sessions 16:00–17:30	Parallel Sessions 16:00–17:30
			Section & Working Group gatherings	Free Evening	Conference Dinner 19:00–Late
	Registration Open 14:00–16:00				Closing Ceremony 15:45–17:45
	Opening plenary and reception 17:00–19:30				

OPENING CEREMONY

@ NANYANG AUDITORIUM

SUNDAY, JULY 13
17:00 - 19:30

CHAIR:

Edson Tandoc

Co-Chair of the Singapore 2025 Local Organising Committee
President's Chair Professor of Communication Studies
Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information
Nanyang Technological University Singapore

WELCOMING WORDS FROM IAMCR PRESIDENT

Daya Thussu

Professor of International Communication at Hong Kong Baptist University
and a Senior Research Fellow at the Institute for Commonwealth Studies
University of London

WELCOMING WORDS FROM LOC

Jack Qiu

Co-Chair of the Singapore 2025 Local Organising Committee
Chair and Shaw Foundation Prof of Media Technology
Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information
Nanyang Technological University

WELCOMING WORDS - HOST INSTITUTION

May Lwin

Associate Provost (Faculty Affairs)
President's Chair Professor of Communication Studies
Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information
Nanyang Technological University Singapore

KEYNOTE ADDRESS

Ang Peng Hwa

Professor
Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information
Nanyang Technological University

WELCOME SESSION

WELCOME TO IAMCR SESSION

@ ABS-SR6 GAIA

TUESDAY, 15 JULY
12:45–13:45

This informal session aims to welcome those new to IAMCR – either new members, or first-time conference participants. Everyone is welcome, especially doctoral researchers and emerging scholars, and those whose work is located outside academia.

It will introduce key features of the conference and Association, providing important information to demystify how IAMCR works – and what opportunities it offers those attending the conference and wishing to become involved in, contribute to, and benefit from, IAMCR – as a rich and generative community for communicating and gaining feedback on their work, meeting people, extending networks, finding collaborators, and helping to shape media and communications, and its research.

The session will feature representatives from IAMCR's governance bodies, including the Executive Board and International Council members, past presidents, and Section and Working Group Heads.

Speakers

- Daya Thussu (Hong Kong Baptist University), IAMCR President
- Karen Arriaza Ibarra (Complutense University of Madrid), IAMCR Vice-president
- Robin Mansell (London School of Economics and Political Science), former IAMCR President
- Cees Hamelink (University of Amsterdam), former IAMCR President
- Ylva Rodny Gumede (University of Johannesburg, South Africa), member of the International Council
- Andrew Ó Baoill (University of Galway), Chair of IAMCR 2026 Local Organising Committee
- Wafa Khalfan (University of Sharjah), Co-Chair, Emerging Scholars Network
- Xavier Ramon (Universitat Pompeu Fabra), Co-Chair Media, Communication and Sport Section
- Anilesh Kumar (Beijing Normal University)
- Hong Kong Baptist University, Vice-chair International Communication Section
- Ruhan Zhao (Communication University of China), Vice-chair Journalism Research and Education Section

PLENARY SESSIONS

PLENARY 2

COMMUNICATING THE CLIMATE CRISIS: TRANSLATING SCIENCE INTO POLICY AND PRACTICE

@ LEE KONG CHIAN LECTURE THEATRE

MONDAY, JULY 14
10:30 – 12:30

While small in size, Singapore faces outsized risks from climate change — risks that may not be immediately visible, especially given the nation's limited natural resources and highly managed environment. So how can a city-state effectively translate scientific insight into public awareness, policy, and meaningful action? What roles do credibility, creativity, and cultural context play in engaging diverse audiences? And how can communication strategies bridge the persistent gap between knowledge and behaviour in an age shaped by digital media?

Bringing together voices from media, policy, climate science, and social media, this panel explores how environmental communication must evolve across platforms and professions to meet the demands of our climate reality. The session aims to spark cross-sector dialogue and offer fresh perspectives for academics, practitioners, and communicators working to make climate change matter—locally and globally.

PANEL CHAIR & MODERATOR:

Edson Tandoc
Co-Chair, IAMCR 2025
Local Organising Committee
President's Chair Professor
Wee Kim Wee School of Communication
and Information, Nanyang Technological
University Singapore

PANELLISTS:

Janil Puthuchery
Senior Minister of State, Ministry of
Education and Ministry of Sustainability
and the Environment, Singapore

Adam Douglas Switzer
Director, CIFAL @ NTU
Professor, Asian School of the
Environment, Assistant Dean
(Development), College of Science, NTU

Audrey Tan
Assistant News Editor (Environment),
The Straits Times,
Singapore Press Holdings

Kong Man Jing (MJ)
Co-founder, Just Keep Thinking

PLENARY 2

SPEAKER PROFILES

Janil Puthucheary

Senior Minister of State, Ministry of Education and Ministry of Sustainability and the Environment, Singapore

Dr Janil Puthucheary is Senior Minister of State at the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Sustainability and the Environment.

Dr Janil Puthucheary is a member of the National Integration Council and an Advisor to Cyber Youth Singapore, and Advisor to Narpani Peravai, People's Association.

He previously held portfolios at the Ministry of Education, the Ministry of Transport, the Ministry of Digital Development and Information and the Ministry of Health.

He chairs OnePeople.sg, which works to promote racial harmony in Singapore, and the Executive Committee of the People's Action Party (PAP) Community Foundation, which provides early childhood education and eldercare services. His political roles include Chair of the Mental Health Group and Whip.

Adam Douglas Switzer

Director, CIFAL @ NTU
Professor, Asian School of the Environment, Assistant Dean (Development), College of Science, NTU

Professor Adam Switzer is a coastal scientist at Nanyang Technological University (NTU), Singapore. He is the founding Director of CIFAL Singapore, a United Nations training centre for sustainable development, and leads the Climate Transformation Programme, which addresses climate risks and solutions in Southeast Asia. His research focuses on sea-level change, tsunamis, and tropical cyclones, integrating geological, historical, and instrumental data to support sustainable coastal planning and disaster risk reduction.

Audrey Tan

Assistant News Editor (Environment), The Straits Times, Singapore Press Holdings

Audrey Tan is an assistant news editor at The Straits Times, a news outlet based in Singapore. She helms coverage of environmental issues at the publication, and has over a decade's worth of experience covering issues related to climate change, biodiversity conservation, and international climate negotiations. She has a special interest in how Southeast Asia is affected by the planetary crises of climate change and nature loss, and how the region is responding to the planetary emergencies. In 2022, she was part of a team that received a grant from the Pulitzer Center's Rainforest Journalism Fund Southeast Asia to pursue an investigative piece on the region's post-pandemic bushmeat trade, and its implications for forest and human health. Audrey holds a masters degree in climate science and policy from the Scripps Institution of Oceanography.

Kong Man Jing (MJ)

Co-founder, Just Keep Thinking

MJ is the co-founder of Just Keep Thinking, an educational media platform that merges science and environmental education with digital storytelling across social media. With a background in environmental biology and teaching, she creates engaging videos, documentaries, and award-winning comic books to raise awareness on biodiversity and sustainability. MJ also leads nature tours, conducts workshops, and recently launched the CDL Eco-Train, a public eco-learning hub. She co-led a government-backed youth panel and represented Singapore's youth delegation at COP29 to amplify youth voices in climate action.

PLENARY 3

ONE HEALTH IN ACTION: GLOBAL INSIGHTS FROM MULTISECTORAL LEADERS

@ LEE KONG CHIAN LECTURE THEATRE

WEDNESDAY, JULY 16
10:30 – 12:30

This plenary session explores the One Health framework through interdisciplinary lens emphasizing how human, animal, and environmental health are interconnected — not only in theory, but in practice on the frontlines of global health concerns. Drawing on real-world case studies such as pandemic response efforts and climate-driven disease outbreaks, the session will discuss how communication practices, information flows shape both the perception and effectiveness of health interventions. Frontline experiences from data scientists, veterinarians, and environmental stewards will be brought into dialogue with academic perspectives. By centering these lived realities alongside scholarly analysis, the plenary invites researchers to critically reflect their roles in contributing to inclusive, context-aware, and actionable One Health solutions.

PANEL CHAIR & MODERATOR:

May Lwin
Associate Provost (Faculty Affairs)
President's Chair Professor of
Communication Studies
Wee Kim Wee School of Communication
and Information Nanyang Technological
University Singapore

PANELLISTS:

Terdsak Yano
Assistant Professor, Department of Food
Animal Clinics, Faculty of Veterinary
Medicine, Chiang Mai University

Kujtim Mersini
Researcher and Lecturer, Veterinary
Epidemiology and Bio-statistics,
Agricultural University of Tirana, One
Health Expert, South East European
Centre for Disease Control,
Tirana, Albania

Tan Sri Dr Jemilah Mahmood
Professor and Executive Director,
Sunway Centre for Planetary Health,
Graduate Centre, Sunway University

PLENARY 3

SPEAKER PROFILES

Terdsak Yano

Assistant Professor, Department of Food Animal Clinics, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Chiang Mai University

Dr Terdsak Yano is an Assistant Professor at the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Chiang Mai University, where he teaches and conducts research in swine medicine. He holds a DVM, MSc, and PhD from Chiang Mai University, and is a Diplomate of the Thai Board of Veterinary Public Health (DTBVPH). His work focuses on swine diseases, epidemiology, and participatory surveillance.

Dr Yano is a trainer in Participatory Epidemiology across Thailand and Southeast Asia, and has led research on Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) in Northern Thailand, including studies on risk factors, outbreaks, and vaccine efficacy. He has also

contributed to efforts addressing Streptococcus suis infections in both pigs and humans. Notably, he co-developed the Participatory One Health Disease Detection (PODD) system — an animal and human health digital surveillance platform now managed by the PODD Centre at Chiang Mai University.

PLENARY 3

SPEAKER PROFILES

Kujtim Mersini

Researcher and Lecturer, Veterinary Epidemiology and Bio-statistics, Agricultural University of Tirana, One Health Expert, South East European Centre for Disease Control, Tirana, Albania

Dr Kujtim Mersinaj is a veterinary epidemiologist with over 20 years of experience advancing public, animal, and environmental health through a One Health approach. He is a researcher and lecturer at the Agricultural University of Tirana, and a senior One Health expert at the South East European Centre for Disease Control. He holds a PhD in Epidemiology and has taught biostatistics, infectious diseases, and epidemiology across various academic and professional programmes. Dr Mersinaj previously led Albania's national Veterinary Epidemiology Department, where he spearheaded zoonotic disease control efforts targeting brucellosis, anthrax, rabies, and

avian influenza. A specialist in digital disease surveillance, he designed Albania's national veterinary information system and contributed to the development of the integrated infectious disease surveillance system during the COVID-19 pandemic. He collaborates with international agencies such as the EU, FAO, and WHO, and has also contributed to environmental conservation efforts in Albania. His work bridges science and policy to strengthen disease preparedness and resilience across Southeast Europe.

Tan Sri Dr Jemilah Mahmood

Professor and Executive Director, Sunway Centre for Planetary Health, Graduate Centre, Sunway University

Dr. Mahmood is a medical professional with more than two decades of experience managing crises in health, disasters and conflict settings. She is currently Professor and Executive Director of the Sunway Centre for Planetary Health at Sunway University in Malaysia. She holds advisory council roles in the Government of Malaysia in Climate and Higher Education. She is also an Adjunct Professor at Universiti Malaya, the Sustainability Advisor at Air Asia, and the national advisor of the Malaysian Red Crescent Society. Globally, she is a member of the boards of Roche in Switzerland, the Norwegian

Refugee Council, Global Ambassador for the Humanitarian Grand Bargain, and the Climate Action Accelerator in Geneva. She currently co-chairs the World Economic Forum Steering Committee on Climate and Health and is a board member of the Global Future Council for Clean Air.

SPECIAL AND PARTNER SESSIONS

ICCA @ IAMCR

THE TRANSFORMATIVE IMPACT OF DISRUPTIVE AI ON TRUST AND ENGAGEMENT IN MEDIA

HSS CONFERENCE ROOM

MONDAY, 14 JULY
14:00

In today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, disruptive AI technologies are revolutionizing not only industries but also the dynamics of human interaction with technology and each other. Within the media realm, these advancements are reshaping content production and consumption while challenging established notions of trust and authenticity. As AI-generated content becomes increasingly commonplace, audiences are faced with the dual challenge of engaging with this content while discerning credible information from misleading sources. This situation prompts essential discussions about the responsibilities of both media creators and consumers in managing an increasingly AI-driven society.

This panel will explore the implications of AI technologies on audience attention, interaction, information dissemination, and trust in AI-generated content through four distinct presentations. Prof. Shuhua Zhou will examine how AI newscasters impact audience attention and entertainment value. Prof. Trisha Lin will investigate the exposure, detection, and sharing of deepfakes in Taiwan using a mixed-method approach. Dr. Shaohai Jiang will analyze the

intentions of young adults in Singapore to use AI chatbots for mental health support. Finally, Prof. Yunya Song will discuss the varying perceptions of trust and how they influence user acceptance and engagement with AI technologies. Together, these discussions aim to deepen our understanding of AI's role in shaping media trust and engagement.

CHAIRS:

Yu-li Liu
Distinguished Professor, School of Journalism and Communication, Shanghai University, China

SPEAKERS:

Shuhua Zhou, Mulin Jiang, Nisi, Yang Wu
City University of Hong Kong; Tsinghua University

Trisha T. C. Lin, Jessy C. Y. Lin
Distinguished Professor, College of Communication, and PhD Student, Department of Management Information Systems, National Chengchi University, Taiwan

Shaohai Jiang, Sing Wei En Wayne
National University of Singapore

Yunya Song, Xuanyu Shi, Jingyi Zhang
The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology

AMIC @ IAMCR

ASIAN MEDIA INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION CENTRE INC. (AMIC) WITH THE COLLEGE OF DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION-UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES LOS BANOS

THE HIVE LHS-TR+27

MONDAY, 14 JULY
14:00

Act now or it's too late for planet Earth. The urgency to address environmental challenges has reached a critical juncture. In response, environmental communication education has emerged as a crucial component of communication and journalism curricula. Its primary objective is to foster a deeper understanding of environmental issues and promote sustainable practices. Environmental communication education plays a pivotal role in shaping the next generation, empowering young individuals to make informed decisions and take meaningful actions toward a sustainable future.

This panel discussion will explore the following key issues:

- 1) How are Asian communication and journalism schools addressing the opportunities and challenges of developing critical environmental consciousness and practices?
- 2) What core communication competencies are essential for effective environmental communication?
- 3) What innovative teaching-learning strategies can be employed to enhance environmental communication education?
- 4) What lessons can communication and journalism schools share with the broader education system at regional and national levels?

CHAIRS:

Ramon Guillermo R. Tuazon
Secretary-General, AMIC

SPEAKERS:

Pamela A. Custodio
Associate Professor, College of Development Communication, University of the Philippines Los Banos

Muneo Kaigo
Dean, Graduate School of Humanities and Social Sciences University of Tsukuba

Sadia Jamil
Assistant Professor, School of International Communications, University of Nottingham, Ningbo, China

Shameen Rezza
Professor, Department of Mass Communication and Journalism, University of Dhaka

ALAIC @ IAMCR

GLOBAL DIALOGUES AND LATIN AMERICAN PERSPECTIVES IN COMMUNICATION STUDIES

THE HIVE LHS-TR+27

TUESDAY, 15 JULY
08:30

Representatives of the main communication organisations in Latin America will participate in this roundtable. The objective is for each speaker, from their organisation or perspective, to present a map of the challenges and problems, along with a brief state-of-the-art overview of the major issues concerning the academic field of Latin American communication—including teaching, research, schools, research centres, and connections with governments and organised civil society. A second objective is to outline the region's challenges from a communication perspective and highlight some of the actions organisations are taking to address them.

CHAIRS:

Andrea Medrado
IAMCR Vice president, Senior Lecturer in Global Communications, University of Exeter

SPEAKERS:

Fernando Paulino
ALAIC

Juan Ramos
FELAFACS

Juliano Domingues da Silva
INTERCOM and Sociedad Brasileña de Estudios Interdisciplinarios de la Comunicación

INTER/ACTIONS: MULTIMODAL ACADEMIC COMMUNICATION TASK FORCE

MEDIA AND COMMUNICATION RESEARCH THROUGH A MULTIMODAL LENS

THE HIVE LHS-TR+36

TUESDAY, 15 JULY
10:30

To launch its report on multimodal scholarship, IAMCR's Task Force INTER/ACTIONS: Multimodal Academic Communication proposes a special roundtable session that will facilitate a broader conversation about the importance of multimodal research, teaching, and publishing in media and communication studies. The following questions will guide the conversation:

- 1) How and to what ends do arts-based methodologies and affective modes of knowledge production expand the boundaries of scholarly communication beyond written texts?
- 2) What can be learned from the various approaches to multimodal scholarship in different parts of the world?
- 3) What are the different models for thinking about multimodal scholarship and academic promotions globally?
- 4) What kind of institutional support do emerging scholars need in this space?

By tackling these questions, the roundtable session will chart some of the epistemological, methodological, ethical, practical, and pedagogical considerations involved in multimodal scholarship. In doing so, it will also reflect on the Task Force's work over the last two years. Welcoming the founding of a new working group on multimodal research, the session will conclude with a discussion about what strategies IAMCR – as a leading academic organization in the field – may implement to further support the work of scholars who embrace multimodality.

SPEAKERS:

Sandra Ristovska
Associate Professor, University of Colorado Boulder, USA

Nico Carpentier
Professor, Charles University, the Czech Republic

Aysu Arsoy
Associate Professor, Eastern Mediterranean University, Cyprus

UNESCO

PRESS AND THE PLANET: PROMOTING SAFETY OF JOURNALISTS AND INFORMATION INTEGRITY TO ADDRESS ENVIRONMENTAL CHALLENGES

THE HIVE LHS-TR+53

TUESDAY, 15 JULY
14:00

Presentations:

Raúl Fernández Daza: Video Message
– Promoting the Global Roadmap for Information as a Public Good in the Face of the Environmental Crisis and the Safety of Journalists

Luciano Mazza de Andrade: Keynote Speech
– Building on the G20 Momentum, Advancing Global Information Integrity as We Look Toward COP30 and the Urgent Need for Climate Action

Libby Lester: Understanding How Media Narratives Shape Public Engagement is Essential for Fostering Trust in Environmental Science and Policy

Kunda Dixit: Emerging Trends in Environmental Journalism Reveal Both Growing Threats to Press Freedom and New Opportunities to Build Public Trust

Ramon R. Tuazon: Ensuring the Safety of Journalists is Essential to Protecting the Integrity of Environmental Reporting and Public Action

CHAIR:

Tarja Turtia
Senior Programme Specialist, Section for Universal Access to Information and Digital Inclusion, Division for Digital Inclusion and Policies and Digital Transformation, UNESCO

SPEAKERS:

Raúl Fernández Daza
Ambassador and Permanent Delegate of Chile to UNESCO, Chair of the Intergovernmental Council of the International Programme for the Development of Communication (IPDC) (video message)

Luciano Mazza de Andrade
Ambassador of Federative Republic of Brazil to Singapore

Ramon R. Tuazon
AMIC Secretary General

Kunda Dixit
Chief editor of Nepali Times, co-publisher at Himalmedia, and author of "Dateline Earth: Journalism As If The Planet Mattered"

Libby Lester
Professor (Research) and Director, Monash University and Monash Climate Change Communication Research Hub

ICA @ IAMCR PANEL

PUBLISHING INTERNATIONAL SCHOLARSHIP DURING TIMES OF DISRUPTION AND SOCIAL CHANGE

THE HIVE LHS-TR+27

TUESDAY, 15 JULY
16:00

This panel brings together scholars from the International Communication Association to discuss the dynamics of publishing scholarly work amid times of disruption, social change, and threats to academic freedom. By bringing together a diverse group of experienced scholars and editors, we aim to foster a collaborative discussion on future strategies and practices that can enhance the visibility and impact of international research, and support "scholarship at risk." Our conversation will cover key topics such as publishing practices that amplify underrepresented voices and promote access to publishing and knowledge dissemination. Speakers will share collaborative approaches that harness the strengths of international scholarly associations and networks to support shared goals and collective efforts.

CHAIR:

Elisia Cohen
University of Minnesota, United States

SPEAKERS:

Barbie Zelizer
University of Pennsylvania, United States

Winston Mano
University of Westminster,
United Kingdom

Ke Guo
Shanghai International Studies
University, China

Jack Qiu
Nanyang Technological University,
Singapore

Ingrid Bachmann
Pontificia Universidad
Católica de Chile, Chile

Yunya Song, Xuanyu Shi, Jingyi Zhang
The Hong Kong University of Science
and Technology

IAMCR TASK FORCE FOR GAMAG

WOMEN AND THE MEDIA: HIGHLIGHTING A FUTURE AGENDA FOR THE POST-BEIJING PLATFORM FOR ACTION +30

THE HIVE LHS-TR+27

WEDNESDAY, 16 JULY
14:00

The Beijing Platform for Action has been the roadmap for promoting gender equality in and through the media and digital communication, particularly through Section J, "Women and the Media," and the recommendations included in its two Strategic Objectives. The PBA has remained relevant thanks to the work of academics, journalists, and women working in the media.

However, evidence shows that these recommendations have been largely ignored by governments and media, telecommunications, and ICT companies. New industry players, such as social media platforms, have also failed to take responsibility for implementing effective strategies to protect women from online violence.

Using the PBA as a roadmap, within the framework of its 30th anniversary, it is urgent to question existing norms and strengthen mechanisms to reinforce gender equality within these sectors through actions such as: promoting regulatory and self-regulatory mechanisms in these industries at national, regional, and international levels; eliminating

sexism and gender discrimination in media and digital communication content; fostering equal access and participation of women at all levels of the communication industries, ensuring full protection of their labor rights; implementing frameworks for algorithmic transparency in digital platforms, including methods such as audits; promoting digital and media literacy programs with a gender perspective; encouraging efforts by women's organizations to use digital media and online spaces to exercise their right to communication and enhance their economic empowerment; ensuring safe conditions for women journalists and professionals in media and telecommunications organizations; eliminating cyber-violence and other forms of gender-based violence in digital spaces (such as the recruitment of women and girls by criminal organizations for sexual exploitation); integrating a gender perspective into the curricula of communication and journalism schools; and fostering academic research on all dimensions of the gender and communication agenda to develop informed policies and regulations.

The purpose of this Special Session is to highlight areas for a future agenda for the Beijing+30.

CHAIRS:

Claudia Padovani
University of Padova, Italy

Lisa French
RMIT, Australia

SPEAKERS:

Claudia Padovani
University of Padova, Italy

Lisa French
RMIT, Australia

Maria Soledad Vargas
Pontificia Universidad
Católica de Valparaíso, Chile

Mark Poole
RMIT, Australia

ARTICULATING THE URBAN AND COMMUNICATION: A TRIBUTE TO GARY GUMPERT

THE HIVE LHS-TR+36

WEDNESDAY, 16 JULY
16:00

Urban Communication has been one of IAMCR's areas of interest, partially through the collaboration with the Urban Communication Foundation (UCF). Now that Gary Gumpert, the founder of the UCF, has passed away, this panel will take stock of the current state of urban communication and the legacy of Gary Gumpert. Friends and colleagues of Gary are warmly invited to join this panel.

CHAIRS:

Nico Carpentier
Charles University, Czech Republic

SPEAKERS:

Peter Haratonik

Janet Wasko
University of Oregon, United States

Myria Georgiou
London School of Economics and
Political Science, United Kingdom

Cees Hamelink
University of Amsterdam,
Netherlands

IAMCR AWARDS CEREMONY

THE HIVE LHS-TR+27

THURSDAY, 17 JULY

08:30

IAMCR offers awards to recognise the contribution of outstanding conference papers to the field of Communication and Media Studies. This special session aims to create a platform where conference participants can get to know the recipients of the IAMCR awards. The speakers include the IAMCR President, Treasurer, representatives of the award selection committees, and the recipients of the IAMCR awards who will be present in Singapore.

CONVENORS:

Daya Thussu
IAMCR President

Skye Doherty
IAMCR Treasurer

PUBLICATIONS COMMITTEE SPECIAL SESSION

THE HIVE LHS-TR+27

THURSDAY, 17 JULY

10:30

Open Access is a fundamental element of inclusive, accessible publishing for IAMCR. The Publications Committee has been hosting a series of webinars and discussions about Open Access, as part of its mandate to promote global perspectives and opportunities for information and knowledge exchange and to promote globally inclusive scholarship. However, it is also a challenging landscape, with questions of accessibility, language, academic recognition, content control, and means of implementation needing further consideration and discussion.

This session is inviting IAMCR members to come together to reflect on the lessons we have learned over the past two years regarding Open Access through the Publications Committee-hosted webinars and discussion sessions. We aim to explore the following questions:

- 1) What are the current concerns and questions regarding Open Access from diverse geographic and language perspectives?
- 2) What are the challenges that IAMCR can take action on to increase access to publication for global scholars?
- 3) What have we learned from the experience of IAMCR members about challenges, strategies, and opportunities for Open Access publication?
- 4) How do we create pathways for Open Access?

CONVENORS:

IAMCR Publications Committee

CHAIRS:

Maria Michalis
University of Westminster,
United Kingdom

Sarah Cardey
University of Reading, United Kingdom

CLOSING CEREMONY

COMMUNICATING FOR A MULTIVOCAL WORLD

@ LEE KONG CHIAN LECTURE THEATRE

THURSDAY, JULY 17
15:45 - 17:45

This closing plenary promotes horizontal dialogue among scholars from diverse cultural and intellectual traditions. In the spirit of IAMCR, it invites meaningful conversation among panellists with deep ties to other international professional communication associations. Together, they will explore how to embrace difference with dignity in an increasingly polarised world.

CHAIR:

Daya Thussu
President, IAMCR
Professor of International Communication,
Hong Kong Baptist University

PANELLISTS:

Cees Hamelink
Emeritus Professor of Communication Science, University of Amsterdam
Professor of Human Rights and Global Health, Vrije Universiteit, Amsterdam
Former President, IAMCR (1990–1994)

Jack Qiu
Co-Chair, IAMCR 2025
Local Organising Committee Chair and Shaw Foundation Prof of Media Technology, Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University

Andrea Medrado
Vice President, IAMCR
Senior Lecturer,
University of Exeter, UK

Ramon Tuazon
Secretary-General, Asian Media Information and Communication Centre (AMIC)

Ylva Rodny Gumedé
Head, Division for Global Engagement,
University of Johannesburg, South Africa

SPEAKER PROFILES

Cees Hamelink

**Emeritus Professor of Communication Science, University of Amsterdam
Professor of Human Rights and Global Health, Vrije Universiteit, Amsterdam
Former President, IAMCR (1990–1994)**

Dr. Cees Hamelink – honorary president of the IAMCR- studied psychology of religion and moral philosophy in Amsterdam and worked as journalist, policy adviser and researcher in many different institutions and countries. He was consultant to several intergovernmental organisations, among them FAO and UNESCO and to UN Secretary General Kofi Annan. He was adviser to many governments on the planning of national communication policies. He received several life-time achievement awards for his contribution and commitment to programmes for social change. He is emeritus professor of international communication at the University of Amsterdam. In 2010 he was appointed Athena Professor of Global Health and Human Rights at the Vrije Universiteit, Amsterdam. He is also honorary professor at the Universidad Autonoma del Estado Hidalgo in Mexico.

He published over 20 books on corporate media, technology policy, the role of news media in peace and conflict and the right to communication.

Jack Qiu

**Co-Chair, IAMCR 2025, Local Organising Committee, Chair and Shaw Foundation
Prof of Media Technology, Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information,
Nanyang Technological University**

Professor Jack Qiu is the Chair and Shaw Foundation Professor of Media Technology at the Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information (WKWSCI), Nanyang Technological University (NTU), where he directs the Asian Communication Research Centre (ACRC). His work focuses on digital media and social change, particularly in Asia and the Global South. Professor Qiu publishes in both English and Chinese, with some of his works translated into French, German, Italian,

Japanese, Korean, Portuguese, and Spanish. He is an elected Fellow of the International Communication Association (ICA) and a recipient of the C. Edwin Baker Award for the Advancement of Scholarship on Media, Markets and Democracy. He also served as a Past President of the Chinese Communication Association (CCA).

SPEAKER PROFILES

Andrea Medrado

Vice President, IAMCR, Senior Lecturer, University of Exeter, UK

Dr Andrea Medrado is a Senior Lecturer in Global Communications and the Co-Director of Research for the Department of Communications, Drama and Film of the University of Exeter in the UK. She is also Co-Vice-President of IAMCR. Andrea is currently a Co-Investigator for the Project "The Social Foundations of Cryptography", funded by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) in the UK, and a Principal Investigator the Project "AIM: AI from/in the Margins", funded by the INCT DSI Consortium in Brazil. She recently published the book "Media

Activism, Artivism and the Fight Against Marginalisation in the Global South" (2023), co-authored with Isabella Rega. She has also published widely in academic journals, such as Big Data & Society, Information Communication & Society, and Tapuya. Her research interests include South-to-South communication, media activism and artivism in the Global South, critical AI and data studies, ethnographic and participatory methods.

Ramon Tuazon

Secretary-General, Asian Media Information and Communication Centre (AMIC)

Ramon Guillermo R. Tuazon is the Secretary-General of the Asian Media Information and Communication Centre, Inc. (AMIC).

From 2020-2024, he served as Communication Specialist at UNESCO Office in Yangon. He assumed the same post from 2012 to 2014.

Mr. Tuazon was president of the Asian Institute of Journalism and Communication (AIJC) from 2007-2020.

He brings over 35 years of experience in communication planning, management, and evaluation.

He was co-author of Media and Information Literacy: Curriculum for Teachers (UNESCO, 2011); Media and Information Literate Citizens: Think Critically, Click Wisely 2nd edition (UNESCO; 2021) Myanmar Journalists' Toolkit in Cultural and Ethnic Reporting (UNESCO 2023); and Towards a MIL Competency Framework in Myanmar (UNESCO 2020).

He has made contributions to numerous international publications focusing on MIL, Safety of Journalists, and Freedom of Expression.

Mr. Tuazon teaches communication subjects in several Philippine universities. He received his Master in Communication Management from the AIJC.

SPEAKER PROFILES

Ylva Rodny Gumede

Head, Division for Global Engagement, University of Johannesburg, South Africa

Professor Ylva Rodny-Gumede is currently the Head of the Division for Global Engagement and a full Professor in the School of Communication at the University of Johannesburg. She holds a PhD from the School of Oriental and African Studies (SOAS), London University as well as an MA degree in Politics from the University of Witwatersrand in South Africa and an MA in Journalism from Cardiff

University in the U.K. She also holds a certificate in Executive Leadership from the Johannesburg Business School, South Africa. Ylva has held fellowships at Universities in South Africa and abroad, including London School of Economics, Duke University in the U.S and University of Aarhus in Denmark.

RESEARCH @ NTU WKWSCI RESEARCH CENTRES

ASIAN COMMUNICATION RESEARCH CENTRE (ACRC)

RESEARCH AREAS

Digital Labour Platforms	Popular Culture Heritage Studies
Asian Cinema	Documentaries

CENTRE DIRECTOR Professor Jack Qiu
Discover more at: <https://www.ntu.edu.sg/acrc>

CENTRE FOR HEALTHY AND SUSTAINABLE CITIES (CHESS)

RESEARCH AREAS

Healthy Ageing	Tech & Healthcare
Science Communication	Telemedicine
Sustainability	Gamification

CENTRE DIRECTORS Professor May Lwin
Professor Theng Yin Leng
Discover more at: <https://www.ntu.edu.sg/chess>

ASIAN CENTRE FOR HEALTH BEHAVIOURAL INSIGHTS & INTERVENTIONS (HABITS)

RESEARCH AREAS

Chronic Disease	Behavioural Science
Lifestyle Habits	Social Factors
Mental Wellbeing	Health Interventions

CENTRE DIRECTOR Professor May Lwin
Discover more at: <https://www.westudyhabits.com>

CENTRE FOR INFORMATION INTEGRITY AND THE INTERNET (IN-cube)

RESEARCH AREAS

Internet and Well-being	Digital Journalism
Fake News and Scams	Online Harms
Emerging Tech (AI & VR)	Online Privacy
Social Media & Analytics	Big Data

CENTRE DIRECTOR Professor Edson Tandoc
Discover more at: <https://www.ntu.edu.sg/incube>

We welcome research partnerships across academia, industry, and government.

Find out more about our research

Find out more by contacting:
WKWSCI-RESEARCH@ntu.edu.sg

CONFERENCE DINNER

CONFERENCE DINNER

@ FLOWER DOME, GARDENS BY THE BAY

WEDNESDAY, JULY 16
19:00 - LATE

Join us for an unforgettable evening at the Flower Dome in Gardens by the Bay, one of Singapore's most iconic attractions. Set against the stunning backdrop of the Marina Bay skyline, this venue offers a unique blend of architectural beauty and natural wonder.

Guests will enjoy a specially curated dinner featuring a vibrant, thematic menu with interactive live stations celebrating Singapore's rich culinary heritage. The evening includes complimentary entry to the Flower Dome and exclusive after-hours access from 9:00 PM to 11:00 PM, a one-way transfer from the conference venue, and a complimentary alcoholic drink to toast the occasion.

Enjoy an evening of meaningful conversations, fresh ideas, and new connections over great food and drinks in a truly stunning setting. It's the perfect mid-conference breather to relax, mingle, and be inspired.

SPECIAL EXHIBITIONS & SCREENINGS

SPECIAL EXHIBITIONS

14 - 17 JULY
08:00 - 19:00

@ WKWSCI RESEARCH HUB

1 A Visual Essay on the House of European History's Constructions of Europeanity
by Nico Carpentier

This exhibition will focus on the representations of Europeanity in the Brussels-based House of European History (HEH), analysing the multiplicity of its significations through 19 photomontages. The 19 photomontages use the method of juxtaposition, communicating the core characteristics of the HEH's construction of Europeanity and showing the contradictions in the more essentialist dimensions of the HEH permanent exhibition.

@ WKWSCI RESEARCH HUB

2 The Cabinet of Lost Memories
by Aysu Arsoy

This exhibition explores the olfactory memories of internally displaced Cypriots, drawing on the role of sensory modalities — specifically scent, sound, and photography — in constructing representations of 'home.' Through a multisensory mixed media installation combining photographic imagery, soundscapes, and ambient odors (printed photos - light - video -sound founded objects), the work evokes a nostalgic reconstruction of belonging and displacement. Extending this notion to olfactory and auditory domains, the exhibition engages with the symbolic interaction of these modalities, enabling viewers to form a sensory and affective understanding of identity, memory, and place.

@ WKWSCI RESEARCH HUB

3 Justice by Video: An Interactive Multimodal Exhibition
by Sandra Ristovska

From cell phones to police body cameras, today's courts increasingly use video as evidence. The U.S. Department of Justice estimates that video appears in about 80% of criminal cases. Yet U.S. courts, at all levels, lack clear guidelines on how video can be used and presented as evidence. This interactive exhibition explores the intricacies of seeing video in court. It asks the viewer to consider how to better use video so that justice is indeed equal and fair for all.

@ WKWSCI MEDIA COLAB

4 Hourglass*
by Charis Chua, Eric Teo, Srinidhi Ragavendran, and Marcus Yeo

The Hourglass exhibition is a deep dive exploration into the sources of sand and looks at systems, displacement and the unseen cost of building a nation. This space also pulls back the curtain on the processes behind the film: the hours spent tracing sand barges, filming in Vietnam and asking difficult questions about a topic that still leaves much to be uncovered.

*Virtual Reality Experience available on Tuesday, 15 July, 13:00 – 20:00.

SPECIAL SCREENINGS

FLOW34 - 2025 EDITION

@ WKWSCV TV STUDIO

14 - 17 JULY
08:30 - 19:30

Flow34 is a curated platform designed to showcase innovative audio-visual works that blend academic insight with artistic expression. It features a diverse selection of videos that skilfully combine research with aesthetics to communicate knowledge in compelling, multimodal ways.

All Flow34 works will be screened throughout the conference on a continuous loop. Attendees are also invited to meet and engage with the creators during their scheduled parallel sessions.

1 Multimodal Communication, Art, and Knowledge Production: An Exploratory Study of the Relationships Between Forms and Content
Directors: Rodrigo Portari and Pedro Oliveira
Duration: 11 minutes 26 seconds

This scientific audiovisual essay presents conceptual insights for arts-based research and discusses various practices of multimodal communication.

2 People in a Small Park
Directors: Xiangning Hong and Ziyu Feng
Duration: 19 minutes 55 seconds

This multimodal research project reveals the poetic coexistence of strangers and the quiet profundity of human presence in shared spaces. More than a portrait of a park, it is a meditation on existence—fleeting, unscripted, and sincere. In each passing face, we glimpse the universality of being, paused for a moment in time.

3 Pen-and-Paper Games as Platforms to Create Environmental Texts
Director: Ahmed Hazyl Hilmy
Duration: 26 minutes 14 seconds

Journaling games are an emergent form of a role-playing game in which the player writes, and sometimes draws, a story based on prompts and random elements (such as dice rolls). This video documents initial findings on how journaling games with environmental themes enable players to practice ecological thinking by creating their own personal environmental texts in which they imagine alternate relationships with the natural world.

4 AGON: Constructions of Democracy
Directors: Ali Minanto, Nico Carpentier and John Sany Purwanto
Duration: 25 minutes 48 seconds

AGON: Constructions of Democracy is a film essay that experiments with the reconciliation of academic and artistic approaches. It is an invitation to consider what democracy is and what it can be, how it is linked to space, how it is a location of political struggle, and how it is threatened and always in need of active protection.

5 Scenes of the Election in Cuiabá: Far Right Despises Political Debate on Environmental Destruction
Director: Pedro Oliveira
Duration: 8 minutes 58 seconds

This scientific audiovisual essay analyzes the issue of extreme heat in Cuiabá and the relationship of strength and weakness of the debate on climate justice between the extreme right and the democratic left in the mayoral election of the capital of Mato Grosso, in the heart of South America, in 2024.

SCREENING BY THE ASIAN FILM ARCHIVE (AFA)

@ WKWSCI LEE FOUNDATION LECTURE THEATRE

SUNDAY, 13 JULY
14:30 - 16:30

The Asian Film Archive (AFA), founded in 2005, is a non-profit organisation dedicated to preserving the rich film heritage of Singapore and Asian Cinema. It promotes scholarly research and encourages critical appreciation of film as an art form.

This special screening, held prior to the opening ceremony, introduces the IAMCR community to the work of AFA and the valuable archival resources available to media scholars. The event also highlights the challenges and opportunities in areas such as the responsible use of AI in archives and sustainability in digital preservation.

The session will begin with an introduction by **Karen Chan**, Executive Director of the AFA, followed by a screening of the restored Singaporean film *Ring of Fury*.

1 Ring of Fury (1973)
Directors: Tony Yeow and James Sebastian
Language: Mandarin
(with English and Chinese subtitles)
Duration: 78 minutes
Rating: PG

A humble noodle-seller refuses to pay protection fees to a gang of thugs. After a tragic loss, he trains in martial arts to seek justice and confront the gang's mysterious masked leader. Banned in Singapore for over 30 years, *Ring of Fury* is the country's first and only classic martial arts film. It was restored in 2017 by the AFA from a surviving 35mm release print.

SCREENING BY WKWSCI FILMMAKERS

@ WKWSCI LEE FOUNDATION LECTURE THEATRE

TUESDAY, 15 JULY
18:00 - 19:30

Join us for a screening of two thought-provoking short films by filmmakers from the Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information. Each screening will be followed by a Q&A session with the respective director(s).

As digital natives, these filmmakers explore the emotional toll of climate anxiety and the overwhelming influx of environmental information in the digital age. *Fading Frequencies* and *Hourglass* present immersive, personal perspectives on ecological crises that aim to inspire deeper reflection and dialogue.

2 Fading Frequencies
Director: Wayne Lim
Duration: 8 minutes

This contemplative documentary follows a field recordist in Iceland on a journey to reconnect with the natural world. Through haunting soundscapes, the film offers a quiet yet urgent reflection on the sonic dimensions of climate change and the deepening disconnection between humanity and nature.

3 Hourglass
Producer: Charis Chua
Director: Eric Teo
Director of Photography: Srinidhi Ragavendran
Editor: Marcus Yeo
Duration: 14 minutes

An investigative short documentary exploring the environmental cost of sand — the world's second-most exploited natural resource. *Hourglass* traces the link between Singapore's urban expansion and the vanishing shores of Vietnam's Mekong Delta, where sand mining displaces communities and accelerates land loss. Combining immersive visuals with rigorous research, the film spotlights an often-overlooked ecological crisis.

¹ Still image from *Ring of Fury* (1973, James Sebastian & Tony Yeow), courtesy of Asian Film Archive

DAY-TO-DAY SCHEDULE

with All Section and Working
Group Parallel sessions

SECTIONS AND WORKING GROUPS

Most parallel sessions in this programme are organised by IAMCR's thematic Sections and Working Groups, each of which is identified in this scheduled with a three letter code.

AUD - Audience Section
COA - Comic Art Working Group
CPN - Communication in Post- and Neo-Authoritarian Societies Working Group
CPT - Communication Policy and Technology Section
CJD - Communication, Social Justice and Democracy Working Group
CAM - Community Communication and Alternative Media Section - CAM
CRI - Crisis, Security and Conflict Communication Working Group
DIM - Diaspora and Media Working Group
DID - Digital Divide Working Group
ESN - Emerging Scholars Network Section
ESR - Environment, Science & Risk Communication Section
ETH - Ethics of Society and Ethics of Communication Working Group
GEN - Gender and Communication Section
GMP - Global Media Policy Working Group
HEC - Health Communication Working Group
HIS - History Section
ICO - Inclusive Communication and People with Disabilities Working Group
INC - International Communication Section
ISM - Islam and Media Working Group

Special and Partner Sessions, organised by IAMCR committees or outside partners, are identified with the code SPS.

JRE - Journalism Research and Education Section
LAW - Law Section
MER - Media Education Research Section
MPA - Media Production Analysis Working Group
MCS - Media, Communication & Sport Section
MPS - Mediated Communication, Public Opinion and Society Section
MSD - Media Sector Development Working Group
MCR - Multimodal Communication Research Working Group
MAR - Music, Audio, Radio and Sound Working Group
ORG - Organisational Communication Working Group
PCR - Participatory Communication Research Section
POL - Political Communication Research Section
POE - Political Economy Section
POP - Popular Culture Working Group
PSM - Public Service Media Policies Working Group
REC - Religion and Communication Working Group
RUC - Rural Communication Working Group
VIC - Visual Culture Working Group

https://iamcr.org/singapore2025/draft_programme -/-_programme2025@iamcr.org

Sunday, 13 July

14:00 **General Registration**
Venue - Singapore Hokkien Huay Kuan Building (SHHK)

17:00 **Panel Opening Ceremony and Keynote**
Venue - Nanyang Auditorium

» Keynote Speaker: Peng Hwa Ang, Professor of Communication and Information at Nanyang Technological University, Singapore

Monday, 14 July

08:30 **Panel : POP-1**
POP - From challenging gender to challenging 'gender'
Venue - The Hive LHS-LT
Organised by: Dr. Florian Vanlee (Panel Chair) (Belgium)

Cyber-Fatherhood in Life Simulation Games: The Role of Game Affordances and Algorithmic Patriarchy

» [Ms. Luyao Guo](#) (China)¹ (1. 济南大学文学院)

"What bothers me is all the wokes behind this." Framing Québec's 2023 controversy on drag story hour

» [Prof. David Myles](#) (Canada)¹, [Ms. Annette Johnson](#) (Canada)², [Prof. Virginie Hébert](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Institut national de la recherche scientifique, 2. Université du Québec à Montréal)

Adolescents' discourses on LGBTIQ+ media: from "tokenism" to "forced inclusion"

» [Mx. Vitor Blanco-Fernández](#) (Spain)¹, [Ms. Anna Iñigo](#) (Spain)² (1. Pompeu Fabra University, 2. University of Barcelona)

Subverting Gender Stereotypes and the Male Gaze: A Critical Analysis of the "LaoDeng Movies" Social Media Hashtag

» [Mr. Jiahang Xu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Kunyue Xu](#) (China)² (1. Communication University of China, Beijing, 2. Communication University of China)

Wanna be Free Like Me? How Do Chinese Female Diaspora Lifestyle Wanghong Strategize Identities for Personal Branding on Xiaohongshu

» [Ms. Ying Qin](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Ji Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. Fudan University, School of Journalism)

08:30 **Panel : HEC-5**
HEC - Digital platforms and our health
Venue - WKWSCI L2 Executive Seminar Room
Organised by: Dr. Livingston White (Panel Chair) (Jamaica) and Dr. Chen Luo (Discussant) (China)

Democratizing Health through Digital Platforms: Examining Health and Fitness Channels in India

» [Dr. K Karthik](#) (India)¹ (1. Central University of Karnataka)

From Bio-politics to Digital Governance: Patient Autonomy and the Controversy of Standardization in Electronic Health Records (EHRs)

» [Ms. Junming Shj](#) (Australia)¹, [Ms. Zihan Xu](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Melbourne)

Living Toward Death: Emotional Interactions and Life Experiences in Digital Farewell Behaviors — An Online Ethnographic Study of Terminally Ill Individuals with Middle- to Late-Stage Cancer

» [Prof. LINGBO TU](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Yuchun Wu](#) (China)¹, [Mr. JINGYI YANG](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

Digital Pathways to Traditional Wellness: A Cognitive-Emotional Analysis of How New Media Engages Youth in Chinese Health-Preservation (Yangsheng) behaviors

» [Dr. Xinjie Lin](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Fangfang Gao](#) (China)², [Ms. Xinyan Xu](#) (China)² (1. Minjiang University, 2. Zhejiang University)

Digital Memory, Cultural Trauma, and Social Reintegration: A Health Communication Perspective on Leprosy Memory in Online Communities

» [Dr. Lan Zhao](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University)

08:30 **Panel : AUD-1**

AUD - Resistance in audience research

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+47

Organised by: [Dr. María Soto-Sanfiel](#) (Panel Chair) (Singapore)

Shock and adaption in opinion research: incivility, disinformation, and the authenticity challenge in synthetic generative AI content

» [Dr. Asta Zelenkauskaite](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Nina Springer](#) (Germany)², [Dr. Christian Baden](#) (Israel)³ (1. Drexel University, 2. University of Münster, 3. Hebrew University of Jerusalem)

Folk Theories About Media Trust: How German Users from Different Social Milieus Navigate Trustworthiness in High-Choice Information Environments

» [Dr. Anna Litvinenko](#) (Germany)¹, [Mr. Florian Primig](#) (Germany)¹, [Ms. Anna-Theresa Mayer](#) (Germany)², [Prof. Christoph Neuberger](#) (Germany)² (1. Freie Universität Berlin, 2. Weizenbaum Institute)

Authoritarian Power and User Resistance: How Users Respond/Resist Politically Manipulated Algorithms on Douyin

» [Ms. Hui Lin](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. King's College London)

The Politics of Idol Worship: Authoritarian Compliance and Resistance in Chinese K-pop Fandom

» [Ms. Xianzhi Ma](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Performing the Underdog: Reverse Identity and Subcultural Resistance Among Chinese Youth in Virtual Games

» [Mr. Qianhui Ju](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Yuguo Luo](#) (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. The London School of Economics and Political Science)

08:30

Panel : JRE-1

JRE - Journalism in the digital age I

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+49

Organised by: [Dr. Matthew Pittman](#) (Panel Chair) (United States) and [Dr. Andrew Kennis](#) (Discussant) (United States)

Unveiling the Mechanics of AI Adoption in Journalism: A Multi-Factorial Exploration of Expectation Confirmation, Knowledge Management, and Sustainable Use

» [Dr. FANGNI LI](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Science News Reporting and the Effects of AI Authorship: A Study of Credibility and Trustworthiness in Automated Journalism

» [Dr. Shiyu Yang](#) (United States)¹, [Mr. Scott Greeves](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Mustafa Oz](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Matthew Pittman](#) (United States)¹ (1. The University of Tennessee)

The potential and limits of appropriating generative AI in reporting natural disasters in South Africa

» [Ms. Soligah Solomons](#) (South Africa)¹, [Prof. Wallace Chuma](#) (South Africa)¹ (1. University of Cape Town (UCT))

Integrating Technology into Journalism: Key Factors Influencing Artificial Intelligence Adoption and Use Among Taiwanese Journalists

» [Prof. Heui-Ling Liu](#) (Taiwan)¹, [Prof. Ven-hwei Lo](#) (Taiwan)², [Prof. Hsiou-Feng Chen](#) (Taiwan)³ (1. Taipei National University of the Arts, 2. National Chengchi University, 3. Journalism department, Shihhsin University)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

08:30 **Panel : JRE-4**
JRE - Environmental journalism: practice and research in diverse contexts I

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+52

Organised by: Prof. Susanne Fengler (Panel Chair) (Germany) and Dr. Jaime Loke (Discussant) (United States)

Investigative Reporting on Environmental Pollution by Mega Corporation in Nigeria and the Culture of Inconclusive Reporting

» [Dr. Hangeior Degarr](#) (Nigeria)¹, [Dr. Kevin Alom](#) (Nigeria)¹ (1. Benue State University, Makurdi)

Media Narratives and Environmental Awareness: How U.S. Journalists Are Preparing for Environmental Coverage in Trump's Second Term

» [Dr. Jaime Loke](#) (United States)¹ (1. Texas Christian University)

The Power of the Press in Climate Action: Advancing Environmental Journalism for a Greener Future

» [Dr. Daniel Chile](#) (Nigeria)¹ (1. Benue State University, Makurdi)

Climate change: The blind spot of migration coverage

» [Dr. Merle van Berkum](#) (Germany)¹, [Prof. Susanne Fengler](#) (Germany)¹, Ms. Johanna Mack (Germany)¹ (1. Erich Brost Institute for International Journalism)

The Impact of "X" Political Discourse on Working Journalists' Approach to News Stories in Pakistan

» [Dr. Muhammad Zahid Bilal](#) (Pakistan)¹, [Dr. SOBIA ABID](#) (Pakistan)² (1. Univdersity of Okara, 2. Department of Film and Broadcasting, University of the Punjab)

08:30 **Panel : CPT-1**
CPT - Governing content and user behaviour on platforms: regulation, policy and practices

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+53

Organised by: Prof. Jonathon Hutchinson (Panel Chair) (Australia)

"Weapons of the Weak": Daily Resistance and Collusion of Platform Content Moderators

» Prof. Enqiang Guo (China)¹, [Dr. Liebing Liang](#) (China)² (1. East China University of Political Science and Law, 2. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

Connecting Policies and Algorithms: A New Governance Framework for Cyberbullying

» Prof. Wei Li (China)¹, [Ms. Qingxuan Cheng](#) (China)¹, Prof. Hao Xu (China)¹ (1. School of New Media, Peking University)

Technology Interventions Addressing Misinformation: A Systematic Review on Types, Efficacy, and Impacts on Users

» [Ms. Mengxuan Cai](#) (Singapore)¹, Dr. Kokil Jaidka (Singapore)¹, Dr. Wynne Hsu (Singapore)¹, Dr. Mong Li Lee (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

Negotiating state-led governance policies: how self-regulation operates on Weibo

» [Mr. Wenhao Zhou](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University)

"Whispers of the Night and Clamor of the Day": Exploring Diurnal and Nocturnal Variations in Weibo Content

» [Ms. Zhiyi Lin](#) (China)¹ (1. Peking University HSBC Business School(PHBS))

08:30 **Panel : CAM-1**
CAM - Community Communication during Disasters: Risk and Resilience

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+56

Organised by: Dr. Amparo Cadavid (Panel Chair) (Colombia)

Disaster and Resilience : Registering People's Voice through Participatory Video in Assam

» [Dr. Alankar Kaushik](#) (India)¹ (1. EFL University, Regional Campus, Shillong)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

Fostering Resilience: Community Radio and Disaster Communication in Odisha, India

» [Dr. Manas K Kanjilal](#) (India)¹, [Prof. Priya Kapoor](#) (United States)² (1. REVA University Bangalore, 2. Department of Politics and Global Affairs, Portland State University, Portland, United States)

Information intermediaries are key to shaping community disaster communication networks

» [Ms. Susan Atkinson](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Canberra)

Community Radio in Times of Cyclone: An influence study on the at-risk coastal people of Bangladesh

» [Prof. Mohammad Sahid Ullah](#) (Bangladesh)¹, [Dr. Rawshon Akhter](#) (Bangladesh)¹ (1. University of Chittagong)

08:30

Panel : GEN-1

GEN - Gender aging and youth, appearance and social exclusion during the life course

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR4

Organised by: [Dr. Shiyu Tang](#) (Panel Chair) (China) and [Prof. Tianle Huang](#) (Discussant) (China)

Quitting the SUBSTANCE: Her Age Anxiety and Her Resistance in the AI Era

» [Prof. Tianle Huang](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Shutong Fan](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Fluid in the Mirror? The Reconstruction of East Asian Masculinity Under Beauty Filters on Social Media: A Cross-Cultural Comparison

» [Mr. Haohan Yuan](#) (Malaysia)¹, [Dr. Ruifeng Qie](#) (Hong Kong)² (1. Universiti Malaya, 2. Hong Kong Baptist University)

How Do Electric Sheep Depict Androids? An Analysis of Female Image Schemas in AI-Generated Art

» [Dr. Huahua Dong](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Shiyu Tang](#) (China)², [Mr. Leyu Wang](#) (China)³ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 2. Shanghai Jiao Tong Univeristy, 3. China University of Petroleum (East China))

K-Beauty and Masculinity: The Practices and Representations of Makeup-Wearing Men in South Korea

» [Ms. WooBeen Suh](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Yonsei University)

08:30

Panel : GEN-2

GEN - Women's voices, patriarchy and 'empowerment'

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5

Organised by: [Prof. Usha Raman](#) (Panel Chair) (India) and [Ms. Nusrat Jahan](#) (Discussant) (China)

Unveiling the Digital Curtain: Women's Privacy and Self-Disclosure in SNSs across Culture

» [Ms. Nusrat Jahan](#) (China)¹, [Ms. kittiporn Saetae](#) (China)², [Mr. Md. Nurur Safa](#) (China)² (1. Shanghai Jio Tong University, China, 2. Shanghai Jiao Tong Univeristy, China)

Women on Women: Gaze Debugging and Gender Awareness of Female Photographers in Platform Women's Image Production

» [Ms. yuyuan ke](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Nanjing University)

Who Holds "Women Power"? Self-representation of Female Media Images in China on Xiaohongshu

» [Ms. Ningjie Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Zhiyang Zhu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Zhouyi YAO](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Bingchen Liu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Qiyue CHENG](#) (China)¹ (1. Fudan University)

Fluid Sisterhood in China: "Jiemei" Culture and the Paradox of Empowerment on Xiaohongshu

» [Ms. qiyue yang](#) (China)¹ (1. communication university of China)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

08:30 **Panel : ESR-1**
ESR - Decolonisation, Environmental Justice and Communication
Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6
 Organised by: Dr. Kerrie Foxwell Norton (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Environmental justice: Communicating the dark side of the ecological crisis
 » [Dr. Mikkel Eskjaer](#) (Denmark)¹ (1. Aalborg University, Copenhagen Campus)

The Elusive Challenge of 'Climate Justice': Differences in the Knowledge Typologies in IPCC's Climate Communication
 » [Dr. Tong Tong](#) (China)¹, Mr. Zefan Li (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Paths to Ecological Justice: Food Biodiversity, Nutrition and Communication in South Asia
 » [Dr. Maitreyee Mishra](#) (India)¹, Ms. Manisha Mishra (Norway)² (1. Manipal Academy of Higher Education, 2. University of Agder)

The courts, environmental justice and protest politics: The Tasmanian experience
 » [Dr. Claire Konkes](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Tasmania)

Comparing news framing of climate change in Caixin and South China Morning Post: Voices of environmental crisis, care, and justice from China
 » [Dr. Wendi Li](#) (Australia)¹, [Ms. ZHENGYU KANG](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Melbourne)

08:30 **Panel : ESR-3**
ESR - Communities, Engagement and Environmental Communication
Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7
 Organised by: Pieter Maesele (Panel Chair) (Belgium)

BRIDGING THE ECO-SOCIAL DIVIDE: THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATION IN PARTICIPATORY WATER GOVERNANCE

» [Dr. Joana Diaz Pont](#) (Spain)¹ (1. Autonomous University of Barcelona)

Engaging the public in fire mitigation: the role of political affiliation in shaping preferences for fuel management

» [Dr. Ami Seivwright](#) (Australia)¹, [Prof. Libby Lester](#) (Australia)¹, Dr. Stefania Ondei (Australia)², Dr. Anna Gjedrem (Australia)², Prof. David Bowman (Australia)² (1. Monash University, 2. University of Tasmania)

Governance Model of "Weed Control via Photo Identification" for Canadian Goldenrod Based on Participatory Communication Theory

» [Dr. Shutang Liu](#) (Macao)¹, Prof. Shaofei Jin (China)², Mrs. Cheng Li (China)³, Mrs. Yingying Jiang (China)⁴ (1. Faculty of Humanities and Arts, Macau University of Science and Technology, 2. Department of Geography, Minjiang University, 3. Faculty of Liberal Arts Education and Art Media, Xiamen Institute of Technology, 4. Faculty of Marxism, Minjiang University)

What Facilitates Public Engagement? A Study on Communication Actors and Agenda-Setting in Climate Communication

» [Ms. XINYU LI](#) (China)¹, Prof. Sabariah Mohamed Salleh (Malaysia)¹ (1. Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM))

From Policy to Public Engagement on social media: The Role of UAE Media in Sustaining Climate Discourse Post-COP28

» [Ms. Daniela Patornilho](#) (Portugal)¹ (1. NOVA-FCSH)

08:30 **Panel : PCR-1**
PCR - Environmental activism, justice and ethics
Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8
 Organised by: Dr. Jessica Noske-Turner (Discussant, Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Reimagining Digital Identity: A Visual Participatory Approach Among Encamped Karen Refugees.

» [Dr. Charlotte Hill](#) (Thailand)¹, [Prof. Mirca Madianou](#) (United Kingdom)² (1. Department of Media Arts and Design, Chiang Mai University, 2. Goldsmiths, University of London)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

Indigenous Battle Over Cultural Beliefs: A Study of the Mukkumlung Protests for Environmental Protection in Nepal

» [Ms. Ikla Subba](#) (India)¹, Dr. Pooja Basnett (India)¹ (1. Sikkim University)

Experimenting with Environmental Justice: Chinese Youth Activism in Rural Reconstruction Movement

» [Prof. Wendy Su](#) (United States)¹ (1. Univeristy of California Riverside)

Many voices, shared responsibility? Principles of dialogic communication in international codes of ethics – a comparative analysis

» Dr. Tobias Eberwein (Austria)¹, [Ms. Marie Rathmann](#) (Austria)¹, Dr. Krisztina Rozgonyi (Austria)¹, Dr. Laura Amigo (Switzerland)² (1. Austrian Academy of Sciences, 2. Università della Svizzera Italiana)

Music as Activism: Emotional Mobilization and Collective Action in Climate Change Advocacy

» [Ms. Meng Yao](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China, Beijing, China)

08:30

Panel : INC-1

INC - Arab Digitalities: Towards an Epistemology of the Digital from the Arab World

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: Dr. Chafic Najem (Convenor) (Lebanon) and Prof. Marwan Kraidy (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Lebanon)

Buying Time: Temporal Digitalities and Off-Label Practices in Lebanon

» [Dr. Chafic Najem](#) (Lebanon)¹ (1. Northwestern University in Qatar)

Fragile Fascism at the Digital Frontier: Kitsch, Control, and (Live) Content Creators in Egypt

» [Dr. Nermin Elsherif](#) (Egypt)¹ (1. Utrecht University)

Digital waiting as a temporal condition: Lagging, anticipating, and occupying time

» [Dr. Heather Jaber](#) (Qatar)¹ (1. Northwestern University in Qatar)

From the Internet, this is the Radio: Hashtags as Affective Connectors

» [Dr. Sulafa Zidani](#) (United States)¹ (1. Northwestern University)

08:30

Panel : MPS-1

MPS - (Theoretical) perspectives on algorithmic media and human machine interaction

Venue - WKWSCI L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: Prof. Jeffrey Wimmer (Panel Chair) (Germany)

Algorithmic media, 'audience datafication' and agency

» [Prof. Susanne Eichner](#) (Germany)¹ (1. Filmuniversität Babelsberg)

Algorithmic Kaleidoscope: The Floating Algorithmic Self And Self-Discrepancy Of Recommendation System Users

» [Ms. Jiayi Ge](#) (Singapore)¹, Ms. Nazira Banu (Singapore)¹, Prof. Hyunjin Kang (Singapore)¹, Prof. Edson Tandoc Jr. (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

Adoption of Human Augmentation Technologies for Non-Medical Applications: A Systematic Review of Empirical Literature

» [Mrs. Giulia Frascaria](#) (Switzerland)¹, Dr. Daniela Jaramillo-Dent (Switzerland)¹, Prof. Michael Latzer (Switzerland)¹ (1. University of Zurich)

Exploring the Integrative Heuristic Processing in Human-AI Relationships and Their Impact on Users' Undersociality: A Perspective of Expectancy Violation and Confirmation

» [Mr. Hongyuan Gan](#) (Hong Kong)¹, Ms. Jiawei DAI (Hong Kong)¹, Ms. Liu Mengyao (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

My Cyborg Self: Speaking Tech to Power

» [Dr. Jaime Riccio](#) (United States)¹ (1. LaGuardia Community College, CUNY)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

08:30

Panel : POL-1

POL - Digital Technologies and Online Political Engagement

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

Organised by: Prof. Kate Nash (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Australia)

Can online discussion predict offline collective actions? Evidence from Anti-ELAB movement in Hong Kong

» [Mr. ZIJIAN ZHENG](#) (China)¹, [Mr. LINYU HUANG](#) (China)¹, Prof. Fei Shen (Hong Kong)², Dr. Wensen Huang (China)¹ (1. Shenzhen University, 2. Department of Media and Communication, City University of Hong Kong)

Online Political Participation and Party Identification in Taiwan's 2024 Election: A Multi-Dimensional Semantic Network Analysis of PTT Discussions

» [Mrs. FangZhou Yang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Trading time for discretion: The response dynamics of grassroots officials on computer-mediated administrative platforms in China

» Dr. He Gong (China)¹, [Mr. Xu Dong](#) (China)², Ms. Yuqi Lv (China)² (1. Renmin University of China, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

Hearing the other side? Podcasting's civic potential

» [Prof. Kate Nash](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Dylan Bird](#) (Australia)², Prof. Mia Lindgren (Australia)³ (1. University of Newcastle, 2. RMIT University, 3. University of Tasmania)

08:30

Panel : MPS-2

MPS - From TikTok to RedNote

Venue - WKWSCI L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: Dr. Pengxiang Li (Panel Chair) (China)

Integrating the Functional Theory and Communication Privacy Management in Teenagers' Motivations and Privacy Considerations for Self-Disclosure on TikTok

» [Ms. Nazira Banu](#) (Singapore)¹, Prof. Hyunjin Kang (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

TikTok Refugees: Analyzing the Impact of Cross-Cultural Interaction on Content Production Models of REDnote Platform in Digital Migration

» [Ms. Zihang Yao](#) (China)¹ (1. Shanghai University)

#TikTok Refugee: Cross-Cultural Social Media Migration to RedNote Amid Platform Ban Concerns

» [Mr. Nebojsa Stevanovic](#) (China)¹, Prof. Liangwen Kuo (China)¹ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

Digital Borders and Algorithmic Refugees: U.S. TikTok Users Migrating to Xiaohongshu (Red Note) Amid Geopolitical Tensions

» [Ms. JiaYi Wu](#) (United States)¹ (1. Davidson College)

From Fragmentation to Knowledge Linkage: Exploring the Impact of Anchor Texts on Users' Knowledge Expansion in Knowledge Short Videos

» [Mr. Lingzhi Zhuang](#) (China)¹, Ms. Xuan Zhang (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Nankai University)

08:30

Panel : CJD-1

CJD - Environmental justice, advocacy and religion

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Dr. Vaia Doudaki (Panel Chair) (Czechia)

From margin to the mainstream: degrowth, counter-publicity, and the public sphere

» Mr. Xuanchen Li (China)¹, [Prof. Li Ji](#) (China)¹, Prof. John Downey (United Kingdom)² (1. Wuhan University, School of Journalism and Communication, 2. Loughborough University)

Framing Under Fire: Navigating Environmental Activism on Social Media Amid Digital Repression

» [Mr. Dien Luong](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Michigan)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

The Mediated Politics of Pollution: Ecology as a Tool of Religious Majoritarianism

» Dr. Srinivas Lankala (India)¹ (1. The English and Foreign Languages University)

Religion, Youth, and Digital Advocacy: Grassroots Mobilization for Environmental Justice in Tampakan, Mindanao

» Mr. David Neil Joseph Lumba (Philippines)¹, Mr. Warren Victor Bea (Philippines)¹ (1. Student, Junior College, College of Arts & Sciences, University of Asia & the Pacific)

From Reverence to Resistance: The Transformative Role of Religious Rhetoric in Shaping Civil Rights Mobilization

» Ms. Lucy Blue Draper (United Kingdom)¹, Dr. Benjamin DETENBER (Singapore)² (1. University College London, 2. Nanyang Technological University)

08:30

Panel : POE-1

POE - Confronting the Crises in Journalism and Print Media

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7

Organised by: Dr. Brent Cowley (Panel Chair) (United States)

HOW IS CANADIAN MEDIA'S PLATFORM DEPENDENCE EVOLVING? A CLOSER LOOK AT THE ONLINE NEWS ACT'S EFFECTS

» Dr. Samuel Lamoureux (Canada)¹ (1. Université TÉLUQ)

Spreading hatred and filing false criminal cases against progressive journalists/writers and cultural activists by the ultra-rightist groups during the regime of the interim government of Mohammad Yunus in Bangladesh: A political economy critique

» Dr. Abdur Razzaque Khan (Bangladesh)¹ (1. Department of Mass Communication and Journalism, University of Dhaka)

Between Restoration and Transformation in Pennsylvania's Nonprofit News Ecosystem

» Dr. David Berman (United States)¹, Dr. Aaron Hyzen (United States)², Dr. Victor Pickard (United States)² (1. Seton Hall University, 2. University of Pennsylvania)

"Oh, the Places They'll Not Go!": The Political Economy of Book Censorship, Platform Capitalism, and the Commodification of Literature

» Dr. Brent Cowley (United States)¹ (1. Brigham Young University-Hawaii)

Labor Negotiation, Production Politics, and Conservative Transformation in China's Publishing Industry: Evidence from Live Streaming Marketing Practitioners

» Mr. Minghan Hou (China)¹, Dr. Yang Shihua (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

08:30

Panel : VIC-1

VIC - Cinema, Characters, Spectatorship & Vloggers

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 8

Organised by: Dr. Denize Araujo (Panel Chair) (Brazil)

Reimagining Neo-Seoul: techno-Orientalism in Hollywood Cinema and East Asian Urban Modernity

» Ms. Yining WANG (Korea, Republic of)¹, Ms. Yiming HAO (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Hanyang University)

Spectatorship: memory, knowledge, perception & repertoire

» Dr. Denize Araujo (Brazil)¹ (1. UTP- Universidade Tuiuti do Paraná, Brazil)

Constructed Identity of Fake Digital Human Characters in films and its socio-economic implications: A Case study of selected films

» Prof. Govind Ji Pandey (India)¹ (1. Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

The Media Practices of "One Day With Me" Vloggers: A Study on the Aestheticization of Daily Life through Self-Representation

» [Ms. Yulin Wang](#) (China)¹, Prof. Luyuan Zhang (China)² (1. Nanjing University, 2. South China University of Technology)

08:30

Panel : MER-1

MER - Digital practices and young people

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: Dr. Devina Sarwatay (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom) and Mrs. Maria José Brites (Discussant) (Portugal)

Understanding Everyday Digital Practices Through the Lens of Young People in the Global South

» [Ms. Wei Jhen Liang](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

Playtime and the video game industry: a major educational challenge

» [Ms. Sara Dethise Martinez](#) (Belgium)¹, Ms. Anne-Sophie Collard (Belgium)¹ (1. Université de Namur)

Confiscate or Co-Play? The Digital Parenting Dilemma and the Pursuit of Happiness —An Empirical Study Based on 301 Parent-Child Responses in Mainland China

» [Dr. Lin Shi](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Jingjie Kuang](#) (China)¹, Dr. Yaoying Zhu (China)² (1. University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, 2. Teaching Center for Writing and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Towards "Screen Reading Resilience": Attributing and Dissolving Digital Reading Alienation Among Youth in an Accelerated Society

» [Mr. Yimin Lin](#) (China)¹ (1. East China Normal University)

Media Education in the Algorithmic Age: Youth, News, and Digital Citizenship

» [Dr. Teresa Sofia Castro](#) (Portugal)¹, Mrs. Maria José Brites (Portugal)¹, Ms. Margarida Maneta (Portugal)² (1. CICANT - Lusofona University, 2. CICANT - Lusófona University)

08:30

Panel : HIS-1

HIS - Empire and (De)Colonialism

Venue - WKWSCI TR+7

Organised by: Dr. Beate Josephi (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Repurposing the nervous system of empire: Protests, revolts and revolutions in Iranian telegraph stations in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries

» [Dr. Sebastian Rose](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Loughborough University)

Colonisation, surveillance and subversion: The roles of radio in colonial West Africa, 1935-1960

» [Dr. Abdullahi Tasiu Abubakar](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. City St George University of London)

Broadcasting and the Creation of a Black Public Opinion in the Portuguese Empire: Using Radio to Promote and Counter Cultural Dominance

» [Prof. Nelson Ribeiro](#) (Portugal)¹ (1. Catholic University of Portugal)

Decolonizing the Public Sphere(s)?: A Historical Trajectory of Justice-Seeking Subaltern Public Communication in the Middle East

» [Dr. Burçe Celik](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Loughborough University)

08:30

Panel : ETH-1

ETH - Ethical Frontiers for Journalism in a Digital Age

Venue - WKWSCI TR+8

Organised by: Dr. María Teresa Nicolás Gavilán (Panel Chair) (Mexico) and Dr. Marta Martín (Discussant) (Spain)

The ethical commitment of investigative journalism: algorithms, robots and Artificial Intelligence

» [Prof. Concha Edo](#) (Spain)¹, Dr. José María Legorburu (Spain)², Dr. Pedro Jerónimo (Portugal)³ (1. Complutense University of Madrid, 2. Universidad San Pablo CEU/CEU Universities, 3. Universidade da Beira Interior)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

Pressing Ethical Issues in the Integration of AI in Local Ibero-American Newsrooms

» [Dr. Elvira García](#) (Spain)¹, Dr. María Teresa Nicolás Gavilán (Mexico)², Dr. Lyudmyla Yezerska (Peru)³, Dr. Concha Edo Bolós (Spain)⁴, Dr. Giovanni Ramos (Portugal)⁵, Dr. David Parra (Spain)⁴, Ms. Mayra Gonzales (Peru)³, Dr. Juan Francisco Jiménez Jacinto (Spain)⁶, Dr. Liza Higuera (Peru)⁷, Dr. Claudia Herrera (Mexico)⁸, Dr. Marta Martín (Spain)⁹ (1. Universidad Cardenal Herrera CEU/CEU Universities, 2. Universidad Panamericana, 3. Universidad de Piura, 4. Complutense University of Madrid, 5. University of Beira Interior, 6. Universitat Abat Oliba CEU/CEU Universities, 7. Universidad Antenor Orrego, 8. Universidad Autonoma de México, 9. Universidad de Alicante)

“Las Grietas del Litio”: Contribuições do jornalismo colaborativo para investigar a mineração na América Latina

» [Dr. Ben Hur Demeneck](#) (Brazil)¹ (1. UEPG (State University of Ponta Grossa))

A Textual and Visual Analysis of Media Framing in School Violence Reporting in China (2014–2024)

» [Ms. Fang bling](#) (China)¹, Ms. Zhang Ruotong (China)¹, Ms. Zhang Xingyu (China)¹ (1. National Sun Yat-sen University)

08:30

Panel : CRI-1

CRI - Disaster and media

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+35*

Organised by: Dr. Minos-Athanasios Karyotakis (Panel Chair) (Hong Kong)

Targeted Misinformation and the Wildfires in Europe: Studying the Ideological Polarization of Online News Coverage in Europe

» [Dr. Minos-Athanasios Karyotakis](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. David C. Lam Institute for East-West Studies (LEWI), Hong Kong Baptist University, Kowloon Tong, Hong Kong)

How AI Constructs Disaster Narratives: A Comparative Analysis of Large Language Models in Multimodal Disaster News Production

» [Ms. Zhang Rui](#) (China)¹, Mr. Rongyi Chen (China)² (1. Jinan University, 2. Central South University)

Erasing the environmental impact of the Nord Stream bombings

» [Dr. Michael Tasserou](#) (Japan)¹ (1. Tokai University)

Supportive Communication in the Los Angeles Wildfires: How Channel Synchronicity, Source, and Trust Interact

» [Dr. Yang Yi](#) (United States)¹, Dr. Dongqing Xu (United States)² (1. Department of Communication, University of Utah, 2. Hubbard School of Journalism & Mass Communication, University of Minnesota - Twin Cities)

PR Cleans, Ocean Screams: How Japan’s Crisis PR Lauanders Fukushima’s Nuclear Legacy in the Tide of Global Backlash

» [Ms. Xinyang Liu](#) (China)¹, Prof. Hongzhe Wang (China)¹ (1. Peking University)

08:30

Panel : DID-1

DID - AI, Media and Environmental Futures

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+36*

Organised by: Dr. Carolina Escudero (Panel Chair) (Spain)

The intersection of AI and emotions: a global view from experienced journalists

» [Dr. Carolina Escudero](#) (Spain)¹, Dr. Ernest Yuyan Zhang (United States)¹ (1. University of Missouri)

Inclusive AI: Building collective capabilities into ‘AI solutions’ to address rural climate risks

» Prof. Anthony McCosker (Australia)¹, [Ms. Dominique Carlon](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Swinburne University of Technology)

Public libraries as agents of AI inclusion and participation

» [Dr. Kieran Hegarty](#) (Australia)¹, Prof. Julian Thomas (Australia)¹, Prof. Anthony McCosker (Australia)² (1. RMIT University, 2. Swinburne University of Technology)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

Bridging the Generative AI Divide: Group Differentiation, Determinants and Governance Innovations

» Ms. Wang Yibing (China)¹ (1. Jilin University)

How Generative AI Visualizes Environmental Activists: Algorithmic Bias in the Representation of Environmental Advocacy

» Mrs. Lei Gao (China)¹ (1. Fudan University)

08:30

Panel : REC-1

REC - Media Events and Religion: The Maha Kumbh Mela, India, Festival

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+37

Organised by: Prof. Priscilla Boshoff (Panel Chair) (South Africa)

State Messaging, News Values, and Digital Devotion at Maha Kumbh Mela - Analyzing India's Contemporary Religious Conundrum

» Dr. Manjushree Naik (India)¹ (1. Manipal Institute of Communication)

Exploring Sacred Ecology in Media Narratives: An Analysis of the Coverage of Maha Kumbh Mela 2025, Prayagraj (Allahabad), India

» Prof. Krishna Sankar Kusuma (India)¹ (1. Jamia Millia Islamia)

Instagram and the Mahakumbh :Digital Devotion in the Age of Social Media

» Dr. Pragati Paul (India)¹ (1. AJK MCRC, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, India)

08:30

Panel : CPN-1

CPN - A Critical Dialogue on the Cosmopolitan Turn: "Cosmopolitan Communication Studies. Towards Deep Internationalization."

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+25

Organised by: Dr. Melanie Radue (Convenor) (Germany), Dr. Anke Fiedler (Convenor) (Germany), Dr. Carola Richter (Panel Chair) (Germany), and Prof. Ylva Rodny-Gumede (Discussant) (South Africa)

Anchoring cosmopolitan communication studies in universal values

» Dr. Cherian George (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

What Afrokology Can Bring to Cosmopolitanism

» Dr. Winston Mano (United Kingdom)¹, Dr. viola milton (South Africa)² (1. University of Westminster, 2. University of South Africa)

Deconstructing the Universal: Navigating the North-South Tensions in Global Media Ethics

» Prof. Michael Yao Wodui Serwornoo (Ghana)¹ (1. University of Maryland)

08:30

Panel : LAW-1

LAW - New Regulatory Solutions for New Challenges

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+26

Organised by: Mr. MacDonald Amaran (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Tension and Synergy between Global Algorithm Regulation and Privacy Protection: Institutional Comparison and Technological Governance Paths

» Ms. Yaoying Zhang (China)¹, Mr. Xujun Gao (China)² (1. school of communication, East China Normal University, 2. Shanghai)

The Role of Platform Ethics in Managing AI-Generated Art's: An Examination of ArtStation Case Through Kidder's List

» Ms. Yan Sun (Singapore)¹, Prof. Peng Hwa Ang (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

From Deepfake to DeepSeek: How AI Laws Shape Environmental Messaging - A Comparative Study of China and the EU

» Dr. Xuan WU (China)¹, Dr. Xia LUO (China)² (1. Wuhan Textile University, 2. The World Bank)

Regulating Emerging Digital Technologies in media and Communication; an analysis of its impact on Conventional media practices, intellectual property rights and online safety.

» Mr. MacDonald Amaran (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Bournemouth University)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

El estudio de la metacognición como factor protector frente a la desinformación

» [Dr. Fernando Gutiérrez](#) (Chile)¹ (1. Facultad de Comunicaciones Universidad del Desarrollo (Chile))

08:30

Panel : ICO-1

ICO - Emerging Technologies, Inclusion, and Disability

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+28

Organised by: Dr. victor zhuang (Convenor, Discussant) (Singapore), Ms. Wenqi Tan (Convenor) (Australia), and Prof. Gerard Goggin (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Apps, Transactions, Disability

» [Dr. victor zhuang](#) (Singapore)¹, Ms. Bella Choo (Australia)² (1. Nanyang Technological University, 2. The University of Melbourne)

Communicating AI and disability in Southeast Asia: Cases from Vietnam and Indonesia

» [Dr. abdul rohman](#) (Viet Nam)¹, Ms. Vo Diem Trang (Viet Nam)¹ (1. RMIT University)

Political, technological and cultural influences on Audio Description as Disability Justice in Australia

» [Prof. Katie Ellis](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Curtin University)

Reimagining environmental justice through disability and virtual reality nature experiences

» [Ms. Wenqi Tan](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Sydney)

10:30

Panel

Plenary / Communicating the Climate Crisis: Translating Science into Policy and Practice

Venue - Lee Kong Chian LT (LKC-LT)

» Speakers: Janil Puthuchery (Senior Minister of State, Ministry of Digital Development and Information, Singapore), Adam Douglas Switzer (Director, CIFAL @ NTU, Asian School of the Environment, Professor, Asian School of the Environment, Assistant Dean (Development), College of Science, Director of CIFAL@NTU, Asian School of the Environment, Nanyang Technological University), Audrey Tan (Assistant News Editor (Environment), The Straits Times, Singapore Press Holdings Kong), Man Jing (Co-founder, Science and Environment, Channel "Just Keep Thinking")

12:30

General Lunch

Venue - GAIA, Level 1 Foyer

14:00

Panel : JRE-2

JRE - Journalism in the digital age II

Venue - The Hive LHS-LT

Organised by: Dr. DAN WU (Panel Chair) (China) and Prof. Qi Zhou (Discussant) (China)

How Podcasting is Transforming Journalism: A Study in Public Communication and Community Engagement

» [Prof. Mia Lindgren](#) (Australia)¹, Dr. Gabriela Perdomo Páez (Canada)² (1. University of Tasmania, 2. Mount Royal University)

"Journalism Is Dead" Digital Criticism and Challenges of Media Legitimacy in China

» [Prof. Haiyan WANG](#) (Macao)¹, Ms. Chenrui Wan (Macao)¹, Prof. David Nolan (Australia)² (1. University of Macau, 2. University of Canberra)

Comparing One's Ability with AI Affects a Journalist's Perceived Job Value: The Moderating Role of Appraisal of AI

» [Dr. DAN WU](#) (China)¹ (1. Shanghai University)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

Exploring the Impacts of Introducing AI-Generated Summaries in News Engagement

» Mr. Bin Li (China)¹, Mr. Seth Seet (Singapore)², Prof. Qi Zhou (China)³ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University, 2. Nanyang Technological University, 3. School of Journalism and Information Communication, Huazhong University of Science and Technology)

"Consider Myself As Doing two Jobs": How Gen AI Use is Sharpening a Dichotomy of Work Among Indian Journalists

» Mr. Kabir Upmanyu (India)¹, Dr. Sneha Mehendale (India)² (1. Symbiosis Centre for Media and Communication, Symbiosis International (Deemed University), 2. Symbiosis Institute of Media and Communication, Symbiosis International (Deemed University))

Platform-dependent journalistic autonomy. Audience patronage, relational labor, and the role of digital micro-funding platforms

» Prof. Raul Ferrer-Conill (Norway)¹, Dr. Luise Salte (Norway)¹ (1. University of Stavanger)

14:00

Panel : MPS-12

MPS - Shaping consciousness and narratives on sustainability

Venue - WKWSC L2 Executive Seminar Room

Organised by: Dr. peng wu (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Energy Transition as a Media and Communication Issue: Narratives, Actors, and Power

» Dr. Stephan Goerland (Germany)¹ (1. University of Münster)

How Discursive Alliances Shift: A Longitudinal Analysis of Australian Climate Change Discourses on Facebook through Practice Mapping

» Prof. Axel Bruns (Australia)¹, Ms. Carly Lubicz (Australia)², Dr. Tariq Choucair (Australia)², Mx. Laura Vodden (Australia)², Dr. Ehsan Dehghan (Australia)² (1. Queensland University of Technology, 2. Digital Media Research Centre, Queensland University of Technology)

Reactive Environmental Nationalism in China: A Computational Analysis of Public Discourse on Social Media

» Mr. Zhangyan Li (China)¹, Mr. Xingye Yao (China)², Ms. Xinrui Wang (China)³ (1. Zhejiang University, College of Media and International Culture, Hangzhou, China, 2. Fujian Minguang Software Co., Ltd., 3. Communication University of China, Beijing, China)

Digital Greenwashing: Analysing the Role of Content Creators in Sustainability Narratives

» Mr. Tanmay Samanta (India)¹ (1. St. Xavier's University, Kolkata.)

From awareness to action: examining the impact of climate change documentaries on college students' attitudes and behavior

» Dr. Dr. Dhyan Singh (India)¹ (1. Govt. College Dharamshala, Himachal Pradesh)

14:00

Panel : AUD-12

AUD - Influencer culture and audiences

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+47

Organised by: Dr. Rafal Zaborowski (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

How do audiences interact with media influencers? Individual differences and parasocial interaction predicting cognitive, affective, and behavioral outcomes

» Dr. Vikanda Pornsakulvanich (Thailand)¹, Dr. Nuchada Dumrongsiri (Thailand)¹ (1. Thammasat University)

Framing Sustainability as Lifestyle: Female Influencers, Audience Engagement, and the Gender Implications of Environmental Advocacy on TikTok

» Ms. Iiajing Niu (United States)¹ (1. University of Colorado Denver)

Exploring Content Creators' Belief Systems within their Social Media Ecosystems

» Dr. Daniela Jaramillo-Dent (Switzerland)¹, Prof. Michael Latzer (Switzerland)¹ (1. University of Zurich)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

Redefining Audiences in the Era of Human-Like Virtual Influencers in Instagram

» Dr. VICTORIA CARRILLO (Spain)¹, Ms. Lydia Corzo (Spain)¹, Dr. María García (Spain)¹ (1. University of Extremadura)

14:00

Panel : POP-2

POP - Social differences in/and popular cinema

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+49

Organised by: Prof. Sofie Van Bauwel (Panel Chair) (Belgium)

The Missing Part: A Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis of the Presentation of Disabled Groups in Modern Cinema

» Ms. Yahan Tang (China)¹, Mr. Wenbo Zhou (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

The moral and aesthetic value of a film about homosexuality: a historical discourse analysis of film reviews published in Belgian Catholic film periodical *Film and Television* (1956-2005)

» Prof. Frederik Dhaenens (Belgium)¹ (1. Ghent University)

Black Panther, Eco-Feminist Critiques, and Politics of the Global South

» Dr. Tabassum Ruhi Khan (United States)¹ (1. University of California, Riverside)

From Independence to Soft Beauty: The Localization and Gender Discourse Reconstruction of European and American Female-Themed Films in China

» Ms. Ziyu Deng (China)¹ (1. University of Colorado Denver)

14:00

Panel : POP-3

POP - Performing and consuming gender in contemporary Chinese mediascapes

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+52

Organised by: Mx. Vitor Blanco-Fernández (Panel Chair) (Spain)

Desire and Power: A Social Gaze at Fitness Streamers' Body Exhibition Videos on Douyin

» Mr. Yue Cui (China)¹, Mr. Qianhui Ju (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Gender Performance in Early Adulthood: How young people Challenge Heteronormative Gender Norms through dressing style cultural practice

» Dr. Jiayixiu Zhao (United Kingdom)¹, Dr. Yimei Zhu (United Kingdom)¹ (1. School of Arts, Media and Communication, University of Leicester)

Performing and monetizing romance on digital platforms: emotional capitalism and couple wanghong in China

» Mr. Yichen Wang (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

Comedy as Method: The Production of Gender Discourse in Chinese Female Stand-Up Comedy Interpretive Communities

» Ms. Sizhe Wu (China)¹ (1. University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences)

14:00

Panel : CPT-2

CPT - Digital geopolitics, sovereignty and technological interdependence

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+53

Organised by: Prof. Robin Mansell (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

The European Third Way: the EU's strategic narrative of a value-based digital order and its global impact

» Dr. Julia Pohle (Germany)¹, Mr. Leo Thüer (Germany)¹, Mr. Milan Schröder (Germany)¹, Prof. Christian Rauh (Germany)¹ (1. WZB Berlin Social Science Center)

Towards a "federated sovereignty"? Mobilizations of decentralized platforms for (European) digital autonomy

» Dr. Ksenia Ermoshina (France)¹, Prof. Francesca Musiani (France)² (1. Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS), Centre Internet et Société, 2. Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS), France)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

Politics, Privacy or Soft Power: TikTok Ban in the U.S. at the State Level

» [Dr. wenhong chen](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Texas at Austin)

Informational Ethos and Digital Sovereignty: Technologies, Neoliberalism, and Coloniality

» [Dr. José Cláudio Castanheira](#) (Brazil)¹ (1. Fluminense Federal University (UFF))

14:00

Panel : CAM-2

CAM - Theoretical Perspectives on Alternative/Community Media Practices

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+56

Organised by: Prof. Vinod Pavarala (Panel Chair) (India)

Passion, purpose, and pathways: a typology of volunteer motivations in community radio

» [Dr. Bridget Backhaus](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Griffith University)

Introducing Alternative Approaches to Media Practices: The Case of Jungle Rani

» [Ms. Sri Kanyaka Sivani Pampana](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Geetanjali Kala](#) (India)¹ (1. Cluster Innovation Centre, University of Delhi)

Sustainability of the Third Media Sector in Spain Design and implementation of an analytical framework to assess the resilience of the sector

» [Dr. ALEJANDRO BARRANQUERO CARRETERO](#) (Spain)¹, [Dr. José Candón-Mena](#) (Spain)², [Ms. Sara García-Caballero](#) (Spain)¹ (1. Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, 2. Universidad de Sevilla)

Lessons from community media for the present moment

» [Dr. Andrew Ó Baoill](#) (Ireland)¹ (1. University of Galway)

Freire y los fundamentos de una comunicación liberadora

» [Dr. Ana Cristina Suzina](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Loughborough University)

14:00

Panel : GEN-19

GEN - Menstruation and sexualization in the online sphere

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR4

Organised by: Yiran Gao (Panel Chair) (United States) and Ms. Yuan Xu (Discussant) (United States)

Recoding Menstruation and Resisting Depoliticization: Online Debates on China's Menstrual Pad Mutual-Aid Box Movement

» [Ms. Kexin Zhou](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Xinyu Xu](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Jinan University)

Silenced or Empowered? Memorable Messages and Communicative Disenfranchisement in Chinese Women's Gynecological Exams

» [Ms. lingyi liang](#) (China)¹ (1. Peking University)

Gendered Voices in Digital Health Discourse: Speculum Discussions on Chinese Social Media

» [Ms. Jiayu liang](#) (China)¹ (1. Nanjing University)

From Taboo to Public Debate: Digital Participation in Breaking Menstrual Shame

» [Yiran Gao](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign)

14:00

Panel : GEN-4

GEN - Feminist entrepreneurship, digital literacy and 'empowerment'

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5

Organised by: Dr. Claudia Reyes Betanzo (Panel Chair) (Chile) and Dr. Mausumi Bhattacharyya (Discussant) (India)

Breaking Age and Gender Barriers: Female Surfers' Stories of Empowerment and Environmental Conscience

» [Dr. Elena Maydell](#) (New Zealand)¹, [Dr. Inessa Love](#) (United States)² (1. Massey University, 2. University of Hawaii)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

Empowerment or catharsis? China's "leftover women" on social media

» [Ms. Chengxu Zhao](#) (New Zealand)¹ (1. Massey University)

Gender Disparity and Victimization: Leveraging Folk Art for Social Change

» [Dr. Mausumi Bhattacharyya](#) (India)¹, [Mr. Apratim Bhattacharya](#) (India)¹ (1. Centre for Journalism and Mass Communication, Visva-Bharati)

The Role of Media in Gender Equity: Perceptions of Female Expert Sources

» [Dr. Claudia Reyes Betanzo](#) (Chile)¹, [Dr. Teresa vernal](#) (Chile)² (1. Universidad del Desarrollo, 2. Universidad Andrés Bello)

Empowering Women Through Digital Entrepreneurship: The Impact of Social Media on Economic Development in Bangladesh.

» [Dr. Mohammad Tipu Sultan](#) (Bangladesh)¹, [Dr. Farzana Sharmin](#) (Bangladesh)² (1. Government Ainuddin College, 2. Bangladesh Accreditation Council)

14:00

Panel : ESR-5

ESR - Communities, Engagement and Environmental Communication

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6

Organised by: [Dr. Kerrie Foxwell Norton](#) (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Walking the Wild Coast: The Cultural Politics of Hiking as Eco-tourism in the Eastern Cape, South Africa

» [Prof. Tanja Bosch](#) (South Africa)¹, [Prof. Mehita Iqani](#) (South Africa)² (1. University of Cape Town, 2. Stellenbosch University)

Interaction of Environmental NGOs in Environmental Governance Agenda-setting: A Case Study of Green Zhejiang in Zhejiang Province of China

» [Prof. CUI BO](#) (China)¹, [Ms. QIUYAN PAN](#) (China)² (1. Communication University of Zhejiang, 2. Kaihua Media Group of Zhejiang Province)

Assessing the Knowledge of Coastal Communities: Lived Experiences of Fisherfolk in Barangays Looc, Opao, and Umapad, Mandaue City, Cebu, Philippines in Communicating Risks on Sea-Level Rise

» [Mr. Cris Fernan Bayaga](#) (Philippines)¹, [Ms. Alyanna Nicole Lauzon](#) (Philippines)¹, [Ms. Lynda Katherine Mecaros](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Cebu)

The 'kentongan' and 'catur gatra': integrating indigenous and scientific knowledge for disaster and climate change mitigations on the slopes of Mt. Merapi, Indonesia

» [Dr. Muzayin Nazaruddin](#) (Indonesia)¹ (1. Department of Communication, Universitas Islam Indonesia)

Cultural Narratives and Environmental Awareness: Exploring Storytelling and Artistic Traditions of Indigenous Tribes in Odisha, India

» [Dr. G Bala Krishna](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Gaman Palem](#) (India)² (1. Gitam Univeristy, Hyderabad, India, 2. Presidency University, Bengaluru)

14:00

Panel : ESR-4

ESR - Science Communication and Journalism

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7

Organised by: [Dr. Joana Diaz Pont](#) (Panel Chair) (Spain)

Ecologically Approaching the Impact of Politicized Science Communication on Environmentally Friendly Practices: A Focus on Misinformation about Climate Change

» [Mr. Zhichao \(Jacob\) Lei](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Department of Communication, Seoul National University)

Attention Over Content: The Impact of Science Literacy Education on Evaluating Climate Misinformation

» [Dr. Stephanie Jean Tsang](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

Communication climate science through the prism of culture. A symbolic-ethical analysis

» [Prof. Oumar Kane](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Département de communication sociale et publique. Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM). Montréal (Canada).)

Making Science "Useful": Blue Carbon Communication in Japanese Commercial Television

» [Mr. Taichi Masu](#) (Japan)¹, [Dr. Yasuhito Abe](#) (Japan)¹ (1. Doshisha University)

When Science Meets Politics: Analyzing Media Coverage and Public Response to Fake News Claims in the Fukushima Treated Water Discourse

» [Ms. Jihyun Choi](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Department of Communication, Seoul National University)

14:00

Panel : GEN-7

GEN - 'Eco-feminism', climate crisis and sustainability through a feminist lens

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: [Dr. Qianru Huang](#) (Panel Chair) (China), [Dr. Dina Listiorini](#) (Discussant) (Indonesia), and [Mrs. Faiza Rafique](#) (Panel Chair) (United Arab Emirates)

Promoting diversity, community, and cultural narratives: A Case Study of Kebetkache's Niger Delta Women's Day of Action for Environmental Justice

» [Ms. Ekaete George](#) (Nigeria)¹ (1. University of Port Harcourt)

Ecofeminist Critique of Climate Crisis Reporting in South Korea

» [Prof. Soo-ah Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Ms. Sean Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Department of Communication, Seoul National University)

Gardening to Economical Survival and Reduce Transphobia in Society: A Narrative Study of the Elder Waria at Waria Crisis Centre Yogyakarta

» [Dr. Dina Listiorini](#) (Indonesia)¹, [Ms. Rully Malay](#) (Indonesia)² (1. Universitas Atma Jaya Yogyakarta, 2. Waria Crisis Centre Yogyakarta)

Veganism as Ecofeminist Revolt: Gender, Nature, and Resistance in Han Kang's The Vegetarian

» [Dr. Qianru Huang](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Chenjie Zheng](#) (United States)² (1. Arizona State University, 2. University of Wisconsin-Madison)

Eco-feminism Themes in Selected Brand Advertisements in Nigeria: Environmental Sustainability or Greenwashing?

» [Dr. Grace Anweh](#) (Nigeria)¹, [Dr. Priscilla Marcus](#) (Nigeria)² (1. Benue State University, Makurdi, 2. Department of Mass Communication, Plateau State University, Bokkos)

14:00

Panel : INC-2

INC - Visualizing Justice: The Power of Documentaries in Amplifying Environmental Voices

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: [Mr. Arjun Chatterjee](#) (Convenor) (Hong Kong) and [Dr. Zhi Li](#) (Convenor) (China)

Stories of Survival and Resistance: Indian Environmental Documentaries as Catalysts for Justice and Advocacy

» [Mr. Arjun Chatterjee](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Dr. Sananda Mukherjee](#) (India)² (1. Hong Kong Baptist University, 2. Assistant Professor, School of Mass Communication KIIT DU, Bhubaneswar, India.)

Nonfiction, Serious Games and Innovative Storytelling: A Case Study on Using Digital Gaming in Documentary to Convey Desert Control Messages

» [Dr. Weikun Fan](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Suli He](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Exploring the Role of Storytelling in Environmental Documentaries: A Case Study of South African Millennials

» [Mr. Xiang Sun](#) (South Africa)¹ (1. China News Service South Africa Branch)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

The effect of documentaries on generation Z's perception and action towards environment: A qualitative study based on Chinese video platform Bilibili

» [Dr. Zhi Li](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Haihan Sun](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

14:00

Panel : HEC-3

HEC - Frames and counter frames

Venue - WKWSCI L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: Joy Wanja Muraya (Panel Chair) and Dr. Monique Lewis (Discussant) (Australia)

Koala Gets Acupuncture: News Framing of the Sustainability of Traditional Chinese Medicine in Australia – A Research Proposal

» [Mr. Shi Feng](#) (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University)

Effects of Message Framing on Prevention and Detection Behaviors: The Moderating Role of Multitasking

» [Ms. Siting Zheng](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Minhwa Jung](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Prof. Se-Hoon Jeong](#) (Korea, Republic of)² (1. Ph.D. Student, School of Media and Communication, Korea University), 2. Professor, School of Media and Communication, Korea University)

Reframing Cigarettes as Social Currency: The Role of Warning Images and Pricing from a Symbolic Interactionist Perspective

» [Dr. Gang Wang](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Kecheng DU](#) (China)² (1. School of Humanities and Communication, Ningbo University, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University)

Examining the Effect of Multidimensional Distance Framing on Information-Seeking of Antibiotic Risk

» [Ms. Jinqiu Chen](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Yuchen Zhou](#) (Hong Kong)², [Prof. Steve Guo](#) (Hong Kong)³, [Dr. Chuanli Xia](#) (Australia)⁴ (1. Guangdong ATV College of Performing Arts, 2. School of Communication, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong, 3. Hong Kong Baptist University, 4. University of Newcastle)

Beyond Health Message Framing: Sexual Strategies Predict HPV Vaccination Intention via Perceived Need

» [Dr. Jiahui Li](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Yiqi Chen](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Jinguang Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. Sun Yat-sen University)

14:00

Panel : SPS-4

SPS - Partner Session/International Chinese Communication Association (ICCA)

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

The Transformative Impact of Disruptive AI on Trust and Engagement in Media

» [Shuhua Zhou](#) (Chair Professor, Department of Media and Communication, City University of Hong Kong), [Trisha T. C. Lin](#) (Distinguished Professor, College of Communication, National Chengchi University), [Shaohai Jiang](#) (Associate Professor, Department of Communications and New Media, National University of Singapore) and [Yunya Song](#) (Professor, Academy of Interdisciplinary Studies, The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology)

14:00

Panel : HEC-4

HEC - Creative narratives, disruptive change

Venue - WKWSCI L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: [Mr. Zirui Wang](#) (Panel Chair) (Canada) and [Prof. ELIZA GOVENDER](#) (Discussant) (South Africa)

Health Silk Road: Framing, Narrating, and Creative Advocacy

» [Prof. Xiaoling Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. Xi'an Jiaotong Liverpool University)

The Pediatric Pacemaker Project: VitalVoices Communications Increases Awareness of Pediatric Patients With Pacemakers

» [Dr. Tania Rosas-Moreno](#) (United States)¹ (1. Loyola University Maryland)

Beyond Fertility: A Cultural-Centered Approach to Disease Narratives among Women with PCOS during the Preconception Stage

» [Ms. Ke Xie](#) (China)¹ (1. Guangdong University of Foreign Studies School of Journalism & Communication)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

Do Stories Save Lives? How Narratives Serve as a Tool to Persuade Participation in Cancer Prevention Choices

» [Ms. Zitong Hong](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Melbourne)

Smoking Is Masculine? Media Framing and Gender Difference in Tobacco Use in China

» [Prof. Francis YIN](#) (China)¹ (1. Nanfang College, Guangzhou)

14:00

Panel : CJD-2

CJD - Media, Democracy and Public perceptions: insights from qualitative research in ten European countries

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Ms. Giulia Ferri (Convenor) (Italy), Prof. Andrea Miconi (Panel Chair) (Italy), and Prof. Nello Barile (Panel Chair) (Italy)

Theory and Methodology: Qualitative methods in Democracy Research – Opportunities and Cross-Country Challenges.

» [Ms. Giulia Ferri](#) (Italy)¹, [Prof. Nello Barile](#) (Italy)¹, [Prof. Elisabetta Risi](#) (Italy)¹ (1. IULM University)

Unpacking perceptions of media and democracy through qualitative methods - the case of Estonia

» [Prof. Alessandro Nanì](#) (Estonia)¹, [Ms. Kristiina Raud](#) (Estonia)¹ (1. Tallinn University BFM)

Models of Democracy and Media's Role – Lessons from a Cross Country Study

» [Dr. Maren Beaufort](#) (Austria)¹ (1. Austrian Academy of Sciences)

The future was in the past: How Czech citizens perceive current struggles and threats to democracy and media

» [Ms. Karolina Šimková](#) (Czechia)¹, [Prof. Jeffrey Wimmer](#) (Germany)² (1. Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism, Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University, 2. University of Augsburg)

14:00

Panel : POE-2

POE - Digital Media in the Global South: Ownership, State Power, and Geopolitical Implications

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7

Organised by: Dr. Bilge Yesil (Convenor, Panel Chair) (United States)

Digital platforms power in the South Cone and challenges for its regulation

» [Dr. Ana Bizberge](#) (Argentina)¹ (1. Pontificia Universidad Católica de Perú)

From Competitive Clientelism to National Champion: The rise and rise of Reliance Jio

» [Dr. Vibodh Parthasarathi](#) (India)¹ (1. Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi)

“The World is Bigger than GAFAM”: Market Dominance of Tech Giants in Turkey and State Officials’ Responses to Data Colonialism

» [Dr. Bilge Yesil](#) (United States)¹ (1. CUNY)

Shifting the Digital Media Sphere Authority in Indonesia

» [Dr. Mufti Nurlatifah](#) (Indonesia)¹ (1. Universitas Gadjah Mada)

14:00

Panel : VIC-2

VIC - AI-Artificial Intelligence

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 8

Organised by: Mr. Jed Senthil (Panel Chair) (Singapore)

The AI Lens: Reimagining Creativity and Visual Storytelling with Large Vision Models

» [Ms. Wanquan Hao](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Ruikai Yu](#) (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University, 2. Kuaishou Technology & Kuaishou Research Institute of Big Data)

New Issues in Film Rhetoric Raised by Artificial Intelligence

» [Mr. Zheng Hui](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Jing Wen](#) (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua, 2. School of Journalism & Communication, Tsinghua University)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

From Algorithmic Alchemy to Creative Collaboration: Exploring the Dual Aspects of Generative AI in Image Production and its Value Dialectic

» [Mr. Qihang Liu](#) (China)¹, Mr. ZiDan Zhou (China)² (1. Shanghai Jiao Tong Univeristy, 2. Communication University of China)

Unleashing Creativity: Exploring Generative AI's impact on innovative content creation in the digital marketing landscape

» [Ms. Nanddeni M G](#) (Singapore)¹, Mr. Jed Senthil (Singapore)² (1. Singapore University of Social Sciences, 2. Nanyang Technological University)

How Does a Script "Compute"? The Love-Hate Relationship Between AI and Screenwriting

» [Ms. SHENG HUAJIE](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. College of Communication, National Chengchi University, Taiwan, R.O.C.)

14:00

Panel : ESN-1

ESN - Media, Inclusion and Society

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: Dr. Jeremiah Nganda (Panel Chair) (Kenya) and Chika Anyanwu (Discussant)

More is Less: Exploring the Relationship between Social Media Overload and Reflective Smartphone Disengagement among University Students

» [Mr. Yiwei Wu](#) (China)¹, Dr. XIAOYUE ZHANG (China)¹, Ms. Ke Qin (China)², Prof. Lin Cai (China)³ (1. Communication University of China, 2. University of International Business and Economics, 3. Southwest Minzu University)

"Rituals are means to carry our past into the future": Taboo, tradition, and transmission in food-based communicative practices of Idu-Mishmi indigenous community of India

» [Mr. Abhilash Bapanasha](#) (India)¹ (1. Department of Mass Communication and Journalism, Tezpur University)

A FLIGHT OVER AOTEAROA NEW ZEALAND (AFOA.NZ) – CREATIVE METHODOLOGIES FOR BUILDING AN INTERACTIVE VIDEOBOOK BASED ON CHILDREN'S LETTERS ABOUT THEIR PLACES

» [Mrs. Gisela De Castro](#) (New Zealand)¹ (1. The University of Waikato)

Boys Love Beyond Borders: How Thai Boys Love (BL) Series Are Redefining Inclusion Across South and Southeast Asia.

» [Ms. Dheera Sasidharan](#) (India)¹ (1. Times School of Media, Bennett University)

14:00

Panel : HIS-2

HIS - Encountering Gaps: Challenges in Historical Inquiry within a Changing Media Environment

Venue - WKWSCI TR+7

Organised by: Dr. Chamee Yang (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Korea, Republic of) and Dr. Susmita Das (Convenor) (India)

Mediating a Silenced Past: The Case of the Jeju 4-3 Incident Investigation Report

» [Dr. Youngkwan Ban](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Jeju 4-3 Peace Foundation)

On Developmentality: An Affective Infrastructure of the "Smart" Urban Future

» [Dr. Chamee Yang](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Department of Communication, Seoul National University)

Missing Archive, Missing History? Power, Preservation, and Advertising Historiography

» [Dr. Susmita Das](#) (India)¹ (1. Department of Film Studies, Jadavpur University)

Everything Not Saved Will Be Lost: Ephemerality and Media Cultures as Archival Challenges in Digital Gaming

» Prof. Christian Schwarzenegger (Germany)¹, Dr. Enrique Uribe Jongbloed (United Kingdom)², Dr. Erik Koenen (Germany)³, [Prof. Anna Wagner](#) (Netherlands)⁴ (1. University of Bremen,, 2. Cardiff University, 3. University of Bremen, 4. Radboud University)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

The Ferrymen of Culture: the transfer of the Jewish press centers from Eastern Europe and Poland to America in the second half of the 19th century.

» [Prof. Gideon Kouts](#) (France)¹ (1. Université Paris 8)

14:00

Panel : ETH-2

ETH - On the Edge of Ethics: Emerging Technologies

Venue - *WKWSCI TR+8*

Organised by: Concha Edo (Panel Chair) (Spain) and Dr. María Teresa Nicolás Gavilán (Discussant) (Mexico)

Antiqua et Nova and the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence: Implications for Communication Ethics

» [Dr. Dominic Maximilian Ofori](#) (Ghana)¹ (1. University of Ghana Department of Communication Studies)

Determination to cure: the ethical control of technology under the myth of medical cure rates

» [Ms. Jiao Yang](#) (China)¹ (1. Fudan University)

Invisible Biometric Extractivism: Surveillance Resistance of Social Media Biometric Extraction Based on Grounded Theory

» [Mr. Jinhua Wang](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Mr. Zhilei Wang](#) (China)² (1. King's College London, 2. South-Central Minzu University)

Developing a Formative Scale to Measure Users' Privacy Concerns within Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI)

» [Ms. Yi Cong](#) (China)¹ (1. Tongji University)

14:00

Panel : CRI-4

CRI - War and media

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+35*

Organised by: Dr. Minos-Athanasios Karyotakis (Panel Chair) (Hong Kong)

Understanding Conflict as Smog: Misinformation Narratives and its Impact on Collective Memory during War in Ukraine

» [Ms. Zhixuan Hu](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Zhaoyi Yang](#) (China)¹ (1. Tsinghua University)

The Rise of Harmony Hub: The Flow of War Narratives in the Gaza War Post-October 7

» [Dr. Mostafa Shehata](#) (Egypt)¹ (1. Menoufia University)

How AI Blurs Simulacra and Reality: A Case Study of Deepfake in the Russia-Ukraine War

» [Ms. Yujie Zhu](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Sixian Lin](#) (China)¹ (1. Beijing Foreign Studies University)

Wars in remix news videos on YouTube in Taiwanese society: A case study of OM Goose's representation of the Russo-Ukrainian war and the Israeli-Palestinian war

» [Dr. Ssu-Han Yu](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. College of Communication, National Chengchi University, Taiwan, R.O.C.)

14:00

Panel : DID-2

DID - Digital Education and Media Literacy

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+36*

Organised by: Dr. Massimo Ragnedda (Panel Chair) (United Arab Emirates)

Digital Inequalities Reshaped in the Age of Generative AI: A National Comparative Study among Chinese College Students

» [Prof. Peiqin Chen](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Yingchun Xu](#) (China)², [Dr. Ruonan Zhang](#) (United States)³ (1. Shanghai International Studies University (SISU), 2. Henan Finance University, 3. Rollins College)

Digital Divide and Rural School Students: Factors predicting students attitude towards ICT usage

» [Ms. MALINI SRINIVASAN](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Shamala Ramappa](#) (India)¹ (1. Central University of Tamil Nadu)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

Digital Inequality in Media Education: Insights from South Asia

» [Dr. Padma Rani](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Bhanu Bhakta Acharya](#) (Canada)², Dr. Kulveen Trehan (India)³, Dr. Lekhnath Pandey (Nepal)⁴, Ms. Madhubhashini Rathnayaka (Sri Lanka)⁵ (1. Manipal Institute of Communication, 2. University of Ottawa, 3. University School of Mass Communication, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, New Delhi, 4. Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, Ratna Rajyalaxmi Campus, Tribhuvan University, Kathmandu, Nepal, 5. National Education and Research Network)

Research on the influencing factors of digital capital level on the willingness of users of generative AI

» [Ms. Jingyuan Lin](#) (China)¹ (1. Southwestern University of Finance and Economics)

Digital inequalities and technology diffusion: case study of youth groups in the United States, China and Ghana

» [Mr. Zixian Wang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Weijia Kong](#) (China)¹ (1. Peking University)

14:00

Panel : REC-2

REC - Sacred Places, Tourism & the Media

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+37

Organised by: Prof. Krishna Sankar Kusuma (Panel Chair) (India)

Evangelizing through tourism: Use of media at Salt Lake City's Temple Square

» [Dr. Chiung Hwang Chen](#) (United States)¹ (1. Brigham Young University-Hawaii)

Typologies for attending "virtual" Sacred Places: Rituals and Nature of Religious Celebrations online and their impact on religious practices

» [Prof. Holger Sievert](#) (Germany)¹, Mr. Ralf Peter Reimann (Germany)² (1. Macromedia University, 2. Evangelical Church in the Rhineland)

Sacred Places and Mediated Religious Tourism in Zimbabwe: The Iconoclastic Venues of Three Flamboyant Prophets

» [Mr. Joseph Muyangata](#) (United States)¹ (1. Light of The World Bible College (Full Gospel Tabernacle International))

14:00

Panel : COA-1

COA - Politics and Education in Digital Culture

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+25

Organised by: Dr. Iván Facundo Rubinstein (Panel Chair) (Mexico) and Prof. Madhavi Reddy (Discussant) (India)

Content, Narrative, Emotion, and Values: The Four Dimensions of Animation Empowering the Innovative Dissemination of Traditional Chinese Culture

» [Ms. Zhang Qiyun](#) (China)¹ (1. The School of Journalism and Communication at Tsinghua University)

Emotionally Constructed Political Communication: Visual Framing Analysis of the Washington Post 's Editorial Cartoons Themed Ukraine War

» [Ms. Chen Mingyi](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Sijia Peng](#) (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. communication university of China)

The evolution of Kenyan cartooning: The rise of political communication in silhouette doodles

» [Prof. Levi Obonyo](#) (Kenya)¹, [Dr. Iesica Mwithia](#) (Australia)² (1. Daystar University, 2. University of Technology Sydney)

Educating Environment: A Comparative Content Analysis on Indian, Japanese and American Television Cartoon Series

» [Mrs. VIII. M.](#) (India)¹ (1. Assistant Professor, SDNB Vaishnav College for Women, Chromepet, Chennai)

14:00

Panel : LAW-2

LAW - New Research Approaches for New Regulatory Responses

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+26

Organised by: Dr. Erik Ugland (Panel Chair) (United States)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

Loot Box Advertising in the UK and South Korea: Using Meta's Ad Repository to Check Whether Video Game Adverts are Disclosing Loot Box Presence

» [Mr. Leon Xiao](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. beClaws.org)

Role of Accountability Forums in Analyzing the Performance of a Media Regulatory Authority: Insights from a Global South Country

» [Dr. Mahnoor Farooq](#) (Pakistan)¹ (1. University of Haripur)

Copyright Review and Subject Reflection on Content Production in the AIGC Environment—Based on an Investigation of the Intellectual Input of AI Users in the AI Novel "The Apostle of Destiny"

» [Ms. Huifeng Liu](#) (China)¹, Prof. Wen Yu (China)¹ (1. East China Normal University)

Mediation as a Shortcut to Justice and the Key Role of the Singapore Convention

» [Prof. Seldag Günes Peschke](#) (Türkiye)¹ (1. Ankara Yildirim Beyazit University)

14:00

Panel : ICO-2

ICO - Accessing the Cyber World, or Integrating into Online Communities? The Residents with Disabilities in Social Media

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+28*

Organised by: Mr. Yuqiao Yan (Convenor) (China), Ms. Xuan Chen (Convenor) (China), Dr. victor zhuang (Panel Chair) (Singapore), and Ms. Wenqi Tan (Discussant) (Australia)

Performing Disability in the Digital Marketplace: Self-Representation, Stigma, and the Commodification of the Body in Chinese Social Media

» [Ms. Peiyi Zhao](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China (CUC))

Visibility Paradox: Digital Anonymity and the Erasure of Disability Identity in Networked Spaces

» [Mr. Yuqiao Yan](#) (China)¹ (1. Tsinghua University)

Constructing Methodology in Fieldwork Research on the Deaf: An Alternative Media Practice Inspired by Bodily Impairments

» [Ms. Xuan Chen](#) (China)¹ (1. Zhejiang University, College of Media and International Culture, Hangzhou, China)

Playing to Connect: Online Game Play and Social Benefits among Blind and Visually Impaired

» [Dr. Yongjie Yue](#) (China)¹, Dr. Junming Yi (China)², Dr. PENGCHENG WANG (China)³ (1. Tsinghua University, 2. Renmin University of China, 3. Shanghai Jiaotong University)

14:00

Panel : POL-13

POL - Political Communication Research Section business meeting

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+27*

Organised by: Dr. Abdullahi Tasiu Abubakar (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

With remote participation from the Head of the Political Communication Section

16:00

Panel : POP-6

POP - Sustainable simplicity and questionable consumerism in contemporary screen culture

Venue - *The Hive LHS-LT*

Organised by: Prof. Qian Zhang (Panel Chair) (China)

Environmental Narrative and Global Resonance in Digital Rural Life: A Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis of Li Ziqi's YouTube Videos

» [Ms. Xiaomin Luo](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

The Pastoral Turn in Contemporary Screen Media: Nostalgia, Ecology, and Critique of Modernity

» [Ms. Xue Jiang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

The (In)Visibility of Environmental Sustainability in Momfluencer Culture: A Content Analysis of German Instagram Accounts

» Dr. Julia Lück-Benz (Germany)¹, Mr. Matthias Hufgard (Germany)² (1. University of Berlin, 2. Filmuniversität Babelsberg)

Digital culture as pedagogical: Cultivating ethical consumption on YouTube

» Dr. Heather Jaber (Qatar)¹ (1. Northwestern University in Qatar)

Poverty Relief or Makeover? Marginalized or Celebrity? Analyzing a YouTube Channel Documenting a Japanese Homeless Person's Escape from Poverty

» Ms. Minjoo Lee (Japan)¹ (1. The University of Tokyo)

"Surrounded with Junk": Reassessing Material Possessions through YouTube Decluttering Videos at the Peak of the COVID-19 Pandemic

» Ms. Barbara Ravbar (Czechia)¹ (1. Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism, Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University)

16:00

Panel : HEC-6

HEC - Towards an effective and ethical use of AI

Venue - WKWSC L2 Executive Seminar Room

Organised by: Dr. Olaf Werder (Panel Chair) (Australia) and Prof. ELIZA GOVENDER (Discussant) (South Africa)

Can Generative AI Correct Vaccine Misbeliefs? Exploring Targeted Messaging Strategies

» Dr. Hang Lu (United States)¹ (1. University of Michigan)

Toward Responsible Artificial Intelligence in Public Health Emergency Communication: Findings from a Multinational Delphi Study

» Dr. Daniela Mahl (Switzerland)¹, Prof. Mike S. Schäfer (Switzerland)¹, Mr. Stefan Adrian Voinea (Denmark)², Mr. Keyrellous Adib (Denmark)², Mr. Benjamin Paul Duncan (Denmark)², Mrs. Cristiana Salvi (Denmark)², Dr. David Novillo-Ortiz (Denmark)² (1. University of Zurich, 2. WHO Regional Office for Europe)

Acceptance of AI in Healthcare: Analysis of Factors Influencing Acceptance of Digital Technologies in Singapore Healthcare

» Ms. Smriti Srivastava (Singapore)¹, Ms. LI XIE (Singapore)¹, Ms. Kalya M. Kee (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

Detection of depression in Russian online texts: (Not going) from pre-computational studies to AI-assisted social aid

» Prof. Svetlana Bodrunova (Russian Federation)¹ (1. St. Petersburg State University)

Chat About My Health Complaints with that 'GAI': Health Communication in the Human-Computer Interaction Between Young Female and Generative AI Health Assistant in China

» Ms. Wang Wendi (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

16:00

Panel : AUD-2

AUD - Environment and audiences

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+47

Organised by: Myria Georgiou (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Sympathy or Schadenfreude in Face of Distant Disaster? Exploring the Factors and Mechanisms Behind Netizens' Empathic Responses to Environmental Disasters in Other Countries

» Ms. Mengying Zhang (China)¹, Ms. Xueli Zhong (China)² (1. Peking University HSBC Business School(PHBS), 2. Communication University of China (CUC))

Continued from Monday, 14 July

Participatory Environmental Communication: Do the Mediated Practices of Digital Communities Truly Contribute to Environmental Protection?—A Case Study of China's "Ant Forest" Project

» [Ms. Huaxi Dong](#) (China)¹, Mr. Jiyu Zou (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

From media engagement to environmental action: How social media audiences become active citizens

» [Ms. Kristiina Raud](#) (Estonia)¹ (1. Tallinn University BFM)

Exploring the Psychological Mechanism behind High Online Environmental Participation - Low Offline Environmental Action Paradox

» [Ms. Qiaoge Xie](#) (China)¹ (1. Shanghai Jiaotong University)

16:00

Panel : JRE-5

JRE - Environmental journalism: practice and research in diverse contexts II

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+49

Organised by: Prof. Abiodun Salawu (Panel Chair) (South Africa) and Dr. Victoria Fielding (Discussant) (Australia)

A Comparative Journalism Study of Mainstream Media on Arctic Environmental Governance in Near-Arctic States

» [Ms. Zicaiqi Liang](#) (China)¹, Ms. Yuwen Feng (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

The Liberal Model of News Media and Climate Action

» [Dr. Victoria Fielding](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Adelaide)

Disempowering 'Empowered' Grassroots: A Case of Decentralised Environmental Journalism for Chivumbe Hill in Malawi

» [Prof. Abiodun Salawu](#) (South Africa)¹, Mr. Saizi Kimu (South Africa)¹ (1. North-West University)

Traditional & Regional Narratives in Environmental Journalism: The Dual Role of Cultural Identity and Media Hostility in Shaping Environmental Consciousness

» [Ms. Jiaqi Guo](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication Nanjing University)

A Proposal for an Ethic of Justice in Climate Change News

» [Dr. Josh Anderson](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Arizona)

16:00

Panel : JRE-7

JRE - Professional journalism: contemporary debates, challenges and practices I

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+52

Organised by: Dr. DAN WU (Panel Chair) (China) and Prof. Qi Zhou (Discussant) (China)

Journalism and the Public Eye: Diverging Expectations, Shared Ideals, and the (Im)Possibility of Journalistic Descriptions of Reality

» [Ms. Verena Albert](#) (Germany)¹, Prof. Wiebke Loosen (Germany)¹ (1. Leibniz-Institute for Media Research | Hans-Bredow-Institut)

Fact-Checking Organisations in China: Characteristics, Verification Approaches, and Practices

» [Dr. Le Cao](#) (Germany)¹ (1. Leuphana University Lüneburg)

Does Media Handling of Official Announcements Affect Public Trust in Media? A Survey Experiment on Environmental News

» [Ms. Zhang Yu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Siwei Tan](#) (China)¹, Ms. Fenglei Ding (China)¹, Ms. Guanqi Liu (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

The Gaze of Desire: A Psychological Mechanism Analysis of Sensationalist News

» [Ms. Yiming HAO](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Hanyang University)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

16:00 **Panel : CAM-ESR-
CAM - ESR - Joint session Environmental Communication and Climate Change**

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+56

Organised by: Dr. Amparo Cadavid (Panel Chair) (Colombia)

Saving our Species: Creating Systemic Change in Regional Communities in New South Wales, Australia

» Dr. Chloe Killen (Australia)¹, Prof. Phillip McIntyre (Australia)¹, Dr. Kerrie Foxwell Norton (Australia)², Prof. Matthew Hayward (Australia)¹, Mr. Luke Foster (Australia)³, Mr. Aaron Mulcahy (Australia)³, Ms. Lucinda Ransom (Australia)³, Mr. Barry Williams (Australia)¹ (1. University of Newcastle, 2. Griffith University, 3. Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water)

Environmental Activism and Indigenous Knowledge: Bridging the Gap

» Ms. Saba Batool (China)¹, Mr. Meetha Ram (Italy)², Mr. Daood Muhammad (China)³ (1. Shenzhen University, 2. University of Ferrara, 3. Wuhan Institute of Technology)

#MasyarakatAdat Series: Understanding Climate Crisis from Indigenous Women in Indonesia

» Ms. Elizabeth Florence Warikar (Indonesia)¹ (1. Soegijapranata Catholic University)

The Golden Langur (*Trachepithacus geei*): Community Communication and Conservation in the Kakoijana Region of Bongaigaon District, Assam (India)

» Dr. Iyotirmay Das (India)¹, Dr. Ashoke Das (India)² (1. Mahindra University, 2. Abhayapuri College)

"The Call of Aprons": Ecological Discourse Construction and Embodied Communication Practices of Rural Environmental Publicity Aprons — A Field Study of Village Clusters in Southeastern China

» Ms. Linfan Shen (China)¹, Ms. Yifei Wang (China)¹ (1. Jilin University)

16:00 **Panel : GEN-6
GEN - Dating diaries: Online identity disclosure and privacy**

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR4

Organised by: Dr. Qianru Huang (Panel Chair) (China) and Dr. Pallavi Bansal (Discussant) (India)

Hiding More than Others: Identity Disclosure in Online Dating among Disabled Gay Men in China

» Dr. Longxuan Zhao (China)¹, Mr. Chen Ke (China)² (1. Tongji University, 2. Communication University of China)

Living a dating lifestyle: Young women's production of dating diaries on Xiaohongshu

» Ms. Yan Tan (Macao)¹ (1. University of Macau)

Navigating Algorithms: LGBTQ+ Identity, Representation, and Discourse in AI-Empowered Dating Apps in China

» Dr. Qianru Huang (United States)¹ (1. Arizona State University)

Did I swipe right? Decoding women's trust dynamics on online dating platforms

» Dr. Pallavi Bansal (India)¹, Dr. Moina Khan (India)¹ (1. Times School of Media, Bennett University)

Heterotopia of Intimacy and Transitional Objects in Fans' Gendered Identification

» Dr. Erika Ningxin Wang (China)¹ (1. The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Shenzhen)

16:00 **Panel : GEN-3
GEN - Beyond the Sex Wars: Feminist Interventions of Sex Work, Pornography, Gender-Based Violence in Asia.**

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5

Organised by: Dr. Eunbi Lee (Panel Chair) (Singapore), Dr. Darshana Sreedhar Mini (Discussant) (United States), Dr. Michelle Ho (Convenor) (Singapore), Dr. Sharmila Parmanand (Convenor) (United Kingdom), Ms. Chihiro Toya (Convenor) (United Kingdom), and Ms. Wi En Ng (Convenor) (Singapore)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

Feminist Discourses on the Nordic Model in Japan: Examining the Role of (Counter-)Media

» [Ms. Chihiro Toya](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. SOAS University of London)

Strange bedfellows: US influence, paternalistic feminisms, and the politics of anti-trafficking in the Philippines

» [Dr. Sharmila Parmanand](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. The London School of Economics and Political Science)

Male Grievances on Reddit: Theorizing Gender-Based Violence in Singapore

» [Ms. Wi En Ng](#) (Singapore)¹, [Dr. Michelle Ho](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

Anti-Sex Work Gentrification: Critical Feminist Discourse Analysis of Red-Light District Demolition in South Korea.

» [Dr. Eunbi Lee](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

More than gender issues or online hate: Exploring discourses of networked misogyny in Chinese context

» [Dr. Fang Yuan](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Tingli Liu](#) (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. tingli8563@cuc.edu.cn)

16:00

Panel : ESR-2

ESR - Oceans and Water: Environmental and Climate Change Communication

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6

Organised by: [Dr. Maitreyee Mishra](#) (Panel Chair) (India)

Reciprocity in human-ocean relationships: Towards the subversion of dominant environmental discourses

» [Ms. Kianna Gallagher](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Tasmania)

How Does the Ocean Lose Its Voice? A Semantic Network Analysis of Japan's Diplomatic Discourse on Nuclear Wastewater Discharge

» [Dr. Xiaoyang Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. Beihang University)

Incidental Exposure to Climate Change Information on Social Media, Climate Change Anxiety, And Engagement in Ocean Renewable Energy in the Pacific: A Serial Mediation Model

» [Dr. Francis Dalisay](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Masahiro Yamamoto](#) (United States)², [Dr. Jay Hmielowski](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Florida, 2. University at Albany - State University of New York)

Cultural narratives from female communities of care: silver female surfers on becoming ocean ambassadors

» [Dr. Elena Maydell](#) (New Zealand)¹, [Dr. Inessa Love](#) (United States)² (1. Massey University, 2. University of Hawaii)

Marine Environmental Risk Perception between National Sentiment and Media Literacy: A Study on the Chinese Short Video Users about Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Water Discharge

» [Dr. wenwen zhao](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Tongwen Xu](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Yunhong Lyu](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Lifei Long](#) (China)¹ (1. guangdong ocean university)

16:00

Panel : ESR-7

ESR - Environmental and Climate Change Protest, Advocacy and Activism

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7

Organised by: [Prof. Libby Lester](#) (Panel Chair) (Australia)

From Likes to Change: Examining environmental advocacy through Instagram influencers in India

» [Dr. Madhavi Ravikummar](#) (India)¹ (1. University of Hyderabad)

Protect? Promote? Privatize?: Examining the Social Media Messaging of Two Environmental NGOs in Cambodia

» [Ms. Sokummono Khan](#) (Cambodia)¹ (1. The University of Queensland)

Challenges of Disaster Communication and Community Participation: A Case Study from Barpeta, Assam

» [Ms. Chinmoyee Deka](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Abhinandan Saikia](#) (India)¹ (1. Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Guwahati)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

Spontaneous Volunteerism in Disasters in Australia: Building community resilience in disaster risk reduction

» [Dr. Kate Delmo](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Technology Sydney)

Exploring Mediatized Environment: A Fieldwork on the Desertification Combating Movement in Alxa Left Banner

» [Dr. A Xi ta](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Shuang Shen](#) (China)² (1. School of journalism and communication, Inner Mongolia Normal University, 2. School of Journalism & communication, Zhengzhou university)

16:00

Panel : PCR-2

PCR - Storytelling and Creative Methodologies

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: Prof. Lauren Dyll (Discussant, Panel Chair) (South Africa) and Dr. Carolina Escudero (Discussant) (Spain)

Voices in the silence: Human and non-human participation in climate change adaptation stories of fisherfolk in Del Carmen, Siargao Islands, Philippines

» [Dr. Daniel Renz Roc](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Los Baños)

Characters, values, aesthetics: Creative methods for water security

» [Dr. Skye Doherty](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Helen Marshall](#) (Australia)¹, [Ms. Joanne Anderton](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Queensland)

Storytellers' Narrative Values in Local Communities: A Study on the Practice of Cultural Communication in Regional Development

» [Mr. Sun Shang-Cheng Lin](#) (Taiwan)¹, [Dr. Anita Kuei-Chun Liu](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. Department of Bio-Industry Communication and Development, National Taiwan University)

Can the commercial be Political? Challenges Para Sport storytelling and social change

» [Dr. Jessica Noske-Turner](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Prof. Mufunanji Magalasi](#) (Malawi)², [Dr. Emma Pullen](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Ms. Jennie Wong](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Dr. Lauren Burch](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Ms. Sheila Cleo Mogalo](#) (Kenya)¹ (1. Loughborough University, 2. University of Malawi)

El boddy mapping como escenario teórico y metodológico en la comunicación participativa

» [Dr. Betty Milena Marrugo Rivera](#) (Colombia)¹ (1. Universidad de Cartagena)

16:00

Panel : INC-11

INC - Global Media and Technology

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: Dr. Anilesh Kumar (Panel Chair) (Hong Kong)

Is It Possible to Fact-Check Political Information Using Deep Learning?

» [Ms. HEEIAY KIM](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Prof. CHUNG JOO CHUNG](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Ms. Shichao Zhang](#) (Korea, Republic of)² (1. Kyungpook National University, 2. Department of Media & Communication, Kyungpook National University)

AI Anchors as Transmitters of Public Diplomacy: Perceived Credibility of Environmental and Political News in China

» [Mr. Yingqiao Zhao](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist Univeristy)

The weaponization of social media: TikTok and the Global Information Warfare

» [Dr. Serge Banyongen](#) (Canada)¹, [Prof. ALEXIE TCHEUYAP](#) (Canada)² (1. University of Ottawa, 2. University of Waterloo)

Glocalization of Environmental Activism: The United Nations Environment Programme's Strategic Communication on Chinese Social Media

» [Dr. Zhifei Mao](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Qianru Zhou](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Shilei Qi](#) (China)¹ (1. Shenzhen University)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

16:00

Panel : MPS-4

MPS - Relation-building and Relation-breaking

Venue - WKWSCI L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: Prof. Di Wang (Panel Chair) (Macao)

Clicks to Commitment: The Interplay of Intrapersonal and Interpersonal Communication in Online Matchmaking

» [Ms. Srushti Govilkar](#) (India)¹, [Ms. Kanishree Pathak](#) (India)², Prof. Ruchi Tewari (India)³ (1. Research Assistant at MICA, 2. Research Fellow at MICA, 3. Professor at MICA)

Eco-Conscious Coupling in India: Examining Environmental Values and Partner Selection

» [Mr. Ananthu Nair](#) (India)¹, [Mr. Joel M Jacob](#) (India)² (1. Manipal Academy of Higher Education (MAHE), Bengaluru Campus, 2. Christ University)

Are You Ready to Connect? Privacy Management and Willingness to Form Social Connections on Social Media

» [Ms. Xueqin Huang](#) (Japan)¹ (1. Nagoya University)

Everyday Polarization and the Incubation of New Ideas: A Study of the Douban Breakup Group

» [Dr. YAN XU](#) (China)¹, Ms. Wenfang Zhou (China)¹ (1. Fudan University)

16:00

Panel : POL-2

POL - Populism, Polarization, and Trust

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

Organised by: Dr. Sebastian Svegaard (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Australia)

When Trust Divides: Scandals, Populists, and the Fragility of Democratic Legitimacy

» [Dr. Karl Patrick Mendoza](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. Polytechnic University of the Philippines)

Trend Towards Far-Right Populism on X: A Case Study of France's Populist Leaders Marine Le Pen and Jordan Bardella

» [Ms. Yuefeng Qu](#) (China)¹, Ms. Huanmo Cui (China)² (1. Shandong University, 2. Peking University)

Is Populism a Discourse or an Ideology: understanding populism's intersections with polarisation and partisanship

» [Dr. Sebastian Svegaard](#) (Australia)¹, Dr. Samantha Vilkins (Australia)¹, Ms. Laura Lefevre (Australia)¹ (1. Digital Media Research Centre, Queensland University of Technology)

Affective Polarization in Online Crosscutting Discussion of Traditional Chinese Medicine: The Moderating Effect of National Identity

» [Dr. Jinzhuo Liu](#) (China)¹, Prof. Jun Zhang (China)² (1. Fudan University, 2. Beijing Normal University)

16:00

Panel : MPS-5

MPS - How users deal with misinformation and fake news

Venue - WKWSCI L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: Ms. Karolina Šimková (Panel Chair) (Czechia)

Navigating the information fog: How users live with misinformation on digital platforms

» [Dr. Dorismilda Flores-Márquez](#) (Mexico)¹ (1. Universidad La Salle Bajío)

Comment Exposure as a Hindrance: How It Undermines the Effectiveness of Misinformation Correction on Social Media

» [Dr. DR. QINYU E](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Lu Liu](#) (China)¹ (1. College of Publishing, University of Shanghai for Science and Technology)

Why Netizens Rebut Transnational Fake News: Examining the Role of Perceived Fake News Seriousness, Emotional Response, and Perceived Issue Importance

» [Dr. YANJUN LIN](#) (China)¹, Prof. xiaoke guo (China)¹, [Ms. Yuge Xu](#) (China)¹, Ms. Zhiqi Zhang (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

Leveraging Public Perceptions Through Strategic Digital Communication (Case Study: Presidential Communication Office in Indonesia's Free Nutritious Meals Program)

» Mrs. Vanny Adriani (Indonesia)¹, Mrs. Amalia Yaksa Parijata (Indonesia)¹, Mrs. Shinta Kristanti (Indonesia)¹ (1. LSPR Institute of Communication & Business)

An Eye-Tracking Study: The Impact of Meme Modality and Social Reaction Cues on Misinformation Credibility

» Ms. Jijiang Tang (United States)¹ (1. University of Miami)

16:00

Panel : CJD-3

CJD - Communication, Social Justice and Democracy in the Global South

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Dr. Fernando Oliveira Paulino (Panel Chair) (Brazil), Prof. Usha Raman (Discussant) (India), and Prof. JULIANO DOMINGUES (Convenor) (Brazil)

Parallels between Mexican and Brazilian Public Communication: Regulatory mirages in the pursuit of democracy, social justice, independence and autonomy

» Prof. Laura Aguila (Mexico)¹, Dr. Fernando Oliveira Paulino (Brazil)² (1. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México (UNAM), 2. University of Brasilia)

The value of transparency and audience participation in democracy: A perspective from media accountability in Chile

» Ms. Constanza Hormazabal (Chile)¹ (1. Universidad de los Andes, Chile)

Communication, social justice and democracy in the management of extreme right-wing governments. The Argentinean case.

» Prof. Daniela Inés Monje (Argentina)¹ (1. Universidad Nacional de Córdoba)

Communication in the Global South: Exploring the Intersection of Media, Social Justice, and Democracy in Pakistan and Nigeria

» Dr. Muhammad Yousaf (Pakistan)¹ (1. University of Gujarat)

Expression and Press Freedom Under Pressure: Violence and Democratic Fragility in Latin America

» Prof. Juliano Domingues (Brazil)¹ (1. Universidade Católica de Pernambuco (Unicap) / Universidade de Pernambuco (UPE))

16:00

Panel : VIC-3

VIC - AI – Artificial Intelligence (2)

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 8

Organised by: Dr. Kristy H. A. Kang (Panel Chair) (United States)

Photorealistic Simulation in Parametric Style: A Study on AI-generated Film Photography and Emotional Cognition

» Ms. Xintian Feng (China)¹, Ms. Yuxuan Fan (China)² (1. Wuhan University, 2. Communication University of China)

Emotion and Machines: Analyzing the Image of AI in Science Fiction Films from Deleuze's Affect Theory

» Ms. Yongxi Lai (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China, Beijing, China)

The Masi Mapping Project: Utilizing AI to Analyze Museum Collections and Cultural Heritage Practices in the Pacific

» Dr. Kristy H. A. Kang (United States)¹ (1. Arizona State University)

Balancing Truth and Compassion: Ethical Principles in Contemporary Photojournalism

» Mr. Richard Sam Dickson (Ghana)¹, Mr. Abdulwahab Tahhan (Hong Kong)² (1. Hong Kong Baptist University, 2. Hong Kong Baptist University)

From the White Cube to the Black Box: AI-Generated Art on Social Media and Cosmopolitan Possibilities

» Ms. Jiayu Chen (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

The Double Effect of AIGC in Polar Crisis Communication: Cognitive Reconstruction and Action Paradigm

» [Ms. Fengjie Bi](#) (China)¹ (1. Nanjing Normal University)

16:00

Panel : MER-6

MER - Media Education Research Section keynote and business meeting

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: Dr. Devina Sarwatay (Convenor) (United Kingdom), Mrs. Rayen Condeza (Convenor) (Chile), and Dr. Oscar Miranda-Villanueva (Convenor) (Mexico)

16:00

Panel : MPA-1

MPA - Reframing Media Work: Identity, Innovation and Industry Shifts in Contemporary Screen Production

Venue - WKWSCI TR+7

Organised by: Dr. María Teresa Nicolás Gavilán (Panel Chair) (Mexico)

Transforming into An Online Short Drama Producer: the reconstruction of professional identity in the Chinese online screen industry

» [Ms. Chengyao Liu](#) (United Kingdom)¹, Dr. Yuan TIAN (China)² (1. University of Leeds, 2. Zhejiang University)

Unveiling Environmental Justice in Malaysian Documentary Film: A Causal Layered Analysis (CLA) of Production Narratives and Industry Constraints

» [Dr. Nur Kareelawati Abd Karim](#) (Malaysia)¹ (1. Universiti Sains Islam Malaysia)

Chinese Micro-dramas: Genre, Market, and Going Overseas

» [Prof. Yuan Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Zhaoyan Huang](#) (China)¹ (1. Xi'an Jiaotong University.)

“We don’t want to commit as micro-drama creators”: how do these professionals navigate opportunities and internalised prejudices in the evolving micro drama industry

» [Mr. JINWEI ZHANG](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Ms. Hui Lin](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. King's College London)

16:00

Panel : MCS-5

MCS - Shaping identities and on and off the field: the role of sports communication

Venue - WKWSCI TR+8

Organised by: Dr. Peter English (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Representing the Little Red Dot: Athletic Success, Authenticity, and National Identity in Singapore

» [Dr. Zesheng Yang](#) (China)¹, Ms. Ximeng Shang (China)², Mr. Lintao Wang (China)³ (1. Independent scholar, 2. Beijing Foreign Studies University, 3. University of Sanya)

Before Half-time: Representation, Cultural Negotiation and Identity Building In US-Brazilian Diaspora NFL News

» [Dr. Tania Rosas-Moreno](#) (United States)¹ (1. Loyola University Maryland)

Video games and ephemera as strategies of queer resistance to cis/heteronormativity in skateboarding

» [Dr. Bethany Geckle](#) (United States)¹ (1. Miami University)

The Rise and Fall of Nationalism in Sports Fandom: A Quadratic Relationship

» [Dr. Dongdong Yang](#) (United States)¹ (1. Montclair State University)

Competing, co-existing, or intersecting: A pluralistic discourse study of Chinese virtual cyclists on the Zwift platform

» [Dr. Luleiya HUANG](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Xuemei BI](#) (China)¹, Mr. Zijie MENG (China)¹, Mr. Xuyang LI (China)¹ (1. Beijing Sport University)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

Constructing National Identity of Naturalized Athletes from the Perspective of Fandom Online Discursive Activism in China

» Ms. Lingmeng Xu (China)¹, Ms. Shuran Jia (China)¹, Ms. Jiayi Ma (China)¹, Ms. Xiaoheng Liang (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University)

16:00

Panel : CPT-3

CPT - Governing vulnerable groups and communities through data and technology

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+35

Organised by: Dr. Andrea Medrado (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Cyberhate towards migrants in Chile and regulation initiatives

» Dr. Nairbis D. Sibrian D. (Chile)¹ (1. Facultad de Comunicaciones Universidad del Desarrollo)

Rethinking responsible digital identity systems: datafication, power asymmetries and recognition among encamped Karen refugees in Thailand.

» Prof. Mirca Madianou (United Kingdom)¹, Dr. Charlotte Hill (Thailand)² (1. Goldsmiths, University of London, 2. Department of Media Arts and Design, Chiang Mai University)

Digital Divide, Social Support, and eHealth Adoption: A Cross-Country Study of Older Adults in Singapore, China, and the United States

» Ms. Zheng Yi (Singapore)¹, Dr. Shaohai Jiang (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

In the Frame of an AI Cold War: Locating Community and Participation as a Means of Resistance

» Dr. Aditya Deshbandhu (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Exeter)

16:00

Panel : CPT-4

CPT - Emerging Digital Technologies Policies and Laws in South Asia Beyond Geopolitical Approach

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+36

Organised by: Dr. Harsha Man Maharjan (Panel Chair) (Qatar), Dr. Anis Rahman (Convenor) (United States), Ms. Shubhangi Heda (Convenor) (Australia), Dr. Mahnoor Farooq (Convenor) (Pakistan), and Dr. Shabana Naveed (Convenor) (Pakistan)

Policy Rhetoric to Practice: The Case of Streaming Services in India

» Ms. Shubhangi Heda (Australia)¹ (1. Queensland University of Technology)

Communication Policies of a Digital Authoritarian Regime in Bangladesh

» Dr. Anis Rahman (United States)¹ (1. University of Washington)

Secretive Digital State: Hidden Policy Documents and the Issues of Transparency and Accountability of the National Identification System in Nepal

» Dr. Harsha Man Maharjan (Qatar)¹ (1. Northwestern University in Qatar)

Dynamics of Elite Capture on Media Regulation: Policies and Practices in Pakistan

» Dr. Mahnoor Farooq (Pakistan)¹, Dr. Shabana Naveed (Pakistan)² (1. University of Haripur, 2. Lahore Garrison University)

16:00

Panel : REC-3

REC - Religion Content Analysis

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+37

Organised by: Prof. Holger Sievert (Panel Chair) (Germany)

Spectacles of Faith, Gods and Superstars and Sacred Screens: Religion, Culture, and Structures of Feeling in Indian Cinema

» Mr. Ram Kumar Dhar (India)¹, Dr. Shamala Ramappa (India)¹ (1. Central University of Tamil Nadu)

Continued from Monday, 14 July

The Digitalization of Religion and the Reconstruction of the Sacred—A Discourse Analysis Based on ask_jesus Livestream

» Mr. Junyu JIANG (China)¹, Ms. Zhen Liu (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Reconstructing the Sacred: Technological Deterritorialization and Symbolic Consumption in Jitong's Spirit Medium Possession Rituals on Short Video Platforms

» Ms. 露杨 (China)¹, Ms. Yichun SUN (China)² (1. Wuhan University, 2. Communication University of China)

16:00

Panel : COA-2

COA - Influence of Comics and Cartoons on Environmental Discourse

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+25*

Organised by: Prof. Levi Obonyo (Panel Chair) (Kenya) and Mrs. VIJL. M. (Discussant) (India)

Activating Environmental Justice through Cartoons: A case study of 'Green Humour' in Advocating Equity and Sustainability

» Prof. Madhavi Reddy (India)¹ (1. Savitribai Phule Pune University)

Sacred Landscapes and Fragile Futures: Shinto and Buddhist Philosophies in the Environmental Narratives of Japanese Manga

» Ms. Ching Yi Chan (Hong Kong)¹ (1. The Chinese University of Hong Kong)

Unsustainable Tourism: Rising Awareness Through a Local Comic Book.

» Dr. Iván Facundo Rubinstein (Mexico)¹ (1. National Autonomous University of Mexico)

16:00

Panel : ORG-1

ORG - Organisational Strategy, Change and Advocacy

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+26*

Organised by: Prof. Gisela Goncalves (Panel Chair) (Portugal)

Whose sustainability is it anyway? Exploring business contributions towards mainstreaming sustainability

» Prof. Abena Yeboah-Banin (Ghana)¹ (1. University of Ghana)

An Examination of the Appropriateness and Effectiveness of Invited Employee Advocacy on Social Media

» Dr. cheng zeng (United States)¹ (1. North Dakota State University)

Benefactor as Beneficiary: Featuring Patient Volunteers in Health

» Dr. Lola Xie (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

Understanding Organizational Change in Nonprofits Through the Configurational Approach: Stakeholder Listening and Organizational Ambidexterity

» Dr. Rong Wang (United States)¹, Ms. Katherine Scrivani (United States)², Dr. Sophia Fu (United States)² (1. Vanderbilt University, 2. Rutgers University)

Eco-Content Creators: How Organizations Adapt to and Induce Change in Sustainability Communication

» Dr. samar benromdhane (United Arab Emirates)¹, Mr. Yasser Mohammed Lodha (United Arab Emirates)¹ (1. Ajman University)

16:00

Panel : DIM-1

DIM - Digital Platforms and Diasporic Identities

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+28*

Organised by: Dr. Jessica Retis (United States)

Digital Diaspora and Emotional Networks: The Returning Experiences of Chinese International Students during COVID-19

» Mr. YU ZOU (China)¹, Ms. 晓欢 张 (China)¹, Ms. siyu cui (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

"Listening" to the Community: Latinx Digital-Native Media Outlets' Engaging Practices During Electoral Processes

» Dr. Lourdes Cueva Chacón (United States)¹, Dr. Jessica Retis (United States)² (1. San Diego State University, 2. University of Arizona)

Continued from **Monday, 14 July**

Female migrant workers building happiness through WeChat: maintaining relationships with parents, siblings

» [Dr. Linxin WANG](#) (China)¹ (1. non)

16:00

Panel : SPS-6

SPS - Partner Session / AMIC: Innovations and Best Practices in Environmental Communication Education in Asian Communication and Journalism Schools

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+27

Organised by: Ramon Guillermo R. Tuazon (Panel Chair), Dr. Pamela Custodio (Discussant) (Philippines), Dr. Muneo Kaigo (Discussant) (Japan), Dr. Sadia Jamil (Discussant) (China), and Dr. S M Shameem Reza (Discussant) (Bangladesh)

Tuesday, 15 July

08:30

Panel : JRE-8

JRE - Professional journalism: contemporary debates, challenges and practices II

Venue - The Hive LHS-LT

Organised by: Dr. Katja Lehtisaari (Panel Chair) (Finland) and Prof. Yu Wang (Discussant) (China)

From Perceived Solutions to Climate Action: Examining the Mediating Role of Trust in Solutions Journalism

» [Mrs. Hye won Cho](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (KAIST))

Communicating trustworthiness in turbulent times? Views of Finnish journalism professionals and audiences on media power, autonomy, and trust

» [Dr. Katja Lehtisaari](#) (Finland)¹, Mr. Mikko Grönlund (Finland)², Dr. Minna Horowitz (Finland)³ (1. Tampere University, 2. University of Turku, 3. University of Helsinki)

The Evolution and Logic of Fact-Checking Practices in China: A Content Analysis of Chinese Fact-Checkers

» [Dr. Lutong Sun](#) (China)¹, Prof. Yu Wang (China)², Dr. He Gou (China)³ (1. China University of Labor Relations, 2. Communication University of China, 3. xi'an Jiaotong University)

Prebunking and Debunking Synergy: Integrating Stakeholder Collaboration, Digital Literacy, and Technological Innovations to Combat Dis/Misinformation in Indonesia

» [Dr. Amia Luthfia](#) (Indonesia)¹, Dr. Muslikhin Muslikhin (Indonesia)² (1. Marketing Communication Program, Communication Department, Bina Nusantara University, 2. Mass Communication Program, Communication Department, Bina Nusantara University)

Is it time for an intersectional approach in journalism practice and media research to become a norm?

» [Dr. Usha Manchanda Rodrigues](#) (Australia)¹ (1. School of Information and Communication Studies, Charles Sturt University)

Understanding the Intricacies of Intentional News Avoidance in Election Times

» [Mr. Chun Hong Tse](#) (United States)¹, Ms. Hayley Sum (Hong Kong)², Ms. Degel Cheung (Hong Kong)³, Dr. Roberto Spiezio (Taiwan)⁴ (1. University of Wisconsin-Madison, 2. St. Paul's Convent School, 3. The Chinese University of Hong Kong, 4. Ming Chuan University)

08:30

Panel : HEC-7

HEC - Trust and mistrust in social transformation

Venue - WKWSCI L2 Executive Seminar Room

Organised by: Ms. Zixi Li (Panel Chair) (Hong Kong) and Dr. Cindy Ngai (Discussant) (Hong Kong)

Continued from Tuesday, 15 July

A Cross-Sectional Study Examining the Role of Doctors' Trust in Patients' Requests for Antibiotics: A Neglected Perspective

» Ms. Aline Rinaldi (Switzerland)¹, Prof. Peter Schulz (Switzerland)¹, Mrs. Anna Bullo (Switzerland)¹, Dr. Serena Petrocchi (Switzerland)¹, Prof. Luca Gabutti (Switzerland)¹ (1. Università della Svizzera Italiana)

Zero Trust and The Future of Telemedicine in Indonesia: Strengthening Security and User Confidence

» Dr. Syahrul Agung Setiawan (Indonesia)¹, Mr. Tatak Setiadi (Indonesia)², Dr. Eko Pamuji (Indonesia)² (1. Universitas Gadjah Mada, 2. Universitas Negeri Surabaya)

Bridging Faith and Health: Harmonizing Cultural Heritage and Public Safety at the MahaKumbh

» Dr. BHARTI GUPTA (India)¹, Dr. Sananda Mukherjee (India)² (1. Assistant Professor, Department of Tourism and Travel Management, Central University of Jammu, India, 2. Assistant Professor, School of Mass Communication KIIT DU, Bhubaneswar, India.)

Whom should I listen to? Understanding the influence of social media information sources and illness representations on infertility treatment preferences in China

» Mr. Jinghan Ma (China)¹, Ms. Nan Yang (China)², Prof. Yungeng Li (China)¹ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 2. East China Normal University)

Trust Transfer from Artificial Intelligence to Healthcare Institutions: An Integrated Framework of Multiple Literacies and Medical Trust

» Dr. jie yao (China)¹, Dr. Chu Chu (China)¹, Dr. Wenhao Han (China)² (1. School of Journalism, Fudan University, 2. School of Psychology, Shandong Second Medical University)

08:30

Panel : POP-4

POP - The endurance of material objects in digital times

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+49

Organised by: Prof. Yongliang Gao (Panel Chair) (China)

Beyond Paper Pieces: A Digital Ethnography Exploring the Persistence and Symbolism of Photocard Culture in China

» Ms. Yan Xu (Hong Kong)¹, Ms. Xinyue Wang (Hong Kong)² (1. Hong Kong Baptist University, 2. The University of Hong Kong)

Object-oriented fandom: A study of K-pop fans' photocards collecting practice

» Ms. XI LIU (China)¹ (1. Shenzhen University)

"Painful cars": Ritual, Representation, and Relation in the Chinese Itasha Community - An Ethnographic Study

» Dr. Xudong Weng (China)¹, Mr. Ruisi Huang (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Participatory Culture, Taste and Distinction Based on Figuration: A Case Study of Electric Car Community

» Mr. Hangeng Yang (China)¹ (1. None)

08:30

Panel : POP-5

POP - Stabilizing and subverting states through popular culture

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+52

Organised by: Dr. Jingwei (Amy) Piao (Panel Chair) (China)

Who is the Thief? Algorithmic Mediation, Digital Nationalism, and the Politics of Cultural Ownership

» Ms. Jiahui Xing (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Sydney)

Embodying the Technocratic Gaze: Aamir Khan's Stardom, Nationalism and Bollywood Cinema

» Dr. Soumik Pal (Bangladesh)¹ (1. North South University)

Aesthetics of Fascism: Ideology and Power in Post-9/11 American Cinema

» Ms. Sophia Hershfield (Canada)¹ (1. York university)

The Universal Language of Democracy: Jazz as an Empty Signifier in U.S. Cultural Diplomacy

» Ms. Tursynay Alikhanova (United States)¹ (1. Florida State University)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

08:30

Panel : CPT-6

CPT - Disability digital citizenship in ableist ecologies: Implications for policy

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+53*

Organised by: Dr. victor zhuang (Convenor) (Singapore) and Ms. Wenqi Tan (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Australia)

Automated Intelligence or Automated Inequality?: automated hiring tools and disability in Singapore

» Ms. Sze Hwee Jace Tay (Singapore)¹ (1. Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University)

Unjustifiable hardship: digital communication, disability and remote work/study policies at South African Universities

» Prof. Lorenzo Dalvit (South Africa)¹ (1. Rhodes University)

Disability and Digital Citizenship in Asia-Pacific Digital Societies

» Prof. Gerard Goggin (Australia)¹ (1. Western Sydney University)

Digital Learning in School and at Work: Challenges and Strategies for Neurodivergent Individuals

» Ms. Neria Loke (Singapore)¹, Ms. Yuan Wang (Singapore)¹, Prof. Chei Sian Lee (Singapore)¹ (1. Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University)

08:30

Panel : CAM-4

CAM - Grassroots Media and Participatory Communication

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+56*

Organised by: Dr. Bridget Backhaus (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Forté FM community radio and the use of indigenous language as conduit for listeners' participation and community development in Alice, South Africa

» Prof. Oluyinka Osunkunle (South Africa)¹ (1. University of Fort Hare)

Narrative Construction and Emotional Engagement in Intercultural Communication by Grassroots' Public Welfare Organizations: A Case Study of Ocean Conservation Namibia's Communication Practices

» Ms. Yuwei Wang (China)¹, Mr. Yu Tian (China)², Mr. Yibo Chen (China)³ (1. Peking University, 2. Xinhua News Agency, 3. Communication University of China)

Conflicto ambiental, participación social y movilización digital. Estudio de caso y modelo de intervención.

» Dr. Gabriel Kaplún (Uruguay)¹, Prof. Martín Martínez Puga (Uruguay)¹ (1. Universidad de la República)

Echoes of Change: Empowering the Marginalised or Disrupting State-Constructed Discourses during Electioneering?

» Mr. Gaolefufa Ioshua Madiba (China)¹ (1. Ph.D. Candidate at School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

08:30

Panel : GEN-8

GEN - Digital Inclusion, Gender and Rural Development

Venue - *GAIA ABS-SR4*

Organised by: Dr. Ke Cai (Discussant) (China), Prof. Wei BU (Convenor, Panel Chair) (China), Dr. Ziyang Wang (Discussant) (China), Dr. Cao Ang (Discussant) (China), and Ms. Jin Yang (Discussant) (China)

A Study on The Digital Literacy Education of Homestay Manager Trainers from The Perspective of Gender

» Dr. Ke Cai (China)¹ (1. Beijing Foreign Studies University)

A Study on the Digital Literacy Practices of Female Homestay Inn Managers in Rural China

» Dr. Cao Ang (China)¹ (1. College of Humanities and Development Studies, China Agricultural University)

Reconstructing gendered development space: urban rural reconciliation, communication technology and discursive practice

» Dr. Ziyang Wang (China)¹ (1. Southwest University of Political Science and Law, China)

Continued from Tuesday, 15 July

Chinese Rural Women as Online Gig Workers: The Negotiation and Presentation of Identities

» [Prof. Yun Long](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Xin Zeng](#) (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. Institute of Journalism and Communication Chinese Academy of Social Sciences)

08:30

Panel : GEN-9

GEN - Gender performance, privacy and the 'perfect body'

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5

Organised by: Dr. Ambrish Saxena (Panel Chair) (India) and Ms. Akosua Asantewaa Anane (Discussant) (Ghana)

From Slim Hegemony to "Fatmosphere": Female Media Practices in Negotiating Body Image with Platforms

» [Ms. Sizhe Wu](#) (China)¹ (1. University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences)

Diversity is Positive: Beauty Diversity as a Relief between Social Media Engagement and Social Appearance Anxiety Among Young Women

» [Ms. Geer WANG](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Yunchao CHAI](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Beijing Normal University)

Filtered Beauty: Exploring Women's Appearance Anxiety in the Social Media Era — A Case Study of Xiaohongshu

» [Ms. huan Yu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. liushuang Shi](#) (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University-Hong Kong Baptist University United International College (UIC))

"CURATING THE SELF: AN EXPLORATION OF FEMALE CELEBRITIES' USE OF BODY MODIFICATION FOR SELF-PRESENTATION SOCIAL MEDIA "

» [Ms. Akosua Asantewaa Anane](#) (Ghana)¹ (1. University of Education, Winneba)

08:30

Panel : ESR-6

ESR - Decolonisation, Environmental Justice and Communication 2

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6

Organised by: Dr. Maitreyee Mishra (Panel Chair) (India)

Communicating Stakeholder Roles and Voices on Environmental Justice in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

» [Prof. Herbert Batta](#) (Nigeria)¹ (1. University of Uyo)

Myth and Mega Projects: Lepcha Resistance and the Struggle for Environmental Justice in Sikkim

» [Prof. Archana Arul](#) (India)¹ (1. SRM University Sikkim)

Community-Led Advocacy: Effective Communication Strategies for Environmental Justice Initiatives: A Case of Mau Forest in Kenya.

» [Ms. Cynthia Cyndy Anyango Odingo](#) (Kenya)¹ (1. Daystar University)

Framing Climate Colonialism within the Net Zero Narrative: Modeling Diverse and Underrepresented Voices in Climate Journalism

» [Ms. Wenwen Guo](#) (Netherlands)¹, [Mr. Yongliang Liu](#) (China)² (1. University of Amsterdam, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Environmental-social Justice Against the Odds of Global Green Supply Chains: The Case of Taiwan's High-tech. Policy and Its Social Impacts

» [Prof. Shih-che Tang](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. National Chung Cheng University)

08:30

Panel : ESR-9

ESR - Visual and/or Creative Communication for Environment and Climate Change Challenges

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7

Organised by: Pieter Maesele (Panel Chair) (Belgium)

Continued from Tuesday, 15 July

Immersive Advocacy Exploring the Role of Virtual Reality in Environmental Awareness and Engagement

» [Dr. Bhavana S](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Vikash Chauhan](#) (India)² (1. Christ University, 2. Christ University, India)

Supa Team 4 as a Conduit for Children’s Climate Literacy: An Analysis of the Seminal African Animation Series to Stream on Netflix

» [Dr. Twange Kasoma](#) (United States)¹ (1. Department of Communication, Appalachian State University)

Climate Change Communication through Online Short Videos: Pathways of Influence in Emotional Appeals

» [Dr. Jie Xu](#) (United States)¹ (1. Villanova University)

Advocating Eco-Conscious Communities through Visual Narratives: An Analysis of A Plastic Ocean and Plastic Island

» [Ms. Madhumita Das](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Tamil Selvi](#) (Oman)², [Dr. Sayan Dey](#) (Oman)² (1. Institute of Leadership, Entrepreneurship and Development (iLEAD), 2. Bayan College)

Visual Framing of Climate Denialism: A Cross-Platform Analysis of Reddit, Twitter, and 4chan

» [Dr. Jing Zeng](#) (Switzerland)¹, [Dr. Kilian Bühling](#) (Germany)², [Prof. Annett Heft](#) (Germany)³ (1. University of Zurich, 2. FU Berlin, 3. University of Tübingen)

08:30

Panel : PCR-3

PCR - Media, Participation and Social Change

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: Aniruddha Jena (Discussant, Panel Chair) (India)

Understanding the Use of Facebook in Humanitarian Contexts: communicating with young people in refugee camps

» [Dr. Valentina Baú](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Western Sydney University)

Climate and environmental justice in Sub-Saharan Africa: New perspectives using the socio-cultural model for communicating development via community radio.

» [Dr. EMMANUEL ESSEL](#) (South Africa)¹ (1. University of KwaZulu-Natal)

Indigenous/Local knowledges and Community Radio in India: Some Learnings from the Field

» [Dr. Pradip Thomas](#) (Australia)¹, [Prof. Vinod Pavarala](#) (India)², [Prof. Kanchan Malik](#) (India)³, [Prof. Vasuki Belavadi](#) (India)², [Dr. Elske van de Fliert](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Queensland, 2. University of Hyderabad, 3. Department of Communication, Univeristy of Hyderabad)

A Decade of Empowered Voices: Charting Digital Participatory Politics in Africa (2014–2024)

» [Dr. Chiemezie Nwosu](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Technology Sydney)

08:30

Panel : INC-4

INC - Climate Justice and Media Representation

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: Dr. Sudeshna Roy (United States)

Climate Justice Narratives in the Global Media: A Discourse Package Analysis of Climate Reportage in Pacific Island Countries

» [Ms. Jingxuan Gao](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Climate Communication as Statecraft: A Content Analysis of Climate Change Communication from Caribbean Governments and Press

» [Dr. Josh Anderson](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Pamala Proverbs](#) (Barbados)², [Dr. Phil Arceneaux](#) (United States)³, [Mr. Ben Lee](#) (United States)¹, [Mr. Harshit Khatwani](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Spiro Kiouis](#) (United States)⁴ (1. University of Arizona, 2. PRMR Inc., 3. Miami University, 4. University of Florida)

Coverage of COP29 in the Indian Media: A Study Using Caney’s Approach to Climate Justice

» [Ms. Varsha M Joseph](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Aasita Bali](#) (India)¹ (1. CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru, India)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Disconnecting the climate? China's English-language news media framing of global floods in 2024

» [Mr. Hao Xie](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Warwick)

War, women and climate justice: Missing Narratives in Indian News Coverage of Gaza

» [Dr. Sweta Singh](#) (India)¹, [Mr. Prashant Bisht](#) (India)², [Mr. Haris Hasan](#) (India)² (1. University School of Mass Communication, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, New Delhi, 2. University School of Mass Communication, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University)

08:30

Panel : MPS-6

MPS - Manipulation through misinformation and covert racial stereotypes

Venue - WKWSCI L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: [Pengxiang Li](#) (Panel Chair)

Undermining the UN Sustainable Development Goal 13 through disinformation: Examining Attitudes of Social Media Users in Three Southeast Asian Countries

» [Dr. Rachel Khan](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Diliman)

Uncovering Covert Racial Stereotypes in Image-Generative AI: a Cross-Platform Multilingual Algorithm Auditing

» [Dr. Yalong Xiao](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Zilu Zou](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Futian Han](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Yaxiong Xu](#) (China)¹, [Dr. DR. JUNFEI LUO](#) (China)² (1. Central South University, 2. School of Humanities, Central South University)

Navigating Complexities: Gendered Political Misinformation, Cognitive Ability, and AI Imaginaries in the 2024 US Election

» [Ms. Yajing LU](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Ms. Mariyam Mohamed MANIK](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Dr. Yuner ZHU](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Prof. Bu Zhong](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

A Cross-Cultural Comparison of Gendered Media Framing of Female Environmental Scholars: A Thematic Analysis

» [Ms. Jingwen Tang](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of New South Wales)

08:30

Panel : POL-3

POL - Polarization and Media Effects

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

Organised by: [Dr. Yuan Zhong](#) (Panel Chair) (Singapore) and [Dr. Amrat Haq](#) (Discussant) (Pakistan)

An Uncivil Volume: Perceived Manipulation as a Mechanism for Effects of Reddit Comment Environments on Affective Polarization Among U.S. Partisans

» [Dr. Rachel Neo](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Benjamin Johnson](#) (United States)² (1. University of Hawaii, 2. University of Florida)

Persuasion or Polarization? A Cross-Platform Computational Study on Discursive Power in Hybrid Media Systems

» [Dr. Yuan Zhong](#) (China)¹ (1. Fudan University)

Does news use lead to higher affective polarization toward Russia and the US in China? The mediation role of political knowledge

» [Mr. Hua LI](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Ms. Yuexin LYU](#) (China)² (1. Hong Kong Baptist University, 2. School of Communication, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong)

Populist Politics and Polarization: Exploring the Moderating Effects of Social Media Echo Chambers on Political Decision Making amongst Young Adults in Pakistan

» [Dr. Amrat Haq](#) (Pakistan)¹ (1. International Islamic University, Islamabad)

08:30

Panel : MPS-7

MPS - Digital feminism, female body images and motherhood

Venue - WKWSCI L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: [Prof. Susanne Eichner](#) (Panel Chair) (Germany)

Continued from Tuesday, 15 July

Crafting Digital Feminist Spaces: The Discussion of Anti-Sexual Harassment Discourse Production on Xiaohongshu

» Ms. Jiaxin Li (China)¹ (1. School of International Journalism and Communication, Beijing Foreign Studies University)

Mothers in Social Media: Practices, Expectations and Limitations of Public Self-Presentation

» Mr. Matthias Hufgard (Germany)¹, Prof. Claudia Wegener (Germany)¹ (1. Filmuniversität Babelsberg)

Mediated Environments Imposing on Young Lebanese Women's Self-Esteem: Pressures for Micro-Fame and Ideal Body Images

» Ms. Christina Issa (Lebanon)¹, Ms. Youmna Yazbeck (Lebanon)¹, Dr. Jessica El-Khoury (Lebanon)¹, Dr. Rita Sayyah (Lebanon)¹ (1. Notre Dame University - Louaize)

"Childbirth Reviewing": Reproductive Landscapes and the Reshaping of Gender Relations under Embodied Narrative

» Ms. Zhou Xinrong (China)¹, Ms. Xinran Zhang (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Differentiation and complementarity in two public opinion fields: a study on the threat and efficacy of fertility agenda

» Ms. XU yandi (China)¹, Ms. Yumeng Zhou (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism & Communication, Tsinghua University)

The Care-Control Paradox in Motherhood: Algorithmic Mediation and the Reconstruction of Ecological Intelligence in China

» Mr. Haolang Li (Germany)¹, Ms. Xinlin Chen (China)² (1. University of Tübingen, 2. Hunan University)

08:30

Panel : PSM-1

PSM - AI, Digital Ecosystems, and Public Service Media

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Dr. Anis Rahman (Panel Chair) (United States)

Public Service Algorithm (PSA): transparent, explainable, and scalable content curation for news content based on editorial values

» Mr. Ahmad Mel (Belgium)¹, Mr. Sébastien Noir (Switzerland)² (1. AISBL EBU-UER (European Broadcasting Union), AIDA IdLab - Ghent University, 2. European Broadcasting Union)

Beyond the Hype? How Artificial Intelligence Tools are Truly Reshaping Internal Workflows in European Public Service Media

» Dr. Martín Vaz Álvarez (Spain)¹, Dr. César Feiras Ceide (Spain)¹, Dr. Miguel Túniz López (Spain)¹ (1. University of Santiago de Compostela)

The Sustainability of Public Service Media and Journalism in Indonesian Digital Media Ecosystem

» Prof. Masduki Masduki (Indonesia)¹ (1. Department of Communication, Universitas Islam Indonesia)

08:30

Panel : POE-3

POE - The Gig Grid

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7

Organised by: Ms. Yiran Cheng (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

The Digital Laborer's Survival in Online Writing: A Case Study of Contextual Evolution in Literature Forums

» Ms. Yiran Cheng (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Cambridge university)

"Differential Centrifugation": Platform Capitalism and the Alienation of Self-Employed Truck Drivers in China's Logistics Industry

» Mr. Jingwei Chen (China)¹, Prof. Zhian Zhang (China)² (1. 657786599@qq.com, 2. zhianzhang@fudan.edu.cn)

A workers' inquiry into the Philippine virtual assistant industry

» Ms. Diana Limbaga (Canada)¹ (1. Simon Fraser University)

Weighing in on Smyth's Labor Ideas: a Digital Rethinking of Advertising Labor

» Dr. Li Li (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

08:30

Panel : VIC-4

VIC - Brazilian Jazz, Day of the Dead, Intermediality, Memory, Visualidad and Environmental Films

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 8

Organised by: Dr. Denize Araujo (Panel Chair) (Brazil)

The trajectory of jazz in Brazil from the 50s to the 90s

» [Mrs. Gisele Filippetto](#) (Brazil)¹ (1. UTP- Universidade Tuiuti do Paraná, Brazil)

Day of the Dead Skull Face Painting as Visual Culture: Hollywood, Halloween, and Social Media

» [Dr. Regina Marchi](#) (United States)¹ (1. Rutgers University)

Chinese with Cameras: Amateur Film and Cultural Memory in Early Modern China

» [Ms. Wei-Ting Hsiao](#) (Macao)¹ (1. Faculty of Humanities and Arts, Macau University of Science and Technology)

Championing the fight against Climate Change: A Thematic Dissection of Selected Indian films on Environmental issues

» [Mr. Tanmay Samanta](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Nitesh Tripathi](#) (India)¹ (1. St. Xavier's University, Kolkata.)

Reflexiones visuales ante el colonialismo verde: Caso Llano en llamas (Sur de Jalisco, México) 2015-2024

» [Dr. Marcela de Niz](#) (Mexico)¹ (1. Universidad de Guadalajara)

08:30

Panel : ESN-2

ESN - Environmental Narratives, Climate Action and Sustainability

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: Dr. Karl Patrick Mendoza (Panel Chair) (Philippines)

Digital Media for Climate Action: A Study on Wipro Earthian and its CSR Initiatives

» [Mr. Bala Krishna Kanukati](#) (India)¹ (1. University of Hyderabad)

Framing in Become a Farmer: Leveraging a Documentary Variety Show for Pro-Environmental Behaviors

» [Ms. Gelan Cen](#) (China)¹ (1. KU Leuven)

How Grassroots Activist Groups Build and Sustain Their Communities: Insights from an Environmental Justice and a Women's Activist Group

» [Dr. Shima Saniei](#) (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University)

The Double-Edged Sword of AI: Innovation, Energy, and the Battle for Sustainability

» [Ms. Yitong Wang](#) (China)¹ (1. Emerson College)

Indigenous and Local Perspectives in BL Narratives: Exploring Traditional Environmental Knowledge in Queer Storytelling

» [Ms. Raisa Rasheeka](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Trent University)

08:30

Panel : HIS-3

HIS - Gender and Race Representations

Venue - WKWSCI TR+7

Organised by: Nelson Costa Ribeiro (Panel Chair) (Portugal)

Ottomanism and gendered sovereignty in a changing Syria

» [Dr. Omar Al-Ghazzi](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. London School of Economics)

"Twenty Girls with Accounting Machines": Gender in Malaya's Data Colonial Modernity (1900s-1965)

» [Dr. Kai Khiun Liew](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Prof. Natalie Pang](#) (Singapore)² (1. Hong Kong Metropolitan University, 2. National University of Singapore)

Flâneuse in Changing Urban Landscape: Gender and Spatial Practices in Shanghai's Street Photographs from 1840 to 1949

» [Dr. Mengyu Luo](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Jian Xiao](#) (China)², [Ms. Yiting Wang](#) (China)¹ (1. University of Shanghai for Science and Technology, 2. Zhejiang University)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Media Witnessing from the Perspective of Black Audiences

» [Ms. Nandi Pointer](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Colorado Boulder)

08:30

Panel : MCS-4

MCS - Global challenges in sport: sportswashing, climate crisis and sports diplomacy

Venue - *WKWSC I TR+8*

Organised by: Dr. Xavier Ramon (Panel Chair) (Spain) and Dr. Peter English (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Combating climate breakdown: Athlete activism, documentary and the environmental politics of Australia's David Pocock

» Dr. Simon Troon (Australia)¹, [Prof. Brett Hutchins](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Monash University)

Sportswashing as a Media-Created Concept: A Longitudinal News Framing Analysis

» [Mr. Luke Bird](#) (New Zealand)¹ (1. University of Auckland)

Sustain-Ability: Examining autocratic investment in women's sports through the rhetorical framing of environmental justice

» [Dr. Kayla Rhidenour](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Mary Anne Taylor](#) (United States)² (1. Baylor University, 2. Emerson College)

A Relational Approach: Branding Australia through the Australian Open

» [Dr. Xiufang \(Leah\) Li](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Juan Feng](#) (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University)

Meritocracy and Its Discontents : Understanding Trolling in the case of League of Legends

» [Ms. Yeonwoo Lee](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Yonsei Electronic Game and Esports Research Center, Yonsei University)

08:30

Panel : AUD-4

AUD - Real or unreal: Artificial intelligence and audiences

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+35*

Organised by: Dr. Asta Zelenkauskaite (Panel Chair) (United States)

Almost Real: How Verisimilitude Influences AI Ad Recognition and Attitudes

» [Dr. Yuhmiin Chang](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. National Chengchi University)

Stupid AI Around? Exploring Human Roles in Human-AI (Mis)alignment Through User Perceptions

» [Mr. Cong Lin](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Longxuan Zhao](#) (China)² (1. Tsinghua University, 2. Tongji University)

Audience Perceptions of Deepfake Narratives: Nostalgia, Transportation, Identification, and Credibility

» [Dr. Maite Soto-Sanfiel](#) (Singapore)¹, Dr. Syed Ali Hussain (United Arab Emirates)² (1. National University of Singapore, 2. University of Sharjah)

Disruptive consolidation? Reflections on human-machine communication as media audience engagement paradigm

» [Dr. ANDREAS SCHELLEWALD](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Goldsmiths, University of London)

08:30

Panel : AUD-5

AUD - Global audience identities

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+36*

Organised by: Dr. nissim katz (Panel Chair) (Israel)

Local Practices, Global Platforms: Understanding Privacy Management and Self-Disclosure Among Facebook Users in Bangladesh

» [Ms. Nusrat Jahan](#) (China)¹, Ms. kittiporn Saetae (China)² (1. Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China, 2. Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China)

Reception Analysis of Indigenous Media in Taiwan: Exploring Audience Agency in Indigenous Television and Self-Media

» [Dr. Guo-Ting Lin](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. National Taiwan University of Arts)

Continued from Tuesday, 15 July

A Person, A Worker, and An Officer: Understanding the Public's Sense-making of Political Media Persona

» Mr. Zuguang XIONG (Hong Kong)¹, Mr. Tianlun ZHOU (Hong Kong)¹, Ms. Fangyuan Liu (Hong Kong)² (1. Hong Kong Baptist University, 2. Hong Kong Baptist Univeristy)

The Future of Audience Studies: A Study on Turkish Dizi as a New Emerging Genre

» Dr. Pinar Aslan (Türkiye)¹ (1. Üsküdar University)

"I'm in Tension Between Identities": The Impact of International Arabic News Networks Exposure on Israeli Arabs' National Identity During "Iron Swords" war

» Dr. nissim katz (Israel)¹ (1. kinneret academic college)

08:30

Panel : REC-4

REC - Nature, The Environment and the Media-Religion matrix

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+37*

Organised by: Dr. Chiung Hwang Chen (Panel Chair) (United States)

A Study on Media Coverage of Religious Celebrations and Their Connection to Environmental Stewardship- Rituals, Nature, and Environmental Justice

» Ms. AMRITA MUKHERJEE (India)¹, Prof. Ganesh Sethi (India)¹ (1. Dept. of Journalism and Mass Communication, Berhampur University)

Nature, Religion and Spirituality: An Integrated Approach to Life and Pro-Environmental Behavior

» Dr. HAPPY JEJJI (India)¹ (1. Punjabi University,Patiala)

Sikhism, Eco Theology, and Climate Action: A Case Study of Eco Sikh's Media Advocacy Campaign

» Ms. Kashish Singh (India)¹ (1. AJK MCRC,Jamia Millia Islamia,New Delhi,India)

Sacred herbs: environmental awareness and muthi on a South African healer's Tik Tok account

» Prof. Priscilla Boshoff (South Africa)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Media Studies Rhodes University)

08:30

Panel : MAR-1

MAR - Podcasting: media and mediations

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+25*

Organised by: Prof. Mia Lindgren (Panel Chair) (Australia)

History emerges in conversation: The interactional politics of the Empire podcast

» Prof. Usha Raman (India)¹ (1. University of Hyderabad)

Ear Buddies: Aural Parasocial Relationships between Listeners and Podcast Hosts from Apple Podcast (2005-2023)

» Dr. Hu Peichen (China)¹ (1. Fudan University)

Analyzing Podcast Community Construction and User Stickiness from the Perspective of Interaction Ritual Chains: A Case Study of the Ximalaya Platform

» Dr. Han Lu (China)¹, Dr. Yuxue Zhou (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. communication university of china)

Mapping the podcasting pipeline: digital infrastructures for audio industries in Spain.

» Dr. Nacho Gallego (Spain)¹ (1. Universidad Carlos III de Madrid)

Beyond Content: Theorizing Hybrid Auditory Spaces and Affective Dynamics in Podcast Media

» Mr. Xianglong Wen (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Nanjing University)

08:30

Panel : ORG-2

ORG - Environmental and Climate Communication

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+26*

Organised by: Prof. Gisela Goncalves (Panel Chair) (Portugal)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

The Halo Effects of Greenwashing in Environmental Airline Advertising: A Case Study of Voluntary Carbon Offsetting

» Mr. Zhiyuan Shao (China)¹ (1. Jilin University)

Organizational communication and Community Perception of Environmental Justice: A Look at Seplat Energy Producing Nigeria Unlimited and the Residents of Ibeno in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

» Dr. Aniebo Samson (Nigeria)¹, Dr. Iniobong Nda (Nigeria)¹, Mr. Borono Bassey (Nigeria)¹ (1. University of Uyo)

Rupturing Mutual Benefits in Public Relations: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Corporate Messaging by Global Fossil Fuel Industry on Climate Action from 2015 – 2024

» Mr. HENRY UGWU (United States)¹, Dr. Jolene Fisher (United States)¹ (1. University of Colorado Boulder)

“Not your grandpa’s zoo”: Understanding Organizational Reputations, Decision-Making, and a Path Forward

» Mr. Hunter Reeves (United States)¹ (1. University of Colorado Boulder)

Talking Green: Organisational Communication, Stakeholder Trust, and Sustainability Disclosures in Prospectuses

» Prof. Shivani Sharma (India)¹ (1. Communication Area, Indian Institute of Management Indore)

08:30

Panel : DIM-2

DIM - Diasporic Communities and Belonging

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+28

Organised by: Dr. Jessica Retis (Panel Chair) (United States)

Sense of Place in Manhattan Chinatown under Urbanization and Multiculturalism: Voices from Tourists and Residents

» Dr. Miao Chu (China)¹, Prof. Connie Yuan (United States)² (1. Xi'an Jiaotong University, 2. Cornell University)

Drawing on Critical Phenomenology of Interaction for Advancing Engaged Research on Translocality

» Dr. Samira Ibnelkaid (Finland)¹ (1. University of Oulu)

Anchored Relationality

» Dr. Angela Labrador (Philippines)¹ (1. De La Salle University)

Achieving Optimal distinctiveness through media portfolio: Overcoming liability of foreignness transnational entrepreneurship

» Mrs. Yuet Chak Yuki Yuen (China)¹, Mr. Wenhan Shen (China)¹, Prof. Daomi Lin (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University, 2. Sun Yat-sen University)

08:30

Panel : SPS-5

SPS - Partner Session / ALAIC

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+27

Organised by: Dr. Andrea Medrado (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom), Dr. Fernando Oliveira Paulino (Discussant) (Brazil), Prof. Daniela Inés Monje (Discussant) (Argentina), and Prof. JULIANO DOMINGUES (Discussant) (Brazil)

Global Dialogues and Latin American perspectives in the Communication studies

10:30

Panel : POP-7

POP - K-Pop travels across the world

Venue - The Hive LHS-LT

Organised by: Dr. Chunmeizi Su (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Adapt K-pop Performances for American TV Culture: A Case Study of BTS on Late-night Talk Shows

» Ms. Yue Liang (United States)¹ (1. University of Massachusetts Amherst)

Global TV Format and Localization in the Idol Industry: "Produce 101 Japan The Girls" and Japanese version K-Pop

» Dr. Sunyoung Kwak (Japan)¹, Ms. Aoi Ishiyama (Japan)¹ (1. Shizuoka University)

Continued from Tuesday, 15 July

Localize the Use of K-pop Lightsticks and Alternatives: A Transnational Comparative Study of Fans in the East and West

» [Ms. Tianyi Yang](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Yue Liang](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Massachusetts Amherst)

Gamified Intimacy: Procedural Rhetoric and Idol Subscription Practices of Chinese K-pop Fans

» [Dr. Qi Zheng](#) (China)¹ (1. Shantou University)

“Make them sing in my language”: The affective prosumption of AI-cover songs in transcultural K-pop fandom in China

» [Ms. Lulu YUAN](#) (China)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

The Negotiation of Identity and Globalization in Southeast Asian Idol Groups: A Study of SB19 and MONSTAR’s Music Videos

» [Ms. Qiuli Tong](#) (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University)

10:30

Panel : MPS-8

MPS - News and social media framing

Venue - WKWSC L2 Executive Seminar Room

Organised by: Dr. Ammina Kothari (Panel Chair) (United States)

Competition Within, Following Between: A Time-Series Analysis of Inter-media Agenda-Setting Dynamics Between Chinese and American Media

» [Dr. Jie Feng](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Yifeng Chen](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Jiajun Tang](#) (China)² (1. School of Humanities, Central South University, 2. School of Information Management, Nanjing University)

How News Constructs Facts: A Comparative Study of Chinese and Korean News Reporting Frames on the Fukushima Nuclear Wastewater Discharge in Japan—Focusing on Content Analysis

» [Mr. Pengfei Xu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Qianer Yan](#) (China)² (1. PhD Candidate in Communication, Macau University of Science and Technology, 2. Shanwei Institute of Technology)

Framing Cyber Violence on Chinese Social Media: A Topic Modeling Analysis of Weibo posts

» [Mr. Shuo Li](#) (United States)¹, [Mr. Yuhang Liu](#) (China)² (1. University of North Carolina at Charlotte, 2. Zhejiang Gongshang University)

National Image Representation and News: Sentiment, Semantic Network Analysis of BBC News Title on Afghanistan

» [Mr. Haroon Hakimi](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University.)

A new generation of news: Finding media pluralism in AI-generated daily news

» [Dr. Timothy Koskie](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Sydney)

Algorithmic Gatekeeping in News Recommendation Systems: A Patent-Based Analysis of Traditional and Algorithmic News Values

» [Prof. Junbin Su](#) (China)¹, [Ms. yuan zhuang](#) (China)² (1. Xiamen University, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Xiamen University)

10:30

Panel : AUD-9

AUD - Fandom and identity

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+47

Organised by: Dr. nissim katz (Panel Chair) (Israel)

From Fandom to Identity: How Adolescents and Social Media Influencers Shape Each Other’s Identity

» [Ms. Jessica Kühn](#) (Germany)¹, [Dr. Claudia Riesmeyer](#) (Germany)² (1. Department of Media and Communication, LMU Munich, 2. LMU Munich)

The Popularity of the Miniature, Serialised Online Short Drama: An Exploration of the Factors Influencing Audiences’ Continuous Viewing Intention and Electronic Word-Of-Mouth

» [Ms. Maria Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Li ZHI](#) (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University- Hong Kong Baptist university united international college)

Continued from Tuesday, 15 July

Insecure Attachment and Online Prosocial Behavior: The Chain Mediating Role of Para-social Intimacy and Perceived Online Social Support in a Fandom Context

» Ms. Fangyi Qu (Macao)¹, Ms. Qiuyu Jin (Macao)¹, Ms. Xun Xu (Macao)¹, Ms. Ziyang Han (Macao)¹, Ms. Xinyan Liu (Macao)¹ (1. Macau University of Science and Technology)

Exploring China's Virtual Idol Fandom Dynamics: A Case Study of A-SOUL From Life-cycle Perspective

» Ms. Zitian Fang (China)¹ (1. Tsinghua University)

Typology of Social Media Users

» Ms. Adeline Tay (Singapore)¹, Dr. Hee Jhee Jioo (Singapore)¹, Ms. Nur Syarafanah Affandi (Singapore)¹, Ms. Filzah Faiqah Amran (Singapore)¹, Ms. Dawn Heng Si (Singapore)¹, Mr. Aidil Hakim Nasar (Singapore)¹ (1. Singapore Institute of Technology)

10:30

Panel : JRE-3

JRE - Journalism in the digital age III

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+49*

Organised by: Prof. Xudong Liu (Panel Chair) (Macao) and Dr. Tai Neilson (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Does immersive journalism erode news objectivity? Effects of immersion on audience emotional engagement and objectivity perception

» Prof. Qi Zhou (China)¹, Prof. Zongya Li (China)¹ (1. Huazhong university of science and technology)

Projection of AI Tools Adoption: The Influence of Perceived AI News Quality, Future utility and Presumed Cohort Appreciation on Intention to Adopt AI Tools

» Ms. Yanning Chen (Macao)¹, Ms. Mingming Fan (Macao)¹, Prof. Xudong Liu (Macao)¹ (1. Faculty of Humanities and Arts, Macau University of Science and Technology)

AI Adoption in Indonesian Newsrooms: Perceptions, Uses, and Challenges

» Dr. Indra Prawira (Indonesia)¹, Dr. Tai Neilson (Australia)² (1. Bina Nusantara University, 2. Macquarie University)

Data -Related Activities as Linking Technologies: Mapping the Expertise Network of News Innovation Labs in China

» Dr. Kang Yan (China)¹, Dr. Tianbo Xu (China)² (1. Anqing Normal University, 2. Anhui University)

Migration of Communication - Exploration of the Transition from Offline to Online Communication Modes

» Ms. Anya Liu (China)¹, Mr. Zhifeng Wang (China)¹, Ms. Xiaopei Zhao (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. Beijing Foreign Studies University)

Exploring the Potential of AI-Driven Environmental Reporting in Oman's Media Landscape

» Dr. Moosa Al Lawati (Oman)¹, Ms. Tuqa Al Hadhrami (Oman)² (1. Sultan Qaboos University, 2. Shaddah Agency)

10:30

Panel : JRE-9

JRE - Journalism practice and research across diverse countries I

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+52*

Organised by: Prof. Ylva Rodny-Gumede (Panel Chair) (South Africa) and Prof. John Downey (Discussant) (United Kingdom)

The contested terrain: Exploring media capture and autonomy in the contemporary Indian journalistic field

» Dr. Nimmagadda Bhargav (India)¹, Prof. John Downey (United Kingdom)², Prof. Vinod Pavarala (India)³ (1. Indian Institute of Management, Indore, 2. Loughborough University, 3. University of Hyderabad)

Hyper visibility and invisibility: Examining the work of racialized Canadian journalists on democracy and racism

» Dr. Ahmed Al-Rawi (Canada)¹, Ms. Sadia Nasrin (Canada)¹, Mr. Devan Prithipaul (Canada)² (1. Simon Fraser University, 2. Alberta University)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Covering Planetary Health: A content analysis of German news media coverage on climate change, environment and human health.

» [Dr. Julia Serong](#) (Germany)¹, Mrs. Anna Gaul (Germany)¹ (1. LMU Munich)

Communication path of global warming news reporting from the framework perspective — Take the report of China Meteorological News (2020-2024) as an example

» [Ms. 家悦原](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China (CUC))

Journalisms Catch 22? Assessing and achieving intertwined processes of sustainability in journalism and sustainability journalism in and from an African perspective

» [Prof. Ylva Rodny-Gumede](#) (South Africa)¹ (1. University of Johannesburg)

Sustainable democracy through diversity? Geographical diversity in Swiss journalistic TV and radio content in order to prevent news deserts

» Ms. Johanna Burger (Switzerland)¹, [Mr. Urban Kalbermatter](#) (Switzerland)¹, Dr. Caroline Dalmus (Switzerland)¹ (1. University of Applied Sciences of the Grisons)

10:30

Panel : CPT-11

CPT - The political economy of digital infrastructure and AI development

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+53*

Organised by: Prof. Francesca Musiani (Panel Chair) (France)

A Comparison of Four Models for Next Generation Broadband Infrastructure Development: The Cases of Australia, Canada, New Zealand and Singapore

» [Prof. Catherine Middleton](#) (Canada)¹, Mr. Kevin Hudes (Canada)¹ (1. Toronto Metropolitan University)

When you wish upon a Star(link): The policies, politics, politics, and practices of low-Earth orbital satellite broadband

» [Dr. Christopher Ali](#) (United States)¹ (1. Penn State University)

The Network Dialectic: The Affordable Connectivity Program and the Contradictions of Philadelphia's Networked Digital Equity Strategy

» [Dr. Pawel Popiel](#) (United States)¹, Dr. David Berman (United States)² (1. Washington State University, 2. Seton Hall University)

Political Economy Critique of the Regionalization in Global Medium Governance: A Case Study of Satellite Internet Governance

» [Prof. Jinhe Liu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Mingyu Shao](#) (China)² (1. Assistant Professor at School of Journalism & Communication, Peking University, 2. School of Journalism & Communication, Peking University, No. 165, Yiheyuan Road, Haidian District, Beijing, 100871, China)

Towards a Decolonial AI in/for Africa: Critical Analysis on Data Capitalism, Epistemic Injustice, and Techno-Ethics

» [Dr. Chikezie Uzuegbunam](#) (South Africa)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Media Studies Rhodes University)

10:30

Panel : CAM-6

CAM - Negotiating Gender Identities through Community Media Practices

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+56*

Organised by: Dr. Ana Cristina Suzina (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Power Asymmetries in the 'Counterpublic': Marginalised women's voices in the environmental justice movement

» [Ms. Kayonaaz Kalyanwala](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of East Anglia)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

“Mom won’t let me use tampons and cups”: Mother-Daughter Intergenerational Interaction about Menstrual Stigma and Hymen Myth

» [Mr. Xiaodong Yan](#) (United States)¹, Ms. Shulun Wang (United States)², Ms. Yujie Zhong (United States)³ (1. University of Colorado Boulder, 2. Penn State University, 3. Temple University)

Style Your Day: Short Video Production, Digital Aesthetics, and Social Interaction among Elderly Chinese Women

» [Mr. Honghao Li](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Information Communication, Huazhong University of Science and Technology)

Using Communication for Positive and Measurable Change on Migration and Gender: Migration Through the Eyes of Women Project

» [Dr. Altug Akin](#) (Türkiye)¹, Dr. Serkan Savk (Kuwait)² (1. Izmir University of Economics, 2. Gulf University for Science and Technology)

Consequences of the digital divide to women slum dwellers during the pandemic

» [Dr. Violet Valdez](#) (Philippines)¹, Ms. Samantha Javier (Philippines)¹ (1. Ateneo de Manila University)

10:30

Panel : GEN-11

GEN - Gender Justice, AI and Digital Governance. Building capacity to promote gender equality in media and technology through the UNESCO UniTwin Network on Gender, Media and ICTs

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR4

Organised by: Prof. Aimee Vega Montiel (Convenor) (Mexico), Prof. Claudia Padovani (Panel Chair) (Italy), and Prof. Lisa French (Discussant) (Australia)

Gendering European digital future? AI regulation and the challenge of gender mainstreaming thirty after the Beijing World Conference on Women

» [Prof. Claudia Padovani](#) (Italy)¹, Dr. Alice Lima Baroni (Italy)² (1. University of Padova, 2. University fo Padova)

Advancing Gender Equality and Mitigating Gender Bias: AI and The Bechdel Test

» [Prof. Lisa French](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Mark Poole](#) (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University)

Proposals for Generative AI Free from Gender Discrimination: Reflections from an Interdisciplinary Collaboration

» [Dr. Maria Soledad Vargas](#) (Chile)¹, [Ms. Camila Buzzo](#) (Chile)¹, Dr. Yanet Martínez (Costa Rica)² (1. Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso, 2. Universidad de Costa Rica)

Hacia una IA Generativa Equitativa: Análisis de Sesgos de Género en la Producción de Contenidos

» [Dr. Maria Soledad Vargas](#) (Chile)¹, [Ms. Camila Buzzo](#) (Chile)¹, Dr. Yanet Martínez (Costa Rica)² (1. Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso, 2. Universidad de Costa Rica)

10:30

Panel : GEN-12

GEN - Gaming, cyber intimacy, and spaces of belonging and threat

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5

Organised by: Prof. PAN Yanan (Panel Chair) (China), Mr. Omar Kouiyache (Discussant) (Morocco), and Mrs. Faiza Rafique (Panel Chair) (United Arab Emirates)

“Utopia” or “Social Hub”? —Community Belonging and Identity Construction at the China Otome Game Convention

» [Ms. Jiawen Hu](#) (China)¹ (1. China Agricultural University)

Playing as a Female Farmer: Exploring Gender, Ecology, and Identity in Game-playing

» Ms. Wang Wendi (China)¹, [Ms. Xiaoying Wang](#) (China)², Ms. kexin Feng (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China, 2. Communication University of China (CUC))

The Dilemma of The Otherness in the Media Representation of Chinese Female Athletes in the Case of Gong Lijiao

» [Prof. PAN Yanan](#) (China)¹ (1. Zhengzhou university)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Virtual Body, Real Love: How Female Players' Bodily Involvement Constructs Human-Computer Intimacy in Otome Games

» [Ms. Yanling He](#) (China)¹, Prof. Lei Wang (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Nanjing University, 2. Nanjing University)

Navigating queer visibility in Chinese game livestreams: performance of absurd femininity

» [Ms. Xinyu Li](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

The Impact of Gender Stereotype Threat on Female Game Players

» [Ms. Bella Lin](#) (China)¹ (1. Tsinghua University)

10:30

Panel : ESR-8

ESR - Extreme Weather and Events: Crisis and Disaster Communication

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6

Organised by: Dr. Claire Konkes (Panel Chair) (Australia)

#WalangPasok: Class suspension posts as a platform for risk communication during typhoons in the Philippines

» [Mr. NHERU VERAFLOR](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Diliman)

Framing Disasters: How Philippine Presidents address Disasters and Disaster Risk Management in State of the Nation Addresses (SONAs), 1998-2024

» [Ms. Jaed Bengzon](#) (Philippines)¹, [Ms. Johanna Feliz Matanguihan](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Diliman)

Rethinking Fijian environmental disaster communication responses

» [Mr. Ashley Gopal](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Deakin University)

Hot Topics in Extreme Heat: A Content Analysis of Heat-Related Messages in California

» [Ms. Louise Xie](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Haiwei \(Valerie\) Huang](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Kennedy Phillips](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Elaine Jeon](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Vivian Zhai](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Lauren Arnold](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Jill Johnston](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Bhavna Shamasunder](#) (United States)², [Dr. Robin Stevens](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Southern California, 2. Occidental College)

10:30

Panel : ESR-11

ESR - Climate Change: Communication, Media and Journalism

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7

Organised by: Dr. Joana Diaz Pont (Panel Chair) (Spain)

Locating emotions: Multimodal analysis of climate journalistic texts in Philippine newspapers

» [Mr. Daniel Silvallana](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Deakin University)

Media responses to climate change-induced migration in India: Analyzing news coverage of 'ghost villages' in the Himalayan state of Uttarakhand

» [Dr. Ram Awtar Yadav](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Amita Amita](#) (India)², [Dr. Santosh Baghel](#) (India)³ (1. University of Allahabad, 2. Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University, 3. Pt. Sundarlal Sharma (Open) University, Bilaspur)

The digital shift of global climate narrative: emotional driving logic and social mobilization mechanism under media linkage

» Dr. Wenjie Li (China)¹, [Mr. Zihao Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. Guangzhou Xinhua University)

Weather presenters turning forecasts into climate conversations

» [Ms. Amelia Pearson](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Lucy Richardson](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Matt Carew](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Monash University)

Some Good Climate News: Positive Climate Messaging and Multidimensional Engagement on TikTok

» [Dr. ION BENEDIK BUNQUIN](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Diliman)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Comparing the coverage of climate change across countries: reporting the eco- imperialist mode of living

» Ms. Yu-Chen Chang (China)¹, Dr. Weili Wang (China)² (1. School of Journalism and New Media, Xi'an Jiaotong University, 2. School of Journalism and New Media, Xi'an Jiaotong University)

10:30

Panel : GEN-30

GEN - Politics, activism, and social movements for justice

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: Dr. Tehreem Azeem (Panel Chair) (Pakistan) and Dr. Mitra Shamsi (Discussant) (Germany)

Unravelling the Layers of Collectivisation: Technology, Resistance and the Politics of Inclusion/Exclusion in a Women's Movement

» Ms. Anila Backer A P (India)¹ (1. PhD Scholar)

Unchaining the Silence: Voices of Rural Women and Resistance against Sexual Violence in China

» Ms. Hannie Zhang (China)¹ (1. The University of Sydney)

The Media Language Divide: A Comparative Analysis of Aurat March Coverage in Pakistani English and Urdu Newspapers from 2018 to 2022

» Dr. Tehreem Azeem (Pakistan)¹ (1. National University of Science and Technology (NUST))

Dokhtaran-e Vatan: Navigating the Nation through Digital Feminist Activism in Iran's 'Woman, Life, Freedom' Movement

» Dr. Mitra Shamsi (Germany)¹ (1. Center for Advanced Internet Studies)

Reconfiguring Patriarchal Paradigms: The Aurat March and Its Role in Reshaping Gender Norms and Feminist Activism in Pakistan

» Dr. Babar Hussain (Pakistan)¹, Dr. Shahbaz Aslam (Pakistan)² (1. University of the Punjab, 2. University of Gujrat)

Negotiating the Algorithm: Feminist Resilience and Resistance in Chinese Social Media

» Ms. Jiaying Zhang (China)¹, Ms. Yuheng Wang (China)² (1. Minzu university of China, 2. Beijing Normal University - Hong Kong Baptist United International College)

10:30

Panel : INC-5

INC - Cross-Cultural Communication in Digital Spaces

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: Mr. Jan Miessler (Panel Chair) (Czechia)

Reducing Cross-Cultural Misunderstandings on TikTok through Cognitive and Affective Empathy ——A Mixed-Methods Analysis of Environmental Justice Dialogues

» Mr. you shi (China)¹ (1. Nanjing Normal University)

"Cyber Refugees" Under the TikTok Ban: A Study on the Media Use and Cross-Cultural Adaptation of Transnational Users

» Prof. Xu HAN (China)¹, Ms. Siyu Luo (China)¹ (1. Hunan Women's University)

A Study on the Effectiveness of Cross-cultural Communication by Foreign Internet Celebrities: An Empirical Analysis Based on Audience Interaction Behavior on Bilibili

» Dr. heng du (Taiwan)¹ (1. National Chengchi University)

From Button-clicking to "Teasing": User's Human-AI Interaction Strategies in Rednote's Translation Feature

» Mr. Yuguo Luo (United Kingdom)¹, Mr. Yufan Yang (China)² (1. The London School of Economics and Political Science, 2. Communication University of China)

Strategies for Engaging the Youth in Global Multicultural Marketplaces via Contemporary Social Media Platforms.

» Dr. Mian Asim (United Arab Emirates)¹, Dr. Fokiya Akhtar (United Arab Emirates)¹, Dr. Azmat Rasul (United Arab Emirates)¹ (1. ZAYED UNIVERSITY)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

10:30

Panel : HEC-1

HEC - Rethinking Environmental Health Communication

Venue - WKWSC L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: Mr. Zirui Wang (Panel Chair) (Canada) and Dr. Monique Lewis (Discussant) (Australia)

Multidimensional Health and Multiple Voices: The Application of Traditional Chinese Medicine's Ecological Holistic Narrative in Global Environmental Justice Actions

» [Ms. Chen Yi](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Yixin Bai](#) (China)¹ (1. Peking University)

Environmental Health Literacy through an Intersectional Perspective: A Content Analysis of NIEHS-Funded Community Engagement Cores

» [Mrs. Mina Sayadi](#) (United States)¹, Dr. Tamar Ginossar (United States)² (1. PhD Student, 2. University of New Mexico)

Heat, disability, and climate crisis: Framing disability and extreme heat in Australian news

» [Dr. Monique Lewis](#) (Australia)¹, Prof. Katie Ellis (Australia)², Prof. Shannon Rutherford (Australia)¹, Ms. Hannah Adler (Australia)¹, Ms. Hannah Adler (Australia)¹ (1. Griffith University, 2. Curtin University)

Many Voices, One Health. Developing local actions to raise awareness on the interconnections between human, animal and environmental health

» [Dr. Miguel Vicente Marino](#) (Spain)¹, Dr. Ana Teresa Lopez Pastor (Spain)¹, Dr. Enrique Morales Corral (Spain)¹, Dr. Miguel Varela Rodríguez (Spain)¹, Ms. Silvia Perez Fernandez (Spain)¹, Ms. Marta Calleja Duque (Spain)¹ (1. University of Valladolid)

Does the Knowledge Gap matter more? A Study on Subjective and Objective Health Knowledge Gap in Pluralized Health Information Environment

» [Dr. Chen Xi](#) (China)¹, Dr. Qin Xuan (China)² (1. Zhejiang University, College of Media and International Culture, Hangzhou, China, 2. Communication University of Zhejiang)

"On Fertile Ground, Seeds Are More Likely to Germinate": How Health Effects Moderate the Relationship Between Climate Change Awareness and Action

» [Ms. Yong Lin](#) (China)¹, Mr. Rui Chen (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

10:30

Panel : POL-5

POL - Identity, Subjectivity and Communication Technologies

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

Organised by: Dr. Sweta Suman (Panel Chair) (India) and Ms. Chenying Tang (Discussant) (Hong Kong)

Gender as a Gift? The Political Image Construction of Tanzania's Current President Samia Suluhu Hassan

» [Mr. Kun Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Gendered Political Communication and Media Representation: A Study of Women's Wings in Indian Political Parties

» [Dr. Sweta Suman](#) (India)¹ (1. Lal Bahadur Shastri Institute of Management)

When Love Meets Ideology: How Couples Communicate Political Attitude Differences and Its Consequences for Relationship Well-being

» [Ms. Zihan WANG](#) (China)¹ (1. Renmin University of China)

Manufacturing Consent Through Ritualized Spectacle: Coercive Discourse, Digital Authoritarianism, and the Erasure of Agency in North Korea's Leader-Cult Music Videos

» [Ms. Chenying Tang](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. School of Communication, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong)

Communication of Population Policy in Vietnam: A critical discourse analysis of changes

» Ms. Trang-Nhung Pham (Viet Nam)¹, Ms. Ngoc-Khanh-Linh Pham (Viet Nam)¹, Mrs. Mai Nguyen-Hoang (Viet Nam)¹, [Mrs. Thu Le](#) (Viet Nam)¹, [Mrs. Nhan Ngo](#) (Viet Nam)¹, Dr. Hong Tien Vu (United States)² (1. Faculty of Public Relations and Communication, Van Lang University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, 2. University of Kansas)

Continued from Tuesday, 15 July

10:30

Panel : HEC-2

HEC - Behavioral Insights for Contemporary health challenges

Venue - WKWSC L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: Mr. Yuchen Zhou (Panel Chair) (Hong Kong) and Dr. Chen Luo (Discussant) (China)

Conceptualizing and Operationalizing Digital Addictive Behavior of the Elderly: A Systematic Review

» Mr. Qiupeng Wang (China)¹, Dr. Kai Kuang (China)¹ (1. Tsinghua University)

Communication Strategies for Promoting Patient Engagement in Telemedicine: A Systematic Review

» Ms. Yangna HU (Hong Kong)¹, Dr. Cindy Ngai (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Polytechnic University)

No More Messages! A Systematic Review of Predictors and Outcomes of Message Fatigue

» Ms. Yu QIU (Hong Kong)¹, Dr. CHANG Leanne (Hong Kong)¹, Ms. Liu Mengyao (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

A Contextual Comprehensive Framework (CCF): A Systematic Approach to Designing an Interactive Online Course for In-Service Communication Training for Health Researchers

» Ms. Vama Shah (India)¹, Mrs. Manisha Pathak Shelat (India)², Ms. Suchetana Sinha (India)³, Mr. Rajni Kant (India)⁴, Prof. Ruchi Tewari (India)², Mrs. Enna Dogra Gupta (India)⁴ (1. Research Assistant at CDMC-MICA, 2. Professor at MICA, 3. MICA, 4. Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR))

Low Effort, Low Effectiveness? Examining the Impact of Perceived Effort on Chatbot Evaluations in Health Communication

» Dr. Buduo Wang (United States)¹, Dr. Shan Xu (United States)¹ (1. Texas Tech University)

Heat, health and livelihoods in a coastal Ghanaian community: a qualitative study on lay perspectives

» Prof. Ama de-Graft Aikins (United Kingdom)¹, Dr. Samuel Amon (Ghana)², Ms. Maame Adwoa Sam (Ghana)², Mrs. Vida Asah-Ayeh (Ghana)², Mr. Kingsley Apusiga (Ghana)³, Dr. Thandi Kapwata (South Africa)⁴ (1. London School of Economics and Political Science, 2. University of Ghana, 3. Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, 4. SAMRC)

10:30

Panel : CJD-4

CJD - Communication, Social Justice and Democracy Dialogues: What is justice?

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Dr. Vaia Doudaki (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Czechia)

Compassionate communication for communicative justice

» Prof. Cees Hamelink (Netherlands)¹ (1. University of Amsterdam)

Ecological Futures: Posthumanism and Remediation

» Prof. Jeremy Swartz (United States)¹, Prof. Janet Wasko (United States)¹ (1. University of Oregon)

New materialisms and ecology of communication for social justice: alteration of value chains and distribution of social damage

» Prof. Daniela Inés Monje (Argentina)¹ (1. Universidad Nacional de Córdoba)

Strains on Deliberative Democracy and Communicative Justice: Some reflections on recent developments in South Asia

» Prof. Vinod Pavarala (India)¹ (1. University of Hyderabad)

The reconfiguration of justice under the Trump administration

» Prof. Barbie Zelizer (United States)¹ (1. University of Pennsylvania)

10:30

Panel : POE-4

POE - Capital Currents and Smart Money

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7

Organised by: Dr. Micky Lee (Panel Chair) (United States)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Ahistorical resource allocation: A political economic critique of how the media covered effective altruism in Sam Bankman-Fried's trial

» [Dr. Micky Lee](#) (United States)¹ (1. Suffolk University)

Super Apps as Escrow Platforms: An Ecosystem Analysis of Grab Indonesia

» [Prof. Adrian Athique](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Queensland)

Housing News in the Age of the Asset Economy: It's a Bourgeoisie Thing

» [Prof. Aeron Davis](#) (New Zealand)¹ (1. Victoria University of Wellington)

Digital Slavery: How Trans-border Telecommunication and Online Fraud Industry in Southeast Asia Reconstruct Global Coercive Exploitation?

» [Mr. Zhenhua Cai](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Zixiang Lu](#) (China)² (1. School of Journalism, Fudan University, 2. University of Chicago)

Cryptocurrency's Ecological Curse: Social Representations of Energy Waste and Financial Speculation

» [Dr. Andrew Prahj](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University)

10:30

Panel : VIC-5

VIC - Ethnography, Climate, Environment, Air-conditioning and Pyrofutures

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 8

Organised by: [Dr. Evelyn Runge](#) (Panel Chair) (Germany)

"We kind of know what it looks like, but we don't know what it feels like." Exploring Climate Visuals through Visual Auto-Ethnography

» [Dr. Evelyn Runge](#) (Germany)¹ (1. University of Cologne & The Institute of Advanced Study in the Humanities Essen)

The Never-ending Story of Climate Crisis: German Children's Media, Affect, and Adaptation in the early 1980s.

» [Dr. Mason Allred](#) (United States)¹ (1. Brigham Young University-Hawaii)

Hidden Treasure Walks: Immersive Storytelling as a Tool for Cultural and Environmental Engagement in Singapore

» [Prof. Ella Raidel](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

Is the Air-Conditioner a Screen?

» [Mr. Hui Wong](#) (Canada)¹ (1. McGill University)

Visualizing Pyrofutures

» [Dr. Alexa Dare](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Portland)

10:30

Panel : ESN-CAM-

ESN - CAM - Joint Session: Media Practices and Marginalities in Context

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: [Dr. Karl Patrick Mendoza](#) (Panel Chair) (Philippines) and [Dr. Amparo Cadavid](#) (Discussant) (Colombia)

Voices from the Field: An Intersectional Approach to Contemporary Documentary Filmmaking in India

» [Ms. Deenaz Raisinghani](#) (India)¹ (1. Savitribai Phule Pune University)

Subverting Hegemony in the Global South: Radio Dhimsa's Cultural and Knowledge Interventions

» [Dr. Aniruddha Jena](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Bridget Backhaus](#) (Australia)² (1. INDIAN INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT KASHIPUR, 2. Griffith University)

Pluralistic Moral Expressions in Online Communities' Environmental Protection Issues: Value Distribution, Group Divergence, and Public Engagement

» [Mr. hao liu](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Yuan Zhong](#) (China)² (1. College of Literature and Journalism, Sichuan University, 2. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Mediated Information Grounds: Navigating Everyday Precarity, Networked Privacy and (Dis)Trust among Rohingya Refugees

» [Dr. Abdul Aziz](#) (Malaysia)¹ (1. Monash University Malaysia)

Resisting Marginalities: Examining Digital Journalists practices outside the metropolitan

» [Mr. Piyush Kumar](#) (India)¹ (1. Indraprastha Institute of Information Technology Delhi (IIIT-Delhi))

Disconnecting through media: The Paradox of Beating Tech with Tech

» [Ms. Yukun You](#) (Norway)¹ (1. University of Oslo)

10:30

Panel : HIS-4

HIS - Propaganda, National Identities and Cultural Diplomacy

Venue - *WKWSCI TR+7*

Organised by: [Dr. Taner Dogan](#) (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Traditional Opera, Modern Propaganda: The Prohibition, Adaptation, and Exportation of Si Lang Tan Mu in Cold War Taiwan

» [Ms. Kexuan An](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Siyue Liu](#) (Australia)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. University of Wollongong)

From "Exhibited China" to "Exhibiting China": Cold War-era Chinese Cultural Exhibitions and Narratives

» [Ms. Feijun Guo](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Jingwen Gao](#) (China)¹, Mrs. Shengnan Liu (China)¹ (1. Fudan University)

Imagining the Telephone: Knowledge Production, National Identity, and Cultural Articulations in Late Qing China

» [Ms. Min Gao](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. London School of Economics and Political Science)

From Partnership to Discord: Media Relations Between the USSR and PRC (1950-1960)

» [Dr. ELEONORA GENEN](#) (Russian Federation)¹ (1. Fudan University)

Comparison Culture in Digital Space-Time and its impact on Knowledge Production

» [Dr. Taner Dogan](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Queen Margaret University)

10:30

Panel : MCS-2

MCS - (Re)examining the Paris 2024 Olympics

Venue - *WKWSCI TR+8*

Organised by: [Dr. Zesheng Yang](#) (Panel Chair) (Singapore)

Digital Media as a Public Sphere for Sports Issues: A Computational Analysis of the Opening Ceremony of Olympic Games Paris 2024 on Weibo

» [Ms. Yirui Jiang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Qinghong Jiang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Framing Gender and Eligibility: A Content Analysis of Social Media Representation of Imane Khelif's Misgendering Controversy

» [Ms. Leen Owaidat](#) (United Arab Emirates)¹, Ms. Habiba Elshennawy (United Arab Emirates)¹, Ms. Fatima Abdulrazzak (United Arab Emirates)¹, Ms. Nasib Tarabishy (United Arab Emirates)¹ (1. American University in Dubai)

What Are We Caring about When Discussing Olympic Athletes Who Miss Gold: A Case Study on the Issue Construction of Losing Gold on Weibo

» [Ms. Lingyu Chu](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Emotions Across Borders: A Study on the Emotional Mobilization Mechanisms of Youtube Official Videos during 2024 Paris Olympics from a transcultural communication Perspective

» [Ms. Shuyi QU](#) (China)¹ (1. China University of Geosciences)

From the Podium to the Spotlight: Media Framing, Image Construction and Ethical Dilemmas of Chinese Underage Athletes

» [Ms. Peiyi Zhao](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Xiangning Tian](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China (CUC))

"Laogongjie" As a Label for Female Athletes: Gendered Language Use on Douyin During 2024 Olympic Games

» [Ms. qi Yao yu](#) (China)¹ (1. King's College London)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

10:30

Panel : CRI-2

CRI - Governing through crisis

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+35*

Organised by: Mazlum Kemal Dagdelen (Panel Chair) (Czechia)

Constructing the Discursive Frontiers: A Discourse Theoretical Analysis of the Blue Homeland Documentary and Its YouTube Comments

» [Mr. Mazlum Kemal Dagdelen](#) (Czechia)¹ (1. Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism, Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University)

Delivering security out of scarcity: “Our Singapore Food Story” as engagement and empowerment

» [Dr. Elaine Xu](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Howard Lee](#) (Australia)², [Dr. Tania Lim](#) (Singapore)³, [Prof. Terence Lee](#) (China)⁴ (1. University of Newcastle, 2. Murdoch University, 3. Singapore University of Social Sciences, 4. University of Nottingham Ningbo China)

The Newsworthiness of Government Messages in Protracted Crises. A Longitudinal and Cross-National Analysis of News Values in State Press Releases

» [Prof. Martin Loeffelholz](#) (Germany)¹, [Dr. Yi Xu](#) (Germany)², [Prof. Audra Diers-Lawson](#) (Norway)³, [Prof. Bengt Johansson](#) (Sweden)⁴, [Prof. Deanna Sellnow](#) (United States)⁵, [Prof. Timothy Sellnow](#) (United States)⁵ (1. Ilmenau University of Technology, 2. University of Jena, 3. Kristiania University College, 4. University of Gothenburg, 5. Clemson University)

The influence of health information trust and family relationships on psychological distress during global health crises: A longitudinal study

» [Mr. Wei Jie Dominic Koek](#) (Singapore)¹, [Ms. Kalya M. Kee](#) (Singapore)¹, [Ms. Anita Sheldenkar](#) (Singapore)¹, [Mr. Alexius Matthias Soh](#) (Singapore)² (1. Nanyang Technological University, 2. National Centre for Infectious Diseases)

The Influence of Media Use Behavior on Public Trust in the Government’s Response to the Itaewon Tragedy: The Mediating Role of Social Cohesion

» [Mrs. Jieun Choi](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Prof. Yungwook Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. School of Communication and Media, Ewha Womans University)

Self-Correction or Correcting Others? Exploring the Role of Psychological Distance and Emotional Motivation in Health Misinformation Correction Intentions

» [Dr. xiqian zou](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

10:30

Panel : SPS-9

SPS - Special Session / Multimodal Academic Communication Task Force

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+36*

Organised by: [Dr. Sandra Ristovska](#) (Panel Chair) (United States), [Prof. Nico Carpentier](#) (Discussant) (Czechia), [Ms. Aysu Arsoy](#) (Discussant) (Türkiye), [Jeremy Shtern](#) (Discussant) (Canada), and [Dr. Pedro Oliveira](#) (Discussant) (Brazil)

Media and Communication Research Through a Multimodal Lens

10:30

Panel : REC-5

REC - Theology and Religion and Communication Working Group business meeting

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+37*

Organised by: [Prof. Ratnamala Vanamamalai](#) (Panel Chair) (India)

The Construction of the Communication System of Mazu Belief and Custom

» [Dr. Tingting su](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Faith-based Activism against Biometric Identification: Resistance to Aadhaar Enrolment in Mizoram

» [Prof. Ratnamala Vanamamalai](#) (India)¹, [Ms. Lalchhandami Lalchhandami](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Harsha Man Maharjan](#) (Qatar)² (1. Mizoram University, 2. Northwestern University in Qatar)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Smartphone as a Devotional Medium: Pooja through Smartphones

» [Mr. Dhanunjay Gondi](#) (India)¹ (1. Central University of Tamil Nadu)

10:30

Panel : CPN-2

CPN - Contesting Authoritarianism: Mass Media, Protest, and Resistance and Working Group business meeting

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+25*

Organised by: Dr. Anke Fiedler (Panel Chair) (Germany)

Adaptive Survivalism in Authoritarian Platforms: How Content Creators Navigate Platformization and Algorithmic Power

» [Ms. Rongjia Li](#) (China)¹ (1. China Foreign Affairs University)

Navigating exile: A comparative analysis of journalists from authoritarian countries in Germany

» [Dr. Carola Richter](#) (Germany)¹, [Dr. Hanan Badr](#) (Austria)², [Dr. Anna Litvinenko](#) (Germany)³ (1. FU Berlin, 2. University of Salzburg, 3. Freie Universität Berlin)

Beyond State Control: Digital Platforms, Media Trust, and Government Messaging in Post-Assad Syria

» [Mr. Abdulwahab Tahhan](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Mr. Richard Sam Dickson](#) (Ghana)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

10:30

Panel : MPA-6

MPA - Environmental Community Engagement and Diversity in Media Production Internationally: Are We Heading in the Right Direction?

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+26*

Organised by: Prof. Karen Arriaza Ibarra (Convenor) (Spain)

Implementation of AI in the analysis of SDGs and public value indicators: the case of national broadcaster RTVE in Spain

» [Prof. Karen Arriaza Ibarra](#) (Spain)¹ (1. Complutense University of Madrid)

Appearance of Women in Turkish TV Series on Turkish TV Channels and Video-on-Demand Platforms in the Context of Culture and Environment

» [Dr. Lutz Peschke](#) (Türkiye)¹, [Prof. Seldag Günes Peschke](#) (Türkiye)² (1. Bilkent University, 2. Ankara Yildirim Beyazit University)

Platform imperialism and the case for cultural diversity in Europe

» [Prof. Andrea Miconi](#) (Italy)¹ (1. IULM University)

Debating Environmental Justice: A Discourse Analysis of Media Reportage from China

» [Prof. Deqiang Ji](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Lin Wang](#) (China)² (1. Communication University of China, Beijing, China, 2. Communication University of China)

10:30

Panel : ICO-3

ICO - Environmental Justice and Inclusive Climate Communication

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+28*

Organised by: Dr. victor zhuang (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Singapore)

Bridging the Gap: Inclusive Communication and Disability Inclusion in Indonesia's Climate Village Program (PROKLIM), A Banguntapan Case Study

» [Mr. Ibnu Darmawan](#) (Indonesia)¹, [Mr. Ikrom Mustofa](#) (Indonesia)² (1. Department of Communication, Universitas Islam Indonesia, 2. Department of Environmental Engineering, Universitas Islam Indonesia)

Platform Labor and Environmental Risks: Adaptation and Challenges of Hard of Hearing Riders in China's Food Delivery Industry

» [Ms. Yifan Jin](#) (China)¹ (1. Wuhan University, School of Journalism and Communication)

Analysing Disabled People's Awareness and Participation in Environmental Justice in Nigeria.

» [Dr. Ngozi Marion Emmanuel](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Birmingham City University)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Accessible Communication and Environmental Justice: The Path to Sensory Democratization of Climate Communication for Disabled Communities in China

» Ms. Meichun Guo (China)¹, Mr. xuanzhong zhang (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. Northeast Normal University)

Climate Change and the Exacerbation of the Disability-Poverty Nexus in Zimbabwe: Building Community Resilience through Inclusive Communication Anchored on Positive Attitudes towards Disability

» Dr. MAKOMBORERO ALLEN BOWA (Zimbabwe)¹ (1. University of Zimbabwe)

10:30

Panel : DIM-3

DIM - Contesting Diasporic Narratives: Media, Power, and Representation

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+27

Organised by: Dr. Sumana Chattopadhyay (Panel Chair) (United States)

Re-articulating India's Soft-Power Narrative: An Investigation of Diasporic Consumption Cultures created by Indian Content on Video-Streaming Platforms

» Dr. Ruchi Kher Jaggi (India)¹, Dr. Pooja Valecha (India)¹, Dr. Kuldeep Brahmhatt (India)¹ (1. Symbiosis Institute of Media and Communication, Symbiosis International (Deemed University))

From border wall to tariff threats and trade wars: Navigating the Texan media's take on Trump's Mexico policies

» Dr. Sumana Chattopadhyay (United States)¹ (1. Marquette University)

Motile Diasporic Subjectivities and its Implications for Understanding Ways of 'Becoming Political'

» Dr. MAITRAYEE BASU (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Leeds)

Between Cultural Appeal and Nationalist Pressures: Chinese Influencers' Portrayal of Japan on Homeland Social Media

» Mrs. Yan Du (Japan)¹ (1. Keio University)

12:30

General

Lunch

Venue - GAIA, Level 1 Foyer

14:00

Panel : JRE-16

JRE - "Global Culture +" Responses to World Journalism Practice and Education: Enhancing Resilience for Global Civil Society

Venue - The Hive LHS-LT

Organised by: Dr. Hsin-Pey Peng (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Taiwan)

Indian-Australian News Media's Contribution to Societal Sustainability and Intercultural Dialogue in Australia

» Dr. Vikrant Kishore (China)¹ (1. University of Nottingham, China)

Building global citizenship consciousness through YouTube among underprivileged and marginalised in India - NMCT as a case study

» Dr. John Britto Parisutham (India)¹ (1. Madurai Kamaraj University)

Cultural Journalism as a Tool for Global Citizenship

» Ms. Shivangi Asthana (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong)

Integrating Global Culture and Local Identity in Journalism Education: Fostering Media Literacy and Global Citizenship through Community Media Practices

» Dr. Chung-Neng Lin (Taiwan)¹ (1. I-Shou University)

Broadcast Journalism and Community Service: An Innovative Approach to Journalism Education through the Service Learning in Malaysia's University for Society (SULAM) Program

» Dr. Rosninawati Hussin (Malaysia)¹ (1. University Sains Islam Malaysia)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

14:00

Panel : HEC-16

HEC - Audiences and social construction of health

Venue - WKWSCI L2 Executive Seminar Room

Organised by: Dr. Livingston White (Panel Chair) (Jamaica) and Dr. Shaohai Jiang (Discussant) (Singapore)

Rethinking Behavioural Change Communication: Is It Still Relevant for Marginalised Women in the Global South?

» [Mrs. Citra Lestari](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Melbourne)

A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Environmental Health Literacy: Assessing Conceptual Development, Measurement Frameworks, and Public Health Impacts

» [Dr. FEIFEI DONG](#) (Malaysia)¹ (1. Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM))

The Process of Social Determination in Health (PDSS): the “mental disorders” caused by hyperconnectivity and online sports betting (BETs) and their interfaces with the deregulation of the media sector in Brazil, in the light of interest groups.

» [Dr. Jorge Silva](#) (Brazil)¹ (1. graduation law)

Big Picture vs. Small Details: A Double-Experimental Study on the Effects and Mechanisms of Different Front-of-Package Labels on Health Guidance

» [Dr. Yongkang Hou](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Practical epistemologies and the rebuttal of scientific consensus: Online health activism against the Fukushima nuclear wastewater discharge

» [Ms. Yixuan Qi](#) (China)¹, Dr. Shaunak Sastry (United States)¹ (1. University of Cincinnati)

14:00

Panel : AUD-6

AUD - Audiences and Intimacy

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+47

Organised by: Dr. María Soto-Sanfiel (Panel Chair) (Singapore)

From Mediated Intimacy to Real-Life Intimacy: Audiences Engaging with the Synergy of Dating Reality Shows and Social Media Platforms

» [Ms. Xinyue Wang](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. The University of Hong Kong)

A Fair Exchange or Exploitation? Examining Dating Show Audiences' Online Engagement in China

» [Ms. Xingyue Dai](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Ms. Yanfei Wu](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Department of Media and Communication, City University of Hong Kong)

Between replication and subversion: Examining sexual scripts in Chinese erotic fanfiction

» [Ms. Don Lok Tung Chui](#) (Hong Kong)¹, Ms. Degel Cheung (Hong Kong)¹ (1. The Chinese University of Hong Kong)

Curative, Performative, Networked: Rethinking Intimacy Through Choreographed Human-AI Interactions in Companion Chatbots

» Ms. Wanyan Wu (China)¹, [Prof. Yupei Zhao](#) (China)¹ (1. Zhejiang University)

14:00

Panel : POP-8

POP - The child's play in/of popular media culture

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+49

Organised by: Prof. Sofie Van Bauwel (Panel Chair) (Belgium)

What's at stake in children's screen time?: Mapping popular discourses and their impact on parents

» [Dr. Kate Mannell](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Deakin University)

From Parenting Show to Cultural Intervention: The South Korean Parenting Show My Golden Kids and Its (Re)Shaping of Family and Individuality in Times of Crisis

» [Dr. Jungyoung Kim](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

“The Idol I loved at Twelve”: First-time fandom as Cyber-Puppy love in Fan Life History —Revisiting the Initial Construction of Fan-Idol Para-intimate Relationship

» [Ms. Wenjun Zhao](#) (China)¹ (1. Lanzhou University)

“We All Love Cinderella But...”: How Young Nigerian Parents Engage with Portrayals of the Female Gender in Disney-Animated Films

» [Dr. Chinedu Ononiwu](#) (Nigeria)¹, [Dr. Chikezie Uzuegbunam](#) (South Africa)² (1. Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, 2. School of Journalism and Media Studies Rhodes University)

Mexican Representation in U.S. Children's Animation

» [Ms. Jimena Abreu](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Simon Fraser University)

14:00

Panel : POP-9

POP - Horror and hope in fictional pasts, presents and futures

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+52

Organised by: Dr. Tabassum Ruhi Khan (Panel Chair) (United States)

Desert Mouse /Environmental injustice and Cold War paranoia in David Lynch's and Denis Villeneuve's Dune adaptations

» [Dr. Gyorgyi Retfalvi](#) (Czechia)¹ (1. Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism, Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University)

When Nature Becomes a Demon: An Ecocritical Discourse Analysis of Contemporary Indonesian Ecohorror Cinema

» [Mr. Khumaid Akhyat Sulkhan](#) (Indonesia)¹ (1. Department of Communications, Universitas Islam Indonesia)

The Zombies of the Teak Forest: A Critique of the Colonial Legacy of Teak Plantations in Indonesia through Film Series

» [Mrs. Dian Dwi Anisa](#) (Indonesia)¹ (1. Department of Communication Universitas Islam Indonesia)

Examining the Social Discourse Around the Futuristic Narratives of Climate Fiction and Climate Apocalypse in the 21st Century Popular Science Fiction Films

» [Ms. Ananya Behera](#) (India)¹ (1. Professional Writer and Independent Researcher 72 Dragons Media)

A Cross-Cultural Diachronic Examination of Audiences' Attitudes Toward Digital Immortality in Science Fiction

» [Dr. Yi Mou](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Jingyi Li](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Lan Jianfeng](#) (China)¹ (1. Shanghai Jiao Tong Univeristy)

14:00

Panel : SPS-3

SPS - Partner Session / UNESCO

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+53

Organised by: Tarja Turtia (Panel Chair)

Press and the Planet: Promoting safety of journalists and information integrity to address environmental challenges

» Speakers: Raúl Fernández Daza (Ambassador of Chile to UNESCO and Chair of the International Programme for the Development of Communication - IPDC), Luciano Mazza de Andrade (Ambassador of Brazil to Singapore), Kunda Dixit (Chief editor of Nepali Times) Ramon Tuazon (Secretary General, Asian Media Information and Communication Centre) and Elizabeth Lester (Monash University, Australia)

14:00

Panel : CAM-5

CAM - Community media as a strategy for social change

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+56

Organised by: Dr. ALEJANDRO BARRANQUERO CARRETERO (Panel Chair) (Spain)

Enhancing Communication Strategies in Urban Communities: An Examination of China's Environmental Communication Model for "Near-Zero Carbon" Initiatives

» [Ms. Tian Ningxin](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Xiao Dong](#) (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China, 2. Academy of Contemporary China and World Studies, China International Communications Group)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Autonomy vs Loyalty: Locating Community as an Intermediary within Indonesia Creative City Project

» [Mrs. Ina Ratriyana](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Monash University)

BEYOND TOKENISM: INTERROGATING COMMUNITY RADIO FOR HEALTH-RELATED SOCIAL CHANGE COMMUNICATION IN AFRICA.

» [Dr. EMMANUEL ESSEL](#) (South Africa)¹, [Prof. ELIZA GOVENDER](#) (South Africa)¹ (1. University of KwaZulu-Natal)

Digital Storytelling and Environmental Justice: India's Digital Media and Climate Change Mobilization

» [Dr. Mochish KS](#) (India)¹ (1. FLAME University, Pune)

Digital Rejection as Community Resistance: Day Laborers' Alternative Media Practices in China's Gig Economy

» [Mr. Jinhao Lei](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Liang huibo](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Bo Xiaojing](#) (China)¹ (1. University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences)

14:00

Panel : GEN-10

GEN - Identity, digital intimacy and companionship

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR4

Organised by: [Dr. Michelle Ho](#) (Panel Chair) (Singapore) and [Prof. 王 Qin 琴 Wang](#) (Discussant) (China)

Revisiting the Digital Closet: Privacy, Intimacy, and Identity Curation on a Chinese Gay Dating Platform

» [Mr. Peng Dai](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Min Jin](#) (China)² (1. Wuhan University, 2. Anhui University)

The Handover's Influence: Changing Depictions of Gender and Intimacy in Hong Kong Romance Films (1977-2017)

» [Ms. Yufei WU](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Shanghai International Studies University)

Cyber Intimacy: Emotional Engagement of Young Chinese Women with AI Companions

» [Prof. 王 Qin 琴 Wang](#) (China)¹ (1. Media and Gender Institute, Communication University of China.)

Queer Side of Things: Digital Intimacies and Dating App Desires Among Men in Singapore

» [Dr. Michelle Ho](#) (Singapore)¹, [Ms. Philippa Self](#) (Singapore)¹, [Ms. Wi En Ng](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

14:00

Panel : GEN-13

GEN - Female journalists, newsroom practices, media representations and coverage

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5

Organised by: [Dr. Kathryn Shine](#) (Panel Chair) (Australia), [Dr. Lubna Zaheer](#) (Discussant) (Pakistan), and [Dr. Yujun Lin](#) (Discussant) (China)

Beyond Gender: How International Audiences React to and Discuss Zhou Shen's Androgynous Performance on YouTube Reaction Videos

» [Ms. Shiran Wu](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

Mediated Care Ethics: Exploring Women's Media Trust During the 2025 Los Angeles Wildfire

» [Dr. Yujun Lin](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Shandong University)

From Headscarves to Headlines: Self-Representation of Afghan Women Journalists on Facebook

» [Mr. Ahmad Jahed Mushtaq](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Qian Wang](#) (China)² (1. Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 2. Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

Does gender influence media engagement? Attitudes and experiences of Australian news sources

» [Dr. Kathryn Shine](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Curtin University)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

14:00

Panel : ESR-10

ESR - Food and Sustainability Communication

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6

Organised by: Dr. Sibó Chen (Panel Chair) (Canada)

Cultural Narratives in Climate Communication for Sustainable Development in Africa

» Mr. Adewale Adekanmbi (Nigeria)¹ (1. Adekanmbi Adewale.M. Dominion University Ibadan)

From Wear to Care: Patagonia's "Worn Wear" Videos as Brand Documentaries Promoting Sustainability

» Dr. Songming Feng (China)¹, Dr. Adele Berndt (Sweden)², Dr. Mart Ots (Sweden)² (1. Beijing Normal University-Hong Kong Baptist University United International College (UIC), 2. Jönköping International Business School of Jönköping University)

The Symbolic Struggle of Social Enterprises in Slow Fashion: Can Sustainability Outlast Trends?

» Mr. Angga Ariestya (Czechia)¹ (1. charles university)

Understanding Early Adopters of Novel Foods in Singapore: A Qualitative Exploration of Cognitive, Social, Moral, and Emotional Drivers

» Ms. Jingyi Xie (Singapore)¹, Dr. Weiyu Zhang (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

A comparison of drivers and barriers towards consumers' acceptance of plant-based protein, mycoprotein, cultured meat, and insect-based protein in Singapore

» Dr. Shelly Malik (Singapore)¹, Dr. Jack Yong Ho (Singapore)¹ (1. Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University)

14:00

Panel : ESR-12

ESR - Environmental Communication, Media and Journalism

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7

Organised by: Pieter Maesele (Panel Chair) (Belgium)

France, January 2025: The PFAS Scandal – A Growing Media-Judicial Offensive

» Prof. Céline Pascual Espuny (France)¹ (1. Aix-Marseille University)

The "Media Adjustment" of Modern Environmentalism and Traditional Ritual: A Study Based on the News Reports of Setting off Fireworks and Firecrackers during the Chinese Spring Festival

» Mr. Wei Li (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication Nanjing University)

Stories of nature and culture: Toward situated practices of environmental journalism in Brazil

» Mrs. Beatriz Sprada Mira (United States)¹ (1. University of Oregon)

Context matters? Investigating social norm misalignment messages' effects on perceived personal responsibility of pro-environmental behavior

» Ms. Pengva Ai (Singapore)¹, Dr. Sonny Rosenthal (Singapore)² (1. Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University, 2. Singapore Management University)

14:00

Panel : PCR-CAM-

PCR - CAM - Participatory Communication Research and Community Communication and Alternative Media Joint Session

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: Dr. Dorismilda Flores-Márquez (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Mexico) and Dr. Andrew Ó Baoill (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Ireland)

Haka Protest and Environmental Justice: Mediated Resistance in Aotearoa(New Zealand)

» Mr. Zeshi Ni (New Zealand)¹, Ms. Qinyi Du (New Zealand)¹ (1. University of Auckland)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Science, Stories, and Solidarity: Bridging Local and Global Activism in the Psychedelic Renaissance

» [Prof. Naíde Müller](#) (Portugal)¹ (1. Universidade Católica Portuguesa, UCP-FCH / CECC)

The role of community participation and localization in environmental justice, with the example of the “Clean Serbia” project

» [Mr. Haitao Bao](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Li Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Amplifying Voices, Not Replacing Them: Community Radio in the Age of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

» [Dr. Manoj Deori](#) (India)¹ (1. University of Hyderabad)

Sakhi Bahinpa's Digital Drive: A Women's Collective Driving Entrepreneurship, Maithili Culture, and Environmental Change through Community Campaign in India"

» [Mrs. Soumya Jha](#) (India)¹ (1. Times School of Media, Bennett University)

14:00

Panel : INC-10

INC - Media Representation and Transcultural Experience

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: [Dr. Uche Onyebadi](#) (Panel Chair) (Kuwait)

Communicating Transcultural Experiences: Highly-Mobile Youth, Identity and Aspirations

» [Ms. Manisha Mishra](#) (Norway)¹ (1. University of Agder)

Television Representation of Black Americans and Stereotyping Among New African Immigrants in the US

» [Mr. Oluwaferanmi Dahunsi](#) (United States)¹ (1. Marquette University)

Empathy and Reciprocity: A Study of New Media Intercultural Emotional Communication of Intangible Cultural Heritage Cuisine

» [Ms. Zhang Qiyun](#) (China)¹ (1. The School of Journalism and Communication at Tsinghua University)

Muted Group Theory, Media Representation of Women in Rural Southern Ghana, and Community Radio: A Critical Literature Review

» [Ms. Victoria Adjetey](#) (United States)¹ (1. Marquette University)

14:00

Panel : MPS-9

MPS - Influencers on social media

Venue - WKWSC I L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: [Ms. Karolina Šimková](#) (Panel Chair) (Czechia)

Unveiling the Crucial Elements in Social Media Influencer Marketing: The Importance of Influencer-Consumer Congruence, Influencer-Product Congruence, Credibility, and Parasocial Relationships

» [Prof. Di Wang](#) (Macao)¹, [Prof. JIAHUI LU](#) (China)² (1. Macau University of Science and Technology, 2. Tianjin University)

Passion Meets Transparency: Authenticity as the Key to Influencer Marketing Success

» [Prof. LIN ZHU](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Mark Kazemzadeh](#) (United States)² (1. Beijing Normal University - Hong Kong Baptist University United International College, 2. University of Massachusetts Boston)

How to make an impact on user engagement: An empirical study of 28 virtual influencers in Instagram

» [Ms. Jieru Fan](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Huiyu Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Xuandi Gong](#) (China)², [Prof. Zeyu Li](#) (China)², [Mr. Zenghua Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Kaiwen Liu](#) (China)³ (1. Communication University of China, 2. Communication University of China, Beijing, China, 3. Ocean University of China)

Misinformation on Social Media: How High-Status Users Shape Online Public Discourse

» [Dr. Soo Young Bae](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. David DeFranza](#) (Ireland)² (1. University of Massachusetts Amherst, 2. University College Dublin)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Does Form Realism Make AI Greenfluencers More Persuasive? Examining the Roles of Perceived Behavioral Realism, Transportation, and Parasocial Interaction

» [Ms. Dandan LIU](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. School of Communication, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong)

14:00

Panel : MCR-2

MCR - Theorizing as Production

Venue - *WKWSCI TV studio (floor space)*

Organised by: Jeremy Shtern (Panel Chair) (Canada)

Justice by Video: An Interactive Multimodal Exhibition

» [Dr. Sandra Ristovska](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Nandi Pointer](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Darija Medic](#) (United States)² (1. University of Colorado Boulder, 2. University of Colorado Denver)

Multimodal Communication, Art, and Knowledge Production: An Exploratory Study of the Relationships Between Forms and Content

» [Dr. Rodrigo Portarij](#) (Brazil)¹, [Dr. Pedro Oliveira](#) (Brazil)² (1. State University of Minas Gerais, 2. Federal University of Mato Grosso)

AGON:Constructions of Democracy

» [Mr. Ali Minanto](#) (Czechia)¹, [Prof. Nico Carpentier](#) (Czechia)¹, [Mr. John Sany Purwanto](#) (Czechia)² (1. charles university, 2. Panglimapromosindo)

The Cabinet of Lost Memories: Tracing Cypriot's memories and nostalgias through sound, smell and objects

» [Ms. Aysu Arsoy](#) (Cyprus)¹ (1. Eastern Mediterranean University)

A visual essay on the House of European History's constructions of Europeanity

» [Prof. Nico Carpentier](#) (Czechia)¹ (1. charles university)

14:00

Panel : POL-4

POL - Environmental Politics and Communication

Venue - *SHHK - HSS Conference Room*

Organised by: [Dr. Serge Banyongen](#) (Discussant) (Canada) and [Prof. ALEXIE TCHEUYAP](#) (Panel Chair) (Canada)

Party Discourse on Environmental Issues on Social Media in Portugal

» [Ms. Ana Margarida Barreto](#) (Portugal)¹, [Mr. Jorge Rosa](#) (Portugal)¹, [Mr. Ilo Alexandre](#) (Portugal)² (1. Associate Professor, ICNOVA FCSH, 2. CICANT - Lusofona University)

Climate change: Political communication and agenda-setting during elections in Canada

» [Dr. Serge Banyongen](#) (Canada)¹, [Prof. ALEXIE TCHEUYAP](#) (Canada)² (1. University of Ottawa, 2. University of Waterloo)

Fighting the Climate Crisis with Humor: Analyzing Climate-Related Internet Memes on Reddit

» [Dr. Simon Luebke](#) (Germany)¹, [Ms. Nadezhda Ozornina](#) (Germany)¹, [Prof. Mario Haim](#) (Germany)¹, [Dr. Jörg Haßler](#) (Germany)¹ (1. LMU Munich)

From Mainstream to the Margins: Assessing News Media Polarisation in Climate Change Coverage

» [Dr. Katharina Esau](#) (Australia)¹, [Prof. Michelle Riedlinger](#) (Australia)², [Mx. Laura Vodden](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Alice Fleerackers](#) (Netherlands)³, [Dr. Tariq Choucair](#) (Australia)¹, [Ms. Carly Lubicz](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Digital Media Research Centre, Queensland University of Technology, 2. Queensland University of Technology, 3. Department of Media Studies, University of Amsterdam)

Assessing barriers to communicating and addressing environmental injustice among mining communities of Plateau State, Nigeria

» [Dr. Adeyanju Apejaye](#) (Nigeria)¹, [Mr. Satkyes Samuel Mwanat](#) (Nigeria)², [Ms. Esther John](#) (Nigeria)¹ (1. Department of Mass Communication, Plateau State University, Bokokos, 2. Department of Mass Communication University of Jos, Plateau State)

Continued from Tuesday, 15 July

14:00

Panel : MPS-10

MPS - Shaping and predicting online public opinion

Venue - WKWSC I3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: Dr. Xiufang (Leah) Li (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Modeling Public Opinion: Large Language Models and Chinese Government Policy Simulations Using Demographic Data

» [Dr. SHAOPENG CHE](#) (China)¹, Prof. Lee Miller (United States)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Predicting Public Opinion with Chain-of-Thought (CoT) in LLMs: A Computational Analysis on the Representative Chinese and American Large Language Models

» [Prof. BAOHUA ZHOU](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Yuan Fang](#) (China)¹ (1. Fudan University)

Decoding Minds, Predicting Clicks: LLMs-Driven Prediction of Short Video Selection

» [Ms. Xiaoxiao Wang](#) (Netherlands)¹, [Mr. Ji Li](#) (China)² (1. University of Amsterdam, 2. Beijing Institute of Technology)

Enhancing Large Language Models' Understanding of Public Data Service Demands Through Prompt Interaction: An Exploratory Study of Chinese Government Message Boards

» [Dr. XIAOYUE ZHANG](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Huimin Liu](#) (China)² (1. Institute of Communication Studies, Communication University of China., 2. Hong Kong Metropolitan University)

Algorithmic Bias in Shaping Gendered Public Opinion: An Empirical Analysis of Social Media

» [Ms. FANSU SUN](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

14:00

Panel : CJD-9

CJD - Communication, Social Justice and Democracy Working Group business meeting

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Dr. Vaia Doudaki (Convenor) (Czechia), Dr. Fernando Oliveira Paulino (Convenor) (Brazil), Prof. Usha Raman (Convenor) (India), and Dr. Tania Rosas-Moreno (Convenor) (United States)

14:00

Panel : POE-5

POE - Industries: The Competition Curve

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7

Organised by: Dr. Ana Bizberge (Panel Chair) (Argentina)

From outrage to (in)action: the dynamics of anti-surveillance activism in South Africa

» [Prof. Jane Duncan](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Glasgow)

Concentrating on "Competition": Denaturalizing Neoclassical Assessments of US Wireless Market Competition

» [Dr. Pawel Popiel](#) (United States)¹, Dr. Christopher Ali (United States)², Ms. Sydney Forde (United States)² (1. Washington State University, 2. Penn State University)

The Multiplex Diversity Model - Making sense of the digital media supply chain

» [Mr. Cameron McTernan](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of South Australia)

Network media economy trends in Latin America

» [Dr. Ana Bizberge](#) (Argentina)¹, Dr. Guillermo Mastrini (Argentina)², Dr. Martín Becerra (Argentina)², Dr. Agustín Espada (Argentina)², Dr. Ornella Carboni (Argentina)², Mrs. Florencia Sosa (Argentina)² (1. Pontificia Universidad Católica de Perú, 2. Universidad Nacional de Quilmes)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Capital Movement and Intersectoral Competition in the Indian Television Market

» Mr. Vyshakh Mundayat (India)¹, Prof. Vigneswara Ilavarasan P (India)² (1. UQ-IITD Research Academy, 2. Indian Institute of Technology Delhi)

14:00

Panel : VIC-6

VIC - Nostalgia, Southeast Asian Imagery, Cosmology and Sollywood

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 8

Organised by: Prof. Govind Ji Pandey (Panel Chair) (India)

Romance, Nostalgia, and Gaze: Wedding Photography in Contemporary China

» Ms. wenging Cheng (Macao)¹, Prof. ZHEN SUN (China)¹ (1. Macau University of Science and Technology)

Vanished Spaces, Everlasting Memories: The Role of Scenes in Chinese Dreamcore's Digital Nostalgia

» Mr. Jiayi Qiang (China)¹, Ms. Xinyi Zhou (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Place, People and Properties: Exploring Nostalgia in the Films of Ritesh Batra

» Mr. Muhammed Swalih K (India)¹, Prof. Sapna Naik (India)¹, Dr. Ragini K S (India)² (1. Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, University of Mysore, 2. School of Media Studies, Malayalam University)

Sensory exploration on film festivals: understanding Southeast Asian urban imagery and environment as materialised, imagined, and lived experiences through festival

» Dr. Zaki Habibi (Indonesia)¹ (1. Department of Communications, Universitas Islam Indonesia)

Performing Gods: Spiritual Rituals as Cosmo-ecological Interventions

» Ms. Mei Jia Ng (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

Tubbi (2018) and Ravi Kinaray (2023): Plagiarism in verité

» Dr. Waijha Raza Rizvi (Pakistan)¹ (1. Film Museum Society | IQRA University Pakistan)

14:00

Panel : MER-2

MER - Learning, skills, and decision-making

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: Dr. Hee Jhee Jiow (Panel Chair) (Singapore) and Mrs. Rayen Condeza (Discussant) (Chile)

Hands-On Learning, Hands-Off Driving: Integrating the Effects of Learning Style and Message Framing

» Ms. Young Eun Kim (Korea, Republic of)¹, Dr. Doha Kim (Korea, Republic of)², Dr. Jae-Gil Lee (Korea, Republic of)³, Dr. Hayeon Song (Korea, Republic of)², Dr. Kwan Min Lee (Singapore)⁴, Dr. Namkee Park (Korea, Republic of)⁵ (1. Department of Human-Artificial Intelligence Interaction, Sungkyunkwan University, 2. Sungkyunkwan University, 3. Hallym University, 4. Nanyang Technological University, 5. Yonsei University)

Exploring The Dynamics of Online Privacy Protection and Self-Disclosure Decision-making on Chinese Social Media Platforms

» Ms. Yating Wang (China)¹, Dr. Yi Ding (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University-Hong Kong Baptist University United International College)

Protection Motivation Theory Based Cyber-Hygiene Intervention

» Dr. Hee Jhee Jiow (Singapore)¹, Ms. Adeline Tay (Singapore)¹ (1. Singapore Institute of Technology)

The Challenges of Embedding Information Credibility Evaluation Skills in the Australian Curriculum

» Prof. Mathieu O'Neil (Australia)¹, Dr. Andrew Ross (Australia)¹ (1. University of Canberra)

Decoding Deception: The Battle for Self-Efficacy and Deepfake Literacy in Media Education

» Ms. huining Cao (China)¹, Mr. Xinyu MA (China)² (1. chuining0518@126.com, 2. xinyu0124520@126.com)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

14:00

Panel : MPA-4

MPA - Producing Media Across Borders: AI, Capital, and the Politics of Collaboration

Venue - WKWSCI TR+7

Organised by: Dr. Concha Edo (Panel Chair) (Spain)

“Sneaking in” and “carving out”: Navigating the conditional solidarity of progressive neoliberalism at media industry events

» [Dr. Brad Limov](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Texas at Austin)

From “Scheduled Delivery” to “Digging for Gags”: Production Culture in Chinese Reality Show Edit Suites and the Transformation of Production-Consumption Relationship in Digital Entertainment

» [Dr. Yuan TIAN](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Yihan Zhou](#) (China)¹ (1. Zhejiang University)

Global Hollywood Against AI: A Critique of Imperialist Technolegislativ Imaginaries in the American Film Industry

» [Mr. Maxime Harvey](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Institut national de la recherche scientifique)

Global Capital Flow and Korean Drama Production: Implications for production Practices and Diversity at the Intersection of the Global and the Local

» [Mr. Woochul Kim](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Simon Fraser University)

Snacking News on TikTok: How Does it Affect News Production?

» [Mr. Enze Zhou](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

14:00

Panel : ETH-3

ETH - Ethical Challenges in Advertising and PR: Perspectives from East and South Asia

Venue - WKWSCI TR+8

Organised by: Dr. Elvira García (Panel Chair) (Spain) and Dr. Ben Hur Demeneck (Discussant) (Brazil)

Efficiency as Exploitation: A Critical Ethics of Generative AI in Chinese Advertising Creative Labor

» [Mr. 川宁程](#) (China)¹, Ms. Wenhan Xie (China)¹ (1. 中国传媒大学)

“Public Charities” or “Poverty Pimps”? A Study on Poverty Porn Content Production in Short Video Charity Advertisements

» [Ms. Qimeng Li](#) (China)¹, Ms. Ziou Li (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University)

Organizational and Personal Drivers of Ethical Awareness in Public Relations: A Study of Practitioner Perspectives

» [Dr. I-Huei Cheng](#) (Taiwan)¹, Dr. Seow Ting Lee (United States)² (1. National Chengchi University, 2. University of Colorado Boulder)

From Nature to Commodity: Ethics, Reality, and Environmental Responsibility in the Representation of Bottled Water in Indian Advertisements.

» [Ms. Juin Barui](#) (India)¹, Prof. Nagamallika Gudipaty (India)¹ (1. The English and Foreign Languages University)

Unveiling the Underlying Tensions in Chinese Corporate Discourse on Human Rights: A Circuit of Culture Perspective

» [Mr. Hua Li](#) (Hong Kong)¹, Dr. Angela Ka Ying MAK (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

14:00

Panel : CPT-9

CPT - Between pieties and policies: Navigating the environmental impact of AI, data and e-waste

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+35

Organised by: Prof. Hopeton Dunn (Panel Chair)

Between green mirage and power plays: Decoding environmental imaginaries in AI policies

» [Ms. Zhe Li](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Lin Sun](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China, Beijing, China)

Mobile telephony and e-waste management and recycling in Kenya: practices and trends

» [Dr. Leah Komen](#) (Kenya)¹ (1. Daystar University)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

A Communication Policy Analysis of Green Jobs in India: Decolonizing Data Narratives

» Ms. Shikha Shalini (India)¹ (1. University School of Mass Communication , Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University , New Delhi)

The Local Politics of Global Data Centers: A Content Analysis based on 2024 GDELT data

» Dr. YUE CAO (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism & Communication , Guangdong University of Foreign Studies)

14:00

Panel : CPT-7

CPT - Confronting AI Governance in Asia and Australia: Policies, Directions and Challenges

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+36

Organised by: Prof. Terence Lee (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Australia), Dr. Jian Xu (Convenor) (Australia), and Prof. Gerard Goggin (Discussant) (Australia)

Opening the 'black box' of algorithms: regulation of AI algorithms in China

» Dr. Jian Xu (Australia)¹ (1. Deakin University)

Riding the waves over generative AI in Malaysia: policies and responses

» Dr. Pauline Leong (Malaysia)¹, Prof. Bradley Freeman (Malaysia)¹ (1. Sunway University)

Be(com)ing Smart: AI and Digital Governance in Singapore

» Prof. Terence Lee (China)¹ (1. University of Nottingham Ningbo China)

Conceptualising 'safety' in India's smart city-based digital safety solutions: Policy implications for women and gender diverse communities

» Dr. Suruchi Mazumdar (India)¹, Dr. Justine Humphry (Australia)², Dr. Lik Sam Chan (Australia)³, Dr. Deepti Prasad (Australia)³ (1. O.P. Jindal Global University, 2. The University of Sydney, 3. University of Sydney)

AI Governance in Australia: From Economic Good to Responsible Regulation

» Ms. Kai-Ti Kao (Australia)¹ (1. Curtin University)

14:00

Panel : RUC-1

RUC - Communication and innovation

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+37

Organised by: Dr. Elske van de Fliert (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Communication, knowledge and information systems for environmentally sustainable agriculture in Ukraine

» Dr. Sarah Cardey (United Kingdom)¹, Dr. Alla Kravchenko (Ukraine)², Dr. Yuliia Negoda (Ukraine)², Dr. Yuri Vlasenko (Ukraine)² (1. University of Reading, 2. National University of Life and Environmental Science of Ukraine)

Living Lab dynamics. A three-dimensional framework for analysis

» Dr. Rico Lie (Netherlands)¹, Dr. Annemarie van Paassen (Netherlands)¹, Dr. Jan Fliervoet (Netherlands)², Dr. Loes Witteveen (Netherlands)³ (1. Knowledge, Technology & Innovation (KTI), Wageningen University & Research, 2. Communication, Participation & Social Ecological Learning (CoPSEL), Van Hall Larenstein University of Applied Sciences, 3. (1) Knowledge, Technology & Innovation (KTI). Wageningen University & Research; (2) Communication, Participation & Social Ecological Learning (CoPSEL). Van Hall Larenstein University of Applied Sciences)

Smart Farming for a Changing Climate: AI-Driven Agricultural Innovations in Andhra Pradesh, India

» Mr. ABHISHEK ACHARYA (India)¹, Dr. Jayanta Kumar Panda (India)² (1. Dept. of Journalism and Mass Communication, Berhampur University, 2. Associate Professor, Dept. J & MC, Berhampur University)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Exploring the complexities of scaling direct-seeded rice (DSR) in the Philippines: The roles of innovations and policy brokering

» [Dr. Jaime IV Manalo](#) (Philippines)¹, [Dr. Rosa Pilipinas Francisco](#) (Philippines)², [Dr. Eduardo Jimmy Quilang](#) (Philippines)¹, [Dr. Karen Eloisa Barroga](#) (Philippines)¹, [Ms. Alice Mataia](#) (Philippines)¹, [Dr. Dindo King Donayre](#) (Philippines)¹, [Dr. Aurora Corales](#) (Philippines)¹, [Mr. Mark Angelo Abando](#) (Philippines)¹, [Mr. Ailon Oliver Capistrano](#) (Philippines)¹, [Dr. Diadem ESMERO](#) (Philippines)¹, [Mr. Elmer Bautista](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. Philippine Rice Research Institute, 2. University of the Philippines Los Baños)

Reconfiguring Rural China through Platformization: Media, Technology, and Capital in Synergy

» [Ms. Yicheng Yan](#) (China)¹ (1. East China Normal University)

14:00

Panel : MAR-3

MAR - Sonic and sound studies

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+25

Organised by: [Dr. José Cláudio Castanheira](#) (Panel Chair) (Brazil)

Shor Machana (Making Noise): The Politics of Sound in an Urban Slum in Hyderabad

» [Ms. Khadeeja Amenda](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

Music and Coal Field in the Desert: Musical Formations and Extractive Logics of Coal Mining in Thar

» [Dr. Shehram Mokhtar](#) (Qatar)¹ (1. Northwestern University in Qatar)

Decolonizing Sound: Rethinking Technologies, Standardization, and Ways of Making Music

» [Dr. José Cláudio Castanheira](#) (Brazil)¹ (1. Federal Fluminense University (UFF))

Warm Interactions: The Impact of IPAs Voice Anthropomorphism on User Evaluation

» [Prof. Feixue Li](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Ruijia Cai](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Reshaping Sound in Independent Smartphone Filmmaking: The Role of Smartphone Audio Tools and Apps.

» [Mr. Dhanunjay Gondi](#) (India)¹ (1. Central University of Tamil Nadu)

14:00

Panel : ORG-3

ORG - CSR, ESG and Corporate Legitimacy

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+26

Organised by: [Prof. Abena Yeboah-Banin](#) (Panel Chair) (Ghana)

Agents Of Change

» [Ms. Niharika Parasar](#) (Netherlands)¹, [Dr. Joao Fernando Ferreira Goncalves](#) (Netherlands)¹, [Dr. Anne-Marie van Prooijen](#) (Netherlands)¹ (1. Erasmus University Rotterdam)

Examining Social Media Opposition to Corporate Social Responsibility Advertising through Social Norms Activation: A Comparative Study of China and the U.S.

» [Dr. Yafei Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Xu Dong](#) (China)², [Dr. He Gong](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Li Chen](#) (United States)³ (1. Renmin University of China, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China, 3. West Texas A&M University)

'This is an insult to our culture!': How public sector communication gaps impede community participation around mineral resource privatisation in rural Ghana

» [Ms. Diana Sebbie](#) (Ghana)¹ (1. University of Ghana Department of Communication Studies)

Greenwashing, thematic avoidance or environment-friendly actions? An analysis of ESG Reporting within US organisations from a European perspective

» [Prof. Holger Sievert](#) (Germany)¹, [Prof. Oliver Hellriegel](#) (Germany)¹ (1. Macromedia University)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Promoting Employee CSR Engagement through Employee-Organization Relationships: Exploring the Mediating Role of CSR Attribution

» [Ms. Xiaoxin Xiong](#) (Australia)¹, [Mr. Lunyan Lu](#) (United States)² (1. University Technology of Sydney, 2. College of Communication & Information Sciences The University of Alabama)

14:00

Panel : ICO-4

ICO - Technological Futures and Disability

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+28*

Organised by: Mx. Sze Hwee Jace Tay (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Singapore)

Connecting Through Experience: Strengthening Communication Skills in Youth with Special Needs

» [Mr. Shengzhe Yang](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Sihao Yang](#) (Hong Kong)² (1. Beijing Normal University-Hong Kong Baptist University United International College (UIC), 2. Hong Kong Baptist University)

"An Extension of the Ear" or "A Mirror of Social Issues"? The Effects of AI Empowerment on Communication and the Unveiling of Imbalanced Communication Rights Structure for Deaf Signers from a Critical Media Perspective

» [Ms. Siqi Lin](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Blurring Boundaries: The Impact of AI Human Voice Blending and Suspicion on Trust, Accessibility, and Social Inclusion in Assistive Technologies

» [Ms. Lai Ying](#) (China)¹ (1. University of California, Davis)

The Space-time Game: workers with disabilities and DPOs in China's AI data annotation industry

» [Dr. Bingqing Xia](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Tongyu Wu](#) (China)² (1. East China Normal University, 2. Zhejiang University)

14:00

Panel : DIM-6

DIM - Diaspora and Media Working Group business meeting

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+27*

Organised by: Dr. Jessica Retis (Convenor) (United States) and Dr. Sumana Chattopadhyay (Convenor) (United States)

16:00

Panel : POP-10

POP - Transcultural Fandoms and Digital Labor: Queer Narratives, Nationalism, and Creative Agency in East Asian Popular Culture

Venue - *The Hive LHS-LT*

Organised by: Dr. Tingting Hu (Convenor) (China)

Transcending Borders: The Digital Queer Spaces of Transcultural Fandom in Boys' Love Narratives

» [Dr. Tingting Hu](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Qiyuan Hu](#) (Australia)², [Ms. Chenchen Zou](#) (United States)³ (1. Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University, 2. University of Sydney, 3. Penn State University)

Transmedia Fan Labor: Affective Agency, Transmedia and Gendered Exploitation in Chinese Boys' Love Cultural Industry

» [Dr. Liang GE](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University College London)

Building Your International Boy Groups: Nationalism and Cosmopolitanism in Transcultural Fandom

» [Ms. Eva Liu](#) (United States)¹ (1. Ohio University)

Curation productivity: Rethinking fan participation and creativity in the age of platformization

» [Dr. Fang Wu](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Di Cui](#) (China)² (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 2. Fudan University)

Vernacular Turns in Transcultural Contexts: The Role of Taiwanese Manga Fans in Political Narratives

» [Dr. Erika Ningxin Wang](#) (China)¹ (1. The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Shenzhen)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

16:00

Panel : MPS-11**MPS - Home and away***Venue - WKWSC L2 Executive Seminar Room*

Organised by: Dr. Leena Ripatti-Torniainen (Panel Chair) (Finland)

Mediating Domestic Space: Smart Cameras, Elderly Media Practices, and the Triadic Dialectics of Home Perception in China» [Ms. yi yao](#) (China)¹, Ms. Yingliang Yuan (China)² (1. Communication University of China (CUC), 2. Communication University of China)**The “Delayed Revolution”Unfolding: Smart Home Technology and the Gendered Division of Household Labor in Chinese Families**» [Dr. xuting wan](#) (China)¹, Dr. wu jingyu (China)² (1. Jinan University, 2. Communication University of China)**My house is empty: A Study of Online Expression and Action of Life Minimalists in Chinese Social Media Community**» [Ms. XIAOYI LU](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)**From Passion to Practice: Theoretical Insights on Social Media’s Influence on Special Forces-style Tourism among Youngsters**» [Mr. Zheyu Zhao](#) (Malaysia)¹, Dr. Kun Sang (Malaysia)¹, [Ms. Zihan Xu](#) (Malaysia)¹, Ms. Yu Gu (Malaysia)¹, Ms. Mingyu Yan (Malaysia)¹ (1. Xiamen University Malaysia)**(Post-)Digital transformation of conflicts: Perceived threats to the media environment in the Czech Republic**» [Ms. Karolina Šimková](#) (Czechia)¹, [Prof. Jeffrey Wimmer](#) (Germany)² (1. Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism, Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University, 2. University of Augsburg)

16:00

Panel : AUD-8**AUD - Performative fandoms***Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+47*

Organised by: Dr. Rafal Zaborowski (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Yearning for Yesterday: Analysing Young Viewers' Comments on Nostalgic Drama» [Dr. Yachi Chen](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. Department of Journalism, Chinese Culture University)**From Screens to Splurges: Parasocial Relationship and Impulsive Buying among Indonesian K-Pop Fans**» [Dr. Laras Sekarasih](#) (Indonesia)¹, Ms. Kayla Shafa Haridsah (Indonesia)¹, Ms. Yolanda Lumbantobing (Indonesia)¹ (1. Universitas Indonesia)**Fans of Husbandos or Celebrity Crush? How Social Media Influence Parasocial Relationship?**» [Ms. Xinyun Wu](#) (China)¹ (1. University of Colorado Denver)**(Re)writing the canon: multivocality and voice in virtual performer fandom**» [Dr. Rafal Zaborowski](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. King's College London)

16:00

Panel : JRE-6**JRE - Environmental journalism: practice and research in diverse contexts III***Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+49*

Organised by: Dr. Zahera Harb (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom) and Dr. Omar Al-Ghazzi (Discussant) (United Kingdom)

Framing Environmental Issues in the UAE: An Analysis of Media Discourses on Sustainability, Innovation, and Crisis» [Dr. Yosra Jarrar](#) (United Arab Emirates)¹, [Ms. Lujain Ammar](#) (United Arab Emirates)¹ (1. American University in Dubai)**Normalizing Climate Change: A Multi-step Discourse Analysis of Chinese Media Post-2015**» [Dr. Miao Xu](#) (Hong Kong)¹, Dr. Mengqi Li (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University - Hong Kong Baptist University (BNBU))**Journalism standards as a trap: Climate change reporting in Russia and the reasons for its deliberate one-sidedness**» [Prof. Svetlana Bodrunova](#) (Russian Federation)¹ (1. St. Petersburg State University)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

“The world is chaotic, and so is the data”: Journalists’ perceptions of the barriers and facilitators to climate reporting in Thailand

» Dr. Siwaporn Sukittanon (Thailand)¹, Dr. Sayyed Fawad Ali Shah (United States)², Dr. Tamar Ginossar (United States)³ (1. Chiang Mai University, 2. Auburn University, 3. University of New Mexico)

Climate Change or Climate Conspiracy? The Green Story of Arab News

» Dr. Zahera Harb (United Kingdom)¹, Dr. Omar Al-Ghazzi (United Kingdom)² (1. City St George's University of London, 2. London School of Economics)

16:00

Panel : JRE-10

JRE - Journalism practice and research across diverse countries II

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+52

Organised by: Prof. Ruhan Zhao (Panel Chair) (China) and Prof. Francis Lee (Discussant) (Hong Kong)

The “Flourishing” of the Aral Sea: The Beginning of Beat Reporting to Promote Environmental Awareness in Uzbek Media

» Dr. Mukarram Otamurodova (Uzbekistan)¹ (1. Journalism and Mass Communications University of Uzbekistan)

Energy Justice and Electric Vehicles: A Qualitative Analysis of China's Media Discourse

» Ms. Yuying Song (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Reaffirming Journalistic Ideals: The Professional Aspirations and Pragmatic Choices of Contemporary Chinese Journalism and Communication Students

» Mr. Runzhe Niu (China)¹, Ms. Siyu Peng (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

A Miniature History of Journalism: An analysis of 48 Autobiographies of International Journalists

» Prof. Ruhan Zhao (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Journalism in Crisis? The Case of Zambia as an Outlier

» Ms. Annastazia Ng'ambi (Zambia)¹ (1. Northwestern University in Qatar)

16:00

Panel : CPT-10

CPT - 'Breaking' news? The challenges of AI and media governance

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+53

Organised by: Dr. Weiyu Zhang (Panel Chair) (Singapore)

AI and news: another nail in the coffin?

» Dr. Michael Davis (Australia)¹, Prof. Monica Attard (Australia)¹ (1. UTS Centre for Media Transition)

A Small Nation's Perspective: Singapore's Policy Approaches to AI in the Creative Media Industries

» Dr. Pei-Sze Chow (Singapore)¹, Dr. Sherwin Chua (Singapore)¹ (1. Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University)

Anticipated Affordances and AI Adoption: Exploring Chinese Journalists' Pre-Usage Perceptions of Artificial Intelligence in Media Industries

» Dr. Runping Zhu (China)¹, Mr. MA zhipeng (China)², Mr. Zhexi Gu (United States)³, Mr. Liheng Chen (China)¹, Ms. Jiayue Fan (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University-Hong Kong Baptist University United International College (UIC), 2. mazhipenggo@foxmail.com, 3. University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill)

The Tech-Media Hybridity in the Global Communication Policy Landscape

» Dr. Qun Wang (United States)¹ (1. Fordham University)

Media subsidies and news content quality

» Dr. Mart Ots (Sweden)¹, Dr. Marcel Garz (Sweden)¹ (1. Jönköping International Business School of Jönköping University)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

16:00 Panel : CAM-7
CAM - Business meeting and new books / published reports

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+56

Organised by: Prof. Vinod Pavarala (Convenor) (India), Dr. Andrew Ó Baoill (Convenor) (Ireland), Prof. Susan Forde (Discussant) (Australia), Dr. ALEJANDRO BARRANQUERO CARRETERO (Discussant) (Spain), and Dr. Amparo Cadavid (Discussant) (Colombia)

New books / published reports

» Susan Forde, Alejandro Barranquero, Amparo Cadavid

16:00 Panel : GEN-15
GEN - Celebrities and self-presentation, gendered digital labour, and social media influencers

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR4

Organised by: Prof. GAURI DURGA CHAKRABORTY (Panel Chair) (India) and Ms. Qiheng Lin (Discussant) (China)

In the Name of "Sisters": Corporate Sisterhoods as Gendered Labor in Chinese Fashion Influencer Industry

» Ms. Qiheng Lin (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

Gender "Performance" vs. "True Self" in Social Circles: Platform-Specific Identity Construction of Femboys Influencers in China

» Dr. Shoukui Cui (Malaysia)¹, Dr. Mohd Adnan Hamedi (Malaysia)² (1. Universiti Malaya, 2. hamedi@um.edu.my)

Gender and Objectification in Influencer Marketing: How Same- and Opposite-Gender Effects Shape Follower Responses

» Mr. Longzhao Zheng (China)¹, Prof. Hui Xiong (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Xiamen University)

Role Models and Platform Dynamics: Exploring Diversity and Stereotypes in the Presentation of German Mumfluencers

» Prof. Claudia Wegener (Germany)¹, Dr. Julia Lück-Benz (Germany)², Dr. Shari Adlung (Germany)¹ (1. Filmuniversität Babelsberg, 2. University of Berlin)

Calculated Authenticity: Algorithmic Visibility and Gender Politics in Taiwan's Influencer Management Platforms

» Prof. Wei-Ping CHEN (Taiwan)¹ (1. National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University)

16:00 Panel : GEN-14
GEN - Gender representation, genre and popular culture

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5

Organised by: Dr. Fitria Angeliqa (Panel Chair) (Indonesia), Ms. Mahnoor Ahmer Ansari (Discussant) (Qatar), Dr. Xingyuan Meng (Panel Chair) (China), and Dr. Bintan Humeira (Discussant) (Indonesia)

Making Time, Spending Time: Interfacing gender, class, and the moral economy of time on TikTok in Pakistan

» Ms. Mahnoor Ahmer Ansari (Qatar)¹, Dr. Clovis Bergere (Qatar)¹ (1. Northwestern University in Qatar)

FROM REALITY TO HYPER-REALITY: MEDIATIZATION ANALYSIS OF FAMILY REPRESENTATION IN TIKTOK

» Ms. Yihan Zhang (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Breaking Barriers with Laughter: Chinese Female Audience Perceptions of Stand-up Comedy as a Feminist Dialogue Starter

» Dr. Xingyuan Meng (China)¹ (1. Peking University)

MYTHS, NATURE AND HIDDEN BIASES IN INDONESIA'S HORROR MOVIES

» Dr. Bintan Humeira (Indonesia)¹, Dr. Fitria Angeliqa (Indonesia)² (1. UIN Syarif Hidayatullah, 2. Universitas Pancasila)

It's Just Humor: Sexist Humor Interpretation in Traditional Entertainment

» Mrs. Dyan Rahmiati (Indonesia)¹, Prof. ENI MARYANI (Indonesia)¹, Mr. Kunto Adi Wibowo (Indonesia)¹ (1. Universitas Padjadjaran)

Continued from Tuesday, 15 July

16:00 **Panel : ESR-13**
ESR - Energy, Carbon & Fuel: The Role of Communication
 Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6
 Organised by: Maitreyee Mishra (Panel Chair)

Communication Strategies for Methane Reduction in African Livestock Farming: A Systematic Review

» Ms. Wilhelmina Antwi (United States)¹, Mr. Fuseini Tia Iddrisu (Ghana)², Mr. Musah Muntari (United States)³, Mr. Patrick Owusu Ansah (United States)⁴, Ms. Barikisu Issaka (United States)⁵ (1. Bellisario College of Communications, Penn State, 2. Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries Science, University for Development Studies, 3. Texas A&M University, Department of Animal Science., 4. Center for Climate Change Communication, George Mason University, 5. Advertising and Public Relations Department, Michigan State University)

Nuclear Narratives and Green Trust: A Cross-National Analysis of Électricité de France's Science Communication Strategies Post-COP28

» Ms. Cailing Zou (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

To Be or Not to Be? The Impact of Media on Public Attitudes toward Dual Carbon Targets in China

» Ms. RUN LIU (China)¹ (1. Beijing Forestry University)

Narrating Carbon Neutrality: Power Structures and Discursive Construction in the Global Shaping of China's Environmental Image

» Ms. 栾珂王 (China)¹ (1. East China Normal University)

AI, Energy, and Environmental Responsibility: A Discourse Analysis of Corporate Sustainability Narratives

» Ms. Mst. Nasrin Akter (Bangladesh)¹ (1. American International University-Bangladesh)

16:00 **Panel : ESR-14**
ESR - Narratives of Environment, Climate and Science
 Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7
 Organised by: Dr. Joana Diaz Pont (Panel Chair) (Spain)

How TED Talks Bridge Science and Action: Discourse Strategies in Climate Communication

» Ms. Lin Wang (China)¹, Prof. Hao Gao (China)¹ (1. Nanjing Normal University)

Story Mapping Sea Culture and Climate Crisis: A Decolonial Science Communication Approach to Documenting Loss and Damage in Cebu Islands, Philippines

» Dr. Crina Escabarte-Tañongon (Philippines)¹, Prof. Jay Nathan Jore (Philippines)¹, Dr. Brisneve Edullantes (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Cebu)

Petro-Rhetoric in Canada: Narrating Extractivism

» Dr. Sibó Chen (Canada)¹ (1. Toronto Metropolitan University)

Climate Change is 'Hear' and Now: A Study of Climate Podcasting by Indian News Outlets

» Dr. Sneha Mehendale (India)¹, Prof. Kanchan K. Malik (India)² (1. Symbiosis International (Deemed University), 2. University of Hyderabad)

Storytelling Climate Change: Analyzing Kadvi Hawa as a Tool for Environmental Awareness

» Mr. Sidharth Verma (India)¹, Dr. Ramalakshmi L (India)², Prof. Durgesh Tripathi (India)³ (1. Centre of Excellence in Disaster Management, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, Delhi, India, 2. VIT School for Media, Arts and Technology (V-SMART), Vellore Institute of Technology, Vellore, India, 3. University School of Mass Communication, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, New Delhi)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

16:00

Panel : PCR-HEC-

PCR - HEC - Participatory Communication Research and Health Communication joint session

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: Dr. EMMANUEL ESSEL (Discussant, Panel Chair) (South Africa)

Health Resilience and Participation of Rural Communities – An Initial Assessment of the Strength-based Approach for Advancing Health Communication in Climate Crises and Disasters

» [Dr. Olaf Werder](#) (Australia)¹, Prof. Jeff Niederdeppe (United States)², Dr. Emily Saurman (Australia)¹, Dr. Norman Porticella (United States)², Dr. Clare Davies (Australia)¹, Mr. Tej Shah (United States)² (1. University of Sydney, 2. Cornell University)

Communicating Resilience: Empowering Caregivers through Socially Engaged Ceramic Art

» [Dr. Christine Choy](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Department of Art and Design, The Hang Seng University of Hong Kong)

Transformational Health Communication: A New Perspective on Healthcare and Prevention

» [Dr. Olaf Werder](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Sydney)

16:00

Panel : INC-12

INC - Global Cultural Content and Adaptation

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: Dr. Stephan Goerland (Panel Chair) (Germany)

Exploring the Globalization of Chinese TV Dramas: A Case Study of the Science Fiction TV Series San Ti (Three-Body)

» [Dr. Yingzi Wang](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Yongchang Liu](#) (China)¹ (1. Nanjing Normal University)

Increasing Local Production and Localization in Global Flows, the Netflix Model Compared with Amazon Prime Video, MAX, and Disney+

» [Dr. Joe Straubhaar](#) (United States)¹, Dr. Swapnil Rai (United States)², [Dr. Melissa Santillana](#) (United States)³, Ms. Silvia DalBen Furtado (United States)¹ (1. University of Texas at Austin, 2. University of Michigan, 3. Texas Tech University)

Mosaic Narrative and the Digital Adaptation of Cultural Symbols: Mainstream Media Strategies in Dragon Boat Culture Communication on Transnational Platforms

» [Dr. Hao Guo](#) (China)¹ (1. Southwest University)

"Dragon" and "Panda" Who are More Suitable for the International Expression of China's Image—Research on Symbol Construction Based on Film Texts

» [Dr. HUANG HAOYU](#) (China)¹, [Mr. YANQING Li](#) (China)² (1. Zhejiang University, 2. Huaqiao University)

How K-Food is Cooking Up Sustainability through Cultural Branding and Food-Tech Innovation

» [Ms. Shin Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, Dr. Namhoon Park (Korea, Republic of)² (1. Tsinghua University, 2. Hanyang University)

16:00

Panel : HEC-10

HEC - Misinformation – Old Problem, New Frontiers

Venue - WKWSCI L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: Mr. Yuchen Zhou (Panel Chair) (Hong Kong) and Dr. Cindy Ngai (Discussant) (Hong Kong)

Virtual Human vs. Human: Who is More Effective at Correcting Health Misinformation?

» [Mr. Xingjian Wang](#) (China)¹, Dr. Chen Min (China)¹, Ms. Qiaoyun Wan (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Information Communication, Huazhong University of Science and Technology)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Knowing More or Less about Health? The Impact of Information-Finds-Me Perception under Media Use and Algorithm Recommendation on Women's Sexual and Reproductive Health Misperceptions

» [Ms. Yanling He](#) (China)¹ (1. Nanjing University)

Accidentally Corrected? Unpacking the Roles of Cognitive Elaboration and Family Communication Patterns in the Relationship between Incidental Corrective Information Exposure and Health Misperceptions

» [Dr. Chen Luo](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Shirley Li](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Yulong Tang](#) (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University, 2. Beijing Institute of Graphic Communication)

Examining the Boomerang Effect in Promoting Influenza Vaccination: The Roles of Psychological Reactance, Message Fatigue, and Normative Perceptions

» [Ms. Zixi Li](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Ms. Huijun Zhuang](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Ms. Xiaoyu Xia](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Dr. Jingyuan \(Jolie\) Shi](#) (Hong Kong)² (1. Hong Kong Baptist University, 2. Hong Kong Baptist University)

Impact of Natural Parks on Health During COVID-19 Lockdowns: A Quasi-Experiment

» [Ms. Yuhao Zhang](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

16:00

Panel : POL-6

POL - Misinformation, Media, and Political Narratives

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

Organised by: [Ms. Yujie Zhong](#) (Panel Chair) (United States) and [Dr. Chia-Shin Lin](#) (Discussant) (Taiwan)

The China factor among older adults: fake news circulation and the 2024 Taiwan Presidential election

» [Dr. Chia-Shin Lin](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. Shih Hsin University)

Belief beyond the Battlefield: How Political Identity Shapes Perceptions of Misinformation in China

» [Mr. Yuheng Wang](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

Deepfakes, Disinformation, and Political Narratives in Pakistan

» [Ms. Maham Sufi](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Cardiff University)

The Role of Social Media News Preference in Political Polarization, Health Science, and COVID-19 Vaccination

» [Ms. Yujie Zhong](#) (United States)¹ (1. Temple University)

Rise in Negative Online Political Advertisement in India and the Related Concerns

» [Dr. Nisha Singh](#) (India)¹ (1. SVKM's Mithibai College of Arts, Chauhan Institute of Science & Amrutben Jivanlal College of Commerce and Economics)

16:00

Panel : HEC-17

HEC - Medicine, Humanity, and Media: Digital Health Usage Across Diverse Populations in the UK, Canada, China, and Hong Kong

Venue - WKWSCI L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: [Dr. Shaohai Jiang](#) (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Singapore)

Exploring User Narratives: A Qualitative Analysis of Hong Kong Adults' Experiences with Health Chatbots

» [Dr. Li Crystal Jiang](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. City University of Hong Kong)

Trust, Quality, and Values: Perceptions of Users' Satisfaction for Online Mental Health Platform in China

» [Ms. Xinjie Zhao](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Zining Wang](#) (China)¹, [Prof. JING XU](#) (China)¹ (1. Peking University)

Bridging the Digital Divide: Understanding Chinese Senior Immigrants' Technology Learning in Canada

» [Prof. Zhenyi Li](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Royal Roads University)

A qualitative study of digital resources and health literacy of pregnant Chinese migrant women in maternity care in England

» [Dr. Sarah Q. Gong](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University College London)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

16:00 **Panel : CJD-5**
CJD - (Platform) power and justice imaginaries
Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6
 Organised by: Prof. Usha Raman (Panel Chair) (India)

Social Justice and Democracy : Social Media-based Political Commentators' Agenda-Setting Power in the Chinese Media Environment
 » Mr. Yushan Y (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China (CUC))

Exploring the Role of Local Media in Communicating Environmental Justice in Nepal
 » Dr. Sandesh Dass Shrestha (Nepal)¹ (1. Purbanchal University, Faculty of Management)

Inequality in Digital Democracy Narratives: Social Imaginaries of Content Creators on Xiaohongshu
 » Ms. Kang Naixin (China)¹ (1. Huazhong Agricultural University)

Toxicity across digital platforms: Impact on vulnerable communities and strategies for mitigation
 » Dr. Martin Oller Alonso (Spain)¹ (1. University of Salamanca)

16:00 **Panel : POE-6**
POE - Manufacturing Media Hegemonies
Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7
 Organised by: Dr. Randy Nichols (Panel Chair) (United States)

Official Media – US Government funding in the hybrid war for democracy
 » Prof. Marcus Breen (United States)¹ (1. Boston College)

It's-A Me, Mario, a Twenty-first Century Commercial Intertext
 » Dr. Randy Nichols (United States)¹ (1. University of Washington Tacoma)

APIs as Logistic Media – Enacting Platform Hegemony with Invisible Infrastructure
 » Dr. Yuanbo Qiu (China)¹, Prof. Xiaojie Cao (China)¹, Prof. Lily Luo (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, South China University of Technology)

The Flow of Television Programs in the Age of Transnational Streaming Services: The Case of Netflix and East and Southeast Asia
 » Prof. William Kunz (United States)¹ (1. University of Washington Tacoma)

Blockbuster Strategies and Environmental Contradictions: The case of Avatar: The Way of Water
 » Dr. Leslie M Meier (United Kingdom)¹, Dr. Nancy Thumim (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Leeds)

16:00 **Panel : VIC-7**
VIC - SCI-FI, Games, VisionArt, Production Design, Instagram Narratives
Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 8
 Organised by: Ms. Linuo Zhao (Panel Chair) (China)

Folk Knowledge and Environmental Imagination: A Case Study of Journey to the West as an Alternative Chinese Sci-Fi Film
 » Ms. Yujia Liu (China)¹, Ms. Elizabeth (Lishan) Qin (United States)² (1. Concordia University, 2. University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill)

Sisyphus Games: The Death Drive and Pleasure of Repetitive Operations in Video Games
 » Ms. Linuo Zhao (China)¹, Ms. Shiya Cheng (China)¹ (1. Beijing Foreign Studies University)

Building Relationships and Envisioning the Future: VisionArte Methodology, Graphic Tools and Sensory Experiences in Community-Based Participatory Action Research (CBPAR)
 » Ms. Alessandra Abrill Abruzzese Aguirre (Belgium)¹ (1. Katholieke Universiteit Leuven)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

Visuality and performativity in The Sparring Partner: The ways of viewing justice through production design and performance utterances

» Dr. Sunny Sui-kwong Lam (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Metropolitan University)

Reclaiming Place Through Symbolic Geographies: Visual Resistance on Palestinian Instagram

» Ms. Insyirah Mujtahid (Singapore)¹, Dr. Nurul Huda Rashid (Netherlands)², Dr. Kokil Jaidka (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore, 2. Leiden University)

Beyond Pandas: Multimodal Narratives of Chengdu's International Image on Instagram

» Mr. Qi Chen (China)¹, Mr. Yubo Liu (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

16:00

Panel : MER-3

MER - Environment and Sustainability

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: Mrs. Rayen Condeza (Panel Chair) (Chile) and Dr. Oscar Miranda-Villanueva (Discussant) (Mexico)

Engrandecer el corazón: towards a fair and sustainable digital transformation

» Dr. Oscar Miranda-Villanueva (Mexico)¹, Dr. Martha Roxana Vicente Díaz (Mexico)¹, Dr. Luis Moises López Flores (Mexico)¹ (1. Tecnológico de Monterrey, School of Humanities and Education)

Digital Awakening: AI's Role in Promoting Environmental Consciousness in Kolkata's Secondary Education

» Ms. Sohini Biswas (India)¹ (1. research scholar)

Evaluating environmental literacy through the framing of extreme heat in Facebook comment threads on heat index-related posts by Filipino news outlets

» Ms. Dezscyrie Pearl Lorenzo (Philippines)¹, Ms. Andreana Dominique Moro (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Diliman)

Eco-Art and Indigenous Aesthetics: The Role of Tribal Visual Narratives in Advancing Environmental Justice and Sustainability in India

» Ms. Soumya Gupta (India)¹ (1. Mahindra University)

Production of environmental news at school: teachers' learning from media education

» Mrs. Rayen Condeza (Chile)¹ (1. Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile)

16:00

Panel : MPA-5

MPA - Media Production Analysis Working Group business meeting

Venue - WKWSCI TR+7

Organised by: Dr. Concha Edo (Convenor) (Spain)

16:00

Panel : ETH-4

ETH - Voicing the Ethics of society: Silence and Power

Venue - WKWSCI TR+8

Organised by: Dr. Elvira García (Discussant) (Spain) and Dr. María Teresa Nicolás Gavilán (Panel Chair) (Mexico)

When rubber trees colonize people: The colonial narratives of ethnic minorities and the erosion of ethics in environmental media representation

» Dr. Yingchun Xu (United States)¹, Dr. Xinyue Zhang (China)² (1. Rutgers University, 2. Southwestern University of Finance and Economics)

Continued from **Tuesday, 15 July**

The Double Struggle: The Privacy Protection Dilemma of Internet Celebrity Children within the Authoritarian-Consumerism Power Structure

» [Ms. Yifan Kang](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University, Wuhan, China)

Can You Hear Nature Sing? Enacting the Syilx Ethical Practice of N̄awq̄nwix̄ to Reconstruct the Relationships between Humans and Nature

» [Prof. Grace Fan](#) (Canada)¹ (1. The University of British Columbia)

“Vegetarianism as Environmentalism”? Middle-Class Discourse Construction and Moral Positioning of Chinese Vegetarianism Bloggers

» [Ms. SHUYANG ZONG](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Transparency: The Supervisor’s right to discuss the plagiarism in a film thesis

» [Dr. Wajiha Raza Rizvi](#) (Pakistan)¹ (1. Film Museum Society | IQRA University Pakistan)

16:00

Panel : CRI-7

CRI - Crisis, Security and Conflict Communication Working Group business meeting

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+35*

Organised by: [Dr. Virpi Salojärvi](#) (Convenor) (Finland)

16:00

Panel : ISM-3

ISM - Islam and Media Working Group business meeting

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+36*

Organised by: [Prof. Fatma Elzahraa Elsayed](#) (Convenor) (Egypt) and [Dr. Saima Shahid](#) (Convenor) (Pakistan)

16:00

Panel : RUC-2

RUC - Marginalized voices and rural communication

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+37*

Organised by: [Dr. Sarah Cardey](#) (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Infrastructuring the last mile: Development, Chinese tech, and densification of Ghana’s rural network

» [Prof. Miao Lu](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Lingnan University)

Women, disasters and community of practices: A collective action towards disaster resilience in Odisha, India

» [Dr. Manas K Kanjilal](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Neelatphal Chanda](#) (India)² (1. Department of Journalism and Communication, REVA University Bangalore, 2. Christ University, India)

Women, mobile, and electronic media in rural South India: Between power and promise

» [Dr. Sujatha Sosale](#) (United States)¹ (1. The University of Iowa)

Exploring Women's Inclusion in Indonesian Agriculture through Information and Communication Technology (ICT): Unravelling Marginalization or Lingering Exclusion?

» [Mrs. Asri Sulistiawati](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Reading)

Cognition - Relationship - Action: New Media Empowers Rural Women's Participation in Environmental Governance

» [Ms. 潇然章](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Weizhen Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

16:00

Panel : CPN-3

CPN - Singapore’s hegemonic authoritarianism: processes of consolidation and resistance

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+25*

Organised by: [Dr. Cherian George](#) (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Hong Kong)

Climate Die, Economy Die, Everybody Die! – Curtailing Activism and Missed Opportunities in Singapore

» [Dr. Howard Lee](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Murdoch University)

Continued from Tuesday, 15 July

Media and University Capture: Lessons from Tracking Invisible Censorship

» [Dr. Cherian George](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

The Law We Need? Assessing Singapore's Foreign Interference (Countermeasures) Act, Four Years On

» [Dr. Ia Ian Chong](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

Challenge or Comply? Evolving Responses to Singapore's Restrictive Media Laws

» [Ms. Alysha Chandra](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. Network for Independent Media for Better Understanding and Support)

16:00

Panel : LAW-4

LAW - Law Section business meeting

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+26*

Organised by: Dr. Fernando Gutiérrez (Convenor) (Chile) and Mr. MacDonald Amaran (Convenor) (United Kingdom)

16:00

Panel : ICO-5

ICO - Technology, Accessibility and Disability

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+28*

Organised by: Prof. Lorenzo Dalvit (Discussant, Panel Chair) (South Africa)

Caught between ubiquity and multiple marginalisation: an intersectional exploration of the digital experiences of Black women with disabilities in a peri-urban and a rural area of the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa

» [Prof. Lorenzo Dalvit](#) (South Africa)¹, Dr. BIMBO FAFOWORA (South Africa)¹ (1. Rhodes University)

Between Encouragement and Discouragement: How Mothers of Children with Developmental Disabilities Relate with the TV Show

» [Ms. Yunhee Cho](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Ms. Sujeong Yoon](#) (Korea, Republic of)² (1. Yonsei University, 2. Seoul National University)

Seeking Visibility, Fearing Visibility, Controlling Visibility: A Study on the Platform Visibility of China's Rare Disease Community

» [Prof. Zhanwei Liu](#) (China)¹, Dr. Ziwen Lei (China)², [Ms. Jie Liu](#) (China)³ (1. Minzu university of China, 2. University of Science and Technology Beijing, 3. Renmin University of China, Nanyang Technological University)

Understanding Information Needs and Seeking in Palliative Care Communication: Building a Behavioral and Cultural Health Services Acceptance Model (BeCHAM)

» Prof. May O. Lwin (Singapore)¹, [Mr. Yumin Lin](#) (Singapore)¹, Ms. Ysa M. Cayabyab (Singapore)¹, Ms. Seraphina Leo (Singapore)¹ (1. Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University)

Disability Inclusive, Healthcare Spending and sustainable Development in sub Saharan Africa

» [Mr. Adewale Adekanmbi](#) (Nigeria)¹ (1. Adekanmbi Adewale.M. Dominion University Ibadan)

16:00

Panel : SPS-1

SPS - Partner Session / ICA

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+27*

Organised by: Dr. Elisia Cohen (Panel Chair), Prof. Barbie Zelizer (Discussant) (United States), Dr. Winston Mano (Discussant) (United Kingdom), Prof. Ke Guo (Discussant) (China), Prof. Jack Qiu (Discussant) (Singapore), and Dr. Ingrid Bachmann (Discussant) (Chile)

Publishing International Scholarship During Times of Disruption and Social Change

Wednesday, 16 July

08:30

Panel : JRE-13

JRE - Journalism education research

Venue - The Hive LHS-LT

Organised by: Dr. S M Shameem Reza (Panel Chair) (Bangladesh) and Dr. Mbongeni Msimanga (Discussant) (South Africa)

Environmental Journalism education in the Global South: Revisiting the University Curricula

» [Ms. Ashfara Haque](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. S M Shameem Reza](#) (Bangladesh)² (1. Texas Tech University, 2. University of Dhaka)

Climate change: Deserted land in journalism education

» [Prof. Susanne Fengler](#) (Germany)¹, [Ms. Johanna Mack](#) (Germany)¹, [Dr. Sara Namusoga-Kaale](#) (Uganda)², [Dr. Enoch Sithole](#) (South Africa)³, [Dr. Merle van Berkum](#) (Germany)¹ (1. Erich Brost Institute for International Journalism, 2. Makerere University, 3. Institute for Climate Change Communication)

Desire for Change but Lack of Support: How Chinese high-educated youth Practice news literacy

» [Dr. yuan he](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Wang Chenyao](#) (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication Nanjing University, 2. Nanjing University)

The Impact of Generative AI on Journalism Education: A Grounded Theory Study on Student Dependency Mechanisms

» [Ms. Huang Mo](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Mengyi Ma](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Understanding Journalism Students' Responses to Negative Speech against Journalism Profession: A Dual Perspective of Social Identity Theory and Psychological Reactance Theory

» [Mr. Chongming Qiao](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

08:30

Panel : HEC-8

HEC - New Dimensions in Risk Communication

Venue - WKWSC L2 Executive Seminar Room

Organised by: Prof. Serra Gorpe (Panel Chair) (United Arab Emirates) and Dr. Monique Lewis (Discussant) (Australia)

Individuals' Intentions to Engage in Protective Behaviors against COVID-19: Application of the Risk Perception Attitude Framework

» [Dr. Jarim Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Ms. Jaeyeon Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Yonsei University)

How gambling influencers and user-generated content on social media can contribute to risky gambling: A social identity approach

» [Dr. Momoko Fujita](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Canberra)

"Is Silence a Special Protection?": Intergenerational Gaps in Reproductive Health Perceptions and Selective Risk Communication

» [Dr. Shuya Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Miao Bao](#) (China)² (1. journalism and information communication school, Huazhong University of Science and Technology, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Central University for Nationalities)

Humanizing, politicizing and surviving HIV: Multimodal discourses of HIV patient influencers on Instagram

» [Dr. Barui Kurniawan WARUWU](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

Building Resilience through Communication: Adaptation and Role Shifts in Chinese Alzheimer's Families

» [Ms. Yue ZHANG](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

08:30

Panel : AUD-3

AUD - Artificial Intelligence literacy

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+47

Organised by: Dr. María Soto-Sanfiel (Panel Chair) (Singapore)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Construction of AI Usage Literacy: Taiwanese Experts' Viewpoint

» Prof. Huiwen Liu (Taiwan)¹ (1. College of Communication, National Chengchi University, Taiwan, R.O.C.)

Ignorance Breeds Fearlessness? AI Literacy, Technophobia, and Public Acceptance of Generative AI Technologies

» Prof. Huaming Chen (China)¹, Ms. Wenhui Liang (China)¹ (1. School of Literature and Journalism, Sichuan University)

Audience News Literacy Behaviors in the Philippines and Potential Implications for Societal Change

» Ms. Maria Jeriesa Osorio (Philippines)¹, Ms. Irish Jane Talusan (Philippines)² (1. University of the Philippines Diliman, 2. University of the Philippines)

Exploring the role of AI anchor image-news content congruency in news-viewing experience among young users: A mixed-method study in the Chinese context

» Mr. Pengbo Qian (China)¹, Mr. Shixin Hu (China)² (1. Fudan University, 2. Sun Yat-sen University)

08:30

Panel : POP-11

POP - National streams and regional flows in audiovisual content

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+49*

Organised by: Dr. Chikezie Uzuegbunam (Panel Chair) (South Africa)

The Impact of Post-Apartheid Political and Economic Climate on Afrikaans Ethnic Media in South African Public Broadcasting Television: Implications for Afrikaans Language and Culture.

» Dr. Kealeboga Aiseng (South Africa)¹ (1. University of the Witwatersrand)

Streaming Germanness: National Narratives in Contemporary German Series

» Dr. Yulia Yurtaeva-Martens (Germany)¹, Dr. Anna Smoliarova (Israel)², Ms. Zeynep Altundag (Germany)¹, Prof. Joachim Trebbe (Germany)¹, Prof. Gisela Dachs (Israel)², Prof. Lothar Mikos (Germany)¹, Mr. Assaf Uni (Israel)² (1. Freie Universität Berlin, 2. Hebrew University of Jerusalem)

Centralizing the Peripheries: Cultural Intermediaries for Southern Media Flows in Africa

» Ms. Fengyi Yin (United States)¹ (1. Temple University)

The Rise of Alternative Digital Narratives: A Study on the Global Popularity Mechanisms of Chinese Micro-Short Plays

» Ms. Xinqiao Zhang (China)¹, Dr. Tingyu Wang (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, Beijing, China, 2. University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences)

Between Local and Global: Thai Webtoon Platforms and the Diversification of Platformization

» Prof. Sungmin Lee (Korea, Republic of)¹, Prof. So-Eun Lee (Korea, Republic of)² (1. Korea National Open University, 2. Pukyong National University)

08:30

Panel : POP-12

POP - Taste and cultural consumption between digits and matter

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+52*

Organised by: Dr. Florian Vanlee (Panel Chair) (Belgium)

Museum as Fan Pilgrimage Site: The Construction of Sacred Place through Social Media Discourse

» Dr. QIJUN HE (China)¹, Ms. XIAODING YANG (China)¹, Ms. Shuangshuang Ma (China)¹, Ms. JING GU (China)², Prof. Yungeng Li (China)³ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Shanghai University, 2. Shanghai Museum, 3. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Material, Platform, and Identity: The Heterotopia of Woman Goths on Xiaohongshu

» [Ms. Kezhu Chai](#) (China)¹ (1. Shanghai Jiao Tong Univeristy)

When Algorithms Dictate Style: The Indiscriminate Erosion and Negotiated Survival of Vintage Cultures in China

» [Mrs. Miaomiao Huang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

'A 2,000 CNY Anime Date': The Exploration of Emotional Consumption in Cosplay Commissions

» [Ms. Zhimeng Jiang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Yiyang Shu](#) (China)² (1. 中国传媒大学, 2. roughroof6@)

You Are What You Listen: The Emergence of Taste Cocoons through Recommendation Algorithms and User Engagement

» [Ms. Yingying Lu](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism, Fudan University)

08:30

Panel : CPT-12

CPT - Dilemmas in data governance: Openness, identity and security

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+53

Organised by: [Dr. Julia Pohle](#) (Panel Chair) (Germany)

Negotiating the Boundary of Openness in the context of Open Government: Mapping the Controversies Surrounding Open Government Data Intermediaries through a Case Study in Australia

» [Ms. Xiaolan Cai](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Canberra)

Unveiling Content Moderation? Benefits and Pitfalls of the DSA Transparency Database

» [Mr. Samuel Groesch](#) (Switzerland)¹, [Ms. Alena Birrer](#) (Switzerland)¹, [Prof. Natascha Just](#) (Switzerland)¹, [Dr. Florian Saurwein](#) (Switzerland)¹ (1. Media & Internet Governance Division, Department of Communication and Media Research, University of Zurich)

Towards large-scale research infrastructure for digital platform observability

» [Prof. Julian Thomas](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Amanda Lawrence](#) (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University)

Governance by Data: Visualisation and Migration Policy Regimes

» [Dr. Verity Trott](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. William Allen](#) (United Kingdom)², [Dr. Elsa Gomis](#) (United Kingdom)³ (1. Monash University, 2. University of Southampton, 3. University of Oxford)

08:30

Panel : CAM-8

CAM - Mediated Communication in Social Movements and Collective Action

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+56

Organised by: [Prof. Vinod Pavarala](#) (Panel Chair) (India)

Farmers' Media Strategies in Community Collective Action: A Case Study from Zhang Village, Northern China

» [Mr. Xiang yang XU](#) (China)¹ (1. Shenzhen University)

The Alternative Media in China's War-time Home Front: Campus Wall Newspaper Publishing at National Southwest Associated University (1938-1945)

» [Dr. Lin Xu](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Qi Zheng](#) (China)² (1. Minnan Normal University, 2. Shantou Unviersity)

Social Movements and Leadership in a Repressive Environment: Telegram in the 2020 Belarus Uprising

» [Dr. Aliaksandr Herasimenka](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Dr. Anastasia Kavada](#) (United Kingdom)² (1. University of Liverpool, 2. University of Westminster)

Sustainable Living Practices in Online Communities: Based on LDA Topic Analysis and In-depth Interviews of the Douban Group "Zero Waste Living"

» [Ms. 子琪郭](#) (China)¹ (1. communication university of China)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

08:30 Panel : GEN-17
GEN - Feminism, TV and film: discourses, representations of everyday life and surveillance
Venue - GAIA ABS-SR4
 Organised by: Dr. Woori Han (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom) and Dr. Xinyang Zhao (Discussant) (China)

Discourse analysis of "Female Carnival" movies from the perspective of post-structural feminism: A case study of the commonality between Her Story and Barbie

» [Ms. YUYuan LIAN](#) (China)¹ (1. 2804849018@qq.com)

The End of Love, the Beginning of Friendship: Exploring Chinese fem-slash fandom and real-person coupling as feminist expressions in China

» [Ms. Jiayi Gu](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Riwei Liu](#) (China)² (1. Fudan University, 2. Xiangsihu College of Guangxi Minzu University)

Digital Sisterhood: Live Streaming Feminism and Network Resilience in China

» [Ms. Shu Li](#) (Australia)¹, [Ms. Yue liang](#) (Australia)² (1. Deakin University, 2. RMIT University)

Misogyny in China's VR livestreaming platform from a techno-feminist approach

» [Dr. Xinyang Zhao](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Altman Peng](#) (United Kingdom)², [Dr. PENGFEI FU](#) (China)³, [Dr. Zhuyun Song](#) (China)¹ (1. Tongji University, 2. University of Warwick, 3. Shanghai Jiao Tong Univeristy)

The rise of TERF (transgender excluionary radical feminism) in Korea?: From a perspective from remediated body and gender

» [Dr. Woori Han](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Exeter)

08:30 Panel : GEN-18
GEN - Gender and philosophy, postcolonialism and emotion
Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5
 Organised by: Ms. Hoornaz Keshavarzian (Panel Chair) (Canada), Dr. Arkaprava Chattopadhyay (Discussant) (India), and Prof. Ya Yang (Panel Chair) (China)

Reframing Chinese Rural Women: Performance, Identity and Social Connection in Kuaishou Short-video Platform

» [Ms. Xinyi Cheng](#) (China)¹ (1. Peking University)

Demystifying Tantra: The Digital Media Initiatives of the Female Tantra Practitioners (Yoginis) of Bengal, India

» [Dr. Arkaprava Chattopadhyay](#) (India)¹ (1. SRM University Sikkim)

Militant Mourning: Walking through Affective Archives

» [Ms. Hoornaz Keshavarzian](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Simon Fraser University)

Oral Narratives, Rituals and Cultural Values of Trees in Tamil Nadu and West Bengal, India

» [Dr. Sithara Puli Venkatesh](#) (India)¹ (1. Loyola College, Chennai)

Voices of Vogue: Understanding postfeminism and popular feminism through visual analysis of magazine covers

» [Dr. Hyunji Doh](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Dr. Claire Shinhea Lee](#) (Korea, Republic of)² (1. Sookmyung Women's University, 2. Pusan National University)

08:30 Panel : ESR-19
ESR - Climate Change: Communication, Media and Journalism 2
Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6
 Organised by: Dr. Kerrie Foxwell Norton (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Odisha's Climate Communication Strategies: A model for Global South resilience

» [Dr. Jayanta Kumar Panda](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Sasmita Dash](#) (India)² (1. Berhampur University, Odisha, 2. GIET University, Odisha)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Hot air and hot topics: Revisiting the association between temperature and media coverage of climate change

» [Mr. Zepeng Tong](#) (United States)¹, Prof. James Shanahan (United States)¹ (1. Indiana University Bloomington)

Are Partisan Media the Culprits for Misperceptions? Conditional Indirect Effects of Fox News and MSNBC Use on Climate Change Misperceptions

» [Dr. Chen Luo](#) (China)¹, Dr. Xizhu Xiao (China)², Dr. Yan Su (United States)³, Prof. Porismita Borah (United States)⁴ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University, 2. Qingdao University, 3. Tarleton State University, 4. Washington State University)

The "Southern Turn" in Climate Journalism from a Strategic Narrative Perspective

» [Ms. Jingwei Tang](#) (China)¹ (1. Tsinghua University)

08:30

Panel : ESR-18

ESR - Environmental Communication, Media and Journalism 2

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7

Organised by: Dr. Kasun Ubayasiri (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Analyzing News Narratives and Trends: Tamil Digital Journalism and Environmental Awareness

» [Mr. AIN S S](#) (India)¹ (1. PhD Scholar, Mizoram University)

Investigating The Framing of EUDR Policy in Indonesian Online Media

» [Ms. Irma Garnesia](#) (Germany)¹, [Ms. Twina Paramesthi](#) (Indonesia)² (1. Ilmenau University of Technology, 2. Trend Asia)

GREENWASH OR GREEN TRUTH? UNMASKING ENVIRONMENTAL REPORTING IN INDIA

» [Mr. Gunjan Sharma](#) (India)¹, [Ms. Sneha Gupta](#) (India)² (1. Mahindra University, 2. Bennett University)

Paid Buzzers and Social Media Influence: Challenges Faced by Environmental Journalists in Indonesia

» [Dr. Pratiwi Utami](#) (Indonesia)¹ (1. Department of Communication Science, Universitas Gadjah Mada)

08:30

Panel : PCR-8

PCR - Participatory Culture, Agency and Change

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: Prof. Naïde Müller (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Portugal)

Brand activism or narratives of change? Advertising as a tool for social impact

» [Dr. Paula Dias Aguiar](#) (Portugal)¹, [Prof. Ana Melo](#) (Portugal)¹ (1. Communication and Society Research Centre - University of Minho)

The Boycott Movement of Israeli Products among Indonesian Consumers: A Reflection of Muslim Solidarity?

» [Ms. Wulandari Aprilda](#) (Indonesia)¹, [Mr. Angga Ariestya](#) (Czechia)² (1. Universitas Multimedia Nusantara, 2. charles university)

Children's Participation in Environmental Rights and Conservation: A Theoretical and Empirical Enquiry

» [Dr. Bijayashree Satpathy](#) (India)¹ (1. Agzistence Intelligence Private Limited)

GenAI as a Technology of the Self: Enhancing Youth Participation in Society

» [Prof. Junming Gu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Xinyi Zhou](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Transcultural Participation and Cultural Mediation: A Case Study of Black Myth: Wukong's Participatory Video Culture on YouTube

» [Dr. Xiaoqing Bai](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Fei Han](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

08:30

Panel : INC-7

INC - Global Media Coverage of Environmental Disasters

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: Dr. Josh Anderson (Panel Chair) (United States)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Media Gaze in International News: A Comparative Study of Cross-National Coverage of Japan's Nuclear Incident Across Five Countries (2011-2024)

» [Mr. haosong zhang](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Xiaoyang Liu](#) (China)¹ (1. Chongqing University of Technology)

Homogenized and 'Indifferent': A Comparative Analysis of the Reporting Frameworks and Media Interaction of the Southeast Asian Heatwave Coverage in 2024 from a Global Communication Perspective

» [Ms. Ruoxi Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Cailing Zou](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

"Elephants' Northern Odyssey ": Ecological Events and the Re-continuation Practice of Media Memory

» [Ms. Yazhu Yangwen](#) (China)¹, Prof. Fangfang Ji (China)¹, Ms. Yunxiao Wang (China)¹ (1. University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences)

From Local Outcry to Global Echo: A Comparative Analysis of Digital Activism in the Kudankulam Anti-Nuclear and Thoothukudi Sterlite Protests

» [Mr. J loynes](#) (India)¹, Dr. Ashish kumar Dwivedy (India)² (1. Doctoral Student, School of Communications, XIM University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India, 2. Assistant Professor, XIM University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India)

Communicating official business: A longitudinal study of Kuwaiti government's use of X (Twitter) in reaching citizens on national issues, with focus on the environment (2022-2025).

» Dr. Mohammad Al-Otaibi (Kuwait)¹, [Dr. Uche Onyebadi](#) (United States)² (1. Kuwait University, 2. Texas Christian University)

08:30

Panel : MPS-3

MPS - Rural and indigenous mediatization

Venue - WKWSCI L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: Dr. YEFU QIAN (Panel Chair) (China)

Digital Rurality: How Short Video Platforms Transform Rural Social Space

» [Ms. Yongxi Lai](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China , Beijing ,China)

Mediatized Transformation and Circle-Breaking: Reconstructing the Communication Ecology of Jingdezhen Handmade Ceramics in the Digital Platform Era

» [Dr. Hui Cai](#) (China)¹, Ms. Fan Huang (China)² (1. School of Foreign Languages, Chongqing University of Technology, 2. School of International Journalism and Communication, Beijing Foreign Studies University)

Imaginative Production and Cultural Grafting: The Generative Logic of Rural Landscapes' Internet-Famous Transformation

» [Dr. LUPENG YUE](#) (China)¹ (1. Sichuan University&University of Electronic Science and Technology of China)

08:30

Panel : POL-8

POL - Cross-Cultural and Diplomatic Political Communication

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

Organised by: Dr. Abdullahi Tasiu Abubakar (Discussant, Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Beyond propaganda: Russia's rising influence in West Africa

» [Dr. Abdullahi Tasiu Abubakar](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. City St George University of London)

Peace vs. War: A Mixed-Methods Analysis of Platform-Specific Diplomatic Narratives in the Russia-Ukraine War

» [Mr. Lu Yanlin](#) (China)¹, Mr. shu lun Yang (China)¹, [Mr. Shang Sun](#) (China)², Mr. Yuxuan Wang (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism, Communication University of China, 2. Communication University of China)

Gu Ailing's Mediatized Body: The Construction of Multiple Identities of a Transnational Sports Star and the Public Diplomacy Game between China and the United States

» Mr. Zhenyuan Feng (China)¹, Prof. Fan Liu (China)¹, [Ms. Mengyuan Li](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China (CUC))

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

"The Shadow and the Mouse": Representations of Yahya Sinwar in the Israeli media

» [Dr. nissim katz](#) (Israel)¹, [Prof. hillel nossek](#) (Israel)¹ (1. kinneret academic college)

Research on political communication between Hong Kong and Macau in 1960s, taking Macau Vila Verde Radio Broadcasting Group as an example

» [Ms. xinyu zhang](#) (China)¹, Mr. Zihao Zhao (China)¹ (1. Macau University of Science and Technology)

08:30

Panel : MPS-13

MPS - Cyberbullying and problematic media use

Venue - WKWSCI L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: Dr. Rachel Khan (Panel Chair) (Philippines)

The Impact of Opinion Leaders' Communication Styles on Young People's Intentions to Engage in Cyberbullying: The Moderating Role of Perspective-Taking and the Mediating Role of Moral Disengagement

» [Mr. 冯洲玥](#) (China)¹, [Mrs. Wendi Fu](#) (China)¹, [Mrs. 辛予溪](#) (China)¹, [Mr. 郑产业](#) (China)², [Mr. 黄浩洋](#) (China)³ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China, 2. Department of Psychology, Renmin University of China, 3. Gaoling School of Artificial Intelligence, Renmin University of China)

Like A Fleeting Show or Snail Pace? A Study of Problematic Short Video Use on Time Perception Distortion: From a Temporal Psychology Perspective

» [Mr. Beixi Jia](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Jingwen Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University)

Why Unwilling to Help? The Connection between Bystander Victim Experience and Intervention Behavior in Cyberbullying: The Inhibitory Effect of Cognitive Emotion Regulation

» [Ms. Yihan Wu](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Yiwei Wu](#) (China)², [Mr. 黄迦南](#) [黄迦南](#) (China)³, [Ms. Jiayu Ge](#) (China)³, [Mr. Jiaqi Shan](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Yang Yang](#) (China)³ (1. University of Shanghai for Science and Technology, 2. Communication University of China, 3. University of Shanghai for Science and Technology)

How I Learned to "Hate" You: The Influences of the Echo Chamber Caused by Algorithm on Cyberbullying in the Digital Era

» [Dr. WANQI LI](#) (China)¹ (1. Shantou University)

08:30

Panel : CJD-6

CJD - Voice, vulnerability and inclusion

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Prof. Nico Carpentier (Panel Chair) (Czechia)

Has Asia Found a Better Path in Deliberation Practices? A West vs. East Analysis

» [Mr. Nicholas Thomas](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. PhD Candidate at National University of Singapore)

Systemic Deliberation and Intersectionality: Analyzing Inclusion of Marginalized Groups

» [Ms. Aira Almeida](#) (Brazil)¹, [Prof. Rousiley Maia](#) (Brazil)¹, [Dr. Maiara Orlandini](#) (Brazil)¹ (1. Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais)

Disability-led Accessibility Audits and the IAMCR conference: Implications for Communication and Social Justice

» [Ms. Sami S. Goh](#) (Singapore)¹, [Dr. victor zhuang](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

Representation of vulnerable groups in Dutch news media coverage of the climate crisis -- An analysis of mainstream narratives

» [Dr. Yijing Wang](#) (Netherlands)¹, [Dr. Dennis Nguyen](#) (Netherlands)², [Dr. Sergül Nguyen](#) (Netherlands)¹ (1. Erasmus University Rotterdam, 2. Utrecht University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

08:30

Panel : POE-7

POE - The political economy of AI

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7

Organised by: Prof. Peichi Chung (Panel Chair) (Hong Kong)

Theorizing the Eco- political economy of AI

» [Prof. Benedetta Brevini](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Sydney)

Direct producers: A class analysis of artificial intelligence

» [Dr. Byron Hauck](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Simon Fraser University)

Digital Labor and Computational Gaming in Esports

» [Prof. Peichi Chung](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Chinese University of Hong Kong)

08:30

Panel : GMP-CPT-

GMP - CPT - Joint Session: The role of big tech in media policy and digital regulation

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 8

Organised by: Prof. Gerard Goggin (Panel Chair) (Australia) and Prof. Claudia Padovani (Discussant) (Italy)

Markets, Regulation and the Intermediation of Digital Technology Policy in India

» [Dr. Khetrimayum Monish](#) (Malaysia)¹ (1. Monash University Malaysia)

"A Faustian Bargain": Deregulation and Asymmetries in Brazil's VoD Market

» Prof. othon jambeiro (Brazil)¹, Prof. NATACHA CANESSO (Brazil)¹, [Prof. JULIANO DOMINGUES](#) (Brazil)², Prof. KATIA MORAIS (Brazil)³, Prof. CLAUDIO BEZERRA (Brazil)⁴, Ms. CLARICE ANDRADE (Brazil)⁴, Mr. ULISSES MELO (Brazil)⁵, Mr. NILTON GOMES (Brazil)⁴ (1. Universidade Federal da Bahia (UFBA), 2. Universidade Católica de Pernambuco (Unicap) / Universidade de Pernambuco (UPE), 3. Universidade do Estado da Bahia (Uneb), 4. Universidade Católica de Pernambuco (Unicap), 5. Universidade Federal de Pernambuco (UFPE))

Unmasking the "Iceberg": A Longitudinal Analysis of Personal Data Breaches, Hidden Risks, and the Evolution of Risk-Notification Frameworks (1971–2023)

» [Prof. Min Wang](#) (China)¹ (1. Wuhan University, School of Journalism and Communication)

China's Race to Generative AI Regulation

» [Dr. Zixue Tai](#) (United States)¹, Dr. Fengbin Hu (China)² (1. University of Kentucky, 2. Fudan University)

08:30

Panel : MER-5

MER - AI and Algorithms

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: Dr. Devina Sarwatay (Discussant, Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

A Critical Examination of Young Users' Falling Love with AI: A cognitive approach

» [Ms. Yiqun Geng](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Zongde liang](#) (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. Communication University of China , Beijing ,China)

AI, Ethics, and Sustainability in Media Education: The Role of Generative AI in Reshaping University Learning in Bangladesh

» [Dr. Harisur Rahman](#) (Bangladesh)¹ (1. North South University)

Cognitive Drivers, Resource Divides, and Cultural Shaping: A Study on the Influence Mechanisms of AI Tool Usage Intentions Among Journalism and Communication Students

» [Mr. zichen liu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. liaying Huang](#) (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. Communication University of China (CUC))

Addressing Media Algorithms and Datafication through Media Education in Indian Schools

» [Ms. Swagata Ghosh](#) (India)¹, Prof. Gajendra Singh Chauhan (India)¹, Ms. Renu Kotwal (India)¹ (1. Birla Institute of Technology and Science Pilani)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

08:30

Panel : HIS-5

HIS - Otherness, Censorship and Resistance

Venue - WKWSCI TR+7

Organised by: Dr. Wajiha Raza Rizvi (Panel Chair) (Pakistan)

Constructing the Enemy on the Discursive Frontlines: A Discourse Theoretical Analysis of the Construction of the Other in Turkish Cypriot Children's Magazines (1950s-1980s)

» Mr. Mazlum Kemal Dagdelen (Czechia)¹ (1. Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism, Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University)

Framing the "Other": The 1974 Rise of Brazil-China Diplomatic Relations Through Veja and Peking Review Magazines

» Ms. Aline Santos (China)¹ (1. School of International Journalism and Communication, Beijing Foreign Studies University)

Resistance in a Time of Surveillance: How Journalists Fought Portugal's Dictatorial Censorship

» Dr. Manuel Carvalho Coutinho (Portugal)¹ (1. Universidade Católica Portuguesa, UCP-FCH / CECC)

Forbidden Images during the Carnation Revolution. Study of censorship cases on RTP (1974-1976).

» Dr. Jacinto Godinho (Portugal)¹, Prof. Carla Baptista (Portugal)² (1. Associate Professor. CICANT - Lusofona University, 2. Associate Professor, ICNOVA FCSH)

Embracing Defeat and Debris: The Destruction and Occupation of Radio Pagodas from 1942 to 1952

» Dr. Tomomi MARUYAMA (Japan)¹ (1. Shizuoka University)

08:30

Panel : MCS-1

MCS - Reflections on sports, media, and politics

Venue - WKWSCI TR+8

Organised by: Dr. Xavier Ramon (Panel Chair) (Spain) and Dr. Peter English (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Sport and politics do mix: Local media coverage of the Brisbane 2032 Olympics

» Dr. Peter English (Australia)¹ (1. University of the Sunshine Coast)

"Media Spectacle" revisited: A comparison of the marketing and politicization of Michael Jordan and LeBron James

» Dr. Joerg-Uwe Nieland (Austria)¹, Prof. Rainer Winter (Austria)¹ (1. Alpen Adria University Klagenfurt)

Political Polarisation in Media Coverage of Athletes' Political Statements: An Analysis of Conservative and Liberal Reporting During the 2024 US Presidential Election

» Mr. Thomas Neumann (Austria)¹, Dr. Philip Sinner (Germany)² (1. Alpen Adria University Klagenfurt, 2. University of Bremen)

Tackling discrimination and advancing accountability: Spanish sports journalists' perspectives and ethical recommendations to counter racism in football reporting

» Dr. Xavier Ramon (Spain)¹, Ms. Carmen Longas (Netherlands)², Dr. José Luis Rojas-Torrijos (Spain)³ (1. Pompeu Fabra University, 2. Erasmus University Rotterdam, 3. Universidad de Sevilla)

Boundary setting and cultural authority Integrating: Research on the metajournalistic discourse construction of Chinese news media under media convergence and digital sports

» Prof. Xuemei BI (China)¹, Dr. Luleiya HUANG (China)¹ (1. Beijing Sport University)

08:30

Panel : POP-14

POP - Sites of struggle: television's cultural and economic value

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+35

Organised by: Dr. Amy Boyle (Convenor) (Australia) and Dr. Elke Weissmann (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Communicating "authentic" queer authorship: industry perceptions of audience expectations and publicity practices for Australian television drama

» Dr. Damien O'Meara (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Supportive Streaming: Considering Apple TV+ and Corporate Soft Power

» [Dr. Alexander Beare](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Adelaide)

Textual and Ideological Limitations in Apple TV+'s Social Justice Narratives

» [Dr. Robert Boucaut](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Adelaide)

The White Lotus Effect: the mixed messages, ethics and outcomes of HBO's series

» [Dr. Amy Boyle](#) (Australia)¹, Prof. Sue Turnbull (Australia)², Dr. Marion McCutcheon (Australia)³ (1. University of New South Wales, 2. University of Wollongong, 3. University of Canberra)

08:30

Panel : DID-3

DID - Digital Literacies and Ethical Engagement: From the Environment to Online Safety

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+36

Organised by: Dr. Maria Laura Ruiu (Panel Chair) (United Arab Emirates)

Decoding the Algorithmic Paradox Across Generations: A Study on Differentiation Mechanisms in Mediatized Environmental Activism

» [Dr. 怡箫李](#) (China)¹ (1. Beihang University)

How does family media ecology influence the digital literacy of Chinese urban and rural adolescents?

» [Dr. He Gou](#) (China)¹, Ms. Hanxi Zhang (China)¹ (1. xi'an Jiaotong University)

Digital Skills and Environmental Orientations: Exploring the Intersection of Digital Practices and Environmental Consciousness

» [Dr. Maria Laura Ruiu](#) (United Arab Emirates)¹, [Dr. Massimo Ragnedda](#) (United Arab Emirates)² (1. American University of Sharjah, 2. University of Sharjah)

Advancing Sustainable Healthcare: The Impact of Health Literacy on Digital Health Adoption pre and post-COVID in Portugal

» [Prof. Hernâni Oliveira](#) (Portugal)¹, Prof. Helena Lima (Portugal)² (1. University of Évora/CITCEM, 2. University of Porto/CITCEM)

Virtual Reality Empowers the Governance of Cyberbullying: Innovative Practices of Immersive Communication in Issues Concerning Minors

» [Ms. Shuailin Song](#) (China)¹ (1. Hunan University)

08:30

Panel : RUC-3

RUC - Perspectives on rural communication systems and services

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+37

Organised by: Dr. Rico Lie (Panel Chair) (Netherlands)

Role of rural communication services (RCS) in shaping farmers' climate risk perception and adaptation behavior in the face of online misinformation: A case study from a marginalized region of Pakistan

» [Dr. Nasir Khan](#) (Canada)¹, Dr. Ataharul Chowdhury (Canada)¹ (1. Univervsity of Guelph)

The Rural Communication Services landscape in Indonesia – where rural communities, government, NGOs, and private companies meet (or not)

» [Dr. Elske van de Fliert](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Queensland)

Internet Poverty Alleviation (IPA): A Model of Development Communication in Rural China

» [Mr. Gang Wang](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Indigenous Communication Systems in Service of Nature: The Case of Soche Hill Reforestation Campaign at Chitsa and Kumwima Villages, Malawi

» [Mr. Saizi Kimu](#) (South Africa)¹, Prof. Abiodun Salawu (South Africa)² (1. North-West University, 2. Akademia; North-West University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Research on the Landscape and Quality Efficiency of Agricultural Technology Dissemination in Agricultural Villages: A Case Study Based on W Village in China

» Prof. Huimin Pang (China)¹, Mr. Chaoning Zhang (China)², Ms. Jie Li (China)¹, Dr. Hongyan Liang (China)¹ (1. Shanxi university, 2. People's Daily Online Co., Ltd. Shanxi Branch)

08:30

Panel : MAR-2

MAR - Radio and podcast

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+25*

Organised by: Prof. Usha Raman (Panel Chair) (India)

Audio Knowledge: a critical review of the intersections between sound, media and information studies

» Prof. Gustavo Ferreira (Canada)¹ (1. University of Toronto)

Is radio killing the indie podcast star? Towards a media ecosystem study of the Australian podcasting market

» Dr. Dominic Knight (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Sydney)

Breaking the Sonic Ceiling? Black Women in South Africa's Podcasting Industry

» Prof. scheherazade safla (Qatar)¹ (1. Northwestern University in Qatar)

Radio discovery in smart speakers: the gatekeeping function of aggregators and voice platforms

» Prof. Ramon Lobato (Australia)¹, Ms. Adrienne Arnot-Bradshaw (Australia)² (1. Swinburne University, 2. RMIT University)

08:30

Panel : ICO-8

ICO - Reflecting on Inclusive Communication and Media

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+28*

Organised by: Dr. Ngozi Marion Emmanuel (Discussant, Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

From "Viewing" to "Inclusion": A Study on the Program Adaptation Mechanism and Audience Feedback of the First Barrier-Free Broadcast of the Spring Festival Gala

» Ms. 文颖梁 (China)¹, Ms. ali Mokou (China)¹ (1. Literature and Journalism and Communications at Sichuan University)

Radio as Care : A Case Study of Radio by Facility for Persons with Severe Physical and Mental Disabilities

» Dr. TOMOKO KANAYAMA (Japan)¹ (1. Institute of Advanced Media Arts and Sciences)

Use of digital media and subjective well-being of visually impaired people in China

» Prof. Qiaolei Jiang (China)¹, Ms. Yuexin Huang (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Digital Transformations: Opportunities and threats for PwDs' well-being in the Global South

» Dr. Dyah Pitaloka (Indonesia)¹, Dr. abdul rohman (Viet Nam)² (1. Monash University, 2. RMIT University)

Emotion and Imagination: How the Visually Impaired Are Seen -- Critical Discourse Analysis of Short Videos and Their Comments/Bullet Screens of Visually Impaired Bloggers

» Ms. Simin Zhu (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

10:30

Panel : MCR-1

MCR - The Environment through a Multimodal Lens

Venue - *WKWSC TV studio (floor space)*

Organised by: Dr. Sandra Ristovska (Panel Chair) (United States)

Title: Promotional Culture and the Silencing of Environmental Sustainability: A Multimodal Study of Public Relations in Cultural Events

» Dr. Mark Rasquinha (New Zealand)¹ (1. Auckland University of Technology)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Pen-and-paper games as platforms to create environmental texts

» Mx. Ahmed Hazyl Hilmy (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

Scenes of the election in Cuiabá: far right despises political debate on environmental destruction

» Dr. Pedro Oliveira (Brazil)¹ (1. Federal University of Mato Grosso)

People in a Small Park

» Ms. Xiangning Hong (China)¹, Mr. Ziyu Feng (China)² (1. Hong Kong Baptist University, 2. non)

Evoking Smell and Place Memories of IDP Cypriots Through Photography

» Ms. Gizem Canalp (Cyprus)¹, Ms. Aysu Arsoy (Cyprus)¹ (1. Eastern Mediterranean University)

10:30

Panel

Plenary / One Health in Action: Global Insights from Multisectoral Leaders

Venue - Lee Kong Chian LT (LKC-LT)

» Speakers: Terdsak Yono (Assistant Professor, Department of Food Animal Clinics, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Chiang Mai University), Kujtim Mersinaj (Researcher/ Lecturer, Veterinary Epidemiology and Bio-statistics, Agricultural University of Tirana; One Health Expert, South East European Centre for Disease Control IPH, Tirana Albania Southeast European Center for Surveillance and Control of Infectious Diseases (SECID), Tirana, Albania), Tan Sri Dr. Jemilah Mahmood (Professor and Executive Director, Sunway Centre for Planetary, Health Graduate Centre, Sunway University)

12:30

General

Lunch

Venue - GAIA, Level 1 Foyer

14:00

Panel : POP-13

POP - Fandom economies in platformed spaces

Venue - The Hive LHS-LT

Organised by: Dr. Bertha Chin (Singapore)

From K-pop Random Free Dancers to Affective laborers: The Transition of K-pop fans in W City Of China

» Ms. Fenglei Ding (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

Becoming "Taitai": Fan Labor, Platformization, and the digital economy of fandom in China

» Ms. Jiayi Wang (Canada)¹ (1. Simon Fraser University)

From Emotional Consumption to Discursive Practice: A Study of Digital Fan Culture in Weibo's "Unfollow-Retaliatio n Wallet-Saving Bot"

» Ms. ali Mokou (China)¹ (1. Literature and Journalism and Communications at Sichuan University)

Fangirls' Subcultural Capital: A Qualitative Analysis of Idol-Fans' Motivations for the Idol-Doll Production

» Ms. Zhenyu Zhang (United States)¹ (1. Penn State University)

Rethinking Collapsed Idols and Popular Culture in Contemporary China: A Psycho-political Perspective

» Prof. Changchang WU (China)¹, Prof. Miaoqing LIAO (China)² (1. school of communication, East China Normal University, 2. Shanghai Theatre Academy)

14:00

Panel : HEC-11

HEC - Health Communication for Seniors

Venue - WKWSC I L2 Executive Seminar Room

Organised by: Mr. Daniel Silvallana (Panel Chair) (Australia) and Dr. Mary Anne Taylor (Discussant) (United States)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Empowering Older Women: The Influence of Health Opinion Leadership on Information Behaviors on Social Media

» [Dr. Wenshu Li](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

Research on the Influence of short videos about Health on the Self: Health-Management Behaviors of Older-Adult Chronic-Disease Patients

» [Ms. Yilin Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Zhenghan Gao](#) (China)¹, Dr. Miao Yu (China)¹ (1. Qingdao University of Technology)

A Study on the Differentiated Health Practices of the Elderly in Elderly Care Institutions in China

» [Dr. Cao Ang](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Guofeng Zhang](#) (China)² (1. College of Humanities and Development Studies, China Agricultural University, 2. College of Humanities and Development, China Agricultural University)

Researching and communicating health and wellness: Evidence from four studies in the Philippines

» [Prof. Fernando Paragas](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Diliman)

Indian Audiences' Engagement with COVID-19 Content on YouTube

» [Ms. Nisha Rani](#) (India)¹, Dr. Usha Manchanda Rodrigues (Australia)², Dr. Padma Rani (India)¹ (1. Manipal Institute of Communication, 2. School of Information and Communication Studies, Charles Sturt University)

14:00

Panel : AUD-7

AUD - News Audiences

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+47*

Organised by: Dr. Miguel Vicente Marino (Panel Chair) (Spain)

Examining News Avoidance: Its Relationship with News Consumption, Influencing Factors, and Societal Implications

» [Prof. Jaemin Jung](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, Dr. Youngju Kim (Korea, Republic of)², Dr. Se-Uk Oh (Korea, Republic of)², Dr. Eunju Lee (Korea, Republic of)³, Dr. Youngju Jung (Korea, Republic of)⁴ (1. Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (KAIST), 2. Korea Press Foundation, 3. Sogang University, 4. Seoul National University)

Metrics and the Digital Newsroom of Bangladesh: An Ethnographic Study of Audience Data Usage

» [Mrs. Tahmina Haque](#) (Bangladesh)¹ (1. University of Dhaka)

Redditors' Perceptions of Negative TikTok Discourse in News and Online Forums: An Experimental Interview Study

» [Dr. Lok Fai Pun](#) (Hong Kong)¹, Mr. Jeremy Ko (Switzerland)², Prof. Anthony Fung (Hong Kong)³ (1. Chinese University of Hong Kong, 2. ETH Zurich, 3. The Chinese University of Hong Kong)

"Why the fuck is this in Spanish": English-language reactions to The New York Times posts in Spanish on X

» [Ms. Hana Park](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Asta Zelenkauskaite](#) (United States)¹ (1. Drexel University)

Media Imaginaries and Deep Stories: Exploring the Emotional Registers of News Engagement

» [Dr. Maria Bakardjieva](#) (Canada)¹, Mr. Jian Chung Lee (Canada)¹ (1. University of Calgary)

14:00

Panel : JRE-15

JRE - Fake News Across Borders: Lessons from Asian Countries Post-COVID-19

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+49*

Organised by: Prof. Edson Tandoc Jr. (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Singapore), Prof. Chei Sian Lee (Discussant) (Singapore), and Mr. Seth Seet (Convenor) (Singapore)

Confronting Misinformation in Hong Kong

» [Dr. Stephanie Jean Tsang](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Fake News in Taiwan: How People Authenticate Fact from Fiction

» Prof. Greg Sheen (Taiwan)¹ (1. Institute of Political Science, Academia Sinica)

Fake news as a social problem: Lessons from Singapore

» Mr. Seth Seet (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

Fake News in India: Superstitions, Myths, and Xenophobia

» Ms. Ritu Arya (India)¹, Prof. Rubal Kanozia (India)¹ (1. Central University of Punjab)

14:00

Panel : JRE-12

JRE - Journalism practice and social media

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+52

Organised by: Prof. Marcel Broersma (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Netherlands)

News sharing in location-based meso-news spaces: Understanding social norms and news-ness in WeChat neighborhood groups

» Ms. Yichen Zhao (Netherlands)¹, Prof. Marcel Broersma (Netherlands)¹, Dr. Qinfeng Zhu (Netherlands)¹ (1. University of Groningen)

Sustainable living on Xiaohongshu: An analysis of narrative themes and characteristics

» Ms. Chen Zhou (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

“Everything’s changed and nothing’s changed”: Emergency broadcasting, social media and reporting on extreme events

» Prof. Sora Park (Australia)¹, Dr. Janet Fulton (Australia)¹, Prof. Stuart Cunningham (Australia)¹, Dr. Kate Holland (Australia)¹, Prof. Kerry McCallum (Australia)¹, Ms. Susan Atkinson (Australia)¹ (1. University of Canberra)

Multimodal Sensationalism and Short-Video News Engagement: Insights from Douyin in China

» Ms. Zhuoyu Wang (China)¹, Prof. Lei Guo (China)¹, Ms. Ningjie Zhang (China)¹, Ms. WeiLin Li (China)² (1. Fudan University, 2. School of Journalism, Fudan University)

14:00

Panel : CPT-13

CPT - Users in focus: Weighing behaviour and attitudes in media governance and platform policies

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+53

Organised by: Dr. Leah Komen (Panel Chair) (Kenya)

Investigating Online News Diversities on WeChat: How are users experiencing news in a platform context?

» Dr. Xuanzi Xu (Australia)¹, Ms. Yiwen Wang (Australia)², Prof. Timothy Dwyer (Australia)³, Prof. Jonathon Hutchinson (Australia)² (1. The University of Sydney, 2. University of Sydney, 3. Charles Sturt University)

I know how it works: Exploring the impact of algorithmic media content awareness on the privacy calculus of self-disclosure

» Dr. Zhang Hao Goh (Singapore)¹, Prof. Gerard Goggin (Australia)², Dr. Kym Campbell (Singapore)¹ (1. Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University, 2. Western Sydney University)

Are All AI Applications Created Equal? Unpacking Public Attitudes Toward AI Policies in Taiwan

» Dr. Tsung-Ien Shih (Taiwan)¹, Ms. WEI-SHAN ZHENG (Taiwan)² (1. College of Communication, National Chengchi University, Taiwan, R.O.C., 2. Telecom Technology Center (TTC), Taiwan, R.O.C.)

Behaviorism Takes Command: A Study on A/B Testing and Experimental Culture in Big Internet Tech Companies

» Ms. Xia Yunxuan (China)¹ (1. Peking University School of New Media)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Characteristics and Regulations of Digital Identity Theft in the AI Era: A Grounded Theory Study of Rednote Micro-Influencers

» [Ms. Yichuan Wang](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Hanze Zhao](#) (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University, 2. Beijing Foreign Studies University)

14:00

Panel : CAM-9

CAM - Navigating Space and Place with Alternative/Subaltern Media

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+56*

Organised by: Prof. Susan Forde (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Heterotrophic Media: Survival Strategies of Latin American Chinese Language Media in Globalization

» [Dr. YAN XU](#) (China)¹ (1. Fudan University)

Boundaries Crossing and Reproduction: Mobility and Glocalization in Chinese Console Gaming Communities

» [Mr. George Ran Zhao](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

Alternative Media and Sense of Belonging: News Consumption and Trust among Multicultural Communities in Australia

» [Mrs. Shengnan Yao](#) (China)¹ (1. University of Canberra)

Amplifying Subaltern Voices in India: Indigenous Film Festivals as Community Platforms for Representation, Cultural Preservation, and Environmental Communication

» [Mr. Wrishav Roy](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Sudarshan Yadav](#) (India)¹ (1. Central University of Jharkhand)

"Her Space": Feminists' Online Community Interaction and Identity Self-Making——Take the Douban Group "Women in Law" as an Example

» [Ms. Junyi Yang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

14:00

Panel : GEN-20

GEN - Popular culture: Suicide, crime, and violence

Venue - *GAIA ABS-SR4*

Organised by: Dr. Beatriz Inzunza Acedo (Panel Chair) (Mexico) and Dr. Teng XU (Discussant) (China)

Suicidology and Narratives of Trans Annihilation

» [Ms. Viridian Sylvae](#) (Canada)¹ (1. McMaster University)

"Eco-Conscious Solitude: Lessons from Japan and the Philippines on Solo Living's Trade-offs for Indonesia—A Media Discourse Analysis"

» [Mrs. sylvia savitri](#) (Indonesia)¹ (1. President University)

Cartel Crew: Representación de la Mujer Latina en Crimen Organizado

» [Dr. Beatriz Inzunza Acedo](#) (Mexico)¹, [Dr. Lorena Rosalía Romero Domínguez](#) (Spain)² (1. Universidad de Monterrey, 2. Universidad de Sevilla)

Oppressive Bloodlust and Precarious Subjectivity: The Violent Visual Expression and Internal Conflict of the "Mad Woman" in Pearl, X, and MaXXXine

» [Dr. Teng XU](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Jia nan Zhao](#) (China)² (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 2. Donghua University)

Seeing Ourselves on TV: Scandal!, Gomora and Township Femininities

» [Ms. Tumi Mampane](#) (South Africa)¹ (1. University of the Free State)

14:00

Panel : GEN-21

GEN - Women's bodies, sexuality and reproductive health

Venue - *GAIA ABS-SR5*

Organised by: Dr. Ali Saha (Panel Chair) (Australia), Dr. Jingjun Wang (Panel Chair) (China), and Dr. Chaoyang Wang (Discussant) (Canada)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

When Benefits Surpass Costs: The Double-Edged Impact of Social Media Exposure on Chinese Women's Fertility Intentions

» Ms. Liwen Zhang (China)¹, Ms. Yu hang Chen (China)¹, Ms. Zhihan Zhou (China)¹, Ms. Yutong Yang (China)¹, Ms. Xinru Jiang (China)¹, Ms. Tong Sun (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Nanjing University)

Fertility Risk and Emotional Reflexivity: Exploring the Perceptions of Unmarried Women of Reproductive Age

» Dr. Jingjun Wang (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Information Communication, Huazhong University of Science and Technology)

Anxiety and Superstition: A Psychological Analysis of the "Receiving Good Pregnancy" Phenomenon in Chinese Digital Spaces

» Dr. Chaoyang Wang (China)¹, Dr. Huan Liu (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

14:00

Panel : ESR-15

ESR - Communicating Risk: Environment and Climate Change

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6

Organised by: Dr. Sibon Chen (Panel Chair) (Canada)

Young Internet Users' Perception of Environmental Issues: An Investigation Employing Think-Aloud Approach

» Ms. Yiqun Geng (China)¹, Ms. Shiyu Qin (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. Communication University of China, Beijing, China)

Risk Communication in Multi-Hazard Scenarios: A Public Communication Approach in a Sacrificial Zone

» Dr. Karla Palma (Chile)¹ (1. Universidad de Chile & CIGIDEN)

Risk Communication and Disaster Response Mechanisms during the Western Han Dynasty: A Study of the 132 BCE Yellow River Flood

» Prof. Runjue Wang (China)¹, Dr. Jiayin Liu (China)¹, Dr. Hanshuang Fu (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China, Beijing)

Fusing cultural knowledge into disaster risk communication: A co-creative storytelling approach with multicultural communities

» Dr. Jenny Zhengye Hou (Australia)¹ (1. Digital Media Research Centre, Queensland University of Technology)

14:00

Panel : ESR-20

ESR - Environmental Communication: Humans and Other Species Interactions

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7

Organised by: Dr. Claire Konkes (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Eliciting Empathy and Anticipated Guilt to Promote Pro-Environmental Actions: The Impact of Narrative and Psychological Distance in Stories about Climate-Change Impacts on Animals

» Dr. Zhuxuan Yan (China)¹, Dr. Laura Arpan (United States)², Dr. Arthur Raney (United States)² (1. Shanghai International Studies University, 2. University at Buffalo)

A Framing Study of the Animals at the Hong Kong Ocean Park and Zoological and Botanical Gardens: Challenging the Perception of Animals as Human Commodities?

» Dr. Minos-Athanasios Karyotakis (Hong Kong)¹, Mr. Filippos Pagonis Karyotakis (Greece)² (1. David C. Lam Institute for East-West Studies (LEWI), Hong Kong Baptist University, Kowloon Tong, Hong Kong, 2. independent researcher)

Bridging the gap: Zoological organizations' role in reducing psychologically distant environmental issues through social media

» Mr. Hunter Reeves (United States)¹, Dr. Tobias Hopp (United States)¹ (1. University of Colorado Boulder)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Social-Ecological Production Landscapes of Wildlife Conservation: Community Participation in the Conservation of Leopard Cats in Taiwan

» [Prof. Ming-Ying Lee](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. Providence University)

Environmental or Ecological Communication? Lessons (too late) from the Great Barrier Reef

» [Dr. Kerrie Foxwell Norton](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Griffith University)

14:00

Panel : GEN-5

GEN - Consumer relations, platform dynamics, and resilience

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: Dr. Joseph Nyanoti (Panel Chair) (Kenya) and Prof. Usha Raman (Discussant) (India)

Does Body Positivity Sell? Understanding Consumer Reactions Toward Body Positivity Campaigns on Social Media

» [Ms. Wenwen Cao](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Minnesota)

Gender-based Algorithmic Fairness: An Empirical Study about Computational Job Advertisements

» [Dr. Zhen-Zhen Wang](#) (China)¹ (1. Shenzhen University)

Gender (mis)representation in Kenyan media: A semiotic analysis of television commercials

» [Dr. Joseph Nyanoti](#) (Kenya)¹ (1. United States International University-Africa)

Gendered Digital Labor: Aspiration and Negotiation among Korean Fashion/Beauty Influencers

» [Ms. Sol Heo](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Seoul National University)

14:00

Panel : INC-8

INC - China's International Communication Strategies

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: Dr. Sudeshna Roy (Panel Chair) (United States)

Mapping Digital Norm Diffusion Networks: China's Three Global Initiatives on Social Media

» [Dr. Chang Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. 乾雯游](#) (China)², Ms. Han Zhao (China)², Ms. Huige Liang (China)², Ms. Min Liu (China)² (1. Communication University of China, Beijing, China, 2. State Key Laboratory of Media Convergence and Communication, Communication University of China)

Ten Years of Transformation: A Comparative Analysis of American News Coverage on China during Xi's Initial and Fifth US Visits

» [Dr. Xianwen Kuang](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Dr. Jesse Owen HEARNS-BRANAMAN](#) (China)² (1. Xi'an Jiaotong Liverpool University, 2. BNU-HKBU United International College, Zhuhai, China)

The role of training courses for journalists in China's cross-cultural communication efforts in Latin America

» [Dr. Pablo Morales](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. London School of Economics and Political Science)

Interrogating China Soft Power Through Its Foreign Media Policy: A Case of Kenya.

» [Ms. Macrina Musili](#) (Kenya)¹ (1. First author)

Proactive or reactive? A Comparative Study of the Coverage of BRICS in Indian and Chinese Media.

» [Dr. Anilesh Kumar](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Hao Sun](#) (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University-Hong Kong Baptist University United International College)

14:00

Panel : MPS-15

MPS - Boundaries of and threats to media institutions

Venue - WKWSC L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: Prof. Hyunjin Kang (Panel Chair) (Singapore)

Media Engagement and Public Discourse in Russia After 2022: Negotiating Boundaries and Strategies of Legal and Illegal Media Practices

» [Dr. Yulia Yurtaeva-Martens](#) (Germany)¹ (1. Freie Universität Berlin)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Enhancing Efficiency: Outcomes from a Sustained Involving Deliberative Experiment in a Local Broadcasting Service in Shanghai

» Prof. WENJING TAO (China)¹, Mr. Yuxuan LIU (China)¹ (1. Shanghai University)

Outsourcing Propaganda and Negotiating Boundaries: Journalists' Role in Managing Government Social Media in China

» Ms. Chunyan Huang (Macao)¹ (1. Department of Communication, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Macau)

Kargo Nyo 'To (This is Your Fault): Uncovering Constructs of Science and Governance in Facebook Comments on a Weather-related Issue

» Dr. Christine Anne Cox (Philippines)¹, Dr. Maria Angela Inez Ponce de Leon (Philippines)¹, Ms. Serena Vaswani (Philippines)¹ (1. Ateneo de Manila University)

14:00

Panel : POL-7

POL - Minsinformation Resources and Infrastructures

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

Organised by: Ms. Hanye Yang (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom) and Dr. Henri-Count Evans (Discussant) (Eswatini)

"Just Asking Questions": Doing Our Own Research on Conspiratorial Ideation by Generative AI Chatbots

» Prof. Axel Bruns (Australia)¹, Ms. Katherine FitzGerald (Australia)¹, Dr. Stephen Harrington (Australia)¹, Prof. Michelle Riedlinger (Australia)¹, Dr. Timothy Graham (Australia)¹, Prof. Daniel Angus (Australia)¹ (1. Queensland University of Technology)

Media regulation by judicial blockade in legislative deadlock: lessons from Musk's defeat and the return of X to Brazil in the political debate for free speech

» Dr. Ivan Paganotti (Brazil)¹ (1. Universidade Metodista de São Paulo)

raming "Lone Wolf Terrorism" in the Era of Information Governance: China Media Lessons from Singapore's Lianhe Zaobao

» Dr. Yan WANG (China)¹, Ms. Xiaoyang Lai (China)¹, Ms. Xiaozhen Jiang (China)¹, Ms. Yajing Zhu (China)¹, Prof. Penghwa Ang (Singapore)² (1. Zhejiang University of Technology, 2. National Technological University)

Balancing Between Ideals and Realities: Comparing Professional Roles of Fact-Checkers in Mainland China and Hong Kong

» Ms. Hanye Yang (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Loughborough University)

14:00

Panel : MPS-16

MPS - Constructing memories

Venue - WKWSCI L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: Prof. Susanne Eichner (Panel Chair) (Germany)

A form of remembrance based on collective action: "Re-archiving" as memory activism

» Mr. Zhekai Xie (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism & Communication, Jinan University)

"Memory" - A Feminist Concept of Public Discourse

» Dr. Leena Ripatti-Torniainen (Finland)¹ (1. Tampere University)

Why Does "Distant Suffering" Matter? The Discursive Construction and Tension of Memorial Space Meaning in the Process of Mediatization: A Case Study of the Shanghai Jewish Refugees Museum

» Dr. XUEYING WANG (China)¹, Dr. YEFU QIAN (China)² (1. Soochow University, 2. Shanghai Jiao Tong Univeristy)

"A Video Takes You Back to the Past": Prosthetic Memory, Public Discourse, and Digital Memory Ecologies in Chinese Nostalgic Videos

» Mr. Jiabao Wu (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

14:00

Panel : PSM-2

PSM - Climate Change, Environmental Justice, and Public Health: Public Service Media in Intersectional Contexts

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Prof. Maria Michalis (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Public Service Media and Environmental Justice: The Role of UK PSM in Environmental Sustainability

» [Prof. Maria Michalis](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Dr. Alessandro D'Arma](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Westminster)

Television, Governance and Climate Change

» [Dr. Elke Weissmann](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Edge Hill University)

Beyond margins and markets: Evaluating Doordarshan's strategic role in environmental justice amidst India's privatized media ecosystem

» [Dr. Madhavi Ravikumar](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Shuaib Shafi](#) (India)² (1. University of Hyderabad, 2. Gitam Univeristy, Hyderabad, India)

Public health, neoliberal discourses and gendered representations in Chinese public service media: Promoting sports for weight loss through multimodal strategies

» [Mr. Run Li](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Dr. Xiang Huang](#) (Macao)² (1. Lancaster University, 2. City University of Macau)

14:00

Panel : POE-8

POE - The Geopolitics of Regulating Digital Markets

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7

Organised by: Dr. Anis Rahman (Panel Chair) (United States)

State-Sponsored Mobile App Surveillance, 2014–2024: Motivations, Methods, and Privacy Implications in the Post-Snowden Era

» [Mr. Dien Luong](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Michigan)

Navigating Performing Rights in Music: Digital-Native Organizations, Changing Values, and Industry Shifts in the US and Beyond

» [Dr. Jim Rogers](#) (Ireland)¹, [Dr. Sergio Sparviero](#) (Austria)² (1. Dublin City University, 2. University of Salzburg)

Limits of policy responses for audiovisual industry in Europe's (digital) periphery

» [Dr. Jaka Primorac](#) (Croatia)¹ (1. Institute for Development and International Relations (IRMO))

The Geopolitics of Banning Chinese Apps in India

» [Dr. Anis Rahman](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Washington)

Shifting Giants: A political economic analysis of regulatory beneficiaries under Project 2025

» [Ms. Sydney Forde](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Abby Simmerman](#) (United States)¹ (1. Penn State University)

14:00

Panel : VIC-8

VIC - Marketing, Eco-Cinema, Nezha Films, Virtual Spaces, Study US and Iran

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 8

Organised by: Dr. Kristian Jeff Agustin (Panel Chair) (Philippines)

Adapting Jewelry Marketing to Modern Digital Platform: Strategies for Maintaining Brand Authenticity through Integrated Marketing Communications

» [Ms. Qinyi Du](#) (New Zealand)¹, [Mr. Zeshi Ni](#) (New Zealand)¹ (1. University of Auckland)

"Vibrant Matter" Network: Material Diffraction and Aesthetic Dimension of Ecological Imaging

» [Ms. 诺程](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Intertextuality and Societal Evolution: Resurgence of Collectivism in Postpandemic China Reflected in Ne Zha Films

» [Dr. Yuan Tian](#) (Macao)¹ (1. Macao Polytechnic University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

The Social Conceptual Motivation Behind the Transformation of Traditional Cultural Images: A Qualitative and Quantitative Study on the Evolution of the Nezha Image and the Interpretation of Social Concepts

» Ms. Ailang Li (China)¹, Mr. Du Chengze (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. Communication Unniversity of China)

Reimagining participation and photovoice in virtual spaces: comparative insights from ethnographic studies of Southeast Asian visual culture

» Dr. Kristian Jeff Agustin (Philippines)¹, Mr. Jules Philip Tillay (Philippines)¹ (1. De La Salle University)

Themes In Popular Coming-of-Age Films & TV Series: A Comparative Study of the US and Iran

» Mr. Amin Mobini (Iran, Islamic Republic of)¹, Dr. Lida Kavousi Kalashami (Iran, Islamic Republic of)¹ (1. Allameh Tabataba'i University)

14:00

Panel : ESN-3

ESN - Global Communication, Technologies and Theoretical Interventions

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: Dr. Wafa Khalfan (Panel Chair) (United Arab Emirates) and Dr. Ana Cristina Suzina (Discussant) (United Kingdom)

Exploring News Literacy Themes in the Philippines through a Scale Development Pilot Study

» Ms. Irish Jane Talusan (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines)

Representation of Africa and Africans in Chinese Audiovisual Media: A Study of Cinema and Video Platforms Content

» Mr. Kirill Kravtsov (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Peking University)

Uses of AI in news media: Mapping the emerging trends and anxieties in Indian newsrooms

» Dr. Shiv Gopal (India)¹, Dr. HARINATH KUMAR (India)¹, Dr. Ram Awatar Yadav (India)¹ (1. University of Allahabad)

Computer vision and visual Framing: the construction of Afghan women's images in global news coverage

» Ms. Yiru Shao (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

14:00

Panel : HIS-8

HIS - History Section Business Meeting

Venue - WKWSCI TR+7

Organised by: Prof. Nelson Ribeiro (Convenor) (Portugal) and Prof. Gideon Kouts (Convenor) (France)

14:00

Panel : ETH-5

ETH - Media Accountability and the Ethics of Self-Regulation in Latin America

Venue - WKWSCI TR+8

Organised by: Dr. Xavier Ramon (Panel Chair) (Spain), Dr. Elvira García (Discussant) (Spain), and Prof. Kanchan K. Malik (Discussant) (India)

Revamping the ombudsperson role: developments and best accountability practices to counter trust decline and news avoidance

» Dr. Xavier Ramon (Spain)¹ (1. Pompeu Fabra University)

Implementation of Ombudsmen's Office for Audiences in Argentina and Mexico: a social demand for the Right to Communication

» Dr. Fernando Oliveira Paulino (Brazil)¹, Dr. Rose Dayanne Santana Nogueira (Brazil)¹ (1. University of Brasilia)

Media Accountability in Chile: Key factors for understanding the limited presence of self-regulation

» Ms. Constanza Hormazabal (Chile)¹ (1. Universidad de los Andes, Chile)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Title: The Role of Self-Regulation in Chilean Media Outlets: A Content Analysis of Ethics Council Jurisprudence (1991–2025)

» Dr. María José Labrador (Chile)¹ (1. Facultad de Comunicaciones Universidad del Desarrollo (Chile))

14:00

Panel : CRI-3

CRI - Civil society and non-institutional actors in conflict and crisis

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+35*

Organised by: Dr. Virpi Salojärvi (Panel Chair) (Finland)

TikTok as a site of transnational political crisis: Brazilian and Venezuelan social media influencers "going political"

» Dr. Virpi Salojärvi (Finland)¹, Mrs. Nuppu Pelevina (Finland)¹ (1. University of Helsinki)

Ethnographic Diary Methods and the Security Needs of a Favela Mothers' Group

» Dr. Andrea Medrado (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Exeter)

Public stigma and prejudice toward minority groups amid the outbreak of COVID-19: A lesson learned from the effects of social media use

» Dr. Thao Nguyen (New Zealand)¹ (1. Massey University)

Global South and North Media Narratives in the "Chip War": Ideological Mechanisms and Discursive Strategies of Social Media Influencers

» Ms. Jiawen Zhou (China)¹, Mr. Zhaofeng Zhang (China)¹, Ms. Mile Shi (China)¹ (1. Shanghai International Studies University)

14:00

Panel : ISM-1

ISM - Media Activism, Social Cohesion, and Environmental Justice

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+36*

Organised by: Prof. Fatma Elzahraa Elsayed (Panel Chair) (Egypt) and Dr. Muhammed Jamiu Mustapha (Discussant) (Russian Federation)

Bridging Faith, Media, and Environmental Justice: The Role of Islamic Teachings and Media Narratives in Building a Sustainable Future

» Dr. Mahdi Yousefi (China)¹ (1. Hainan Normal University)

Reconstructing Environmental Justice Narratives from the Global South Perspective: A Critical Dialogue Based on CNN Arabic and Al Jazeera Climate Reports (2020-2024)

» Mr. Jian Song (China)¹ (1. Beijing Foreign Studies University)

Understanding the Role of Islamic Gatherings to Bring Social Cohesion in the Digital Age

» Dr. SOBIA ABID (Pakistan)¹, Dr. Muhammad Zahid Bilal (Pakistan)² (1. Department of Film and Broadcasting, University of the Punjab, 2. University of Okara)

Media Activism on Zakat for Women Victims of Violence in Indonesia

» Prof. ENI MARYANI (Indonesia)¹, Mrs. Kismiyati El karimah (Indonesia)¹, Mrs. Dyan Rahmiati (Indonesia)² (1. Universitas Padjadjaran, 2. Universitas Brawijaya)

Representation of Chinese Green Brands in Arab social media and Impacts on Arab Gen Z Youth

» Prof. Ke Guo (China)¹, Ms. Hui Zhou (China)¹ (1. Shanghai International Studies University (SISU))

14:00

Panel : RUC-4

RUC - Climate and environmental change

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+37*

Organised by: Dr. Sarah Cardey (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Communicating Environmental Justice through Community Online Radio in the Philippines: Insights from Radyo DZLB's "Para sa Agrikultura at Kalikasan" (For Agriculture and the Environment)

» Prof. Ryan Jay Galang (Philippines)¹, Mr. Christopher Calamlam (Philippines)² (1. Assistant Professor, University of the Philippines Los Baños, 2. University of the Philippines Los Baños)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Rural Climate Communication: 'Aram Thinai'- Communicating Climate Complexity through Podcast Narratives.

» [Dr. K Padmakumar](#) (India)¹ (1. Manipal Institute of Communication)

Nostalgia and Ecological Restoration: A Cultural Narrative Study in Rural Environmental Governance in China

» [Dr. Yue Wang](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Qianqian Li](#) (China)² (1. Beijing Institute of Graphic Communication, 2. Capital University of Economics and Business)

Strategizing Natural Dyes in Global Market: Economic Dynamics, Environmental Conservation, and Agricultural Sustainability of Langa Tenun Ikat from Flores Island

» [Dr. Muhammad Taufiq Al Makmun](#) (Indonesia)¹, [Dr. Rustina Untari](#) (Indonesia)², [Dr. Angelika Riyandari](#) (Indonesia)², [Dr. Johanna Debora Imelda](#) (Indonesia)³, [Prof. Radhika Gajjala](#) (United States)⁴, [Ms. Debipreeta Rahut](#) (United States)⁴ (1. Universitas Sebelas Maret, 2. Soegijapranata Catholic University, 3. Universitas Indonesia, 4. Bowling Green State University)

14:00

Panel : MAR-6

MAR - Music, Audio, Radio and Sound Working Group business meeting

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+25

Organised by: [Ignacio Gallego](#) (Convenor) (Spain) and [Prof. Mia Lindgren](#) (Convenor) (Australia)

14:00

Panel : ORG-6

ORG - Organisational Communication Working Group business meeting

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+26

Organised by: [Prof. Abena Yeboah-Banin](#) (Convenor) (Ghana), [Prof. Gisela Goncalves](#) (Convenor) (Portugal), and [Dr. Shehram Mokhtar](#) (Convenor) (Qatar)

14:00

Panel : ICO-9

ICO - Inclusive communication and People with Disabilities Working Group business meeting

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+28

Organised by: [Mr. Yuqiao Yan](#) (Convenor) (China)

14:00

Panel : SPS-2

SPS - Partner Session / IAMCR Task Force for GAMAG

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+27

Organised by: [Prof. Claudia Padovani](#) (Panel Chair) (Italy), [Prof. Lisa French](#) (Panel Chair) (Australia), [Dr. Maria Soledad Vargas](#) (Discussant) (Chile), and [Dr. Mark Poole](#) (Discussant) (Australia)

Women and the Media: highlighting a future agenda for the post-Beijing Platform for Action +30

16:00

Panel : JRE-19

JRE - Journalism Research and Education Section business meeting

Venue - The Hive LHS-LT

Organised by: [Sadia Jamil](#) (Convenor) (China), [Prof. Abiodun Salawu](#) (Convenor) (South Africa), and [Prof. Ruhan Zhao](#) (Convenor) (China)

16:00

Panel : MPS-14

MPS - Mediated Communication, Public Opinion and Society Section business meeting

Venue - WKWSC L2 Executive Seminar Room

Organised by: [Prof. Susanne Eichner](#) (Germany)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

16:00

Panel : AUD-10

AUD - Livestreaming and gaming audiences

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+47*

Organised by: Dr. Rafal Zaborowski (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Invisible Technical Flaws in Virtual Idol Live Streaming: A Fan Experience Perspective and Insights from RI-CLPM

» [Ms. Hanrong Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Can Sha](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Youran Huang](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Qilin Huang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Qizhen Yue](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Huijuan Chen](#) (China)¹ (1. Nanjing University)

Platformized Audiencing of C-dramas in the Streaming Era

» [Ms. Gina Junhan Fu](#) (Singapore)¹, [Ms. Huiyi Wang](#) (China)² (1. National University of Singapore, 2. Renmin University of China)

From Fulfilling Needs to Expressing Authenticity: A Study on the Emotional Relationship Between Virtual Streamers and Their Audiences

» [Ms. ShuQi Peng](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China (CUC))

The Moderating Role of Culture in Video Games: How Nationalism Influences Player-Avatar Identification

» [Ms. Chenchen Zou](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Yilan Guo](#) (United States)¹ (1. Penn State University)

More Interactive, More Aggressive? A Meta-Analysis of Interactive Game Mechanics and Youth Aggression

» [Ms. Danping Wu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Jingjing Li](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Jun Yan](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Manli Wu](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Information Communication, Huazhong University of Science and Technology)

16:00

Panel : POP-15

POP - Collisions and coalescences between fans and their communities

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+49*

Organised by: Prof. Yongliang Gao (Panel Chair) (China)

"Go Read Your Novel": Fan Discourse Conflicts and Discursive Actions in Chinese Xianxia's Transmedia Storytelling on Bilibili

» [Dr. YEFU QIAN](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Li Yuyan](#) (China)¹ (1. Shanghai Jiao Tong Univeristy)

My Dearest Fu Bao: panda fandom and the culture of cute

» [Dr. Bertha Chin](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

Reconstructing the Boundaries of Justice: Power Topology, Digital Ecology, and Critical Experimentation in China's Fandom Governance

» [Mr. Yaoyu Li](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Lidingna Ma](#) (China)² (1. PhD candidate at the School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China, 2. PhD candidate at the School of Journalism and Communication, Nanjing University)

Affective circulation: disease de-stigmatization through fan activism and fans' dual identities

» [Mr. Yabo Tang](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Melbourne)

Entertainment Becomes an Amplifier? The Roles of Transnational/regional Celebrities and Fans in Dual Nationalist Propaganda Networks in China

» [Ms. Ge Zhu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Tianyi Yang](#) (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China, 2. University of Massachusetts Amherst)

16:00

Panel : POP-19

POP - Digital geographies and online temporalities

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+52*

Organised by: Prof. David Myles (Panel Chair) (Canada)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

The New York Times is a Gaming Company: Imperialism, Shaping Reality, and capitalising on the engagement economy.

» [Dr. Aditya Deshbandhu](#) (United Kingdom)¹, Prof. Usha Raman (India)² (1. University of Exeter, 2. University of Hyderabad)

TikTok Refugees and Content Transfer - Grassroots movement under platform imperialism

» [Dr. Chunmeizi Su](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. XU CHEN](#) (China)² (1. University of Sydney, 2. Xiamen University)

Fan Practices in the Platformized Era: How Platforms and Algorithms Intensify Fan Engagement

» [Ms. HYE YEON SEO](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Simon Fraser University)

Platform Affordances and Culture Hybridisation: The Migration of TikTok Refugees to Xiaohongshu

» [Ms. qiyao yu](#) (China)¹ (1. King's College London)

Capturing the Ephemeral: A methodological reflection on the ethics of studying influencer Instagram Stories

» [Ms. Anuja Premika](#) (India)¹ (1. University of Hyderabad)

16:00

Panel : CPT-14

CPT - Digital governance in East Asia: Streaming, AI and autonomous vehicles

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+53

Organised by: [Dr. Julia Pohle](#) (Panel Chair) (Germany)

The Draft Regulations Governing Internet Audiovisual Services in Taiwan: Challenges, Gaps, and Responses from Streaming Platform Entrepreneurs and Audiovisual Professionals

» [Dr. Wan-Shin CHEN](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. independent researcher)

Artificial Intelligence, Platform Ecosystem, and Regulatory complexity in China's Digital Publishing Industry

» [Dr. Xiang Ren](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Sydney)

Artificial Intelligence Uncertainty and Algorithmic Bias in the Recommendation of Autonomous Taxi Videos on the Douyin Platform

» [Dr. Luchuan Zheng](#) (China)¹ (1. Shanghai University)

Parallel Deplatformization in China: Implicit Governance of UGC Platforms through MCN Role Shifts

» [Ms. huailin mu](#) (China)¹ (1. Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University)

16:00

Panel : SPS-10

SPS - Articulating the Urban and Communication: A tribute to Gary Gumpert

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+56

Organised by: Peter Haratonik (Discussant), Prof. Nico Carpentier (Panel Chair) (Czechia), Prof. Cees Hamelink (Discussant) (Netherlands), and Myria Georgiou (Discussant) (United Kingdom)

16:00

Panel : GEN-22

GEN - Mental and sexual health, ethics and inclusivity

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR4

Organised by: [Dr. Yosra Jarrar](#) (Panel Chair) (United Arab Emirates) and [Dr. Rafael Ventura](#) (Discussant) (Spain)

Navigating the Ethics of Hymenoplasty: Doctors' Perspectives on Cultural, Social, and Medical Dilemmas

» [Ms. Simran Gambhir](#) (India)¹ (1. Indraprastha Institute of Information Technology Delhi (IIIT-Delhi))

Reframing Toxic Masculinity on TikTok: Gender Norms, Mental Health, and Counter-Narratives in Online Discourse.

» [Dr. Yosra Jarrar](#) (United Arab Emirates)¹, [Ms. Lujain Ammar](#) (United Arab Emirates)¹, [Dr. Gabriel Nweke](#) (Türkiye)² (1. American University in Dubai, 2. Girne American University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

The influence of social media on sexual health among LGBTQ+ youth
The influence of social media on sexual health among LGBTQ+ youth

» [Dr. Rafael Ventura](#) (Spain)¹, [Dr. Olatz Larrea](#) (Spain)² (1. Universitat de Lleida, 2. Universitat de Barcelona)

Balancing health through re-domestication of algorithms: a qualitative study of female digital laborers in China

» [Prof. Zhang Lin](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Shanghai University)

Advancing gender-sensitive Health Communication Research: A framework of gender inclusivity and diversity in the research process

» [Prof. Anna Wagner](#) (Netherlands)¹, [Prof. Doreen Reifegerste](#) (Germany)² (1. Radboud University, 2. Bielefeld University)

16:00

Panel : GEN-26

GEN - Gender marginalisation and climate justice, from scientists to parliamentarians

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5

Organised by: [Dr. Christy Mady](#) (Panel Chair) (Lebanon) and [Ms. Kayonaaz Kalyanwala](#) (Discussant) (United Kingdom)

Reclaiming the Voices of Women Communication Researchers in Ibero-America: A Proposal for Epistemic Justice

» [Dr. Iuan-Jose Sanchez-Soriano](#) (Spain)¹, [Dr. Leonarda Garcia-Jimenez](#) (Spain)², [Prof. Miquel Rodrigo-Alsina](#) (Spain)³ (1. Rey Juan Carlos University, 2. University of Murcia, 3. Pompeu Fabra University)

Marginalized Voices and Environmental Justice: The Role of Female Scientists in Global Environmental Crisis Communication

» [Ms. Xuanxuan Wu](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Inside out or outside in: Articulating female experiences of climate change as independent women filmmakers

» [Mr. Sabyesachi Bharti](#) (India)¹, [Prof. GAURI DURGA CHAKRABORTY](#) (India)² (1. CMS VATAVARAN, 2. Times School of Media, Bennett University)

Voicing Environmental Justice in Lebanon: Investigating how a Female Parliamentarian Willed the Environment into the Country's Official and Unofficial Agendas

» [Dr. Christy Mady](#) (Lebanon)¹, [Dr. Jessica El-Khoury](#) (Lebanon)¹ (1. Notre Dame University - Louaize)

16:00

Panel : ESR-25

ESR - Environment, Science and Risk Communication Section business meeting

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6

Organised by: [Dr. Kerrie Foxwell Norton](#) (Convenor) (Australia), [Dr. Maitreyee Mishra](#) (Convenor) (India), [Pieter Maesele](#) (Convenor) (Belgium), and [Dr. Joana Diaz Pont](#) (Convenor) (Spain)

16:00

Panel : GEN-16

GEN - Optimistic Fantasies: Motherhood, and fatherhood conversations with the teenage son

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7

Organised by: [Dr. Julienne Thesa Baldo-Cubelo](#) (Panel Chair) (Philippines), [Prof. ENI MARYANI](#) (Discussant) (Indonesia), and [Dr. Zhijuan Chen](#) (Discussant) (China)

Why Mothers are Less Enthusiastic About Breastfeeding than the Experts in China: Evidence from the Social Media Platform Zhihu

» [Prof. GEGE FANG](#) (China)¹, [Ms. ZHIYUN CHEN](#) (China)², [Prof. LANSHAN ZHANG](#) (China)¹ (1. Beijing University of Posts and Telecommunications, 2. Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

Mothering Always On: Childcare through CCTV Cameras among Chinese Urban Working Mothers

» [Ms. Zhidan Bai](#) (China)¹ (1. Shaanxi Normal University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

“Bai lan” parenting or not “bai lan”? A case study of the topic # “Bai lan” parenting on Douyin

» Dr. Zhijuan Chen (China)¹, Ms. Litang Fu (China)² (1. Communication University of China (CUC), 2. Communication University of China)

Fathering in the Age of Domsday and Unlimited Energy: Father-Teenage Son Conversations Surrounding Social Media Content About the Future

» Dr. Julienne Thesa Baldo-Cubelo (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines)

Can Gen Z Women Be Happy Moms? Optimistic Fantasies on Xiaohongshu and the Cruel Realities of Motherhood

» Ms. XU YAN (China)¹ (1. jinan)

16:00

Panel : PCR-4

PCR - Environmental narratives, self- presentation and local participation

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: Dr. Valentina Baú (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Australia)

Tourism as a Medium: A Cultural Narrative Study on the Dissemination of Environmental Justice through Tourism Activities

» Dr. Fang Wen (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China, Nanjing)

Strengthening participatory communication through Applied Cultural Studies in South African public-private-community tourism

» Prof. Lauren Dyll (South Africa)¹, Prof. Keyan Tomaselli (South Africa)² (1. University of KwaZulu-Natal, 2. University of Johannesburg)

Ecological Imagination: The Dissemination of Hmong Creation Myths and Residents’ Environmental Willingness

» Ms. Yuhan Xu (China)¹, Ms. Siyu Huang (China)² (1. School of Television, Communication University of China, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University, Wuhan, China)

Place-making weaves community solidarity: a case of “Guozhuang” square dance among urban Tibetan immigrants

» Ms. Siyu Peng (China)¹, Ms. Yuqi Cui (China)², Ms. Jing Liu (China)³ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Nanjing University, 2. Wuhan University, School of Journalism and Communication, 3. journalism and information communication school, Huazhong University of Science and Technology)

16:00

Panel : INC-9

INC - Digital Platforms, Cultural Adaptation and Identity Formation

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: Dr. Misook Lee (Panel Chair) (Japan)

Towards a Cultural Understanding of Platform Migration: Exploring the Cultural-Embedded Migration Model through TikTok-to-Rednote Migration

» Dr. Chang Zhang (China)¹, Ms. Ran Si (China)², Ms. Wenjing Qian (China)², Ms. Fu Jiayi (China)² (1. Communication University of China, Beijing, China, 2. Communication University of China (CUC))

The Entanglement of Automation and De-Automation in Platform Expansion: Ethnographic Insights on Bigo Live’s Expansion in Australia

» Ms. Yiran Liu (China)¹, Dr. Tingting Liu (Australia)² (1. Jinan University, 2. University of Technology Sydney)

Mobile phone app uses, IT identity, and adaptation of non-local students in Hong Kong and the UK

» Dr. Vincent Huang (Hong Kong)¹, Mr. Fei Vincent Mo (Austria)² (1. Hong Kong Baptist University, 2. Central European University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Rebuilding Environmental Justice through Transnational Community Empowerment: A Social Media Content Analysis of Greater Los Angeles Wildfires on Xiaohongshu (RedNote)

» Ms. Haiwei (Valerie) Huang (United States)¹, Ms. Lijun Luo (China)² (1. University of Southern California, 2. Beijing Normal University & Hong Kong Baptist University United International College)

Multicultural Significance of the Three Lamps Public Space: A Field Study of the Southeast/South Asian Laborers Intercultural Co-creation of Identity

» Mr. Chenghan Zhou (United States)¹, Ms. Rui Jiang (United Kingdom)², Ms. Zihan Wang (United Kingdom)³, Ms. Xixi Sun (United Kingdom)⁴ (1. Marquette University, 2. the University of Manchester, 3. University of Leeds, 4. Kings College London)

16:00

Panel : HEC-14

HEC - People, Media and behavior dynamics

Venue - WKWSC L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: Dr. EMMANUEL ESSEL (Panel Chair) (South Africa) and Dr. Jarim Kim (Discussant) (Korea, Republic of)

Can Music Listening History Predict Depression? A Study on Correlates of Depressive Posts on NetEase Cloud Music

» Mr. Yening Jia (China)¹, Dr. Lili Shang (China)¹, Ms. Yiran Fan (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

An explorative study to understand the communication strategies implemented by Community Health Workers (CHWs) during COVID 19.

» Ms. Gouri Chandana R.G (India)¹, Dr. Raof Mir (India)², Mr. Anurag Dwivedi (India)² (1. Alliance University, 2. Assistant Professor)

The Effects of Message Types on HPV Vaccination-Related Behaviors among Women in 20s in South Korea: Focusing on the Inoculation Theory

» Prof. Yungwook Kim (Korea, Republic of)¹, Mrs. Hyejung Kim (Korea, Republic of)¹, Ms. Damyi So (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. School of Communication and Media, Ewha Womans University)

Hallucination vs. Taste: The Cultural Struggle of Mushroom Poisoning Prevention Communication in Yunnan

» Dr. JIE YIN (China)¹ (1. Nanjing Normal University)

Study of the Media Construction of "Health" Discourse in the New Era — A Critical Discourse Analysis Based on People's Daily

» Ms. Litong Zhao (China)¹ (1. School of Television, Communication University of China)

16:00

Panel : POL-9

POL - Digital Cultures Between Connection and Conflict: Memes, Podcasts, and Algorithmic Divide

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

Organised by: Dr. Ratan Kumar Roy (Discussant) (Bangladesh) and Mr. Tengda Zhong (Panel Chair) (China)

Cross-border Cultural Politics and Communication in India and Bangladesh: Interplay of Humours and Rumours in the Digital Age

» Dr. Ratan Kumar Roy (Bangladesh)¹, Ms. Preeeksha Malhotra (India)² (1. Department of Sociology, South Asian University, 2. Independent researcher)

From Press Rooms to Podcast Kingdoms: Political Authority and Parasocial Power in Contemporary Media

» Ms. Lea Redfern (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Sydney)

Examining the Effect of IP Location Display on Cross-cutting and Like-minded Discussions

» Ms. Jinqiu Chen (China)¹, Mr. Yuchen Zhou (Hong Kong)², Dr. Chuanli Xia (Australia)³ (1. Guangdong ATV College of Performing Arts, 2. School of Communication, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong, 3. University of Newcastle)

Humorous Political Irony: The Cross-cultural Communication and Interaction of "Spy" Meme on the rednote Platform

» Ms. Jinxin Zhu (China)¹, Prof. Hao Gao (China)¹ (1. Nanjing Normal University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

When Serendipity Fuels Debate: Dual-Path Interaction Effects of Political Knowledge, Intolerance of Uncertainty and Relative Deprivation Between Incidental News Exposure and Political Discussion

» Mr. Zhirui Chen (China)¹, Mr. Tengda Zhong (China)¹, Mr. Xinpeng Gao (China)¹, Ms. Liyue Zhao (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

16:00

Panel : HEC-13

HEC - Policy and Practical issues in Telehealth

Venue - WKWSCI L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: Mr. Zhichao (Jacob) Lei (Panel Chair) (Korea, Republic of) and Prof. ELIZA GOVENDER (Discussant) (South Africa)

Enhancing Well-Being Through Telehealth: The Roles of Patient-Provider Communication and Health Efficacy

» Ms. Qianfeng LU (Switzerland)¹ (1. Università della Svizzera Italiana)

Technological Discipline and User Empowerment in Health Communication: An Empirical Study of Algorithmic Recommendations and Content Moderation in the "ED Girls" Community on Xiaohongshu Platform

» Mr. Hongsheng Zhao (China)¹, Ms. Yixuan Liu (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Understanding eHealth Literacy in Four Asian Countries: Exploring Its Measurement Properties and Effect on Vaccine Hesitancy

» Prof. May O. Lwin (Singapore)¹, Prof. Peter J. Schulz (Singapore)², Dr. Shelly Malik (Singapore)³, Mr. Yumin Lin (Singapore)¹, Prof. Sierin Lim (Singapore)² (1. Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University, 2. Nanyang Technological University, 3. Lee Kong Chian School of Medicine, Nanyang Technological University)

Competence or Warmth? Impact of Health Chatbots Attribute Selection Preferences on Patients' Health Adherence Intentions

» Dr. xiqian zou (China)¹, Mr. Xiang Ou (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Nanning Normal University)

Evolving Public Attitudes Toward the HPV Vaccine on Social Media: A Fine-Grained Emotion Analysis of Sina Weibo (2016 vs. 2024)

» Dr. Bowen Shi (China)¹, Ms. Weiyu Lu (China)², Dr. Junran Wu (China)³, Ms. Ying Hao (China)², Ms. Zhongyu Guo (China)², Ms. Keyi Wang (China)² (1. Communication University of China (CUC), 2. Communication University of China, 3. Beihang University)

16:00

Panel : PSM-3

PSM - Public Service Media Governance and its Challenges

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Prof. Paulo Faustino (Portugal)

Ten Faces for Public Service Media Governance: An Exploratory Model Based on a Pilot Empirical Study

» Prof. Paulo Faustino (Portugal)¹ (1. CITCEM | Faculty of Arts and Humanities of the University of Porto)

Are we suddenly cried out for saving Taiwan public service media? A challenge to or affirmation with de-colonialization behind historical drama

» Dr. Hamilton Cheng (Taiwan)¹ (1. Taiwan Public Television Service Foundation)

Dive into the organization: Bringing ATI/FOI request to public service media research

» Mr. Yujia Cheng (Hong Kong)¹ (1. School of Communication, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong)

16:00

Panel : POE-9

POE - Colonialism and globalism: Cases from Africa, Asia, and the Middle East

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7

Organised by: Dr. Tewodros Workneh (Panel Chair) (United States)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Media's Imagination of the Global South from the Global South's Perspective: Chinese Media's Conceptualisation of the Global South

» [Dr. Taeyoung Kim](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Loughborough University)

Recuperating the 'Global Polycrisis' Concept

» [Prof. Wayne Hope](#) (New Zealand)¹ (1. Auckland University of Technology)

Struggles from Below: the Making of the New World Information and Communication Order

» [Prof. Shinloun Yeo](#) (United States)¹ (1. Queens College, CUNY)

Imperial Competition, Infrastructural Contestations, and Environmental Entanglements: A Brief History of a Cable Station in Iraq?

» [Dr. Sebastian Rose](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Dr. Burçe Celik](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. Loughborough University)

Digital Sovereignty or Colonial Discourse? An Examination of Western Human Rights Organizations' Framing of Internet Shutdowns in Sub-Saharan Africa

» [Dr. Tewodros Workneh](#) (United States)¹ (1. Kent State University)

16:00

Panel : VIC-9

VIC -Cinema, Photojournalism & Visual Culture Activities

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 8

Organised by: [Dr. Denize Araujo](#) (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Brazil) and [Prof. Govind Ji Pandey](#) (Convenor) (India)

Cinematic Manuality: Pre-Cinema History as the History of Material Image

» [Prof. Tianle Huang](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Yu Yang](#) (China)² (1. Communication University of China, 2. Peking University & Yale University)

Regime change and Visual Culture. The role of photojournalism in post-Revolutionary Portugal

» [Prof. Carla Baptista](#) (Portugal)¹, [Prof. Jacinto Godinho](#) (Portugal)² (1. Associate Professor, ICNOVA FCSH, 2. CICANT - Lusofona University)

The Second Time Rooted: A Material Representation of Urban Migrants via Chinese Feature Film

» [Ms. Yilin Shi](#) (Malaysia)¹, [Dr. Nurzihan Hassim](#) (Malaysia)¹, [Dr. Shamsiah Kadir](#) (Malaysia)¹, [Mr. YANG ZHOU](#) (Malaysia)¹ (1. Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia)

16:00

Panel : ESN-CPT-

ESN - CPT - Joint Session: Critical Perspectives on Policy, Technology, and ICT Infrastructures

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: [Dr. Wafa Khalfan](#) (Panel Chair) (United Arab Emirates) and [Dr. Leah Komen](#) (Discussant) (Kenya)

Can Chatbots Become Opinion Leaders in Human-Computer Communities? Investigating the Impact on Group Emotion and Individual Decision-Making

» [Dr. Zehang Xie](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Hui Hui](#) (China)² (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 2. School of Artificial Intelligence, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

AN ANALYSIS OF POLICY PROVISIONS FOR DATA INTEROPERABILITY IN THE KENYA HEALTH SECTOR

» [Dr. Jeremiah Nganda](#) (Kenya)¹ (1. Initiative to Develop African Research Leaders (IDeAL))

Dependency Road? "African Agency" in Kenya's Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Policies

» [Mr. Gang Wang](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Evolution and development of digital public spheres and deliberative spaces: Socio-Technological Affordances in Reddit's r/ChangeMyView

» [Ms. Saloni Meghnani](#) (Netherlands)¹, [Dr. Roberto Spiezio](#) (Taiwan)² (1. Jan Van Eyck Academie, 2. Ming Chuan University)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

16:00

Panel : HIS-6

HIS - Media, Memory and Archaeology

Venue - WKWSCI TR+7

Organised by: Prof. Gideon Kouts (Panel Chair) (France)

Media discourse on scientific knowledge: the atomic bomb in Portuguese media - uncertainty or the lack of

» Ms. Inês Fernandes (Portugal)¹ (1. Universidade Católica Portuguesa, UCP-FCH / CECC)

Activism(s) as echoes from the past: press as a battlefield for the dual discourse around vaccines

» Prof. Helena Lima (Portugal)¹, Prof. Hernâni Oliveira (Portugal)² (1. University of Porto/CITCEM, 2. University of Évora)

Has Collective Memory Come to an End? — The Dual Narratives and Collaborative Practices of Digital Memory of the Korean War

» Dr. Sheng Wang (China)¹, Mr. Jiale Yang (China)² (1. journalism and information communication school, Huazhong University of Science and Technology, 2. School of Humanities, Zhejiang University of Technology)

Memory Revival or Perceptual Illusion? Public Cultural Identity Deviation and Pathways of Reformation in AI-restored Historical Photos

» Ms. Jing Wan (China)¹, Prof. Xiaoyue Ma (China)², Prof. Yang Liu (China)³ (1. School of Journalism and New Media, Xi'an Jiaotong University, 2. School of Journalism and New Media, Xi'an Jiaotong University, 3. School of Management, Xi'an Jiaotong University)

Soundscapes of Division: A Media Archaeology of the Jinmen-Xiamen Radio War (1950-1992)

» Mr. Lin Hanxun (China)¹ (1. Minzu university of china)

16:00

Panel : MCS-8

MCS - Media, Communication and Sport section business meeting

Venue - WKWSCI TR+8

Organised by: Dr. Xavier Ramon (Convenor) (Spain) and Dr. Peter English (Convenor) (Australia)

16:00

Panel : POP-16

POP - Activism, social engagement and contemporary pop culture

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+35

Organised by: Prof. Frederik Dhaenens (Panel Chair) (Belgium)

"Her flaws are the same as my flaws": Fan engagement with the Sad Girl archetype in contemporary television

» Ms. Lisa Cooper (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Adelaide)

"Chinese-style Heroism" in Film and Television Adaptations of Contemporary Literature

» Dr. Song Meiqi (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Peking University)

Changing the world one post at a time: Digital activism in student/ campus life TV series

» Mrs. Victoria Balan (Netherlands)¹, Dr. Delia Dumitrica (Netherlands)¹ (1. Erasmus University Rotterdam)

Neo-global Popular Culture and Local Values: Negotiating Youth Identity Through Chinese Rap Shows

» Dr. Jingwei (Amy) Piao (China)¹, Ms. Weishan Xing (China)¹ (1. Xiamen University of Technology)

16:00

Panel : RUC-8

FAO/ IAMCR Rural Communication Services Awards and book launch

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+37

Organised by: Dr. Rico Lie (Panel Chair) (Netherlands) and Mr. Mario Acunzo (Panel Chair) (Italy)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Book Launch "Collaborative Change – Towards Inclusive Rural Communication Services"

» Dr. Rico Lie (Netherlands)¹, Mr. Mario Acunzo (Italy)², Dr. Sarah Cardey (United Kingdom)³, Dr. Elske van de Fliert (Australia)⁴, Dr. Maria Stella C. Tirol (Philippines)⁵, Dr. Loes Witteveen (Netherlands)⁶, Mr. Paoloregel Samonte (Italy)² (1. Knowledge, Technology & Innovation (KTI). Wageningen University & Research, 2. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), 3. University of Reading, 4. The University of Queensland, 5. University of the Philippines Los Baños, 6. (1) Knowledge, Technology & Innovation (KTI). Wageningen University & Research; (2) Communication, Participation & Social Ecological Learning (CoPSEL). Van Hall Larenstein University of Applied Sciences)

DEVELOPING A NATIONAL STRATEGY FOR ENABLING, SHAPING, AND SEEDING MEANINGFUL COMMUNITY-CENTERED CONNECTIVITY IN RURAL INDONESIA

» Dr. Subekti Priyadharma (Indonesia)¹, Mr. Rudi Hartanto (Indonesia)², Mr. Donny Utoyo (Indonesia)³, Dr. Devie Rahmawati (Indonesia)⁴, Ms. Dita Rachmawati (Indonesia)⁵, Mr. Indriyatno Banyumurti (Indonesia)⁶, Mr. Gustaff Iskandar (Indonesia)⁷, Mrs. Tisha Anwar (Indonesia)⁷, Mr. Akhmat Safrudin (Indonesia)⁸, Mr. Elanto Wijoyono (Indonesia)⁹, Mr. Savero Dwipayana (Indonesia)¹⁰ (1. Universitas Padjadjaran, 2. Center for Communication, Media and Culture, and Information System, 3. IPB University, 4. Universitas Indonesia, 5. Pratisara Bumi Foundation, 6. ICT Watch, 7. Common Room Networks Foundation, 8. Perkumpulan AirPutih, 9. Combine Resource Institution, 10. Portal Kesehatan Masyarakat (Portkesmas))

ICTs, Community Empowerment and the Politics of Inclusion and Exclusion in Rural Bangladesh

» Prof. Mohammad Sahid Ullah (Bangladesh)¹ (1. University of Chittagong)

The Impact of Trust in Information Source on Farmers' Intentions to Adopt Agricultural Technologies: An Empirical Study from Inner Mongolia, China

» Prof. Li Zhang (China)¹, Mr. Zongyi Huo (China)¹, Ms. Yu Su (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

16:00

Panel : CPN-4

CPN - Whose Story? Framing Power and Resistance in Global Contexts

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+25*

Organised by: Dr. Katja Lehtisaari (Finland)

Russian media at two extremes: How Russian state-controlled and independent television framed terrorism within an increasingly repressive media landscape

» Mrs. Nicole Marie Klevanskaya (United States)¹ (1. University of Minnesota)

How to capture even social media? - Hostile Narratives in Pro-Government Political Influencer Videos During the 2024 Hungarian Elections

» Ms. Kata Horváth (Hungary)¹ (1. Universidade Católica Portuguesa, UCP-FCH / CECC; Mérték Média Monitor)

Rethinking media democratisation at critical junctures: The framing of Chinese mining impacts on digital platforms and public media in post-2017 Zimbabwe

» Dr. Musara Lubombo (South Africa)¹ (1. University of KwaZulu-Natal, North-West University)

Mitigated Scepticism as a Dispositional Affect: An Exploration of Nigerian Elites' Discourses on China's Soft Power and Sino-African Engagements

» Dr. MISTURA ADEBUSOLA SALAUDEEN (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

Powering a Movement through Protest Writing: Examining Online Slogans Used by Kenyan Gen Zs to Protest Excessive Taxation

» Dr. Dorothy Njoroge (Kenya)¹ (1. United States International University-Africa)

16:00

Panel : LAW-3

LAW - Protecting Rights against

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+26*

Organised by: Dr. Fernando Gutiérrez (Panel Chair) (Chile)

Continued from **Wednesday, 16 July**

Protecting Free Speech and Democracy: A Need for A New Framework for Assessing Social Media Speech

» [Dr. Chris Demaske](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Washington Tacoma)

Reviving and Reconceptualizing the Neutral Reportage Privilege

» [Dr. Erik Uglund](#) (United States)¹ (1. Marquette University)

How different models of media regulation influence approaches to social inequality: A comparative qualitative analysis of key legal texts from Germany and the UK

» [Dr. Anke Fiedler](#) (Germany)¹, Prof. James Morrison (United Kingdom)² (1. Universität Greifswald, 2. University of Stirling)

Analysis of disinformation in the general elections of governors and mayors (October, 2024) in Chile

» [Dr. María José Labrador](#) (Chile)¹, [Dr. Pedro Anguita](#) (Chile)² (1. Facultad de Comunicaciones Universidad del Desarrollo, 2. Universidad de los Andes, Chile)

16:00

Panel : DIM-4

DIM - From Silence to Strategy: Diasporic Responses to Displacement, Discrimination, and Digital Platforms

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+28

Organised by: Dr. Sumana Chattopadhyay (Panel Chair) (United States)

Borderless voices: Journalism and the reconfiguration of symbolic borders from exile

» [Dr. Ayesha Jehangir](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of New South Wales)

"Digital Activism and Knowledge Production in Italy's Diasporic Communities: a case study on the Black Lives Matter movement in Italy"

» [Dr. Nathasha Fernando](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Westminster)

WeChat, the Chinese Diaspora, and Black Lives Matter: A Transnational Perspective on Digital Media

» [Ms. Manging Ye](#) (China)¹ (1. Independent researcher)

Wavering between silence and resistance: Chinese diasporas' conflicted responses to racial discrimination in the United Kingdom

» [Dr. Haili Li](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Exeter)

16:00

Panel : MCR-3

MCR - Multimodal Communication Research Working Group business meeting

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+27

Organised by: Ms. Aysu Arsoy (Convenor) (Türkiye), Dr. Pedro Oliveira (Convenor) (Brazil), and Dr. Sandra Ristovska (Convenor) (United States)

Thursday, 17 July

08:30

Panel : POP-17

POP - Assembling games, gaming and gamers in contemporary China

Venue - The Hive LHS-LT

Organised by: Dr. Aditya Deshbandhu (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Defense for Capitalized Female Gaze: Power Dynamics Between Chinese Otome Game Producers and Fans

» [Ms. Wanyue Zhang](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology)

Continued from Thursday, 17 July

Writing Love Beyond Borders: A Transcultural Study of Intimacy, Romantic Fantasies, and Self-Expression in Fanfiction of Chinese Otome Game

» Ms. Xinye Yang (China)¹, Ms. Xi Wang (China)², Ms. Yizhe Cui (China)³, Ms. Xiaoxi Zhou (China)⁴ (1. Independent researcher, 2. The Chinese University of Hong Kong, 3. University of Nottingham, Ningbo, China, 4. Fudan University)

Coding Romance: the Technological Affordance of Intimacy in Otome Games

» Ms. JINGRU YANG (China)¹ (1. 1148945581@QQ.COM)

From 'Domineering CEO' to 'Emotional Plushie': Multidimensional Gaze and Dependent Masculinity in Romance Video Games

» Mr. Yanghaibo Liu (China)¹, Ms. Xiaoyou Qin (China)², Ms. Zhouyi YAO (China)³ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Shandong University, 2. Zhejiang University, College of Media and International Culture, Hangzhou, China, 3. Fudan University)

Digital Games as Popular Culture: Cross-Culture Fan identity and National Image in Black Myth: wukong

» Mr. Zihe Hao (China)¹, Prof. Rong Han (China)¹ (1. Northwestern Polytechnical University)

08:30

Panel : HEC-12

HEC - Unleashing the Power of Old and New Media

Venue - WKWSC L2 Executive Seminar Room

Organised by: Mr. Daniel Silvallana (Panel Chair) (Australia) and Dr. EMMANUEL ESSEL (Discussant) (South Africa)

Applying Interactive Media Design to Promote Intentions to Seek Professional Help for Depression: Extending the TIME from a Narrative Perspective

» Ms. Yijing Li (China)¹, Ms. Xiubin Duan (Macao)¹, Mr. Yuxuan Wang (China)¹, Ms. Siyu Xu (China)¹ (1. Faculty of Humanities and Arts, Macau University of Science and Technology)

Spanish newspapers' coverage of mental health on Twitter (2015-2022): Analysis of sentiment and language used

» Dr. Sergio Arce Garcia (Spain)¹, Dr. Jesús Díaz-Campo (Spain)¹ (1. Universidad Internacional de La Rioja)

How does internet usage impact fertility intentions of individuals in reproductive age? Evidence from cross-sectional and longitudinal study

» Dr. Yi Tao (China)¹, Prof. Yang Chen (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

The Effect of Health Tips in Online Video Games from the Perspective of Psychological Reactance Theory -- A Case Study of Health Tips in MOBA Game "Honor of Kings"

» Mr. Jiachen Lyu (Australia)¹ (1. University of Melbourne)

Ideal Health News Reporting from the UAE Journalists and Opinion Leaders' Perspective

» Dr. Nassir Bouali (United Arab Emirates)¹, Prof. Serra Gorpe (United Arab Emirates)¹, Prof. Jairo Alfonso Lugo-Ocando (United Arab Emirates)¹, Dr. Emeyeonu Chinyeaka Ogadimma (United Arab Emirates)¹, Dr. Muhammad Awais (United Arab Emirates)¹, Prof. Erkan Yuksel (Türkiye)² (1. University of Sharjah, 2. Anadolu University)

08:30

Panel : AUD-13

AUD - Generational audiences

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+47

Organised by: Dr. Miguel Vicente Marino (Panel Chair) (Spain)

Socially enhancing or compensating? A study of the impact of digital media use on offline social participation among diverse older adults

» Ms. Geng Wang (China)¹ (1. Liaoning University)

Spatiotemporal Reshaping: A Study of Curated Self-Presentation among Chinese Youth

» Ms. Chaojing Huang (China)¹, Prof. Jinxia Shen (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China (CUC))

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Creeping counter-revolution? Young adults and information and film on the air/online. Ways of consuming television information and feature films made available by television broadcasters online, based on the example of Poland in 2025.

» [Dr. Monika Koźdoń-Debecka](#) (Poland)¹, [Dr. Anita Zawisza](#) (Poland)¹ (1. Faculty of Journalism, Information and Book Studies, University of Warsaw)

Invisible young people: How absent voices contribute to a biased perspective

» [Dr. Maria José Brites](#) (Portugal)¹, [Dr. Teresa Sofia Castro](#) (Portugal)¹, [Ms. Margarida Maneta](#) (Portugal)¹ (1. CICANT - Lusófona University)

08:30

Panel : JRE-17

JRE - Journalists' perceptions of pressures and safety in Asian countries

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+49

Organised by: [Dr. Beate Josephi](#) (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Australia)

The Dynamics of Media Capture and Journalistic Resilience under Rapid Autocratization: The Hong Kong Experience

» [Prof. Francis Lee](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Chinese University of Hong Kong)

Journalists' perceptions of pressures and safety in Uzbekistan

» [Dr. Beate Josephi](#) (Australia)¹, [Mr. Berdak Bayimbetov](#) (Kazakhstan)², [Dr. Mukarram Otamurodova](#) (Uzbekistan)³ (1. The University of Sydney, 2. SDU University, 3. Journalism and Mass Communications University of Uzbekistan)

Bhutan's journalists' perceived pressures: What difference does a decade make?

» [Dr. Buntly Avieson](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Beate Josephi](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Sydney)

From low wages to disinformation: The evolving threats facing Filipino journalists

» [Prof. Edson Tandoc Jr.](#) (Singapore)¹, [Ms. Sofia Tan](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

Journalists in India: Precarious Pressures, But Mostly Safe and Unstressed

» [Prof. Iyotika Ramaprasad](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Manasvi Maheshwari](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Ambrish Saxena](#) (India)² (1. University of Miami, 2. South Asian University)

08:30

Panel : JRE-18

JRE - Journalism research from diverse perspectives

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+52

Organised by: [Dr. Diana Bossio](#) (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Ethnographic Methodologies for understanding young people's news consumption.

» [Dr. Diana Bossio](#) (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University)

Expanding our REACH: a new project seeking to elevate and promote diverse voices as news sources

» [Dr. Glynn Greensmith](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Curtin University)

"Hewers of wood and drawers of water" power dynamics in transnational collaborative investigative journalism practices

» [Prof. allen munoriyarwa](#) (South Africa)¹ (1. Walter Sisulu University)

The motivations of audiences to seek any journalism

» [Mr. David Gilchrist](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Queensland)

Epistemología feminista y periodismo. Pensar la sociología de la producción de noticias desde la teoría de género

» [Dr. Cosette Celecia Pérez](#) (Mexico)¹, [Dr. Abel Somohano](#) (Mexico)¹ (1. Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Hidalgo)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

08:30

Panel : CPT-5

CPT - Generative AI Governance: Institutions, Imaginaries, Innovations

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+53*

Organised by: Ms. Joanne Kuai (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Australia) and Prof. Haiqing Yu (Discussant) (Australia)

Innovation vs Imagination in GenAI: A Comparative Patent Analysis of China, Europe, and the United States

» [Dr. Yuner ZHU](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Dr. Xinzhi Zhang](#) (Hong Kong)², [Prof. Bu Zhong](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University, 2. City University of Hong Kong)

Assembling Generative Artificial Intelligence: Mapping Policy Evolution and Governance

» [Dr. Chao Su](#) (United States)¹ (1. Boston University)

Strikes and unrest in Hollywood media industry: bringing workers into the debate over GAI regulation and governance

» [Mr. ANDRE ROCHA](#) (Brazil)¹ (1. DigiLabour research lab)

Preemptive Dispositif: Data Annotation, Security, and the Territorialisation of Generative AI in China

» [Dr. PENGFEI FU](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Jian Lin](#) (Hong Kong)² (1. Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 2. Chinese University of Hong Kong)

08:30

Panel : CAM-10

CAM - Pedagogy, Literacy and Community Communication

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+56*

Organised by: Dr. Andrew Ó Baoill (Panel Chair) (Ireland)

Communication management in public health: An educational and communication model for the inclusion of Venezuelan migrants in Colombia

» [Dr. Sergio Alvarado Vivas](#) (Colombia)¹, [Ms. Laura Martínez](#) (Colombia)¹, [Mr. Jonnathan Pinto](#) (Colombia)¹ (1. Corporación Universitaria Minuto de Dios - UNIMINUTO)

The creation of a subaltern public sphere on the boundaries of journalism by marginalised students in a small South African city

» [Dr. Andre Gouws](#) (South Africa)¹ (1. Akademia; North-West University)

UNDERSTANDING NATURE AND TERRITORY TO MAKE THE PLANET SUSTAINABLE TODAY

» [Dr. Amparo Cadavid](#) (Colombia)¹ (1. Corporación Universitaria Minuto de Dios - UNIMINUTO)

Let environmental journalism be seen: The professional training and development of professionalism of agricultural Journalists in Taiwan.

» [Dr. Shih-Hsien Hsu](#) (Taiwan)¹, [Ms. Tsai-Hsuan Lin](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. Department of Bio-Industry Communication and Development, National Taiwan University)

Formally illiterate but digitally literate: A case study of Rohingya Activists

» [Mr. MD Tareq Hossain](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. PhD Candidate: Cultural Studies in Asia Program, National University of Singapore)

08:30

Panel : GEN-24

GEN - Postfeminism, Femvertising and marketing

Venue - *GAIA ABS-SR4*

Organised by: [Dr. 冯 Ran 冉 Feng](#) (Panel Chair) (China) and [Dr. Saima Shahid](#) (Discussant) (Pakistan)

Entangled Interpretation of the Impact of Femvertising in China: A Perspective on Corporate Social Responsibility

» [Dr. 冯 Ran 冉 Feng](#) (China)¹ (1. City University of Macau)

My baby has no gender: A study of gender performance in cotton doll parenting

» [Ms. Shuxin Mo](#) (China)¹ (1. Department of Humanities and Law, Huazhong Agricultural University)

Reforming the normative structure of a South-Asian patriarchal society; a postcolonial-feminist study of femvertising in Pakistan

» [Dr. Saima Shahid](#) (Pakistan)¹ (1. Independent Researcher)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Art, identity and empowerment: Emirati women reshaping modern art perception in UAE

» [Mrs. Faiza Rafique](#) (United Arab Emirates)¹ (1. Canadian University in Dubai)

08:30

Panel : GEN-25

GEN - LGTQ+, sexual identities' activisms, research and pleasure

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5

Organised by: Dr. Benjamin DETENBER (Panel Chair) (Singapore), Dr. Ma. Rosel San Pascual (Panel Chair) (Philippines), and Dr. Maria Soto-Sanfiel (Discussant) (Singapore)

Understanding the Fuzzy Reception of Gay Characters in Spanish Television

» [Ms. Gina Junhan Fu](#) (Singapore)¹, [Dr. María Soto-Sanfiel](#) (Singapore)¹, [Dr. Juan-José Sánchez-Soriano](#) (Spain)² (1. National University of Singapore, 2. Rey Juan Carlos University)

Between subversion and slippery: the dynamic gender boundaries of cross-dressing performances on Douyin in contemporary China

» [Mr. Ren Jianzheng](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Qishen Chen](#) (China)² (1. Jinan University, 2. Shenzhen University)

Normalizing Queerness Online: Social Media Participation and Social Representation of Singaporean Gay People

» [Mr. Langcheng Zhang](#) (Singapore)¹, [Dr. Benjamin DETENBER](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

Digital pakikipagkapwa through social media messages: The case of LGBTQIA+ organizations' fight for SOGIE Equality

» [Dr. Ma. Rosel San Pascual](#) (Philippines)¹, [Dr. Jonalou Labor](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Diliman)

08:30

Panel : ESR-21

ESR - Visual and/or Creative Communication for Environment and Climate Change Challenges 2

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6

Organised by: Dr. Miki Kawabata (Panel Chair) (Japan)

The Current State of Environmental Communication through Social Media Platforms: A Case Study of Capturing Invasive Alien Species YouTube Channels in Japan

» [Dr. Naoyuki Ohara](#) (Japan)¹, [Dr. Kentaro Nagai](#) (Japan)² (1. Graduate School of Environmental Science, Hokkaido University, 2. Department of Information and Management, Tokyo Online University)

Leveraging Augmented Reality for Fostering Environmental (In)Justice Awareness

» [Dr. Ching-Hua Chuan](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Wan-Hsiu Tsai](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Xueer Xia](#) (United States)² (1. University of Miami, 2. University of Florida)

Digital Activism, Social Media and Policy Advocacy: A Study of #DelhiAirPollution Campaign on Twitter (X)

» [Mr. Anshul Chauhan](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Dheeraj Kumar](#) (India)² (1. PhD Scholar, Mizoram University, 2. Assistant Professor, Mizoram University)

Cultural Narratives of Resilience in Climate Change Discourse on YouTube

» [Dr. Delaney Harness](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Aasita Bali](#) (India)², [Dr. Nancy Jennings](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Cincinnati, 2. Christ University)

Cross-cultural comparison of visual framing in natural disaster coverage

» [Dr. Miki Kawabata](#) (Japan)¹ (1. Mejiro University)

08:30

Panel : ESR-22

ESR - Environmental activism and public engagement

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7

Organised by: Dr. Kerrie Foxwell Norton (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Amplifying Diverse Stories of Environmental Youth Activism in Indonesia

» Mr. Detta Rahmawan (Indonesia)¹, Mr. Justito Adiprasetyo (Indonesia)¹, Mr. Kunto Adi Wibowo (Indonesia)¹ (1. Universitas Padjadjaran)

“To Run or Not to Run?” How People React to AI Disaster Alerts When AI Makes a Mistake in Emergency Response

» Dr. Lola Xie (Hong Kong)¹, Ms. April Wanhui Zhou (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

“Solastalgia”: Surviving (dis)placed Sinking Village

» Mr. Iven Sumardiyantoro (Indonesia)¹, Mr. Puji Rianto (Indonesia)¹ (1. Department of Communication, Universitas Islam Indonesia)

Designing an AI Chatbot for Social Change: Quotidian Civic Tech and Environmental Advocacy in China

» Dr. Vincent Guangsheng Huang (China)¹, Dr. Lin Yuan (China)², Dr. Da Mao (China)³ (1. Zhejiang University, 2. Independent Organizational Researcher and Consultant of WD, 3. Chair of the Board and Strategy Director of WD)

08:30

Panel : GEN-29

GEN - Creative Confrontations: Centering Trans-Asian Sex Work Activism

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: Dr. Eunbi Lee (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Singapore), Dr. Sharmila Parmanand (Convenor, Discussant) (United Kingdom), Ms. Chihiro Toya (Discussant, Panel Chair) (United Kingdom), Ms. Vanessa Ho (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Singapore), and Ms. Raksha Mahtani (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Singapore)

Dismantling manufactured consent: Writings from Singapore about, around, and against the stigmatisation of sex work

» Ms. Raksha Mahtani (Singapore)¹, Ms. Vanessa Ho (Singapore)¹, Mx. nor NA (Singapore)¹ (1. Project X)

The possibilities and impossibilities of participatory research: reflections from a co-filmmaking project with Japanese sex worker activists

» Ms. Chihiro Toya (United Kingdom)¹ (1. SOAS University of London)

The politics of knowledge production in sex work research: lessons from a collaborative project with the Philippine Sex Workers Collective

» Dr. Sharmila Parmanand (United Kingdom)¹ (1. The London School of Economics and Political Science)

I Am Not a Feminist”: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Korean Sex Workers’ Perspectives on Feminism

» Dr. Eunbi Lee (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

When Female’s Invisible Predicament Is Seen: LDA and Sentiment Analysis of Online Discussion About Female Shame on Xiaohongshu

» Ms. Gao Ya jie (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University)

08:30

Panel : INC-6

INC - Media Systems and International Perspectives

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: Dr. Melanie Radue (Panel Chair) (Germany)

The System That Never Was: Theoretical Contradictions in Hallin and Mancini’s Media Systems Framework

» Mr. Jan Miessler (Czechia)¹ (1. Charles University Prague)

Expressing Community: Global Nationality in International Communication

» Mr. Guolin Shen (China)¹, Mr. Xiaolei ZHANG (China)¹ (1. Fudan University)

Equality and Globality of Global Communication on Twitter: 2012-2022

» Mr. Zeyu Zhu (United States)¹ (1. Yale University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Splitting Waves: Comparative Analysis of Polarised Discourses in Malaysian and German Political Communication Networks

» [Dr. Melanie Radue](#) (Germany)¹, [Mrs. Gayathry Venkiteswaran](#) (Malaysia)² (1. Universität Passau, 2. University of Nottingham, Malaysia)

Between Centripetal and Centrifugal: Factors that Influence the Dynamics of Moral Circles Across Eras and Cultures

» [Ms. Yiming LIU](#) (China)¹ (1. Fudan University)

08:30

Panel : MPS-17

MPS - How emotions and media content influence user behaviour

Venue - WKWSCI L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: Prof. Ya Yang (Panel Chair) (China)

“Icing on the Cake”: How Emotional Contagion Affects the Interaction Willingness of Social Media Users

» [Mr. zilun wang](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Shaoqiang Liu](#) (Hong Kong)² (1. +86 18211075219, 2. +852 59575659)

Orchestration of Contesting Emotions: A Discourse Analysis of Public Discussion on Technological Expectations of Artificial Intelligence in China’s Social Media

» [Dr. Zifan Man](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Fudan University)

Why do we choose different algorithmic resistance strategies? Algorithmic resistance driven by power perception

» [Ms. Tianqin Cui](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China (CUC))

The Spiral of Anger: Public Emotion Evolution in Reversed News from a Mediatization Perspective

» [Ms. XiaoLu Ji](#) (China)¹ (1. 重庆大学)

08:30

Panel : POL-12

POL - Artificial Intelligence’s Effect on Political Communication

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

Organised by: Prof. Philippe J. Maarek (Convenor, Panel Chair) (France)

Mapping Sociotechnical Imaginaries in Global AI Governance: A thematic analysis of AI regulations among 13 countries

» [Ms. Zhe Li](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Deqiang Ji](#) (China)¹, Mr. Lin Sun (China)¹, Mr. Haodong She (China)², Mr. Yiwei Li (China)³ (1. Communication University of China, Beijing, China, 2. China Media Group, Beijing,, 3. Communication University of China, Beijing)

Favela Activism in Brazil and Grassroots Inputs to AI Governance from the Margins

» [Dr. Andrea Medrado](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Exeter)

The Impact of Social Media on Political Communication in Morocco: Perspectives and Challenges in the Era of Globalized AI

» [Ms. KENZA Benmoussa](#) (France)¹, Prof. Philippe J. Maarek (France)², Prof. Nicolas Pelissier (France)¹ (1. University Côte d’Azur, 2. University Paris East - UPEC)

Intersections in Campaign Technologies: AI and Media Empowerment in Japanese Elections in 2024

» [Prof. Leslie Tkach-Kawasaki](#) (Japan)¹ (1. University of Tsukuba)

08:30

Panel : MCS-6

MCS - New developments in gender, communication, and sport research

Venue - WKWSCI L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: Dr. Kulveen Trehan (Panel Chair) (India) and Dr. Xavier Ramon (Panel Chair) (Spain)

“My love is not a crime”: How do Chinese female table tennis fans negotiate the legitimacy of their identity?

» [Ms. Yuda Cheng](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Humility over visibility: 'Feeling' representation through photo-elicitation with sportswomen in Kerala, India

» [Ms. Amritha Mohan](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Monash University Australia)

Negotiating Gender Identity in Competitive Gaming: Female Players' Resistance Against Gender Stereotypes in Shooter Esports

» Ms. Ying Liu (China)¹, [Ms. Qimin Zhang](#) (China)² (1. Communication University of Shanxi, 2. The London School of Economics and Political Science)

The Generation Mechanism and Structural Critique of Gender Bias in Chinese Sports Fandom

» [Ms. Lin Luo](#) (China)¹ (1. Shandong University)

Framing Women's Cricket in India : Perceptions of Indian Women's U-19 T20 World Cup 2025 Campaign on Social Media

» [Dr. Kulveen Trehan](#) (India)¹ (1. University School of Mass Communication , Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University , New Delhi)

08:30

Panel : GMP-2

GMP - Hardware Afterlives: Value, Materials, and Governance in Electronics Reuse

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Dr. Dang Nguyen (Convenor) (Australia), Prof. Melissa Gregg (Convenor) (United Kingdom), Prof. Rahul Mukherjee (Convenor) (United States), Prof. Ramon Lobato (Convenor) (Australia), Prof. Claudia Padovani (Panel Chair) (Italy), and Prof. Gerard Goggin (Discussant) (Australia)

Introduction: Centering Reuser Experience

» [Prof. Melissa Gregg](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Bristol)

Second Hand Smartphones in India: Perspectives of Users, Repair Persons, and Distributors.

» [Prof. Rahul Mukherjee](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Pennsylvania)

The Afterlife of Smartphones: Phone Farms in Southeast Asia

» [Dr. Dang Nguyen](#) (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University)

Governing TV hardware in Australia: spectrum management, access, and e-waste

» [Prof. Ramon Lobato](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Swinburne University)

08:30

Panel : POE-10

POE - Gender and race in capitalism

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7

Organised by: Dr. Deya Xu (Panel Chair) (China)

Beyond Viral-Hit Music: Female Music Performers and Song-Centred Production in China's Platformised Music Industry

» [Ms. Yuan Yao](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Leeds)

"It's becoming increasingly difficult to undermine the foundations of capitalism": The Practice of Consuming True-Fake "Original Orders" Fashion Items in China

» [Dr. Deya Xu](#) (China)¹, Dr. Tingting Liu (Australia)² (1. School of Communication, East China Normal University, 2. University of Technology Sydney)

Reproduction of Daily Life, Capitalist Accumulation and Gendered Precarity: Exploring the Linkage Through Unorganised Women Workers' Organisation of Resistance

» [Ms. Anila Backer A.P](#) (India)¹ (1. PhD Scholar)

Feminist-Consumer Movement Against Misogyny on Digital Media Platforms

» [Dr. Hoyoung Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Yonsei University)

Labour, Gender, and Resistance: Female Domestic Migrant Workers in Lebanon Amid Ongoing Crisis

» [Ms. Ekaterina Letunovskaya](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Simon Fraser University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

08:30 **Panel : ESN-GEN-**
ESN - GEN - Joint Session: Feminist Resistance, Media, and Control
Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4
 Organised by: Dr. Jeremiah Nganda (Panel Chair) (Kenya) and Dr. Ambrish Saxena (Discussant) (India)

Podcasting as micro-resistance: how feminists in China reclaim self-agency and care

» [Ms. Yijia Gu](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Deakin University)

The Authentic Self in Aging? Middle-Aged Women's Self-Presentation on Social Media

» [Ms. Jinyi Zang](#) (Macao)¹ (1. Faculty of Humanities and Arts, Macau University of Science and Technology)

Protecting or Controlling the girls in online spaces? Understanding surveillance of digital interactions of young rural Indian girls by Community members

» [Ms. Sanju Kumawat](#) (India)¹ (1. Central University of Punjab)

Imagined Fences: Gendered Strategies and Algorithmic Negotiation on RedNote

» [Ms. Yue Qin](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Ms. Xiaoyi Liu](#) (Ireland)² (1. University of the Arts London, 2. University College Dublin)

Gender Fluidity and Cross-Dressing in Chinese Lolita Subcultural Practice

» [Dr. Jiayixiu Zhao](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Dr. Yimei Zhu](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. School of Arts, Media and Communication, University of Leicester)

08:30 **Panel : MPA-3**
MPA - Behind the Scenes and Between the Lines: Production Cultures in Global Media Context
Venue - WKWSCI TR+7
 Organised by: Dr. Concha Edo (Panel Chair) (Spain)

Geopolitics and place-making in transnational media production – The case of Sino-Singapore collaborations

» [Dr. Siao Yuong Fong](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. King's College London)

Appendage or Co-Creation? The Role of 'Creators' and Human-AI Collaboration in AIGC Video Production

» [Dr. guo jing](#) (China)¹ (1. The School of Journalism and Communication, Jinan University)

Defaced Treasure: A Comparative Analysis of News Frames in Philippine Coverage of the Chocolate Hills Controversy

» [Prof. Annie Fe Perez-Gallardo](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Cebu)

Agenda Setters or Agenda Senders? The Expected Role of Global South Journalists in The Changing Tide of Global Climate Communication.

» [Mr. Hafiz Muhammad Tahir Idrees](#) (Australia)¹ (1. Deakin University)

08:30 **Panel : ETH-6**
ETH - Between Researcher and Researched: Reflexivity and Intersubjectivity in Communication Research

Venue - WKWSCI TR+8

Organised by: Ms. Thu Luong Le (Convenor) (Australia), Ms. Swastika Samanta (Convenor) (Australia), and Dr. Pradip Thomas (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Employing reflexivity to address ethical dilemmas in qualitative research: Insights from Vietnam

» [Ms. Thu Luong Le](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Queensland)

'Why do you need to talk to me?': Ethics of communicating research goals to women participants in rural India

» [Ms. Debjani Chakraborty](#) (India)¹, [Ms. Chhavi Garg](#) (India)¹ (1. Central University of Punjab)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

08:30

Panel : ISM-2

ISM - Sociopolitical Representations of Islam and Muslims

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+35*

Organised by: Prof. Ke Guo (Panel Chair) (China), Prof. ENI MARYANI (Discussant) (Indonesia), and Dr. SOBIA ABID (Discussant) (Pakistan)

What is the image of China in the news media of Islamic countries: Empirical study based on mainstream media in Iran, Saudi Arabia, and Pakistan

» Mr. Donglin He (China)¹, Ms. Huan Zhao (China)¹ (1. Dongbei University of Finance and Economics)

Framing Al-Assad Ousted and Al-Sharaa Presidency in the Egyptian Media

» Prof. Fatma Elzahraa Elsayed (Egypt)¹ (1. Arab Academy for Science, Technology, and Maritime Transport)

"Put words in Chinese Muslim's mouth": Media presentation on Youtube of the daily life in Xinjiang

» Ms. Weiru Cheng (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

Creating a Sustainable Information Ecosystem Using Proposed Islamic Perspectives-Driven Framework

» Dr. Muhammed Jamiu Mustapha (Russian Federation)¹, Mr. Mutiu Iyanda Lasisi (Russian Federation)² (1. RUDN University, 2. HSE University)

'Eco Masjid' and the Ecological Movement: Building Islam-based Environmental Awareness

» Mrs. Fatma Nuraini Zahra (Indonesia)¹ (1. Department of Communication Universitas Islam Indonesia)

08:30

Panel : DID-4

DID - Algorithmic Justice and Data Citizenship

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+36*

Organised by: Dr. Bhanu Bhakta Acharya (Panel Chair) (Canada)

Data Citizenship: Learning to challenge Big-Tech

» Dr. Elinor Carmi (United Kingdom)¹ (1. City St. George's, University of London)

Making a connection: A comparative analysis of broadband regulation structure and its impacts on speed in OECD nations

» Ms. Abby Simmerman (United States)¹ (1. Penn State University)

DIGITAL INCLUSION FOR DEMOCRACY AND ENVIRONMENTAL ADVOCACY

» Mr. Satish Radhakrishnan (India)¹, Dr. Dinesh Kumar I (India)¹, Dr. Lavanya Rajendran (India)¹, Mrs. Lakshmi Devi G (India)¹ (1. Anna University)

From Digital Divide to "Drone Divide": A Reflection of the 2024 Twitter Chinese Drone Account "Global Link"

» Prof. Jack Liu (China)¹, Ms. Siyu Jia (China)¹ (1. Guangdong University of Foreign Studies)

08:30

Panel : RUC-6

RUC - Communication and community cohesion

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+37*

Organised by: Dr. Loes Witteveen (Panel Chair) (Netherlands)

Communicable Rural Towns and the Reproduction of Rural Social Relations: A Case Study from Shanxiang Rural Town, Jiangxi Province, China

» Mr. Xiang yang XU (China)¹ (1. Shenzhen University)

Sowing Seeds of Belonging: "The Harvest Day" and Children's Sense of Place in Rural Taiwan

» Ms. Yi-lung Lee (Taiwan)¹, Prof. Yu-Chan Chiu (Taiwan)¹ (1. Department of Bio-Industry Communication and Development, National Taiwan University)

Locating Media Theory in Rural Communities: The Case of Radio Dhimsa

» Dr. Aniruddha Jena (India)¹ (1. INDIAN INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT KASHIPUR)

Continued from Thursday, 17 July

Social dialogue, stewardship and human wildlife conflict

» [Dr. Prakash Raj Bista](#) (Nepal)¹, Mr. AJIT TUMBAHANGPHE (Nepal)², Dr. Jan Fliervoet (Netherlands)³, Mr. Umesh Paudel (Nepal)², Dr. Naresh Subedi (Nepal)² (1. Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development, 2. National Trust for Nature Conservation, 3. Communication, Participation & Social Ecological Learning (CoPSEL), Van Hall Larenstein University of Applied Sciences)

08:30

Panel : ORG-4

ORG - Political, Legal, and Socio-Cultural Communication

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+26

Organised by: Prof. Gisela Goncalves (Panel Chair) (Portugal)

The ethical transgressions of global corporations in host countries: A socio-cultural perspective

» [Prof. asha kaul](#) (India)¹, Dr. Vidhi Chaudhri (Netherlands)² (1. Indian Institute of Management, Ahmedabad, 2. Erasmus University Rotterdam)

Title: Organisational Constraints and Environmental Narratives: A Video Ethnographic Study of Political Campaigns in India

» [Dr. Mark Rasquinha](#) (New Zealand)¹ (1. Auckland University of Technology)

Building Trust for a Sustainable Future: CSR, Charismatic Legitimation, and Diverse Voices in Australian Mining

» [Dr. Tanya Muscat](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Elaine Xu](#) (Australia)², Dr. Hao Xu (Australia)³, Dr. Xiufang (Leah) Li (Australia)⁴ (1. Curtin University, 2. University of Newcastle, 3. University of Melbourne, 4. RMIT University)

Dismantling DEI with Narratives to Justify a Radical Change

» [Ms. Xue \(Sunny\) Xiang](#) (Canada)¹, Mr. Tianheng Zhang (Canada)¹, Prof. Soo Min Toh (Canada)¹ (1. University of Toronto)

Communicating 'global' climate change in a 'local' context: Insights from Indian business

» [Dr. Vidhi Chaudhri](#) (Netherlands)¹ (1. Erasmus University Rotterdam)

08:30

Panel : ICO-7

ICO - Sociological Approaches to Disability in Global Media Cultures

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+28

Organised by: Mr. Yuqiao Yan (Discussant, Panel Chair) (China)

The nexus between accessible communication and information resilience during global crisis events: The case of migrants and people with disability

» [Dr. Ashleigh Haw](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Canberra)

A critical phenomenological and interactional framework for unraveling the intersection of racism and ableism in the digital era

» [Dr. Jullia Avgustis](#) (Finland)¹, [Dr. Samira Ibnelkaid](#) (Finland)² (1. Tampere University, 2. University of Oulu)

Do Online Communities Truly Help? The Paradox of Digital Affordances in ASD Identity Construction on Social Media

» [Ms. Qimeng Li](#) (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University)

The Ethical Rights Behind Disability Narratives: Navigating Indonesia's Disability Content on Instagram

» [Mr. Umar Syaroni](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Sydney)

Shifting Paradigm From Charity to Inclusion: Perceptions of PWDs for their Self-worth and Role of Media

» [Prof. abida ashraf](#) (Pakistan)¹ (1. University of the Punjab)

08:30

Panel : SPS-7

SPS - Special Session / IAMCR Awards Ceremony

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+27

Organised by: Dr. Skye Doherty (Convenor) (Australia) and Prof. Daya Thussu (Convenor)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Unpacking cultural politics at the metarepresentational conjuncture: Towards an interfaced approach to representation

» [Dr. Florian Vanlee](#) (Belgium)¹ (1. Ghent University)

Media Witnessing from the Perspective of Black Audiences

» [Ms. Nandi Pointer](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Colorado Boulder)

“Mom won’t let me use tampons and cups”: Mother-Daughter Intergenerational Interaction about Menstrual Stigma and Hymen Myth

» [Mr. Xiaodong Yan](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Shulun Wang](#) (United States)², [Ms. Yujie Zhong](#) (United States)³ (1. University of Colorado Boulder, 2. Penn State University, 3. Temple University)

Sense of Place in Manhattan Chinatown under Urbanization and Multiculturalism: Voices from Tourists and Residents

» [Dr. Miao Chu](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Connie Yuan](#) (United States)² (1. Xi'an Jiaotong University, 2. Cornell University)

Is the Air-Conditioner a Screen?

» [Mr. Hui Wong](#) (Canada)¹ (1. McGill University)

Spatial Practices of Girl Children in Chennai’s Resettlement Areas through Photo voice

» [Ms. Krishna Priya P B](#) (India)¹ (1. research scholar)

Cultural narratives from female communities of care: silver female surfers on becoming ocean ambassadors

» [Dr. Elena Maydell](#) (New Zealand)¹, [Dr. Inessa Love](#) (United States)² (1. Massey University, 2. University of Hawaii)

Voices in the silence: Human and non-human participation in climate change adaptation stories of fisherfolk in Del Carmen, Siargao Islands, Philippines

» [Dr. Daniel Renz Roc](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Los Baños)

Reclaiming Place Through Symbolic Geographies: Visual Resistance on Palestinian Instagram

» [Ms. Insyirah Mujtahid](#) (Singapore)¹, [Dr. Nurul Huda Rashid](#) (Netherlands)², [Dr. Kokil Jaidka](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore, 2. Leiden University)

Militant Mourning: Walking through Affective Archives

» [Ms. Hoornaz Keshavarzian](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Simon Fraser University)

Towards a Decolonial AI in/for Africa: Critical Analysis on Data Capitalism, Epistemic Injustice, and Techno-Ethics

» [Dr. Chikezie Uzuegbunam](#) (South Africa)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Media Studies Rhodes University)

10:30

Panel : JRE-11

JRE - Journalism practice and research across diverse countries III

Venue - The Hive LHS-LT

Organised by: [Dr. Stephanie Jean Tsang](#) (Panel Chair) (Hong Kong) and [Dr. Alex Segrè Cohen](#) (Discussant) (United States)

Solutions for the environment? An audience perspective study on the scope of constructive environmental news in India

» [Ms. Lekshmi Priya Sanal](#) (India)¹, [Dr. I. Arul Aram](#) (India)¹ (1. Anna University)

The role of place attachment and extreme weather on climate misinformation belief: Experimental evidence from Oregon Wildfires

» [Dr. Alex Segrè Cohen](#) (United States)¹, [Ms. Beatriz Mira](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Jesse Abdenour](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Oregon)

Personal anecdotes as a storytelling tool in news coverage of stress-related health issues: A Vietnamese study

» [Mrs. Mai Nguyen-Hoang](#) (Viet Nam)¹, [Ms. Ngoc-Khanh-Linh Pham](#) (Viet Nam)¹, [Ms. Trang-Nhung Pham](#) (Viet Nam)¹, [Mrs. Thu Le](#) (Viet Nam)¹, [Mrs. Nhan Ngo](#) (Viet Nam)¹, [Prof. An Nguyen](#) (United Kingdom)² (1. Faculty of Public Relations and Communication, Van Lang University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, 2. Bournemouth University)

Continued from Thursday, 17 July

A Comparative Analysis of Climate Journalism Education in Graduate Programs Across Countries

» [Ms. Hye kyung Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Dr. Mina Lee](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Sookmyung Women's University)

Digital Communities of Practice in Journalism Education: A Case Study of the 'Deep Training Camp' in China

» [Ms. Tiantian Zhang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Xiangyu Feng](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shenzhen University)

Ownership of Muslim Media Outlets in India

» [Dr. Arshad Amanullah](#) (India)¹ (1. Centre for Contemporary Studies, Prime Ministers Museum and Library)

10:30

Panel : HEC-9

HEC - Media and the health of Young people

Venue - WKWSC L2 Executive Seminar Room

Organised by: [Prof. Serra Gorpe](#) (Panel Chair) (United Arab Emirates) and [Dr. Cindy Ngai](#) (Discussant) (Hong Kong)

Understanding Fertility Anxiety on Social Media: The Impact of Information and Communication Overload on Young Chinese Women

» [Dr. Lutong Sun](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Yu Wang](#) (China)², [Dr. Bian Na](#) (China)³ (1. China University of Labor Relations, 2. Communication University of China, 3. Beijing Information Science and Technology University)

Engaging young people about vaping harm: an analysis of the response to an influencer-led campaign

» [Dr. David Micallef](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Juan Feng](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Edward Hurcombe](#) (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University)

'Malice from obesity': Young women's experience and coping strategies of obesity stigma

» [Dr. jingjing nie](#) (China)¹ (1. Wuhan University)

Examining the Impact of Social Media on Youth Vaping Behavior in China: An Analysis of the Mediating Role of Perceptions of Policy Enforcement

» [Dr. Tong-Chen Lucas WANG](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Mei-luan ZHANG](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Hualin Zhang](#) (China)², [Ms. Wei NIE](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shenzhen University, 2. Division of Arts, Shenzhen University)

Exploring the Impact of Traditional Chinese Medicine Information Exposure on Chinese Youth's Willingness to Choose TCM for COVID-19 Prevention and Treatment: A Health Communication Perspective

» [Dr. XIN YE](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Shulin GONG](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Hao Chen](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Jingyi Yang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of Zhejiang)

Immaculate Conceptions: Investigating Christian Teachers' Conceptions of the Role of Social Media in Sex Education through the Case of a Metro Manila Private School

» [Mr. Raphael Saria](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Diliman)

10:30

Panel : AUD-11

AUD - Platformization and audiences

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+47

Organised by: [Dr. Rafal Zaborowski](#) (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

The Equal, Long-term, and Sustainable Relationship: Exploring the Long-term Practice of Interaction Between Users and Social Media Platform Algorithm from the Perspective of Actor Network Theory

» [Ms. Hengyu Du](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Platform Paradox and Beyond: How do platform users practice the paradoxes in platform engagement?

» [Prof. Yeran Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Prof. Yong-Chan Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)², [Prof. Joo-Young Jung](#) (Japan)³, [Ms. Danbi Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)², [Dr. Miran Pyun](#) (Korea, Republic of)⁴, [Ms. Eunjean Jung](#) (Korea, Republic of)², [Ms. Lu Fang](#) (Korea, Republic of)² (1. Kwangwoon University, 2. Yonsei University, 3. International Christian University, 4. Seoul National University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Intergenerational Differences and Algorithmic Perception: How Social Media Affects Low-Carbon Intention and Green Mobility Behavior Across Generations in China — A Moderated Mediation Model Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior

» [Ms. Yishen Zhao](#) (China)¹ (1. Sanjiang University)

Deep diving. Adolescents' egocentric networks as an approach for qualitative audience research

» [Dr. Claudia Riesmeyer](#) (Germany)¹, [Ms. Jessica Kühn](#) (Germany)¹ (1. LMU Munich)

Emotional Contagion in Online Co-Viewing: How Facial Expressions Shape Audience Engagement

» [Dr. Yoojin Chung](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Ewha Womans University)

10:30

Panel : POP-18

POP - Popular confrontations of ecological transformations

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+49

Organised by: Prof. Yongliang Gao (Panel Chair) (China)

Climate Change Narratives and Collective Memory Construction in Chinese Popular Music

» [Prof. Qian Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Sustaining Peranakan cultures and Identity within East Asian Pop Culture in multicultural Singapore: From "The Little Nyonya" to "The Emerald Hill"

» [Dr. Tania Lim](#) (Singapore)¹, [Dr. Eunice Tan](#) (Singapore)² (1. Singapore University of Social Sciences, 2. Singapore Institute of Management)

Digital Humor as Ecological Praxis: Youth Meme Cultures in Climate Communication

» [Ms. Liyun Wang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China (CUC))

Symbiotic Desire: Interspecies Intimacy, Eco-Justice, and Decentralised Environmentalism in Chinese Post-Apocalyptic Danmei Fiction

» [Dr. Zhaowei Dang](#) (China)¹ (1. Xi'an University)

From Narrative to Action: The Multimodal Narrative of <Alba: A Wildlife Adventure> and Its Environmental Mobilization Effect in the Chinese Context

» [Ms. Yujing Zhao](#) (China)¹ (1. Beijing University of Posts and Telecommunications)

Poetic Dwelling, Ecofeminism, and Technology in Chinese Female Nomadic Practices

» [Ms. Fei mo](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Jinan University)

10:30

Panel : POP-20

POP - Online spaces as contemporary cultural playgrounds

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+52

Organised by: Dr. Heather Jaber (Panel Chair) (Qatar)

Roles and Obstacles: Netspeak as A Hidden Language

» [Dr. Ke Jiang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China (CUC))

In the Name of Crazy: Exploring the Playfulness of Youth Internet Popular Culture in China

» [Dr. Zhao Wu](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Xinyang Zhao](#) (China)² (1. Xiangtan University, 2. Tongji University)

Algorithmic oracles: a media sociological examination of youth groups' cyber fortune-telling practices

» [Ms. 怡清 陈](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China (CUC))

Peak storytelling? The 'theatrics of craft' and the limits of social media

» [Dr. Michelle Phillipov](#) (Australia)¹, [Prof. Susan Luckman](#) (Australia)² (1. The University of Adelaide, 2. University of South Australia)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Industrial Reconfiguration of Post-Humanity: Digital Technologies and the Cultural Industry's Expansion of Human Boundaries in Popular Media

» [Mr. Woonchul Kim](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Simon Fraser University)

10:30

Panel : CPT-15

CPT - What drives digital adoption and regulation? Between moral panics and digital identity

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+53*

Organised by: Jeremy Shtern (Panel Chair) (Canada)

Do Sleeping Sovereigns Dream of Digital Identities?: Identity, Sovereignty, Citizenship

» [Mr. James Rosenberg](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Wisconsin-Madison)

The Anxiety of Age: Moral Media Panics over Children's Social Media Use as a Tool to Regulate

» [Dr. Catherine Page Jeffery](#) (Australia)¹, Dr. Justine Humphry (Australia)², Prof. Jonathon Hutchinson (Australia)¹ (1. University of Sydney, 2. The University of Sydney)

One World, Different Priorities: AI Technology Policies and the Global South

» [Prof. chika Anyanwu](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of New South Wales)

Understanding Digital Cryptocurrency Communities: Digital Participation, Infrastructure, and Social Networks in the Global South

» [Dr. Ionalou Labor](#) (Denmark)¹ (1. Aarhus University)

Media's Embrace of Technology: How Media Portrays the Use of Autonomous Taxis and Its Impact on Individuals' Adoption Intentions

» Prof. Christine Yi-Hui HUANG (Hong Kong)¹, [Ms. Ruoheng LIU](#) (China)¹, Ms. Shuang GAO (China)¹, Ms. Bo CHANG (China)¹ (1. City University of Hong Kong)

10:30

Panel : CAM-12

CAM - Witness and Voice in Citizen's Media

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+56*

Organised by: Dr. Amparo Cadavid (Panel Chair) (Colombia)

Isn't this just how the world supposed to be?" Citizen transcultural communication on RedNote

» [Dr. Jingshan Liu](#) (China)¹, Dr. Zhiyao Liu (China)¹ (1. Guangzhou University)

The role of alternative media in voicing environmental justice

» Prof. Catia Ferreira (Portugal)¹, [Prof. Carla Ganito](#) (Portugal)¹ (1. Universidade Católica Portuguesa, UCP-FCH / CECC)

Lecciones aprendidas de las comunidades afrodescendientes del departamento del Chocó, ubicado en el Pacífico de Colombia, sobre su vínculo con territorio ancestral y la naturaleza

» [Dr. Betty Milena Marrugo Rivera](#) (Colombia)¹ (1. Universidad de Cartagena)

Fighting for Environmental Justice in South Baltimore Through Citizen Witnessing

» [Dr. Krishnan Vasudevan](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of Maryland College Park)

A Place of Old and New Ways: How Australian Indigenous broadcasting provides a space for the 'black witness' in the transformed media environment

» [Prof. Susan Forde](#) (Australia)¹, Dr. Debbie Bargallie (Australia)¹, Dr. Heather Anderson (Australia)¹, Dr. Harry Van Issum (Australia)¹, Dr. Troy Meston (Australia)¹ (1. Griffith University)

10:30

Panel : GEN-27

GEN - GBV: Masculinity, gender norms, and counter-narratives and discourses

Venue - *GAIA ABS-SR4*

Organised by: Dr. HAO CAO (Panel Chair) (China), Prof. Lin Zhu (Discussant) (China), and Dr. Yansong ZHANG (Discussant) (China)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

The Changing Landscape of Gender Issues in China Through the Lens of Masculine Traits on Weibo — An Empirical Study Based on Weibo Text Mining

» [Ms. jie shao](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

Red Pill Ideology in the Chinese Digital Sphere: Localization, Gender Antagonism, and the Construction of Male Identity

» [Dr. Yansong ZHANG](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Ting Chen](#) (China)², [Ms. Liu Xiaoling](#) (China)¹ (1. Minzu university of China, 2. Nanchang University)

Boys Hate Boys: Platformization of Gendered Hate towards Male Celebrities in Chinese Digital Manospheres

» [Mr. Pengcheng ma](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Yuchen Wang](#) (China)² (1. Peking University, 2. Shanghai Jiao Tong Univeristy)

Shaped by AI: The Multiple Masculinities of “Zhiban Dad”

» [Prof. Lin Zhu](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Yue Qiu](#) (China)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, HeBei University, 2. Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong SAR)

Gender opposition on Chinese social media: Fact or fiction?

» [Dr. HAO CAO](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Yuqi Cui](#) (China)², [Ms. Shuang Shan](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Mengru Li](#) (China)¹ (1. Wuhan University, 2. Wuhan University, School of Journalism and Communication)

Intimate Image Abuse: A Case Study of Meaning-Making on Social Media

» [Dr. Jaime Loke](#) (United States)¹ (1. Texas Christian University)

10:30

Panel : GEN-28

GEN - Gender discrimination and equality

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5

Organised by: [Dr. Mariana De Maio](#) (Panel Chair) (United States) and [Ms. Willemien Sanders](#) (Discussant) (Netherlands)

Research on the Construction of Multidimensional Female Identities on the Internet under the "Gender Performative Theory" — Taking Female "Alliances" and Identity Contempt Chains as Examples

» [Ms. 艾东罗](#) (China)¹ (1. 四川大学)

Proverbial discrimination: A feminist critical discourse analysis of Hindustani proverbs

» [Dr. . Swatantra](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Nimmagadda Bhargav](#) (India)¹ (1. Indian Institute of Management, Indore)

Platformized Leisure, Gendered Labor: A Lifeworld Analysis of Women's Agency and Constraints in China's Algorithmic Urban Culture

» [Ms. Nan Ding](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. London School of Economics and Political Science)

From "History" to "Herstory": Discourse Innovation and the Reconstruction of Female Subjectivity by Female Self-Media Bloggers

» [Ms. Li Zuonian](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Researching, learning and moving forward together. Reflecting on collaborative research to improve gender equity

» [Ms. Willemien Sanders](#) (Netherlands)¹ (1. Utrecht University)

The 108: from stigma to symbol of the fight for gay rights in Paraguay

» [Dr. Mariana De Maio](#) (United States)¹, [Mr. Adolfo Ruiz Ferreira](#) (Paraguay)², [Dr. Luis Brunstein](#) (United States)¹ (1. Lehigh University, 2. Universidad Nacional de Asunción)

Gender Bias in AI Language Models: A Comparison of ChatGPT 4.0 and DeepSeek R1 Across Cultures

» [Ms. CHOU CHIA-HSUAN](#) (Taiwan)¹ (1. 清华大学)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

10:30

Panel : ESR-16

ESR - AI and Environmental Communication

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6

Organised by: Dr. Miki Kawabata (Panel Chair) (Japan)

The Environment Impacts of the “Golden Era of AI Growth”: An Analysis of the U.S. Media Coverage of AI's Carbon Footprint

» [Prof. Suda Ishida](#) (United States)¹ (1. Hamline University)

The role of artificial intelligence generated comic in promoting climate change mitigation behaviors from the perspective of situational theory of public

» [Ms. Siyu Xu](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Yu Guo](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Yiwei Li](#) (China)² (1. Faculty of Humanities and Arts, Macau University of Science and Technology, 2. Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, BNU-HKBU United International College)

Knowledge Production and Exchange Processes of Sustainable Research and Innovation Networks in AI-based Research Environments

» [Dr. Frans Folkvord](#) (Netherlands)¹, [Dr. Lutz Peschke](#) (Türkiye)², [Prof. Rens van de Schoot](#) (Netherlands)³ (1. Tilburg School of Humanities and Digital Sciences, 2. Başkent University, 3. Utrecht University)

MEDIATED AI HYPES IN THE GLOBAL SOUTH: A VIETNAMESE CASE STUDY AND ITS IMPLICATIONS

» [Mrs. Minh Tran](#) (Viet Nam)¹, [Prof. An Nguyen](#) (United Kingdom)² (1. The University of Da Nang, 2. Bournemouth University)

How will Generative Artificial Intelligence affect Users' Sustainable Practices? An Empirical analysis From Information Characteristics to User Modalities

» [Dr. Zhang Fa](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Yuting Cui](#) (China)², [Prof. Chunlin Duan](#) (China)³ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, South China University of Technology, 2. Guangdong University of Foreign Studies, Guangzhou, 3. South China University of Technology)

10:30

Panel : ESR-17

ESR - Environmental Communication, Generations and Gender

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7

Organised by: Dr. Kerrie Foxwell Norton (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Unpacking Climate Anxiety in China: Survey Insights into Emotional Reponses and Action Tendencies Among Generations Y and Z

» [Dr. Junqing Xu](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Xuan Huang](#) (Japan)² (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University, 2. Graduate School of Agricultural and Life Sciences, The University of Tokyo)

Bridging Conservation and Community: The Saga of Rural Women Climate Champions in India

» [Mr. Saswat Pati](#) (India)¹, [Dr. Vijay Kumar Vijayan](#) (India)² (1. School of Communications, XIM University, 2. Associate Professor & Dean, School of Communications XIM University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India.)

‘Doing our bit’: How do parental interpretations of environmental and climate-related communication shape action towards sustainable futures?

» [Dr. Maria-Nerina Boursinou](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Dr. Thomas Roberts](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Prof. Ranjana Das](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Dr. Emily Setty](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Surrey)

Parenting chaos, mediated environmental communication and the potential impact on transitions to more sustainable household practices.

» [Dr. Thomas Roberts](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Dr. Maria-Nerina Boursinou](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Dr. Emily Setty](#) (United Kingdom)¹, [Prof. Ranjana Das](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Surrey)

“Exploring the organizing pattern and communication strategies of the ‘Van Suraksha Samiti,’ a women’s forest protection group in Jharkhand, India”

» [Dr. Nisha Singh](#) (India)¹ (1. SVKM's Mithibai College of Arts, Chauhan Institute of Science & Amrutben Jivanlal College of Commerce and Economics)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Shifting from Climate Impacts to Climate Participation: The Role of Children and Youth in Local Climate Actions in Indonesia

» [Mr. Ikrom Mustofa](#) (Indonesia)¹, [Mr. Ibnu Darmawan](#) (Indonesia)² (1. Department of Environmental Engineering, Universitas Islam Indonesia, 2. Department of Communication, Universitas Islam Indonesia)

10:30

Panel : PCR-9

PCR - 'Key Notes' and Business Meeting

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: [Dr. Jessica Noske-Turner](#) (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom), [Prof. Lauren Dyll](#) (Panel Chair) (South Africa), and [Aniruddha Jena](#) (Panel Chair) (India)

How we advanced knowledge about participatory communication: an analysis of PCR Section production (2017-2024) for the imagined future

» [Prof. Ana Melo](#) (Portugal)¹, [Dr. Dorismilda Flores-Márquez](#) (Mexico)² (1. Communication and Society Research Centre - University of Minho, 2. Universidad La Salle Bajío)

10:30

Panel : INC-13

INC - Gender Perspectives, Media Narratives, and Global Relations

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: [Anilesh Kumar](#) (Panel Chair)

Media's Silence on Sexual Abuse in Japan: Analysis of the self-examination TV programs on the "Johnny's Sexual Abuse"

» [Dr. Misook Lee](#) (Japan)¹, [Ms. Jimmine Yoo](#) (Japan)² (1. Otsuma Women's University, 2. The University of Tokyo)

A Comparative Study on Sexual Harassment Experiences and Coping Strategies Among Chinese and Western Urban Female Youth on Dating Applications

» [Ms. Ziyang Yang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China(CUC))

Media as a Bridge and a Barrier: Mediatized Integration Processes During COVID-19

» [Dr. Stephan Goerland](#) (Germany)¹ (1. University of Münster)

From Global South to Global South - A Critical Analysis of Chinese Vloggers' Representations of Africa on Douyin

» [Ms. Ruoyi Wang](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of Melbourne)

Green Diplomacy of EU in the Global Energy Crisis: Conceptual Framework, Trade Practices, and Media Discourse

» [Ms. Jinnan Huang](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Ruhan Zhao](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

10:30

Panel : MPS-18

MPS - Trust in news media and AI

Venue - WKWSCI L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: [Dr. SHAOPENG CHE](#) (Panel Chair) (China)

Polarization and Racial Disparity: How Partisanship Influences Trust in Political News Sources

» [Dr. Ying Xiong](#) (United States)¹, [Dr. Ammina Kothari](#) (United States)² (1. University of Rhode Island, 2. Simmons University)

Tiwala: Exploring Filipino conceptions of media trust as affective and relational

» [Mx. Czekaina Esrah Rapanot](#) (Philippines)¹, [Dr. Ma. Aurora Lolita Liwag-Lomibao](#) (Philippines)¹, [Mx. Giselle Manuel](#) (Philippines)¹, [Mx. Danica Jill Arienda](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Diliman)

Fake It Till You Vote For It: AI, deep fakes, and political memes and its impact on Filipino Gen X voters and their media literacy in the digital age

» [Ms. Stephanie Lim](#) (Philippines)¹, [Ms. Tijmie Anne Tan](#) (Philippines)¹, [Ms. Francesca Gabrielle Lopez](#) (Philippines)¹, [Ms. Arianna Mae Del Valle](#) (Philippines)¹, [Ms. Maegan Danielle Villalon](#) (Philippines)¹, [Ms. Krizzia Anne Marie Tan](#) (Philippines)¹, [Ms. Eulaine Crispino](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. De La Salle University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

"I was there, and I (dis)agree!" How User Comments Affect the Credibility of International News

» [Ms. Xiao Yang](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Xueshan Zhao](#) (China)¹ (1. University of Amsterdam)

Can Generative AI Write Good News? A Study on the Perceived Credibility of AIGC News and Its Impact Mechanisms

» [Ms. can tang](#) (China)¹ (1. Sichuan Normal University)

Crowd Counting in Protests: Applying Open-Source AI for Reliable Turnout Estimation

» [Dr. Márcio Moretto Ribeiro](#) (Brazil)¹ (1. University of São Paulo (USP))

10:30

Panel : POL-11

POL - News Framing and Political Narratives

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

Organised by: [Dr. Dharma Adhikari](#) (Discussant) (China) and [Dr. Francisco Tagle](#) (Panel Chair) (Chile)

Social Protest as a Catastrophe: Television News Coverage During the Chilean Social Outbreak

» [Dr. Francisco Tagle](#) (Chile)¹ (1. Universidad de los Andes)

News coverage of broken election promises: An Australian case study

» [Prof. Lisa Waller](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Lucy Morieson](#) (Australia)¹, [Mr. Frank Algra-Maschio](#) (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University)

"Building the Floor": Elite Indian Newspapers' Framing of the Xi-Biden Summit

» [Dr. Dharma Adhikari](#) (China)¹ (1. Xi'an Jiaotong Liverpool University)

Media Factors in Shaping Hierarchical Government Trust—An Empirical Study on Official Online Media Exposure and Trust among University Students in Beijing

» [Ms. Ping Han](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Lihua Yang](#) (China)², [Ms. Siqing Dong](#) (China)³ (1. +86 18501013189, 2. +86 13027257093, 3. +86 13701030533)

The Politics of Naming in Chinese State News: A Case Study of the 'Islamic State'

» [Ms. Qiang Zhang](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Sheffield)

10:30

Panel : MPS-19

MPS - User interaction with and acceptance of AI

Venue - WKWSC L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: [Justin C. Cheung](#) (Panel Chair) (Singapore)

"Controlling the Algorithm, or Being Controlled?"—The Identity Construction and User Interaction Practices of Weibo's Social Robot

» [Ms. Bingqing Liang](#) (China)¹ (1. College of Media and International Culture of Zhejiang University)

Dare to Miss Out? Explicating the Affective Process in Social Media News Personalization

» [Prof. Biying Wu](#) (Hong Kong)¹, [Prof. Shuning Lu](#) (United States)², [Prof. Hsuan Ting Chen](#) (Hong Kong)³ (1. The Education University of Hong Kong, 2. North Dakota State University, 3. The Chinese University of Hong Kong)

"Am I Missing Out by Not Using AI": a National Investigation of AI Anxiety on College Students in China

» [Ms. Yu Chen](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Ruonan Zhang](#) (United States)² (1. Shanghai International Studies University (SISU), 2. Rollins College)

Can Gen AI Help Students Navigate the Transition to University?

» [Mr. Hao Wei Tay](#) (Singapore)¹, [Mr. Lucas Tan](#) (Singapore)², [Prof. Chei Sian Lee](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University, 2. Nanyang Technological University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Resistance Hidden in Overcoming Death Anxiety: Exploring Illness Narrative and Platform Visibility on Chinese Social Media

» Ms. Shu Yang (China)¹, Ms. Yingyuan Li (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

A Study on the Public's Acceptance of AI-based Digital Humans: Can Messages Delivered by AI Announcers Affect the Public's Behavioral Change Intention?

» Ms. Miyoung Yoon (Korea, Republic of)¹, Mrs. Hyejung Kim (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. School of Communication and Media, Ewha Womans University)

10:30

Panel : CJD-7

CJD - Gender struggle and creative practice

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Dr. Vaia Doudaki (Panel Chair) (Czechia)

Engineering Identity, Structuring Society: Far-Right AI-Imaginations and the Construction of Gender

» Ms. Sandra Kero (Germany)¹ (1. University of Bremen,)

Activism in Daily Communication: Afghan Women's Online and Offline Resistance Strategies Under the Taliban Regime

» Mr. Fardin Ayar (China)¹ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

"I'm Coming Out as an Anti-Zionist Jew": A Discourse Theoretical Analysis of Queer Identities and Subject Positions in Media Outlet Autostraddle's Engagement with Palestinian Solidarity and Political Organising (2009-2024)

» Ms. Maedbh Pierce (Czechia)¹ (1. Charles University Prague)

Decentering Dance as Social Theory: Polysemic bodies, Protests, and the Securitization of Youth in Guinea

» Dr. Clovis Bergere (Qatar)¹ (1. Northwestern University in Qatar)

Democratising participation through art: The case of the participatory art project 'The Forest Owners'

» Dr. Vaia Doudaki (Czechia)¹, Prof. Nico Carpentier (Czechia)¹ (1. charles university)

10:30

Panel : POE-12

POE - E-waste and Digital Environmental Justice

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7

Organised by: Dr. Pradip Thomas (Panel Chair) (Australia)

Data Centres and the Environment in India

» Dr. Pradip Thomas (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Queensland)

Circulating Second-Hand Electronics in the Global South: Layered Geographies of Classification, Valuation, and Repair

» Ms. Yifan Wang (Hong Kong)¹, Dr. changwen chen (China)² (1. Lingnan Univerity, 2. Tsinghua University)

Environmental Injustice in Policy Making: A Case Study of China's Straw Burning Ban

» Ms. Xiaoshuang Yang (China)¹ (1. Shanghai University)

"Making a Living through Skill": The Politics of Obsolescence and Technical Negotiation in China's Mobile Phone Repair Services

» Mr. Yu Long (China)¹ (1. Huazhong University of Science and Technology)

Philanthropy or Profit? Carbon Assets in the Era of Platform Capitalism, Taking Ant Forest as an Example

» Ms. Weiru Cheng (Singapore)¹ (1. Nanyang Technological University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

10:30

Panel : GMP-3

GMP - Roundtable: Alternatives for Global Media Policy: Doing Justice to/for Environment, Labour, Sovereignty and New Politics of Technology

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 8

Organised by: Prof. Gerard Goggin (Panel Chair) (Australia), Prof. Claudia Padovani (Panel Chair) (Italy), Prof. Terence Lee (Discussant) (Australia), Prof. Cheryl Ruth Soriano (Discussant) (Philippines), Dr. Weiyu Zhang (Discussant) (Singapore), Prof. Usha Raman (Discussant) (India), Prof. Robin Mansell (Discussant) (United Kingdom), and Prof. Melissa Gregg (Discussant) (United Kingdom)

GMP Roundtable: Alternatives for Global Media Policy: Doing Justice to/for Environment, Labour, Sovereignty and New Politics of Technology

» Terence Lee (Nottingham Ningbo), Cheryl Soriano (De La Salle, Manila), Weiyu Zhang (National University of Singapore), Usha Raman (University of Hyderabad), Robin Mansell (London School of Economics and Political Science) and Melissa Gregg (University of Bristol)

10:30

Panel : MER-4

MER - Media literacy and education

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: Dr. Oscar Miranda-Villanueva (Panel Chair) (Mexico) and Prof. Donna Chu (Discussant) (Hong Kong)

Combating mis/disinformation through higher education: Digital media literacy education in Indonesian universities

» Mr. Albertus Prestianta (Australia)¹ (1. Queensland University of Technology)

The role of media education in promoting inclusive education and democracy as a way of counteracting authoritarian policies. A case study of Poland

» Dr. Joanna Leek (Poland)¹ (1. University of Lodz)

Assessing media literacy among Vietnam's media undergraduate students

» Mr. Vy Tran (Viet Nam)¹, Mrs. Minh Tran (Viet Nam)² (1. The University of Danang, 2. The University of Da Nang)

Mind the media literacy business: Lessons from a knowledge transfer initiative

» Prof. Donna Chu (Hong Kong)¹ (1. The Chinese University of Hong Kong)

Reconstructing educational ecology in a mediatized society: a study of multidimensional empowerment mechanisms of youth media in media education

» Ms. tiemei Wang (China)¹ (1. 18119906158@163.com)

10:30

Panel : MPA-2

MPA - Media Production in Transition: Social Platforms, Artificial Intelligence and Cultural Activism

Venue - WKWSCI TR+7

Organised by: Elvira de Torres (Panel Chair) (Spain)

Digital Activism for Climate Action: A Netnography Study of Indian Green Activists on Instagram

» Mr. Nilotpal Bhattacharjee (India)¹ (1. Department of Mass Communication, Assam University)

Adoption of AI, Collaboration, and Participation in Local Ibero-American Newsrooms: A Predictive Analysis

» Dr. Elvira García (Spain)¹, Dr. Lyudmyla Yezers'ka (Peru)², Dr. Giovanni Ramos (Portugal)³, Ms. Mayra Gonzales (Peru)², Dr. Liza Higuera (Peru)⁴, Dr. Claudia Herrera (Mexico)⁵ (1. Universidad Cardenal Herrera CEU/CEU Universities, 2. Universidad de Piura, 3. University of Beira Interior, 4. Universidad Antenor Orrego, 5. Universidad Autonoma de México)

The nostalgia mode of Squid Game

» Prof. Renira Rampazzo Gambarato (Sweden)¹, Dr. Johannes Heuman (Sweden)² (1. Jönköping University, 2. Södertörn University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

10:30

Panel : MCS-3

MCS - Approaches to strategic communication in sport

Venue - *WKWSC TR+8*

Organised by: Dr. Xavier Ramon (Panel Chair) (Spain)

MeSort: Application, testing and further development of a qualitative computational sorting software to analyze media repertoires in organizational sports communication of clubs

» Dr. Philip Sinner (Germany)¹, Mr. Thomas Neumann (Austria)², Dr. Joerg-Uwe Nieland (Austria)² (1. University of Bremen, 2. Alpen Adria University Klagenfurt)

Heteroglossia in sports crisis communication: A Discourse Analysis of FC Guangzhou's Team Disbandment

» Dr. Xueyao Zhang (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

The 'Boxingscapes' of the Philippines and the Communication of Sociocultural, Political, and Economic Realities of the Visayas and Mindanao

» Mr. Jason Paolo Telles (Australia)¹ (1. Monash University Australia)

Paid OTT Services in Korea: Factors Influencing the Continued Use of TVING's Korean Professional Baseball Content

» Mr. Sun Hong Min (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (KAIST))

The Rise and Reign of Pay-TV: Transforming FIFA World Cup Broadcasting in Africa

» Dr. Gerard Akindes (Qatar)¹, Dr. Nurhaya Muchtar (United States)² (1. Northwestern University in Qatar, 2. Indiana University of Pennsylvania)

10:30

Panel : CRI-6

CRI - The future of crisis communication

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+35*

Organised by: Mrs. Nuppu Pelevina (Panel Chair) (Finland)

Emotion-Based Social-Mediated Crisis Communication Research Development: A Systematic Review

» Dr. Song Harris Ao (China)¹, Dr. Angela Ka Ying MAK (Hong Kong)², Ms. Yan Xu (Hong Kong)² (1. Sun Yat-sen University, 2. Hong Kong Baptist University)

Can AI make good Crisis Communication?— A Experimental study on the Narrative Persuasive Effects in Crisis Public Relations

» Dr. Shuya Zhang (China)¹, Dr. Wangchuan Li (China)¹ (1. journalism and information communication school, Huazhong University of Science and Technology)

Crises & Collaboration (C&C): An immersive tabletop/online role-playing approach to collaborative training for crisis contexts

» Dr. Ryan Tan (United States)¹, Dr. Sharon Baldinelli (United States)¹ (1. University of Nebraska-Lincoln)

Risk Persuasion of Multinational Enterprises: Meaning Communication and Discourse Logic Analysis Based on TikTok's Weekly Funding Announcement at the US Hearing Session

» Dr. Guo TangXing (China)¹, Dr. Lai Cheng-Neng (Taiwan)² (1. Shih Hsin University Taipei, Taiwan, 2. Full-time Professor)

Amplification or Attenuation? The Role of Social Media Use and Political Trust in Shaping Public Response to Cyberattacks in Taiwan

» Dr. Tsung-Ien Shih (Taiwan)¹ (1. College of Communication, National Chengchi University, Taiwan, R.O.C.)

10:30

Panel : DID-5

DID - Digital Inclusion and Community Empowerment

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+36*

Organised by: Dr. Kulveen Trehan (Panel Chair) (India)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Digital Participation of Chinese Elderly Influencers: Bridging the Digital Divide for Environmental Communication and Justice Advocacy

» Mr. Wenrui LIANG (Malaysia)¹, Mr. JUNHAO WEN (China)², Ms. HUI SHEN (China)³, Mr. Haoyang He (China)³ (1. university of malaya, 2. guangzhou university, 3. BNU-HKBU United International College, Zhuhai, China)

Bridging the Digital Divide: Digital Exclusion of China's Elderly in Smart Governance and Pathways for Inclusive Environmental Participation

» Mr. Yufan Yang (China)¹, Mr. Yue Cui (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Research on Digital Inequality Among Rural Elderly in China from the Perspective of "Double Disengagement": A Case Analysis of the Rural Elderly in Ying County, Shanxi Province

» Mr. Duansheng Wang (China)¹, Mr. Xiangkai Yu (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Using Smartphones: Daily Resistance, Identity Construction, and Environmental Communication Among the Elderly in a Mediated Society

» Ms. Qi Wang (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Peking University)

10:30

Panel : RUC-5

RUC - Media

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+37

Organised by: Dr. Elske van de Fliert (Panel Chair) (Australia)

From Family to Platform: Reconfiguring Traditional Craft Inheritance, Knowledge Transmission, and Power Dynamics through Live Streaming E-Commerce in Rural China

» Dr. xi zhuang (China)¹, Mr. xu wang (China)¹, Ms. yihan miao (China)¹ (1. Nanjing Normal University)

The navigation and negotiation of mobile internet access in post-coup Myanmar

» Mr. Thant Sin Oo (United Kingdom)¹ (1. King's College London)

Suffering as Landscape: The Production and Critique of Visual Exploitation in Livestreaming for Rural Assistance

» Ms. 笑尘 刘 (China)¹, Ms. Chuxin Lin (China)¹, Ms. Mengyi Ma (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Bridging the Educational Divide: The Role of Mobile Media in Enhancing Competitive Exam Readiness Among Rural Youth

» Ms. deepati gautam (India)¹, Ms. Chhavi Garg (India)¹ (1. Central University of Punjab)

Peatland.asia - a virtual living lab with serious game elements for peatland conservation

» Mr. faisal Risq Efendy (Netherlands)¹, Dr. Lailan Syaufina (Indonesia)², Dr. Peter Van der Maas (Netherlands)³, Dr. Tri Soeprbowati (Indonesia)⁴, Mrs. Marelle van der Snoek (Netherlands)⁵, Dr. Dwina Roosmini (Indonesia)⁶ (1. Department of Human Media Interaction Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Mathematics and Computer Science University of Twente, 2. Faculty of Forestry and Environment, IPB University, IPB, Indonesia, 3. Research group Sustainable Water Systems, Van Hall Larenstein University of Applied Sciences, Leeuwarden. The Netherlands, 4. School of Postgraduate Studies, Diponegoro University, Indonesia, 5. Research group Sustainable Water Systems, Van Hall Larenstein University of Applied Sciences, Velp. The Netherlands, 6. Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering and Center of Environmental Studies, Institut Teknologi Bandung (ITB), Bandung. Indonesia)

10:30

Panel : MAR-4

MAR - Music issues: industry, technologies and consumption

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+25

Organised by: Prof. Gustavo Ferreira (Panel Chair) (Canada)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

How does AI aversion influence users' continuous use intention of AI music generator applications? The significant role of general trust, perceived playfulness and platform word-of-mouth

» Mr. Kaige Zhang (China)¹, Ms. Rundi Ding (China)², Mr. Haoyu Wang (China)³ (1. School of New Media and Communication, Tianjin University, 2. Shenzhen Branch, China Mobile Group Guangdong Co., Ltd., 3. School of Marxism, Lanzhou University)

From computational regulation training to adaptive collusion: A study of platform-label-musician collaboration mechanism in China's digital music industry

» Ms. Yingzixuan Zhang (China)¹, Ms. Mengle Liao (China)¹, Prof. Zhian Zhao (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Navigating Religious Soundscape in the Post-secular Age: A Critical Analysis of the (Re-)Production and Consumption of Digital Religious Music among Chinese Youth through the Lens of Music as Mediations

» Mr. Wenwei LONG (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University-Hong Kong Baptist University United International College)

From Global Stadium to Global Media: Analyzing the Environmental Issues on Taylor Swift's and Coldplay's World Concerts through News Discourse

» Ms. Jauhar Wahyuni (Indonesia)¹, Dr. Bambang Dwi Prasetyo (Indonesia)², Mr. Rifal Hasan (Indonesia)³ (1. Universitas Negeri Surabaya, 2. Universitas Brawijaya, 3. Universitas Gadjah Mada)

Cultural Resilience in Music: How Cantopop Reflects and Responds to Hong Kong's Economic Shifts

» Ms. Yitong Gu (China)¹, Dr. Yin Zhang (Hong Kong)¹ (1. School of Communication, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong)

10:30

Panel : ORG-5

ORG - Technology, AI, and Communication Ethics

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+26*

Organised by: Prof. Abena Yeboah-Banin (Panel Chair) (Ghana)

The Time When AI Invades Our Jobs: How does AI Foster Job Anxiety?

» Prof. Lingzhi Fang (China)¹, Prof. Heng Yang (China)² (1. Communication University of Zhejiang, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Shanghai University)

The Emergence of AI Deepfakes and Their Impact on Public Relations Practice: Practitioners' Perspective from Kenya

» Ms. Teresia Nzau (United States)¹, Mr. John Maina Karanja (China)² (1. University of Missouri, 2. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

The Impact of AI on Dialogic Communication and Relational Outcomes: Mediating Roles of Mutuality and Openness in Kenya Using a PLS-SEM Approach.

» Mr. John Maina Karanja (China)¹ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

Towards an Ethical Framework for Crisis and Risk Communication: A Theoretical Inquiry

» Prof. Gisela Goncalves (Portugal)¹, Dr. Bianca Persici Toniolo (Portugal)¹, Dr. Vera Antunes (Portugal)¹ (1. University of Beira Interior, LabCom)

Online faith-holder communities in crisis: proposing and testing a dual-challenge model

» Ms. Rugin Ren (China)¹ (1. Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

10:30

Panel : ICO-6

ICO - Gender and Intersectional Experiences of Disability

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+28*

Organised by: Prof. Katie Ellis (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Australia)

Exploring Gender Differences in Digital Sonic Intimacy: Online Romantic Relationships Among Visually Impaired People

» Prof. Min Wang (China)¹, Prof. Dan Wu (China)² (1. Wuhan University, School of Journalism and Communication, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan Sports University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Intersectionality of Mental Illness and Social Vulnerabilities in Digital Space: Depression Narratives in Weibo's 'Negative Energy' Communities

» [Ms. Suheng ZHU](#) (China)¹ (1. The London School of Economics and Political Science)

Black and White: Media Representations of Autism

» [Dr. Beatriz Inzunza Acedo](#) (Mexico)¹ (1. Universidad de Monterrey)

Exploring Disability Models in Chinese Short-Video: Self-Representation, Gender, and Urban-Rural Divides

» [Dr. Yongning Li](#) (China)¹ (1. Zhejiang Sci-Tech University)

Culture Negotiation and Sensory Politics: Creative Resistance to Audism Discourse through Sign Language Teaching in Digital Platforms

» [Ms. Zimeng Pan](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

10:30

Panel : SPS-8

SPS - Open Access Publishing: Lessons and Conversations

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+27

Organised by: Dr. Sarah Cardey (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom), IAMCR Publications Committee (Convenor), and Prof. Maria Michalis (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

12:30

General Lunch

Venue - GAIA, Level 1 Foyer

14:00

Panel : POP-21

POP - Thinking on rethinking popular culture

Venue - The Hive LHS-LT

Organised by: Dr. Yimei Zhu (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

How Do You Feel About It? An Exploration of the Importance of Emotions and Feelings in the Study of the Representation of Social Inequalities in Popular Media Content.

» [Prof. Sofie Van Bauwel](#) (Belgium)¹ (1. Ghent University)

The Evolution of "Aura" in the Age of Intelligent Reproduction: A Digital Ethnographic Study of AIGC Posts on RedNote

» [Dr. Kaining Chen](#) (China)¹ (1. Wuhan University)

Unpacking cultural politics at the metarepresentational conjuncture: Towards an interfaced approach to representation

» [Dr. Florian Vanlee](#) (Belgium)¹ (1. Ghent University)

Populism/Neo-populism on China's Social Media: Representation of Popular Culture and Their Impacts on Culture and Society

» [Prof. Yongliang Gao](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

Cultural knowledge as practical knowledge - A transmedia analysis of popular culture and how it can be integrated into social lives and practices

» [Mr. Moritz Schweiger](#) (Germany)¹ (1. University of Augsburg)

14:00

Panel : HEC-15

HEC - Communities, institutions and social change

Venue - WKWSCI L2 Executive Seminar Room

Organised by: Ms. Zheng Yi (Panel Chair) (Singapore) and Dr. Mary Anne Taylor (Discussant) (United States)

Sharing Stories, Saving Lives: Storytelling vs. Direct Instruction in a CHW-Led Maternal Health Program

» [Mr. Haroon Hakimi](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Media and Communication, Shanghai Jiao Tong University.)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Comply or Survive? Uncovering the effectiveness of government COVID-19 communication on behavioral responses in Vietnam

» [Ms. Thu Luong Le](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Queensland)

Communicating for Health-as-Development: A case study of two pandemics in South Africa

» [Prof. ELIZA GOVENDER](#) (South Africa)¹ (1. University of KwaZulu-Natal)

Fostering Hope through Mediated Nature: Photobook as Medium of Therapeutic Photography

» [Mrs. Nadia Utami](#) (Indonesia)¹, [Ms. Desyatri Mayangsari](#) (Indonesia)¹ (1. Department of Communication Universitas Islam Indonesia)

Transcending the displacement-augmentation dualism: Modality switching in mobile social network gaming and implications for health outcomes

» [Dr. Bingrui Huang](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Hongfeng Qiu](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Xiamen University)

14:00

Panel : AUD-14

AUD - Consumer culture and audiences

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+47

Organised by: [Dr. nissim katz](#) (Panel Chair) (Israel)

Mapping the audience measurement industry in the digital age from a political economy perspective

» [Dr. Miguel Vicente Marino](#) (Spain)¹ (1. University of Valladolid)

Meat Alternative Marketing: Beyond Brawny Bodies and Bold Buzzwords An Online Experiment into the Effects of Masculine versus Neutral Meat Alternative Advertisements on Men's Perceived Association between Meat and Masculinity

» [Prof. Gaelle Ouvrein](#) (Belgium)¹, [Ms. Amber Peeters](#) (Belgium)², [Dr. Paulien Decorte](#) (Netherlands)³ (1. Vrije Universiteit Brussel, 2. University of Antwerp, 3. Maastricht University)

Unveiling the Magic of Word-of-Mouth: How Different Types of Word-of-Mouth Influence Consumers' Willingness to Pay for News?

» [Prof. Yu Jia](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Jiayi Ma](#) (China)², [Ms. Yihui Li](#) (China)², [Mr. Yao Ding](#) (China)² (1. Center for Studies of Media Development, School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University, 2. School of Journalism and Communication, Wuhan University)

Personality, Social Signals, and Digital Engagement: Understanding Motivations for Luxury Content Consumption on TikTok

» [Ms. Insyirah Mujtahid](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

How do older characters featured in short videos influence the communication effects? An experimental study among Chinese older consumers

» [Ms. QIQI LI](#) (Hong Kong)¹ (1. Hong Kong Baptist University)

14:00

Panel : JRE-14

JRE - Conflict and crises reporting

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+49

Organised by: [Prof. Lisa Waller](#) (Panel Chair) (Australia) and [Dr. Alonit Berenson](#) (Discussant) (Israel)

On "Not Being There": Digital war reporting and the interplay of trauma and self-care in correspondents covering conflicts from afar

» [Ms. Lidia Kelly](#) (Australia)¹, [Ms. Christine Kearney](#) (Australia)², [Prof. Lisa Waller](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Lucy Morieson](#) (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University, 2. UTS)

Conflict or Coexistence? Media Framing of Jewish-Arab Relations during the May 2021 Riots in Israel

» [Dr. Alonit Berenson](#) (Israel)¹ (1. Zefat Academic College)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Do War Video News Reports Expose Intensified Violence? A Comparative Analysis of South Korean Coverage of the Israel-Hamas Conflicts in 2014 and 2023

» [Dr. Kumhee Jung](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Ms. Miyoung Yoon](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, Prof. Yunjung Choi (Korea, Republic of)¹, Ms. Yeoneui Kim (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Ewha Womans University)

14:00

Panel : CPT-8

CPT - The Digital Transactions Turn: Making Policy and Governance Fit-For-Purpose

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+53*

Organised by: Prof. Gerard Goggin (Convenor, Panel Chair) (Australia)

TikTok Refugees and the Cross-Cultural Public Sphere: Social Transactions and International Communication Policy

» [Prof. Haiqing Yu](#) (Australia)¹ (1. RMIT University)

Platform Labor and Transaction Chains

» [Prof. Cheryl Ruth Soriano](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. De La Salle University Manila)

E-commerce logistics in Southeast Asia: the cases of Shopee and Lazada

» [Dr. Emma Baulch](#) (Malaysia)¹ (1. Monash University Malaysia)

Digital Transaction Platforms in Asia

» [Prof. Adrian Athique](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Queensland)

14:00

Panel : CAM-11

CAM - Digital Adoption and Resistance in the Alternative Media Landscape

Venue - *The Hive LHS-TR+56*

Organised by: Dr. Andrew Ó Baoill (Panel Chair) (Ireland)

Digital Shift in Community Radio: A Study on the State of Digital Adoption in Community Radio Stations in Bangladesh

» [Ms. Treesa John](#) (India)¹, [Prof. Vinod Pavarala](#) (India)¹ (1. University of Hyderabad)

Performative Resistance in the Age of Algorithms: The Case of Tagging Culture on Xiaohongshu

» Mr. 尧刘 (China)¹, [Dr. Kun Fu](#) (China)¹ (1. Beijing Normal University-Hong Kong Baptist University United International College (UIC))

Digital transformation of alternative media: the case of community radio in Nigeria

» [Dr. Ke Cai](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Jingwei Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. Beijing Foreign Studies University)

14:00

Panel : GEN-23

GEN - Precarity vs. empowerment, female digital labour and work

Venue - *GAIA ABS-SR4*

Organised by: Prof. Bernadette Barker-Plummer (Panel Chair) (United States), Dr. Ambrish Saxena (Discussant) (India), and Dr. Susmita Bala (Discussant) (India)

Visual Political Cultures and Gendered Negotiated Visibilities: The Seen and The Unseen

» [Ms. Rituparna Banerjee](#) (Ireland)¹ (1. Dublin City University)

From Invisibility to Visibility: Self-Presentation of Divorced Chinese Women on Short-Video Platforms and the Reconstruction of Gender Order

» [Ms. Jiaxin Li](#) (China)¹, Dr. Heli Sun (China)¹ (1. xian jiaotong university)

Voting decisions and preferences of women electorates in India: A study of parliamentary and assembly elections 2024

» [Dr. Ambrish Saxena](#) (India)¹, Dr. Susmita Bala (India)¹, Mr. Prince Shadwal (India)² (1. South Asian University, 2. Amity University)

"There are Only Two Genders": Gender Essentialism and Transphobia in US Conservative Policy Discourse

» [Prof. Bernadette Barker-Plummer](#) (United States)¹ (1. University of San Francisco)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

14:00

Panel : GEN-31

GEN - Advocacy: Gender, resettlement, and spatial development

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR5

Organised by: Dr. Jian Xiao (Panel Chair) (China) and Dr. Yang Ding (Discussant) (China)

Cinematic Representations of Hong Kong Space: Everyday Life in Ann Hui's All About Love

» [Ms. Xueyan Cheng](#) (Singapore)¹ (1. National University of Singapore)

Spatial Practices of Girl Children in Chennai's Resettlement Areas through Photo voice

» [Ms. Krishna Priya P B](#) (India)¹ (1. research scholar)

Flâneuse in the platform era: Spatial reconstruction and empowerment in China

» [Dr. Jian Xiao](#) (China)¹, [Dr. Mengyu Luo](#) (China)² (1. Zhejiang University, 2. University of Shanghai for Science and Technology)

Empowered Voices in the AI Industry: Digital Feminist Spaces and Gender Advocacy in China

» [Dr. Yang Ding](#) (China)¹ (1. China Women's University)

Beauty queens, dancers and maidens: Gender and energy in Australia

» [Dr. Kate Fitch](#) (Australia)¹, Prof. Belinda Smaill (Australia)¹ (1. Monash University)

14:00

Panel : ESR-23

ESR - Framing the environment

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR6

Organised by: Pieter Maesele (Panel Chair) (Belgium)

Framing Wildfires: A Comparative Analysis of Media Narratives and Public Engagement in the US, UK, and Arab Region

» [Dr. Alyaa Anter](#) (United Arab Emirates)¹, Dr. Nermin Soliman (United Arab Emirates)¹ (1. Ajman University)

Visualizing Climate Justice: How Imagery Shaped Narratives of Equity and Responsibility in Pakistan's Flood Crisis and Moved Global Audiences to Action

» [Dr. Shahbaz Aslam](#) (Pakistan)¹, Dr. Babar Hussain (Pakistan)² (1. University of Gujrat, 2. University of the Punjab)

Communicating Environmental Justice between Neighboring Rivals: A Longitudinal Cross-National Analysis of News Media Framing Responsibility of Smog and Blame Game

» [Dr. Muhammad Yousaf](#) (Pakistan)¹ (1. University of Gujrat)

Framing Grassroots Environmental Justice: Media Coverage of Deforestation Movements in Southeast Asia

» [Prof. Bradley Freeman](#) (Malaysia)¹, Ms. BABELYN Cabalar (Philippines)² (1. Sunway University, 2. West Visayas State University)

14:00

Panel : ESR-24

ESR - Social media and environmental communication

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR7

Organised by: Dr. Maitreyee Mishra (Panel Chair) (India)

Epistemic Resistance from the Margins: Environmental Activism, Social Media, and the Global South

» [Prof. Shivani Sharma](#) (India)¹, Dr. Aparna Vincent (India)² (1. Communication Area, Indian Institutue of Management Indore, 2. Indian Institute of Management, Indore)

Second Age Medium: Surfacing Facebook Group Dynamics in Online Wildlife Discourse

» [Mr. Jonah Kaygvan](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Diliman)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

#IndonesiaDaruratSampah: Critical Discourse Analysis towards Waste-Emergency Messages in Environmental Agencies of Indonesian Government's Official Instagram Accounts

» [Mrs. Mashita Phitaloka Fandia Purwaningtyas](#) (Indonesia)¹, [Mrs. Lidwina Mutia Sadasri](#) (Indonesia)¹ (1. Universitas Gadjah Mada)

14:00

Panel : PCR-5

PCR - Public Communication, Citizen Participation and Policy

Venue - GAIA ABS-SR8

Organised by: [Dr. Pradip Thomas](#) (Discussant, Panel Chair) (Australia)

The participation-communication nexus: An integrative analysis model for critically assessing institutionalized participatory processes

» [Dr. Moshe Schwartz](#) (Israel)¹ (1. Ben Gurion University of the Negev)

Never forgotten: the resilient search for Spain's forced disappeared children

» [Dr. Carolina Escudero](#) (Spain)¹ (1. University of Missouri)

The Light Stick Protest: How Entertainment Became a Part of Political Activism

» [Ms. Cherin Park](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Dr. Dam hee Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)² (1. MA Student, School of Media and Communication, Korea University), 2. Professor, School of Media and Communication, Korea University)

The PAR-fication of Citizen Parliaments: A Reconsideration of Participatory Intensities

» [Prof. Nico Carpentier](#) (Czechia)¹, [Dr. Vaia Doudaki](#) (Czechia)¹, [Dr. Milos Hroch](#) (Czechia)¹ (1. charles university)

14:00

Panel : INC-3

INC - Environmental Communication in a Global Context

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 9

Organised by: [Dr. Sweta Singh](#) (Panel Chair) (India)

Navigating Environmental Communication: Digital Youth Voices in Jordan

» [Ms. Thawab Hilal](#) (Austria)¹, [Dr. Hanan Badr](#) (Austria)¹ (1. University of Salzburg)

Voices of Justice: Media Framing and Grassroots Movements in Environmental Advocacy

» [Dr. Mahdi Yousefi](#) (China)¹ (1. Hainan Normal University)

Fuzzy logic but clear agenda: machine-assisted advertorials, cybernetic everyday, and influencer vernaculars for environmental activism in the global south

» [Dr. Troy Chen](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. City, University of London)

14:00

Panel : MPS-20

MPS - Social bots as social actors

Venue - WKWSC L2 Seminar Room 2

Organised by: [Prof. Biying Wu](#) (Panel Chair) (Hong Kong)

Social Bots as Social Actors: How Comment Sentiment Polarity Manipulates User Engagement

» [Ms. Qingxuan Cheng](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Hao Xu](#) (China)¹, [Prof. Jing Dong](#) (China)², [Prof. Shaobo Liang](#) (China)³ (1. School of New Media, Peking University, 2. School of Information Management, Central China Normal University, 3. School of Information Management, Wuhan University)

Does the vulnerability expression of chat robots improve artificial empathy?— An empirical analysis based on a self-developed chat robot.

» [Ms. Min Zhou](#) (China)¹, [Mrs. Xiuli Zhao](#) (China)², [Ms. Feiyang Chen](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Beijing Normal University, 2. Beijing Normal University)

Cultural Shock in Artificial Love: Examining the Cross-Cultural Relationships of Chinese Users with Western AI

» [Ms. Dan Xie](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Shuang Xie](#) (China)² (1. Beijing Foreign Studies University, 2. Shanghai International Studies University (SISU))

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

The Myth of Efficiency and the Reality of Exclusion: A Critical Algorithmic Study of AI Customer Service Failures

» [Dr. GUONING ZHAO](#) (China)¹ (1. Institute of Communication Studies, Communication University of China.)

14:00

Panel : POL-10

POL - Media Effects on Political Engagement and Avoidance

Venue - SHHK - HSS Conference Room

Organised by: Ms. Zhieh Lor (Panel Chair) (Korea, Republic of) and Dr. Renee Barnes (Discussant) (Australia)

The influence of media use and communication activities on everyday political consumerism. Results of a diary study

» [Mr. Marco Dohle](#) (Germany)¹, [Mr. Ole Kelm](#) (Germany)¹, [Mr. Lasse Scheipers](#) (Germany)¹ (1. University of Duesseldorf)

The politics of avoidance: Unpacking the cultural, personal and social influences on political news engagement in Australia

» [Dr. Renee Barnes](#) (Australia)¹, [Dr. Melissa Innes](#) (Australia)¹ (1. University of the Sunshine Coast)

The more knowledge one has, the more silent one becomes: The political socialization of youth in China's platform society

» [Ms. XUE MI](#) (China)¹, [Dr. yang YANG](#) (China)², [Dr. zhen RAN](#) (China)¹ (1. Fudan University, 2. Dongguan University of Technology)

Beyond the Virtuous Circle: Political Participation, News Behaviors, and Political Competencies Among Young Adults in South Korea

» [Ms. Zhieh Lor](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Ms. Jaehyun Lee](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, [Prof. Jihyang Choi](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Ewha Womans University)

14:00

Panel : MPS-21

MPS - Grassroot movements and their influence

Venue - WKWSCI L3 Seminar Room 1

Organised by: Prof. WENJING TAO (Panel Chair) (China)

Assembling Cloud Juries? Post-truth, Marginal Narrative and Justice Practice in Chinese Social Media

» [Dr. peng wu](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Gloucestershire)

“You Are the Media Now”: The Disruption of Knowledge Orders in the Age of Digital Oligarchy

» [Ms. Sandra Kero](#) (Germany)¹, [Prof. Christian Schwarzenegger](#) (Germany)¹ (1. University of Bremen,)

Tweeting Power: How Grassroots Influences Elite Narratives in David Hogg Debates

» [Ms. Qian Li](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Rongxin Ouyang](#) (China)², [Mr. Wei Shi](#) (China)³ (1. Arizona State University, 2. National University of Singapore, 3. Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

The Temporal and Spatial Patterns of Chinese Netizens' Views on the Russia-Ukraine War

» [Mr. Zhexi Gu](#) (United States)¹, [Mr. MA zhipeng](#) (China)², [Dr. rick krever](#) (Australia)³ (1. University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, 2. mazhipenggo@foxmail.com, 3. University of South Australia)

14:00

Panel : CJD-8

CJD - Dissent and contestation in constrained spaces

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 6

Organised by: Dr. Clovis Bergere (Panel Chair) (Qatar)

Whistleblowing or agitation? The use of the phrase fake news in times of climate crisis, COVID-19 and elections on the example of the Polish presidential election campaign in 2020

» [Mr. Grzegorz Kowalczyk](#) (Poland)¹ (1. University of Warsaw)

State-Citizen contestation in democratic struggles: A critical discourse analysis of Pakistani television news media

» [Ms. Sadia Zamir](#) (Czechia)¹ (1. charles university)

The Ludic Representation of Environmental Trauma: How Digital Games Amplify Multivocal Justice and Catalyze Ecological-Democratic Action

» [Ms. Xinyu Kang](#) (China)¹, [Mr. Yuantong Yun](#) (China)² (1. Peking University, 2. Tsinghua University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Digital Carceral Mobilities: Mobility and Smuggled Mobile Technologies in Prisons

» [Dr. Chafic Najem](#) (Lebanon)¹ (1. Northwestern University in Qatar)

Ink on Walls, Fire in the Streets: Graffiti's Role in Shaping Political Resistance and Disrupting Authoritarian Narratives

» [Mr. Nilotpal Bhattacharjee](#) (India)¹ (1. Department of Mass Communication, Assam University)

14:00

Panel : POE-11

POE - Knowledge production through ideology, narrative, and technology

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 7

Organised by: Gabriela Martinez (Panel Chair)

Indigenization of Infrastructure: the origins of Chinese satellite communications and the politics of its development behind 'Nixon's visit to China' (1972-1984)

» [Mr. Zhilun Zhong](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Mapping the Hidden Costs of Volunteer Academic Labour in the R Language Ecosystem

» [Ms. Xiaolan Cai](#) (Australia)¹, [Prof. Mathieu O'Neil](#) (Australia)¹, Prof. Stefano Zacchiroli (France)² (1. University of Canberra, 2. Telecom Paris)

Humans as Black Boxes: Replacing Data Production Labor with Large Language Models and the Changing Power Dynamics of Platforms

» [Mr. Zhiyuan Pan](#) (China)¹ (1. Peking University School of New Media)

Frame Competition and Institutional Breakthrough: A Study of Alternative Narratives in Global South Climate Communication during COP Summits

» [Ms. Xiao Zhang](#) (China)¹ (1. Shanghai University)

The Tripartite Making of Hangzhou City Brain: Understanding Automated Decision-Making Infrastructures and Its Disagreement through Assemblage Thinking

» [Prof. Yu Hong](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Yiran Wei](#) (China)¹ (1. Zhejiang University, College of Media and International Culture, Hangzhou, China)

14:00

Panel : ESN-PCR-

ESN - PCR - Joint Session: Participation and Representation in Transition

Venue - SHHK - HSS Seminar Room 4

Organised by: Dr. Jeremiah Nganda (Panel Chair) (Kenya) and Dr. Aniruddha Jena (Discussant) (India)

Nostalgic Futures: A Cultural Discourse Analysis of the 'Cottagecore' Trend on TikTok and YouTube

» [Ms. Honor Sandall](#) (New Zealand)¹ (1. University of Auckland)

Conquering Nature? How Environmental Spaces in Trail Running Events Reshape the Body: An Ethnographic Study of the Spartan Race

» [Dr. Qianhe Ji](#) (China)¹ (1. 中国传媒大学)

How Knowledge Production Shapes Environmental Policy: A Discourse Analysis of China's Environmental Governance in the Ecological Civilization Era

» [Ms. Yongxin Du](#) (China)¹ (1. Peking University)

Re(reading) identity performance in the celebrification of Indian women family vloggers

» [Ms. Debopriya Roy](#) (India)¹ (1. Department of Mass Communication and Journalism, Tezpur University)

The Role of AI-Mediated Communication in Shaping Self-Perception: Examining Social Comparison Between Humans and AI in Supportive Communication Contexts

» [Mr. Jaemin Kim](#) (Korea, Republic of)¹, Prof. Soo Yun Shin (Korea, Republic of)¹ (1. Department of Communication, Seoul National University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

From Ignoring to Exploring: Can Algorithms Reignite News Engagement? A Survey of User Preferences for Recommender Systems

» Ms. Michelle Kulig (Switzerland)¹, Dr. Willem Buyens (Belgium)², Prof. Manuel Puppis (Switzerland)¹, Prof. Steve Paulussen (Belgium)², Prof. Hilde Van den Bulck (Belgium)² (1. University of Fribourg, 2. University of Antwerp)

14:00

Panel : HIS-7

HIS - Media Ecology and Digital Cultures

Venue - WKWSCI TR+7

Organised by: Mr. Mazlum Kemal Dagdelen (Panel Chair) (Czechia)

Toward Digital Linguistic Justice: A Critical Study of Data Practices in Latin American Language Technology Development

» Ms. Melissa Gasparotto (United States)¹ (1. Rutgers University)

Adapting to the Misinformation Crisis: Evolution of Indian Fact-Checking Organizations Through the Lens of Institutional Isomorphism

» Mr. Vinayak Jha (India)¹, Dr. Rajesh Kumar (India)¹ (1. Central University of Jharkhand)

Reconstructing media ecology studies: Thinking with Jussi Parikka's ecological media materialism

» Dr. Hui-Lan Chang (Taiwan)¹ (1. Department of Information and Communication, Tamkang University.)

Films in flames: the act of film burning as a method of control, protest, and expression

» Dr. Serkan Savk (Kuwait)¹ (1. Gulf University for Science and Technology)

14:00

Panel : MCS-7

MCS - Sports fandom in digital environments

Venue - WKWSCI TR+8

Organised by: Dr. Peter English (Panel Chair) (Australia)

The Power of Narrative Transportation in Shaping Engagement Among Filipino Pro Wrestling Fans

» Mr. Karlvin Chester Vallejos (Philippines)¹, Mr. Raimon Carl Jalandoni (Philippines)¹ (1. De La Salle University)

From Arena to Avatar: A Content Analysis of Virtual Reality in Shaping NBA Fan Engagement on Reddit

» Ms. Yibo Yang (China)¹, Dr. Shahrul Nazmi Sannusi (Malaysia)¹, Dr. Ammar Redza Ahmad Rizal (Malaysia)¹ (1. Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia)

Ultras, trolls and normies: football events, digital fandom, and public discourse

» Dr. Rafal Zaborowski (United Kingdom)¹, Dr. Mark Hill (United Kingdom)¹ (1. King's College London)

14:00

Panel : CRI-5

CRI - Peace and conflict journalism

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+35

Organised by: Dr. Virpi Salojärvi (Panel Chair) (Finland)

Reclaiming the Fourth Estate's mandate to call out war crimes and mass atrocities

» Dr. Kasun Ubayasiri (Australia)¹ (1. Griffith University)

The Media Organisation Steps Up: Legal and Other Approaches to Safety Regulation

» Mr. Simon Levett (Australia)¹ (1. University of Technology Sydney)

Bridging narratives: Exploring feasibility and impact of collaborative peace journalism between Afghan and Pakistani journalists

» Dr. Ayesha Jehangir (Australia)¹, Prof. Shabir Hussain (Pakistan)² (1. University of New South Wales, 2. Bahria University)

Representations of 'Islamic State' in Chinese News Media: A Single Case Exploratory Study with Discourse Analytical Approaches

» Ms. Qiang Zhang (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Sheffield)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

14:00

Panel : RUC-7

RUC - Communication, governance and participation

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+37

Organised by: Dr. Loes Witteveen (Panel Chair) (Netherlands)

Uncertainty reduction: Shaping China's poverty alleviation relocation (PAR) villages in digital era

» [Dr. Xiaoyu Chen](#) (China)¹ (1. Guangxi Arts University)

The Promise and the Paradox of Innovation: Understanding Governance Challenges in the Stagnation Phase of the Living Lab Enrekang, Indonesia

» [Ms. Nurdahalia Lairing](#) (Indonesia)¹, Prof. Loes Witteveen (Netherlands)², Prof. Darmawan Salman (Indonesia)¹, Dr. A. Amidah Amrawaty (Indonesia)¹ (1. Hasanuddin University, 2. Van Hall Larenstein University of Applied Sciences)

Bridging aspiration: Incorporating informal communication in channelling community development needs for more inclusive development.

» [Mr. Andi Mulyadi](#) (United Kingdom)¹ (1. University of Reading)

ENGAGING COMMUNITIES IN PROGRAM EVALUATION: THE CASE OF A PILOT RISK COMMUNICATION PROGRAM FOR LANDSLIDE-PRONE AREAS IN THE PHILIPPINES

» [Ms. Maria Thresha Ursolino](#) (Philippines)¹ (1. University of the Philippines Los Baños)

14:00

Panel : MAR-5

MAR - Listening practices

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+25

Organised by: Ignacio Gallego (Panel Chair) (Spain)

Listening to News: How Human and AI Anchors Influence Listeners' Attitudes towards Podcast News

» [Ms. Ying Jin](#) (China)¹, [Ms. Chuyu Yang](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Tsinghua University)

Listening though the Static: 1945

» [Ms. Utsha Roy](#) (Australia)¹ (1. The University of Adelaide)

Listening to Inequality: Noise Pollution, Environmental Justice, and the Politics of Sound

» [Ms. Lea Redfern](#) (Australia)¹, Dr. Diana Chester (Australia)¹, Ms. Venu Arora (India)², Dr. Berenike Jung (United Kingdom)³ (1. The University of Sydney, 2. O.P. Jindal Global University, 3. University of Southampton)

Trust in the Ear: How Podcast Listeners Assess Credibility in the Age of Synthetic Media

» [Mrs. Miaomiao Huang](#) (China)¹ (1. Communication University of China)

An Actor-Network Analysis of Smart Speakers in Domestic Practice

» [Ms. CHANG SU](#) (China)¹ (1. School of Journalism and Communication, Renmin University of China)

14:00

Panel : DIM-5

DIM - Diasporic Lives Online: Emotion, Identity, and the Reconfiguration of Space and Time

Venue - The Hive LHS-TR+28

Organised by: Myria Georgiou (Panel Chair) (United Kingdom)

Digital Activism by Afghan Refugees in the Diaspora: The Deterritorialization of Space in Canada

» [Ms. Monica Yousofi](#) (Canada)¹ (1. Simon Fraser University)

Emotional repercussions of online hatred towards migrants in Chile

» [Dr. Nairbis D. Sibrian D.](#) (Chile)¹ (1. Facultad de Comunicaciones Universidad del Desarrollo)

"The Making of a Climate Refugee": A Critical View on How Affects Construct and Deconstruct Hegemony in Discourses

» [Ms. Qingqu Yuan](#) (China)¹ (1. Sun Yat-sen University)

Continued from **Thursday, 17 July**

Reconceptualizing (lost) time: Polymedia and temporal challenges in Filipino transnational familyhood

» Mr. Petronilo Figueroa (Philippines)¹, Dr. Randy Jay Solis (Philippines)¹
(1. University of the Philippines Diliman)

15:45

Panel

Closing and Plenary / Communicating for a Multivocal World

Venue - Lee Kong Chian LT (LKC-LT)

Communication Scholars at Singapore Management University

Singapore Management University is Asia's premier global city university with research and education at the nexus of management, social sciences and technology. Our communication faculty's expertise covers a rich and broad expanse. Our interdisciplinary approach integrates social science, applied communication and computational data science to drive impactful research in areas such as AI ethics, corporate reputation, environmental communication, and the future of work. By bridging traditional and emerging fields, we are shaping the future of communication research and education in an evolving world.

MARK CHONG
Risk Perception & Communication | Generative AI & Communication

SHYAMALA DEENATHAYALAN
Communication Management | Culture & Cross-Cultural Management

SUN SUN LIM
Technology Domestication | Future of Work | AI Ethics

TRACY LOH
Social Media & Digital Engagement | Relationship Management | Risk Communication

TAMAS MAKANY
Conversational UX Design | Design Education | Educational Technologies

ONG SIOW HENG
Cross-Cultural Communication | Speech Communication | Persuasion

AUGUSTINE PANG
Crisis Management | Communication & Leadership | Image & Reputation Management | Media Management

SUNGJONG ROH
Judgment & Decision Making | Communicating Science | Health | Environment | Risk Computational Data Science

SONNY ROSENTHAL
Media Use & Climate Change Perceptions | Informational Nudges & Proenvironmental Behavior

SU LIN YEO
Corporate Reputation | Crisis Communication | Public Policy Communication

SPONSORS AND PARTNERS

SPONSORS AND PARTNERS

Hosted By

Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information
College of Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences

Organised By

Held In

Supported By

Gold Sponsors

Northwestern | QATAR
Institute for Advanced Study in the Global South

Silver Sponsors

Bronze Sponsor

Other Sponsors and Partners

Conference Exhibitors

Department of Media and Communication,
City University of Hong Kong

Institute for Advanced Study in the Global South,
Northwestern University in Qatar

School of Communication,
Hong Kong Baptist University

School of Journalism and Communication,
Tsing Hua University

School of Media and Communication,
Shanghai Jiao Tong University

Springer Nature

Taylor & Francis Asia Pacific

Conference Advertisers

Department of Media and Communication,
City University of Hong Kong

Institute for Advanced Study in the Global South,
Northwestern University in Qatar

Northwestern University in Qatar

School of Communication,
Hong Kong Baptist University

School of Journalism and Communication,
Tsing Hua University

School of Media and Communication,
Shanghai Jiao Tong University

Singapore Management University

Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and
Information, Nanyang Technological University